

**STORIES TOLD AND UNTOLD: A NARRATIVE ETHNOGRAPHY
OF A HIDDEN POPULATION OF WOMEN WHO USE DRUGS
IN SCOTLAND**

KAREN HAMMOND

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For the next generation and their grandmothers

There is one elementary TRUTH– the ignorance of which kills countless ideas and splendid plans:

The moment one definitely commits oneself, then providence moves too. All sorts of things occur to help one that

Would otherwise have not occurred...

Whatever you do

Or dream you can do

Begin it.

Boldness has genius, power and magic in it.

Begin it now.

(Goethe).

And so it was. While there continued to be obstacles to overcome, I found there was always someone or something there when I needed it the most. That someone was usually my Mum or Dad.

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Abstract

Women who use illicit drugs can be a particularly hidden and ‘invisible’ group in society, given that they experience greater levels of stigma and discrimination than their male counterparts (Simpson and McNulty, 2008). There is particular lack of representation of women who are not in contact with treatment agencies or the criminal justice system (McPhee, 2013). In this narrative ethnography (Gubrium and Holstein, 2008), I address this significant gap in the literature, using snowball sampling methods (Woodley and Lockard, 2016) to identify and recruit 20 women with experience of illicit drug use. It has been suggested (Marechal, 2009) that ‘marginal intellectuals’ who tap their ‘outsider within status’ can offer an alternative perspective. Through the use of auto-ethnographic vignettes, I make links between my life history and the research focus, utilising my own multiple marginality as a research tool in accessing and engaging women who use drugs.

Trust is especially vital to the success of hidden population research and through reflexive writing I render visible the series of challenges encountered in the recruitment process. Guided by a feminist sensibility (Ettorre, 2017), the demonstrative empathy narrative interview method (DENIM) was developed to address the power dynamic inherent in interviews with marginalised populations. DENIM is an informal approach to interviewing which considers seriously the social context, positionality and role of the researcher in co-constructing meaning, in particular the desire for social acceptability (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008; Esin et al, 2013). The analytic approach adopted for this study views narratives as forms of social code - the making of meaning - and stories as socially and dialogically constructed (Bakhtin, 1981; Frank, 2010; Sullivan, 2012). Dialogical narrative analysis of ambiguity highlights the inherent complexity of the women’s identity work. Drawing inspiration from Belotti (2016), significant relationships are located within the concentric circles of trust. These insider/outsider narratives are implicated in group boundary maintenance.

Seven small stories are presented (Smith, 2016) and these function to retrieve and restore control and self-empowerment, to command respect and authority and to rework and locate cultural narratives of risk. I argue that this cohort of socially included women have access to narrative resources which allow them to perform relatively socially acceptable identities in order to manage stigma. Adopting subject positions that give a sense of being an acceptable human being often results in a reproduction of the social structure (Esin et al 2014). Women’s accounts of drug use thus shape and are shaped by the surrounding culture of stigma, shame and prohibition.

Ettorre (2017) suggests that gender sensitive harm reduction might be achieved through paying attention to the neglected arena of embodiment. Forming a dialogical perspective of women’s drug talk, I suggest the concept of narrative habitus (Frank, 2010: 2012), which links women’s narrative identity work with the body and social networks. A renewed focus on storytelling, particularly how stories are circulated and embodied, has much to add to the understanding the interplay between structure and agency in the lives of women who use drugs (Fleetwood, 2016).

In closing, I argue that future research might employ the ‘circles of trust’ as a tool for narrative elicitation and a model for the social networks in which hidden populations of women who use drugs are embedded. In terms of methodological advancement, the use of DENIM will assist in enhancing engagement with particularly stigmatised segments of the population, such as opioid using parents.

Contents

Acknowledgements.....	2
Abstract.....	5
List of tables.....	10
Introduction.....	11
Chapter One Hidden population Research: Context and Rationale.....	17
Introduction.....	17
Hidden population research: a brief background.....	17
Hidden population research in Scotland.....	19
The challenge of accessing women.....	22
Estimating the prevalence of women’s drug use in Scotland.....	22
Why are women who use drugs predominantly hidden?.....	23
The utility of hidden population research.....	27
The dark potential of hidden population research.....	28
Improving the methods of hidden population studies.....	28
Aims and objectives of study.....	29
Chapter Two: ‘Methodological Considerations’.....	31
Introduction.....	31
The reflexive turn.....	32
Problematizing realist ethnographies.....	33
Social constructionism.....	34
Epistemology: knowledge as partial and situated.....	35
Ontology: The problem of relativism and multiple truths.....	37
Theorising ‘the subject’ in gender studies.....	38
The problem of agency.....	42
Subjectivity through the lens of narrative.....	43
Complicity and conscientization.....	45
Negotiating complex subject positions: between choosing and being chosen.....	46
The promise of narrative.....	48
Conclusion.....	49
Chapter Three: ‘Locating the researcher’.....	51
Positionality.....	53
The dilemma of disclosure for drug researchers.....	53
A matter of social justice.....	55
Reflections upon researcher identity.....	57
Auto-ethnographic vignette – ‘The Outsider Within’.....	57

The utility of a fringe location	61
Embracing vulnerability	62
Connecting the dots	62
Conclusion	64
Chapter Four: ‘Accessing and Engaging Hidden Populations’	66
Introduction	66
Inclusion criteria.....	66
Sampling.....	67
Thoughts on limitations of sampling method.....	68
Evolution in research design	70
Recruitment	71
Identifying Potential Gatekeepers	73
Pitching the study	73
Pilot stage.....	75
A Series of Setbacks	75
Getting in	78
Serendipity	79
Authenticity.....	81
Learning the language.....	83
Learning from Failures	85
Defended/ defensive subjects	87
Interview technique: developing DENIM.....	88
Ethical challenges.....	93
Healing vs harmful narratives	96
Table (1): Participant profiles.....	99
Social Networks.....	100
Conclusion.....	101
Chapter Five: ‘Introducing Dialogical Narrative Analysis’	103
Navigating the field	103
Method as guidelines	104
Identifying Stories.....	105
Beyond big and small stories	106
A dimensional approach to defining narrative	107
Questions to guide the analysis of the stories.....	109
Finding Focus.....	111
Outline of analysis chapters	114

How it should be read	114
Chapter Six ‘Circles of trust: boundary narratives of drug use and connection’	117
Introduction	117
Circles of trust	117
Positioning significant relationships in the circles of trust	120
Inner circle: knowledge and participation	123
On the margins: Limited knowledge without participation.....	123
Outsiders: no knowledge no participation	124
Positioning friendships	125
Unique bonds: social ties in the inner circle.....	125
Drug use on the fringes: from close friends to associates.....	130
Friendship beyond drug use	133
Friendship with outsiders	134
Positioning new friends: feeling it out.....	136
Positioning Partners.....	138
Partners on the inside	139
Unequal partnerships: the dark side of the circle of trust.....	141
Locating intimate partners on the margins	145
Positioning parent/child relationships.....	147
Woman as mothers.....	147
Women as daughters.....	155
Employers and Colleagues	158
Discussion.....	164
Chapter Seven ‘Seven small stories of illicit drug use’	171
Introduction	171
Risk narratives	172
Similarities and Differences	182
Respectability Narratives.....	184
Similarities and differences	192
Lost and Found: Retrieval Narratives	195
Similarities and Differences	201
Conclusion	202
Chapter Eight: a dialogical perspective on women’s drug talk.....	205
Introduction	205
Part One: The features of ‘good stories’	205
Ambiguity.....	206

Resolution	209
Common tools for building good stories: artefacts and metaphors.....	210
Good stories: an exemplar	211
Part two: Circulation and embodiment	214
Novel and well- rehearsed stories	214
Stories told and untold	216
Vicarious intoxication.....	220
Improving the work of stories.....	223
Conclusion.....	224
Chapter Nine: Discussion and conclusion	228
Introduction	228
The parameters of present knowledge claims.....	229
Analytical contributions	231
Limited choices	232
Constructing risk and relationship	233
Stories as capital	237
The power in silence	240
Methodological contributions	241
Resonance effect: an alternative view on the role of the researcher	241
The development and potential of DENIM	245
Recommendations for future research.....	246
Conclusion.....	248
Epilogue.....	254
References	257
Appendices.....	276
Appendix One: Consent Form	276
Appendix Two: Participant Information Sheet	277

List of tables

Table 1: participant profiles	pp. 100
Table 2: social networks	pp. 101
Table 3: positioning of others in the circles of trust	pp. 122
Figure 1: circles of trust	pp. 120

Introduction

Due to the clandestine nature of illicit drug use it is notoriously difficult to gain access to drug using populations which remain out with the gaze of authorities (Taylor and Kearney, 2005). Within this group, women who use illicit drugs are particularly hidden and hard to reach, given that they experience greater levels of stigma and discrimination than their male counterparts. Consequently there is a lack of understanding about the characteristics and experiences of women who use drugs in non-captive populations. This narrative ethnography (Gubrium and Holstein, 2008) is intended to address this significant gap in the literature by identifying and recruiting 20 women and presenting their experiences of illicit drug use.

Chapter 1 of this thesis sets the scene for this hidden population study. Here, I introduce the term hidden population to describe the heterogeneous group of people who use illegal drugs in a variety of different ways, whose master status is not that of a 'drug user' and consequently remain largely invisible in a climate of prohibition (McPhee, 2013). To locate this research, I chart the history of this tradition and highlight the ways existing research within it has challenged mainstream thinking about illicit drugs and the people who use them. I then introduce the rationale for the present study through highlighting women as the most hard to reach, yet the most under-researched aspect of the hidden population in Scotland to date. The chapter concludes with an exploration of the potential reasons put forward as to why women who use drugs are such an invisible population such as stigma, appropriate services and fear over child protection intervention.

In chapter 2, I explore issues of philosophical and methodological relevance to this study of women who use drugs in Scotland. In brief, I argue that knowledge is situated by one's social location which is comprised of multiple experiences of privilege and oppression (Brown and Strega, 2005). That agents of knowledge are both embodied and socially located complicates the traditional view of relationship between the subject and the object of knowledge; the same kinds of social forces which shape the lives of objects (in this case women who use drugs) may also shape the lives of subjects or knowers (Harding, 1993).

To lay the foundations of the analysis of gender, drug use and storytelling, I present the notion of subjectivity as a contradictory and fluid self that is shaped by language, power relations and discourses in the context of everyday practices and relationships (Jackson, 2004). I highlight

the importance of emphasising complexity and plurality, and avoiding essentialised notions of what it means to be a specific category of woman, in this case women who use drugs, in order to keep signs unstable and open to redefinition (Youngblood Jackson, 2004).

This chapter explores the particular promise of narratives which are introduced as the scaffolds which women use to construct stories about their self and their place in the world in relation to others (Smith, 2016). In closing of this chapter I argue that a constructionist view of narrative makes sense when we consider the nature of ‘choices’ that women make in constructing a subjectivity as they speak about their drug experiences.

In chapter three, I present reflexive auto-ethnography as a means to think about the connected life experience of the researcher, which according to Mizzi (2010) is often downplayed or overlooked in traditional ethnographic methods. Crucially, I suggest this allows us to become aware of hidden privileges and makes us mindful of how we present ourselves to research participants. In the spirit of self- reflexivity, I tentatively explore the links between my own life history and the research focus, explicitly utilising my own multiple marginality as a research tool in accessing and engaging with women who use drugs. Following Patricia Hill Collins, I adopt the status of the ‘outsider within’, of being both close and yet somewhat distant at the same time. This positionality allows researchers to see patterns that may be obscured from those more immersed within the culture while being near enough to have members confide in them about difficult experiences. I end this chapter by suggesting that marginal intellectuals who tap their ‘outsider within status’ are well placed to offer an alternative perspective than that more commonly generated (Marechal, 2009).

In chapter 4, I employ this mode of reflexive writing to make explicit the series of challenges encountered in the recruitment process and the ways in which they were overcome. This adds a dimension of context which is hitherto missing in the limited literature, assisting future researchers of hidden and hard to reach populations.

Snowball sampling is useful for researching private matters where insider knowledge is crucial (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981) and in cases where distinguishing features are not readily apparent (Cohen and Arieli, 2011), thus making it ideal for penetrating the social worlds of people who use drugs. It is especially useful in feminist research as it sheds light on the social

relationships in which women are embedded (Woodley and Lockard (2016). In this chapter, I explore practical and ethical challenges in recruitment and suggest strategies for fostering productive research relationships with women who use drugs, emphasising that trust is especially vital to the success of hidden population research, as it is with any study which involves the narration of sensitive topics (Stranden, 2009). I argue that in order to avoid further stigmatisation, as marginalised research subjects women should make sense of their life experiences using their own language and frames of reference (Krumer-Nevo and Sidi, 2012).

After encountering several barriers to engagement I designed an innovative interview method called the Demonstrative Empathy Narrative Interview Method (DENIM). The DENIM draws upon the empathic method of qualitative interviewing. As illicit drug use is considered a deviant and stigmatised activity, this method was deemed indispensable due to its potential to enhance an exchange of sensitive information by fostering a degree of trust and understanding. In the DENIM, the emphasis on demonstration foregrounds the active quality of empathy as something that someone does instead of something they have (Ettorre, 2017). I present this innovative research tool as a means to address the power dynamic inherent in interviews with marginalised populations and in light of the desire for social acceptability, show how it is particularly well suited to the study of hidden populations of women who use drugs (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008), (Esin et al, 2013).

Chapter five lays out the analytic approach adopted for this study which views narratives as forms of social code, and stories as socially and dialogically constructed (Bakhtin, 1981; Frank, 2010). Here I explain that dialogical narrative analysis does not seek to uncover the truth as much as it creates possibilities for truth (Sullivan, 2012); stories do not imitate an independent social reality but constitute a social reality in and of themselves (Frank, 2010). Rather than following precise steps to arrive at the singular truth of a phenomenon, narrative researchers agree there are multiple valid interpretations and as such the task becomes one of building a persuasive case for a particular interpretation (Squire, 2010). To familiarise the reader with dialogical narrative analysis, I introduce the idea of analysis as a method of questioning grounded in theoretical assumptions. I then outline the questions used to guide this dialogical narrative analysis based on the work of Frank (2010) and Smith (2016) in an attempt to ‘let the reader in’ to the process of analysis and interpretation (Dickie 2003; Riessman 2008).

In chapter 6 I look across the collection of women's narratives and present relationships as the major theme throughout the data. Drawing inspiration from Belotti (2016), for each of the 20 women, I locate significant relationships within the concentric circles of trust which depicts varying degree of knowledge and participation in the women's drug use. Here I attempt to shed light on the social and relational processes which contribute to the phenomenon of hidden populations and explore the women's decision making processes around disclosing this stigmatised aspect of their identity to others. This lengthy chapter functions to highlight the way in which group boundaries are constructed in and through narrative. Women's subjective accounts of various relationships suggest they are important for the regulation of drug use, countering cultural narratives of drug using women as pathological in relationship. At the end of this chapter I proceed with an in-depth discussion of how this knowledge contributes to the growing body of evidence on the use of informal social controls through the provision of regulatory norms that help to keep drug use within relatively socially acceptable levels.

In chapter 7 I present seven small stories as sites for the analysis of women's identity work. Stories operate on multiple levels and simultaneously achieve many different effects (Bamberg, 1997). Thinking dialogically about these stories through asking questions, I think critically about the work of the women's drug storytelling, with the intention of opening up the dialogue further (Smith, 2016). I underline the manner in which these stories function to retrieve and restore control and self-empowerment, to command respect and authority and to rework and locate cultural narratives of risk and further, I explore the complex negotiation of subject positions that the women must make in narrating socially acceptable identities and managing the potential stigma and discrimination that comes with being a woman who uses illegal drugs. The narrative resources which are available to the women to perform this identity work are available to them on account of their social positioning and background in order to contribute new knowledge to the study of hidden populations. Through attention to the manner in which these seven small stories reproduce normative femininity and categories of good and bad women, I demonstrate how women's accounts of drug use are shaped largely by the surrounding culture of stigma and prohibition.

In the study of sensitive topics in particular, it is important to be wary of ‘concealing’ those we research in their suffering, by becoming too caught up with the dark side of their lives (Hyden, 2013). In chapter 8 of this thesis, through dialogical narrative analysis of ambiguity I demonstrate the inherent complexity of women’s identity work and the resulting textured quality of women’s accounts of illicit drug use. A core facet of the identity work for these women is reconciling aspects of identity which operate in different social groups and different social worlds, which are at times conflicting and without cohesion. The primary manner in which monological analyses of women’s drug talk manifest is the tendency to foreground either the good or the bad, though the latter is much more common. To favour pro-centripetal or pro-centrifugal interpretations is to discount half of the narrator’s dialogic voice (DeSantis, 2001).

Through the example of Mary I suggest good stories are those which achieve the goals of women’s drug talk. Employing effective narrative strategies such as the use of artefacts they are rich in metaphor; they are ambiguous, and they provide a sense of resolution. I form a dialogical perspective on women’s drug talk, suggesting a starting point is the unifying concept of narrative habitus, which links women’s narrative identity work with the body, making a unique contribution to knowledge in the study of women’s drug use. In telling stories of their drug use, women seek the embodied experience of resonance that exists between people that have had similar experiences and I consider the importance of this for understanding the insider/ outsider debate at large.

Narrative habitus ties the development of stories to the circles of trust, allowing us to appreciate how in hidden populations women experience safety in numbers, through the sharing and building upon narrative resources that allow them to perform socially acceptable identities in the context of a potentially hostile culture. A renewed focus on storytelling, particularly how stories are circulated and embodied, has much to add to the understanding of the interplay between structure and agency in the lives of women who use drugs.

I begin the discussion chapter by laying out the parameters of the thesis knowledge claims and show how a narrative perspective provides the means to reconcile a relativist and constructionist stance with the objective of social justice. As the purpose of the study is to explore the subjective meanings of drug use for the women as well as the best way to research hidden populations, the discussion addresses both analytical and methodological contributions to knowledge. In this section of the thesis I emphasise how the success of my attempts at

accessing and engaging with this hidden population is largely down to my positionality. My similar life experiences and background, which has given me a similar world of stories. Recommendations for future research are made the end of the discussion and these relate to the advancement and further development of the concepts and contributions of the thesis.

In conclusion, narrative methods are presented as a re-humanising alternative and effective means to gain insight into the lives of women who use drugs. Thinking about the work of women's stories assists in the development of a more critical understanding of gender and drug use. Everyday stories of drug use give women who use drugs a much needed sense of agency and empowerment that is integral to a dynamic and ambiguous sense of self that is not entirely identified with or reduced by previous instances of victimisation. Although the women's choices are limited in constructing their narratives of drug use, they are privileged in so far as stigma is managed, defended from and at times deflected through deployment of narrative resources that have been developed in the context of relative social inclusion. Women's everyday stories of illicit drug use thus provide a rich and fertile ground to analyse areas of key relevance to the study of hidden populations specifically and gender and drug use in general. To draw to a close the auto-ethnographic component of the study, following the conclusion I provide an epilogue which contains reflections on the manner in which my own storytelling practices have evolved over the course of the research project.

Chapter One Hidden population Research: Context and Rationale

Introduction

The study of drug use is truly an interdisciplinary field. Analysed through the multiple lens' of sociology, social work, psychology, anthropology and epidemiology (Galea, Nandi and Vlahov, 2004), the plethora of meanings attached to the use of psychoactive substances has resulted in important insight, not only on the nature of drugs and the people who use them but more generally on the nature of social relations and individual and group behaviour in contemporary society. Although research on illicit drug use is a multi-disciplinary enterprise, due to ease of access most drug research is conducted on treatment or criminal justice populations (Duncan et al, 2003). Speaking about the North American context in particular, Duncan et al (2003) suggest that these 'captive' populations have been so extensively described that the general public, including clinicians and researchers, have come to see them as representative of all illicit drug users. It is the purpose of hidden population research to address this imbalance.

This chapter will give a brief background to the history of population research in the field of alcohol and drug studies. It will then contextualise the present study within a distinctly critical strand of hidden population research which seeks to challenge the dominant discourse of illegal drugs and the people who use them. I discuss the notable absence of women's voices and experiences in hidden population research specifically and in the field in general, exploring some of the potential explanations put forward to explain this. The chapter concludes with a consideration of the utility of hidden population research for furthering knowledge on women's illicit drug use before defining the particular aims and objectives of the present study.

Hidden population research: a brief background

According to Rhodes and Moore (2001), drug ethnography can be traced back to the 19th Century but regained popularity through the Chicago School of Sociology which approached the phenomenon of illicit drug use as a 'social problem' (Rhodes and Moore, 2001). Many contemporary ethnographies of drug use have been concerned with drug users that do not belong to clinical or institutional populations meaning they are less visible and accessible, giving rise to the term 'hidden populations' (Watters and Biernacki, 1989).

Drug ethnographies of this kind have focused heavily on street-based injecting drug users in particular (Magnani et al, 2005) as much of the early hidden population research was motivated by an attempt to halt the spread of HIV (Duncan et al, 2003). In populations such as this where there are visible indicators of belonging to a stigmatised minority it is likely individuals will have a shared sense of identity as their predicament becomes their ‘master status’ (Becker, 2008). On the other hand, individuals from ‘hidden populations’, who lack visibility because the socio-political climate carries risk of exposure, likely form a heterogeneous group loosely linked by only one aspect of their identities. They are characterised as a population insofar as they share in the secret of being a person who uses drugs in the context of legal and moral censure (McPhee, 2013). Heterogeneity and concealability of stigmatised attribute are thus two features which help to disentangle the ‘hard to reach’ from the ‘hidden population’.

A review of the existing hidden population literature has identified two different strands that are suggestive of a transatlantic divide, distinguishable in the manner in which they have come to support or challenge mainstream thinking on illicit drugs and the people who use them. A monograph on hidden population research published by National Institute of Drug Abuse (NIDA) captures the essence of the North American approach (edited by Lambert, 1990). Collated by the Division of Epidemiology and Prevention Research, the justification for this series of studies was the belief that hidden populations are at most risk of drug related morbidity. The association with extreme vulnerability and criminality justifies the need for state intervention and efforts to access and engage with these ‘elusive drug users’ are clearly with a view to increasing technologies of surveillance. As well as widening the nets of social control in the context of the war on drugs, there was another perhaps less obvious motivation for focusing on hidden populations in the 1990’s. As Wayne Wiebel suggests;

‘it is fortunate for the qualitatively oriented social scientist that the field of substance abuse offers such fertile testing ground for qualitative methods and research designs’ (Wiebel, ed. by Lambert, 1990: 4)

The move away from captive populations was thus instrumental in re-legitimising the role of ethnography and qualitative research in general, at a time within the field where large scale quantitative projects had become the norm. The impact of this wider context is evident in the conceptual focus of the NIDA monograph, which centres heavily on methodological issues around sampling.

One of the key studies to emerge at this time came from Watters and Biernacki (1989), who managed to recruit a total of 600 participants from field sites that were not connected to institutions. Using a mixed methods design, they found more variation in usage patterns, frequency of injecting and drugs of preference than studies recruiting from ‘captive’ populations. This built on previous important findings from Biernacki in (1986) which showed how some individuals that had become addicted to heroin were able to recover without treatment or formal intervention.

Indeed, the existence of non-addicted heroin use was first acknowledged as far back as the 1930’s when Alfred Lindesmith described intermittent users of heroin as ‘joy poppers’ (Weinberg, 1997). The phenomenon was later confirmed by researchers who accidentally stumbled upon ‘non-abusive’ users of heroin in community outreach projects targeted at ‘abusers’, however it was implied that such patterns of use would eventually progress into addiction and as such did not warrant further investigation (Duncan et al, 2003).

Despite widespread disagreement amongst ethnographers in North America in the 1960’s and 1970’s as to whether illicit drug users should be regarded as sick or criminal, or indeed neither, the 1980’s saw hidden population research specific take on a framework of meaning that describes drug use in terms of pathology. This was largely due to the emerging AIDS crisis, when curbing the spread of this disease became the key objective of community outreach research at this time (Feldman and Aldrich, ed. By Lambert, 1990).

However, the paradigm of pathology was something that had firmly taken root in hidden population research, influencing research designs which measure and categorise perceived dysfunction. For example, Conrod et al (2000) recruited a sample of three hundred non-treatment seeking women who use drugs in Montreal, subsequently categorising them into five different subtypes with varying degrees of ‘psychopathology’. Couched within the discipline of psychiatry, such research favours the determinants of dependency, viewing drug use as a manifestation of mental disorder (Galea et al, 2004).

[Hidden population research in Scotland](#)

In Scotland, hidden population research has played a key part in challenging mainstream assumptions about drug use and addiction. In his 2013 hidden population study ‘The intentionally unseen’, McPhee departs from the mainstream tradition in his rejection of the populist view which

'approaches drug use as a social problem to be solved by medicine, social work and drug enforcement agencies' (McPhee, 2013: 3).

Using a bricoleur method inspired by the anthropology of Levi Strauss, he investigated the hidden worlds of 24 'socially competent' drug users in Scotland, finding intoxication with illicit substances to be one of many social activities engaged in within the wider context of an otherwise ordinary lifestyle. In this heterogeneous sample of men and women who were united in their rejection of the stigmatised addict identity, there was evidence of a range in patterns of consumption from 'intermittent' to 'chaotic' to 'controlled'.

Yet for some researchers the term hidden population is synonymous with recreational drug use. According to Stetina et al (2008):

'hidden populations are inconspicuous drug users who do not regard themselves as drug users in the traditional way, who differ in many ways from usual clinical study populations and who engage in recreational drug use that is the use of mind altering substances for the purpose of altering one's mental state, typically without supervision of a physician, and mainly for direct or indirect pleasure. In contrast to use for utilitarian purposes such as relief from fatigue or control over appetite'

(Stetina et al, 2008: 1)

Although it is recognised that there are risks associated with all forms of illicit drug use, recreational use, on account of its less frequent occurrence, is generally deemed to be less of a problem for individuals and society. To date it has been researched largely in the context of the night-time economy (Stetina et al, 2008). Framing hidden populations of drug users as recreational is intended to set them apart from other key populations, such as those placed within the problematic category. In contrast to recreational or occasional use, problematic drug use is the routine and prolonged use of opioids and/or the use of benzodiazepines, as defined by the Information Services Division (ISD) of the NHS in Scotland (ISD, 2019).

The common perception of some drugs, namely ecstasy, cannabis, LSD, as recreational, and others, namely crack cocaine and heroin, as drugs of addiction, leaves a false impression that the former are used for fun while the latter are used in a compulsive, routine and monotonous and ultimately destructive way (Shewan and Dalgarno, 2005). In a hidden population study from Shewan and Dalgarno, both heroin and crack cocaine, traditionally considered drugs of addiction, were used in manner they describe as 'unobtrusive'. This manner of use, which they

suggest is possible for any drug given the correct set and setting (Zinberg, 1984), refers to a pattern which does not dominate the lives of the individuals nor cause damage or distress to those around them. When the premise is accepted that outcomes are a result of many social and psychological factors and are not purely pharmacological, then the usual ways of categorising forms of drug use, and by extension populations of drug users on the basis of substance alone becomes troublesome.

Alternatively, the term ‘non-abusive’ drug use has been attached to hidden populations, which Duncan et al (2003) define as

‘the consumption of a drug in a controlled manner in terms of frequency and quantity, where the desired effects are experienced without significant toxic adverse physical or psychological consequences’ (Duncan et al, 2003: 208).

However, as Valentine and Fraser (2008) show, in practice the distinction between recreational/problematic and abusive/non-abusive drug use can be difficult to maintain; the lines are very often blurred. The routine method of labelling drug use in hidden populations may thus distort the reality of patterns of drug use, which a growing body of research suggests is dynamic, fluid and at times overlapping.

The Scottish hidden population studies in particular highlight the potential of hidden population studies to be challenging to the status quo through the production of knowledge which counters mainstream narratives of drug use. Not only in terms of highlighting contrary patterns of use to those implied by dominant models of addiction, but in the characteristics of those who use them. The McPhee (2013) study offers a view of hidden populations as health-conscious individuals capable of managing risk; responsible, otherwise law-abiding citizens. That such unremarkable people engage in illicit drug use, and are neither criminal nor sick, undermines the perception that it is the domain of a ‘deviant minority’ in society. In similar vein, the cohort of 126 long term heroin users that had never been in treatment in the Shewan and Dalgarno (2005) study were distinguishable only for the lack of high levels of negative health and social outcomes, challenging the stereotypical view of those who use ‘hard drugs’.

For example, most of their participants were well educated and employed in levels comparative to the general population, which contrasts with traditional captive populations. At follow up, only one individual had experienced loss of employment as a result of their heroin use. At first interview only 5% of the sample reported negative health related effects from their drug use, and the authors note the role of other substances in such instances. The sample also stands out

for a notable lack of negative social outcomes, with a minority expressing family disapproval and concern and at second interview one male participant had lost access to his son (Shewan and Dalgarno, 2005).

In this regard it could be said that Scottish studies have picked up on a potentially dangerous strand of thinking that was germinated in the context of the early US ethnographies, but later subsumed under public health concerns for the spread of blood borne viruses. Arguably, within this tradition, the primary motivation for researchers is to discover patterns and presentations of illicit drug use which similarly defy dominant understandings of drugs and the people who use them. Within this quest, high-functioning hidden heroin users are the equivalent of research gold.

The challenge of accessing women

As a social group, people who use drugs are bound not only by the laws designed to control use but also by the exercising of power through the discourses used to explain drug use and related processes. They are routinely pathologised, stigmatised and discriminated against (Coomber, 1998), which makes them hard to reach by nature. As such, access constitutes a major challenge within hidden population studies. According to the international network of people who use drugs:

“People who use drugs already make up a hidden population due to criminalisation and stigma, which makes population size estimates tricky. Women who use drugs are all but invisible, with very little data as to the size of this community.” (INPUD, 2014:1)

Indeed, across the field of substance use research participants have been predominantly male (Tuchman, 2010). Accessing and recruiting females has historically proved particularly challenging; as a result, women are largely absent from the academic literature.

Estimating the prevalence of women’s drug use in Scotland

The data to provide an estimate of the extent of problem drug use in Scotland is gathered using the method of capture recapture, which involves combining available data on the known population with an estimate of the unknown population. The available data is drawn from three

main sources; clients registering with drug treatment, drug-related hospital admissions, and criminal justice social work reports. This is the most generally accepted method in drug use epidemiology and has been used in Scotland since 2000. It is emphasised that resulting figures likely underestimate the true extent of the problem. With that in mind, figures published in 2015/2016, the time of data collection in this study, estimate approximately 55,800 – 58,900 individuals are engaging in problem drug use, with the highest regional rate in the West of Scotland. Within this group, 29% are female and this figure is thought to represent 0.92 % of the general population of females in Scotland (Information Services Division (ISD), 2019)

Due to the hidden nature of most drug use it is very difficult to gauge the extent of women's illicit drug use in general. In the UK women tend to respond poorly to calls for participation in large scale anonymous surveys. For example, a 2008 study by Stetina et al, surveyed 9,268 'recreational drug users' from English and German speaking countries. Within the sample, 28 % of overall respondents were female, and out of a range of countries across the continents, Great Britain had the lowest number of female respondents (17.82%). These differing response rates do not reflect the statistics which suggest that equal numbers of men and women are now using in the general population which is explained in terms of greater ease of access to illicit drugs (Neale, 2004).

A recent report published by Tweed, Miller and Mathieson (2018) contains a more worrying statistic that shows the number of women in the latest figures for drug related deaths in Scotland is increasing. While men constitute the overall majority in these figures, the number of female decedents has been rising at a greater rate, with consistent increase in percentage of women every year in the last decade. A number of factors have been put forward to explain this rise in deaths among women who use drugs, such as greater vulnerability to welfare reform and the reduction in provision of services. The phenomenon is largely unexplained, leading to a call for a greater understanding of risk factors specifically related to women (Lynn et al, 2020). Amidst their list of recommendations, Tweed et al suggest further research into the 'possibility' of hidden populations.

Why are women who use drugs predominantly hidden?

Due to the hidden nature of most drug use, the characteristics of women in the wider population of people who use drugs in Scotland are unknown. Existing knowledge is based on observations about female drug use largely drawn from clinical population data, which is not representative

of the wider population of people who use illicit drugs in Scotland. With that important caveat in mind, it is necessary to explore on the basis of this limited research, the potential factors which contribute to why women who use drugs are, as Fiona Measham et al (2011) describes them, ‘cloaked in invisibility’. Several reasons have been put forward to explain this phenomenon.

Motherhood

A wide-ranging study examining the lived experiences of key populations including people who use drugs found that:

“Parents feel significant pressure to meet rigid requirements and to conceal their status as a member of a marginalised and/or criminalised community, forming a barrier to accessing appropriate services, healthcare and social service provision.” (policy brief by INWUD, the impact of stigma and discrimination on key populations and their families, 2018).

The role of the female as the primary caregiver in the current climate of child protection hypervigilance acts as a strong motivator to keep drug using activity secret. Once identified, they are portrayed as so-called fallen or bad women and unfit mothers (Jurgens et al, 2010). Indeed, in Scotland, it is estimated that around 40% of child protection review cases involve parental substance use, affecting 6142 children in the Glasgow area alone (Hay et al, 2005). The notion that female drug users avoid seeking treatment as it increases likelihood of children being removed from parental care is supported by evidence from Gilchrist and Taylor (2009) who suggest that over half of the women in treatment have children that reside elsewhere.

On the contrary, research by Jessup (2003) has highlighted that amongst this vulnerable group the role of motherhood can act as a powerful motivator to engage with treatment services, despite external barriers such as stigma and discrimination. For Radcliffe (2011), becoming pregnant intensifies the need to have an identity that is morally acceptable, which is already felt by women in a society which labels female drug users as unclean and undesirable. Research which shows that males, even when they are drug users themselves, prefer to have non- drug using female partners is testament to this (Simpson and McNulty, 2008) Thus the transition into motherhood represents a turning point for many drug using women to engage with treatment services. As Reid et al., (2008) point out, managing the ‘bad mother’ identity alongside the stigmatised ‘junkie’ identity is an added challenge for drug using women who struggle to cope with the needs and demands of being a mother.

Lack of appropriate services

Drug treatment services are well known for gender imbalance with only a quarter of the total treatment population made up of women (National Treatment Agency, 2010). The fear of child protection intervention is often acknowledged by drug workers, however more commonly reported barriers to entering treatment include a lack of access to appropriate childcare and women only services (NTA, 2010). Indeed, it is widely purported that drug treatment services in the UK fail to meet the complex needs of women who use drugs (Simpson and McNulty, 2008) and accordingly, much of the research looking at females and drug use calls for a more gender sensitive approach to harm reduction (Ettorre, 2004).

Some argue for gender sensitive treatment services for women on account of observed gender differences in drug taking behaviour and biological and subjective responses to drugs including shorter spans between first use and addiction, contributing to the perception of women's greater overall vulnerability to addiction (Tuchman, 2010). Other studies have found similar drug using profiles in treatment populations between men and women (Neale, 2004), but clear differences in other life areas such as general health, relationships, experiences of abuse and victimisation, extent of involvement in criminal activity, employment and homelessness. Such studies are unable to explain why the ration of men to women in treatment agencies is so imbalanced. While the need for an improvement in services for women is not in dispute here, this discourse acts as a window into the dominant way of understanding women's drug use. The underlying assumption being that treatment is indeed required even if not desired

Societal reaction and stigma

As a direct result of the illegality of consumption of mind- altering substances in contemporary Western society, there exists a climate of 'moral and legal censure' (McPhee, 2013), in which drug use has been cast as a thoroughly deviant activity. Accordingly, a culture of stigma and discrimination forms the backdrop for all research on illicit drug use.

For Robin Room (2005), analysis of the widespread literature on stigma can help us to understand the different ways it relates to drug use by looking closer at the way in which the concept has been applied to different groups. Stigma may be simple or complex, abstract or concrete, visible or concealed. In the case of the mentally ill and the disabled, stigma is generally noted for its negative effects while in contrast, in studies oriented towards criminality

it is framed as a necessary method of social control (Room, 2005). In the field of alcohol and drug studies however, the concept of stigma is used in both ways, reflecting differing, though not necessarily conflicting, attitudes towards drugs and the people who use them.

According to Ahern et al (2007) the impact of stigma and discrimination is so under researched because of the perceived benefits of stigmatising this population are believed to outweigh any negative consequences. However, stigma and discrimination create poor mental and physical health outcomes for drug users, whose range of responses alternate between living with anger, speaking out in defence, withdrawing from social interaction and alienation through internalisation of negative stereotypes (Ahern, Stuber and Galea, 2007).

The scant literature on drug use and stigma is based mostly on the experiences of men however it is well documented that females experience greater levels of discrimination than their male counterparts, as they are subject to discrimination on the basis of both drug use and gender (Simpson and McNulty, 2008). According to Malloch (2004) social stigma is the key factor which acts to reinforce women's silence around drug use; when they come to the attention of the criminal justice system they are often constructed as risky and their behaviour highly 'inappropriate'.

Health and social care professionals often have negative attitudes towards women who use drugs, a less reported barrier to seeking help for drug related problems (Jambert-Gray et al., 2009; Fraser et al., 2007; Adams, 1999). Evidence suggests that discriminatory attitudes towards drug users within health and social care professions is an ongoing problem with negative consequences for levels of engagement and related poor outcomes for women and their children (Simpson and McNulty, 2008).

In addition, media coverage is higher and more negative for poor and minority women regardless of the degree of adverse health consequences associated with the specific drug used (Springer, 2010). According to Elizabeth Ettore (2018) the low social status of women who use drugs is visible even within the women's movement, where they are regarded as 'failed moral guardians' (Ettore, 2018). Consequently, the importance of societal reaction should not be underestimated in understanding why women who use drugs are largely invisible, however the literature reviewed in preparation for this study points towards a variety of complex and overlapping factors.

The utility of hidden population research

Why is it important to concentrate effort and resources into the understanding of drug using populations who appear to require no intervention?

There is a considerable and growing body of research to suggest that drug related harm is context dependent (Duff, 2007). Consequently, there is an urgent need to contextualise drug use as current understandings fit only poorly with realities faced by drug users (Moore and Fraser, 2006), (McPhee, 2013). Hidden population studies to date are predominantly public health oriented and it is argued that the knowledge generated from this kind of research, very rich in context, can be translated into effective harm reduction practices. For example, Moore (1993) highlights the implications of drug ethnography for public health by revealing the social controls in the form of social sanctions and rituals that contribute to a user ideology of harm minimisation.

Hidden population research may also be of particular interest to policymakers who approach problematic drug use from the perspective of prevention. How do women's drug problems begin and what can be done to prevent them from escalating? In bringing to light the range of social issues experienced by women who use drugs, this study could make a contribution to the emerging strategy to address Scotland's evolving drug death crisis.

Specifically, the findings may translate into more suitable environments for those who seek treatment to address the lack of appropriate services for women. What are the structural barriers to accessing treatment for those who desire to do so? Do any of the women presenting with problems desire to access treatment but cannot due to problems with employment, housing, childcare etc? Are there psychosocial barriers to accessing services such as fear of child protection or being stigmatised in the community? If so, the experiences of these women can be used to help create environments in which women feel safer in coming forward for help with drug related issues. From the women whose drug use is currently less problematic, how are the dangers minimised and what practises of harm reduction are in evidence? Hidden population research could bring to light any gender specific behaviours that keep women's drug use to a manageable and therefore concealable level.

The dark potential of hidden population research

Studying groups where apparently controlled and sensible use of illicit drugs constitutes the norm can thus generate valuable harm reduction knowledge that can be applied to populations where drug related problems are far more prevalent. While this is a laudable aim, it risks failing to recognise the importance of structural factors in shaping the individual experience of drug use. Society is an uneven playing field, and factors which act as protective in one setting might prove unattainable in another. Lack of sensitivity to this fact can lead to erroneous conceptions of hidden populations, (many of whom are middle class users) being marked by some superior individual trait, such as a greater degree of self-control that is absent in more visible populations or the absence of a specific gene that causes addiction and out of control-ness.

While it is interesting and important to know more about the lives of less researched populations of people who use illicit drugs, efforts to do so should be accompanied with some kind of attempt at understanding the role of privilege. If this is absent, the narratives from such studies run the risk of reinforcing inequality through the inscription of middle-class drug users as representative of responsible drug use.

Improving the methods of hidden population studies

Visible or captive populations are predominantly lower class disempowered people who use drugs. Understanding the phenomenon of hidden and visible populations requires that their social worlds be studied more closely, with a real sensitivity to context. Rosenbaum and Murphy (1990) suggest that data collection techniques in ethnographies of women who use drugs should take into account women's lifestyles and be conducted by researchers who can appreciate women's unique experiences. I develop this argument further in the next chapter in an in-depth discussion on the importance of researcher identity.

At present, hidden population research is a developing field of knowledge which requires an ongoing evaluation of different methods. While much inspiration has been drawn from the studies previously mentioned, there is very little in the way of methodical instruction particularly vis a vis the methods of recruitment used in snowball sampling which have been obscured for many years.

To date, research of this kind has been data driven, paying less attention to the processes of accessing the hidden population. While in reality most of the researcher's time is spent gaining access and building and maintaining trust with the social group, generally the research text

does not reflect this, focusing heavily on the data ‘extracted’ from participants. In such an approach much is being downplayed. The challenges of accessing hidden and hard to reach populations and how these were overcome, and also the role of the researcher in the construction of knowledge. Consequently, in this thesis, I devote more space than is customary to the recruitment process, offering up excerpts from the reflective diary, in order to address this barrier to further research of this kind. As Dickson- Swift et al (2007) rightly point out, too little attention is given to the processes of qualitative research. Purposeful documentation of these processes opens up space for new conversations and new evolutions in practice (Gergen and Gergen, 2000). My intent is to foster a dialogical engagement with other hidden population researchers in order to exchange insight and practical solutions to myriad challenges encountered during this process.

Aims and objectives of study

Traditional hidden population research has generated valuable insight into the nature of marginalised populations; however, the knowledge is limited by the way in which drug use is routinely interpreted through the lens of deviance, suggesting the behaviour to be characteristic of a minority group in society. Approaching the study of hidden populations from this particular perspective serves to reinforce the belief that taking illicit drugs is an inherently dangerous activity performed by characters of a dubious nature.

At present the characteristics of the hidden population of women who use drugs in Scotland are unknown. It is therefore reasonable to suspend any assumption with regards how their drug use should be categorised. That said, based on the evidence from other key hidden population studies and the barriers to seeking treatment in the climate of distrust it is not unreasonable to expect patterns of use that are more than ‘recreational.’ In this study, the definition of hidden populations is inclusive of a range in frequencies and patterns of use. The term will be used to describe the heterogeneous group of people who use illegal drugs in a variety of different ways, whose master status is not that of a ‘drug user’ and consequently remain largely invisible in a climate of prohibition and following McPhee (2013), illicit drug use will not be interpreted through the lens of deviance or pathology.

The overall aims of this exploratory study are to investigate:

1. The social and historical context of women’s drug use including relationship between participant narratives and the dominant narratives of drug use

2. The utility of narrative and ethnographic methods in researching hidden populations of women who use drugs in Scotland.

These research questions have been designed to interrogate how a cohort of women, as the most under researched aspect of hidden populations, construct themselves and other key features of their social worlds. It is hoped that the additional focus on methods will bring to light some of the main issues and challenges that arise from accessing and engaging with this unknown population in order to pave the way for future research that can then take a more targeted and specific approach.

Chapter Two: ‘Methodological Considerations’

Introduction

While the field of alcohol of drug studies has been largely characterised by research consisting of quantitative measurements and statistics, the impact of qualitative studies is now becoming more noticeable (Nichter et al, 2004). Hidden population research is a response to this quantitative bias, and most hidden population studies are qualitative in nature (Neale et al, 2005) The so called ‘user perspectives’ gained from this kind of research have been used for a variety of purposes such as; mapping trends of illicit drug use (Clatts, 2002), exploring barriers to accessing treatment services (Neale and Thompkins, 2007), and understanding the impact of drug policy on harm reduction (Cooper et al, 2005). Generally taking a naturalistic, interpretative approach (Ritchie et al, 2013), it is argued that qualitative research has the potential to create richer more nuanced accounts of human action (Gergen and Gergen, 2003).

However, coming from a poststructuralist perspective, Martin and Stenner (2004) contend that in contrast to the common belief that qualitative methods in drug research are the antidote to the dominance of the quantitative, both types of research may be seen as a ‘technology of government’. This is because they often both share the same realist ontological assumptions, namely that truth exists independently from the observer. This stands in contrast to the idealist conception of reality as consisting of multiple socially constructed meanings that are mind dependent (Benton and Craib, 2001).

According to Martin and Stenner (2004), a consequence of the ontological supremacy of realism within the field of drug studies, is that great emphasis is placed upon using the correct methods to determine truth, as opposed to spending more time reflecting on the philosophical underpinnings of our endeavours. The purpose of this chapter is to answer this call for reflection. According to Kothari (2004) when we talk of research methodology we talk ‘*not only of the research methods but also consider the logic behind the methods we use in the context of our research study and explain why we are using a particular method or technique and why we are not using others*’ (Kohari, 2004:8). Research methods are thus but one aspect of the research methodology. It is with this key distinction in mind that I explore the logic behind the methods, or the philosophical and theoretical underpinnings of the study in this

chapter, focusing later on the particular methods employed in chapter 4 ‘accessing and engaging hidden populations’.

The reflexive turn

Both naturalism and positivism engage in a joint concern with ‘eliminating the effects of the researcher on the data’ (Hammersley and Atkinson, 1983:15). The strongly held assumptions about a reality which exists in separation from its observer means the role and contribution of the researcher remains a common point of attack on qualitative methods in general, on the basis that researcher subjectivity is viewed as a form of bias interfering with the objective process of data collection (Bryman, 2012). However, Hammersley and Atkinson (1983) point to the futility of this endeavour, given that we as researchers are part of the social world in which we study:

‘Both positions assume that it is possible, in principle at least, to isolate a body of data uncontaminated by the researcher, either by turning him or her into an automaton or by making him or her a neutral vessel of cultural experience.’

(Atkinson and Hammersley, 1983:14)

This realisation has stimulated a reflexive turn in qualitative research, that is, the process whereby investigators attempt to demonstrate their historical and geographical situated-ness, believing true bias lies in the failure to be explicit about social and political backgrounds (Gergen and Gergen, 2003). While acknowledging and questioning the researcher’s existing viewpoint constitutes the very heart of reflexivity in qualitative research, the concept of reflexivity is marked by terminological ambiguity (Hamati- Ataya (2013). Particular importance is placed upon transparency by researchers who situate their inquiries within the critical paradigm, in which this study can be located. Rather than bracketing or attempting to control the values and assumptions of the researcher, the aim is to make those values and the way in which they shape the decisions made throughout the research process, explicit.

For Bulpitt and Martin (2010), embracing the self as a research instrument within qualitative inquiry can lead to very meaningful situated understandings of those with whom we form research relationships. Arguably, the most visible expression of a writer’s presence is the use of first-person pronouns and explicitly affirming one’s role in the discourse is key to the construction of an ‘authorial self’ (Hyland, 2002). Emphasising the interactive nature of academic discourse, first person writing brings together issues of audience and visibility, which

for Hyland, is the most effective means through which researchers can effectively convey a particular stance (Hyland, 2005). According to Hyland (2002):

“First person is a powerful means by which writers express an identity by asserting their claim to speak as an authority, and this is a key element of successful academic writing.”
(Hyland, 2002:1094)

Theoretically, the use of first-person challenges accepted wisdom and the notion of disembodied objectivity in academic writing. Increasingly creative forms of situated writing suggest a paradigm shift from an objectivist, ‘faceless’ form of discourse (Maroko, 2013). It can take many forms and writers have taken different approaches to engaging reflexive writing in research texts. For example, Alecia Youngblood Jackson (2004) inserts her voice and reflections as ‘interruptions’ in the text to foreground the constructed nature of her knowledge claims.

Indeed, as academic discourse becomes more widely accepted as a form of dialogical engagement between the writer and the reader (Hyland, 2005; Thompson, 2002), first person writing becomes increasingly legitimate. No longer a transparent window onto some external reality, the research text is viewed a means through which social relations are produced (Frank, 2010), thus raising important issues about identity and authority in knowledge making.

Consequentially, first person writing is used most often by prominent critics of the dominant modes of representation in scientific writing by researchers that align with marginalised research methodologies (Brown and Strega, 2005). Such difference- centred perspectives, of which feminism and indigenous research are examples, share in a concern that the minority status of many groups in society is perpetuated through research which fails to address the power relations inherent in knowledge production. Questions such as; ‘who has the authority to speak the truth?’ and ‘who owns this knowledge and why was it created?’ are of relevance to anti- oppressive researchers who defend the use of first person in academic writing (Brown and Strega, 2005).

Problematising realist ethnographies

In her Foucauldian analysis of drug policy and female ‘users’, Natasha Du Rose (2015) deploys the concept of governmentality to make sense of how women who use drugs are constructed as objects of government, outlining the rationalities that underpin these constructions. Adopting a critical perspective, the ‘problem’ of women’s drug use has less to do with risk based on scientific evidence and more to do with the desire to shape, guide, correct and modify

the behaviour of women who use drugs. The technologies of power which govern women drug use flow through a number of heterogeneous channels including non-state institutions such as the family, the church or the workplace. These mechanisms of control, as Du Rose points out, depend upon constructions of women who use drugs as problematic and pathological, visible in treatment interventions tailored specifically for females which situate them as unfit mothers (Du Rose, 2015).

Sensitive to this political dimension of researching women who use drugs, Nancy Campbell in 'Using Women', offers an interesting critique of realist ethnographies. Emphasizing the links between knowledge production and social control, Campbell (2000) raises important questions about 'state ethnographies' and the cultural meanings of women who use drugs they inscribe which are racialised and sexualised, particularly in the North American context. White women are generally constructed as 'cleaner' with different motivations for engaging in drug use than black women, 'dirty' addicts whose drug use has been historically depicted as driven by sexual compulsion. Drawing upon Foucault, Campbell refers to the dominant discourses of women who use drugs as governing mentalities, frames the issue of women's drug use and its regulation a matter of social justice as the dominant discourses reveal what appears to be a 'thin veneer of equality' amongst women.

Social constructionism

Becoming conscious of the politics of representation often leads to a crisis of purpose for many critical qualitative researchers (Ellis et al, 2008). For many researchers critical of mainstream research on illicit drug use, a social constructionist approach has the potential to shed light on the relations of power which influence the knowledge making process. Holstein and Gubrium (2008) speak of ethnography with a constructionist impulse as opposed to traditional ethnographic inquiry underpinned by a naturalistic view of social research:

'Whereas the naturalistic impulse in fieldwork is typically to ask "What is going on?" with and within social reality, constructionist sensibilities provoke questions about how social realities are produced, assembled and maintained. Rather than trying to get inside social reality, the constructionist impulse is to step back from that reality and describe how it is socially brought into being'.

(Holstein and Gubrium, 2008:375)

The assumption that knowledge is historically situated and therefore socially constructed underpins many different approaches to social research that can be perceived as critical or anti

-oppressive in nature including post modernism, Marxist, feminist and difference- centred (Brown and Strega, 2005). What these theories have in common is a shared critique of the epistemological and ontological foundations of Positivism and a vision for social research to create social change.

Epistemology: knowledge as partial and situated

Epistemologically speaking, the notion of situated knowledge challenges the traditionally held 'view from nowhere'. This disembodied objectivity which characterises the Enlightenment project has been referred to by critical thinkers as 'the god trick' which obscures the power relations inherent in knowledge production. That knowledge is historically contingent, stands in contrast to the belief that socially situated 'beliefs must break ties with the local, with values and agendas, in order to gain the status of knowledge (Harding, 1993). This matter is of huge significance to many critical scholars, not least of all for feminist writers such as Sandra Harding (2007) and Donna Haraway (1988) who have offered sustained critique on the embedded assumptions of scientific practice. Put simply, situated knowledges imply a relationship between who you are and what you know.

In agreement, Takacs (2003) suggests that much of what we have deemed to be universal truths may in fact be shaped by identity and life experiences. It is therefore necessary to cultivate a sense of 'informed scepticism' that involves questioning the authority of all knowledge sources, including ourselves. After all, by its very nature, situated knowledge implies a boundaried perspective, outside of which things can become difficult to see. That agents of knowledge are both embodied and socially located complicates the traditional view of relationship between the subject and the object of knowledge; the same kinds of social forces which shape the lives of objects (in this case women who use drugs) may also shape the lives of subjects or knowers (in this case myself) (Harding, 1993).

Situated knowledge implies an inextricable link between knowledge and experience. Knowledge is situated by one's social location which is comprised of multiple experiences of privilege and oppression (Brown and Strega, 2005). To illustrate this point, Moosa Meetha (2005) gives the example of racialisation, suggesting that is not possible to understand what it means to be racialised unless you have had that experience. According to Patricia Hill Collins (2002), a prominent voice within the black feminist thought movement:

'it is impossible to separate the structure and thematic content of thought from the historical and material conditions shaping the lives of its producers'

(Hill Collins, 1986:16).

In seeking to understand the social forces which shape the lives of black women, black feminist thought draws upon everyday experience and social theory. In essence, this represents a reconciliation of subjectivity and objectivity, the marrying of what we have been trained to see as opposites. Writers like Collins try to convey this both/and conceptual stance by becoming visible in this text through the use of first person, whilst maintaining rigorous standards of critical analysis.

Theories of situated knowledge have developed to challenge the dominance of Enlightenment epistemology which rests on binary oppositions that privilege the white, and the male above the dark and the female, investing the former with rationality and the latter with irrationality (Strega, 2005). This Eurocentric mode of thinking has had major consequences for knowledge production which critical scholars sensitive to gender, race and class differences have sought to address. Speaking of women caught within the psychiatric gaze, Diana Rose explains:

'We are defined by our unreason or irrationality, our closeness to brute nature, are deemed overwhelmed by our emotions. Rationality and intellect are the province of those who help us and those who do research into our condition'

(Rose, 2009:45)

The status of knowledge produced by those who socially and politically locate themselves is thus often deemed inferior, unreliable and inherently problematic. Contesting this asymmetrical division is the basis of theories which challenge the normative assumptions of mainstream approaches to social research. In an attempt to redress the embedded inequality, feminist theories have responded in different ways to hierarchical dualism, challenging (white male) representations of womanhood and normative constructions of gender. While individualist feminists have emphasised woman's sameness to men, relational feminists, on the other hand, valorised woman's difference suggesting that woman's unique characteristics are complementary to men (Cranny-Francis et al, 2007).

Difference centred theorists have a problem with the universality inherent in the previous responses. Arguing that both individualist and relational feminists attempt at addressing inequality keeps the fundamental hierarchy intact, they suggest attempts at furthering social

change with these approaches are likely to be limited. What is required is an approach which moves beyond the same/different binary.

Difference centred feminist theory works against the silencing impulse of ‘othering’ (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003). This is important as women who use drugs are positioned by the discourse of rationality in multiple sites of disadvantage and the dominant discourses of drug use which imply an inherent pathology. This positioning leads a devaluation of their experiential knowledge and also to a devaluation of feminist scholars who research and align with them (Ettorre, 2017).

Such situated experiential knowledge has the potential to challenge these forms of oppression, evidenced by the survivor research movement in the field of mental health, which has at its base a desire to challenge the very meanings placed on their experiences by psychiatry, producing a body of knowledge to counter medical models of madness (Rose, 2009). However, it is important to state however that experiential knowledge does not always pose a challenge to the structures and institutions that govern women’s drug use. The proliferation of recovery narratives which seek to centre lived experience in recent years has arguably reinforced the dominant discourse in situating women’s drug experiences within a disease model of addiction. Hence, the centring of lived experience does not automatically challenge or resist the production of stereotypical understandings. What is required is an approach that places situated knowledge at the centre, whilst embracing differences in women’s experiences. Unlike ‘othering’, difference does not render that which is not the ‘same’ as inferior (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003). This particularly important in light of the existing literature which underscores the inherent heterogeneity of hidden populations of people who use drugs.

Ontology: The problem of relativism and multiple truths

For some feminist theorists, rejecting universalism does not inevitably lead to a position of epistemological relativism (Harding, 1993). Proponents of feminist standpoint theory, for example, suggest that while a range of different views about the world exist, there are some social situations which make for better starting points for scientific projects and starting thought from the perspective of the most disadvantaged can reveal much about the social order (Hekman, 1997). From this vantage point, the lives from which thought has started are always present and visible in the results of that thought, irrespective of the removal of all traces of the personal through the ways in which the scientific method is operationalised. According to

standpoint theory, the perspective of the dominant in society is ‘partial yet perverse’ while the knowledge which comes from the subordinate is closer to ‘truth’.

Standpoint theory might offer a workable solution to the problem of relativism whilst rooting knowledge to lived experience, however as Hekman (1997) points out, it still presupposes an outside reality, an underlying truth waiting to be represented by those with privileged positions. Not as concerned with the visibility of the subject of knowledge (the knower) as it is with disrupting the ‘delusion’ of a scientific project that transcends historical location that is typical of dominant groups in this age, standpoint theory inevitably creates a power dynamic whereby the researcher or knower becomes the expert with the ability to interpret the meaning of the experiences of the researched.

Indeed, narrative scholar Arthur W. Frank’s discomfort with the interpretivist claim of privileged access to realities which are denied to the uninitiated is largely what motivates him to develop an alternative approach to the making of meaning from qualitative accounts of the social world (Frank, 2010). While interpretation cannot be avoided, it can be achieved in a manner sensitive to the politics of interpretive privilege without ‘*making peoples inability to know their own truth a principle of the human condition*’ (Frank, 2010:93). The question of knowing the truth of one’s own life leads on to a consideration of the ‘subject’ and the underlying set of assumptions regarding the nature of human beings which guide and influence interpretation of data.

Theorising ‘the subject’ in gender studies

According to Rebughini (2014), the subject and subjectivity are key concepts which bring together the interrelated disciplines of sociology, social theory and philosophical reflection. Owing to the diversity in theoretical orientation there exists a wide range of definitions and understandings of these terms. For example, subjectivity may be viewed as interiorization of domination or as an expression of emancipation and free will. Theories of the subject and subjectivity are seen as vital within contemporary gender studies as they are key to understanding that gender is constructed and not natural or essential. Put simply, subjectivity is primarily concerned with understanding how we come to be as we are. Intended to replace notions of the self as a fully fixed, rational, autonomous being, the subject is viewed as less powerful and inescapably shaped by forces beyond their control (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003)

That there exists a common universal experience of having any specific gender for all whom identify with it, is the basis of an essentialist conception of gender identity. Feminist scholars

have contended with the problem of essentialism for decades. On the one hand, attributing a universal characteristic to all women, be it biological or sociocultural in nature, is damaging as it implies a common experience of womanhood. This takes no account of social positioning and too often, the experience of white privileged women is taken to represent all women. Indeed, one of the main weaknesses of feminist standpoint theory is that it constructs the category of woman as a unifiable whole. The radical feminist construction of 'women' as a meaningful identity category on the basis of having a shared experience of gendered oppression in the context of patriarchy is an idea that has been criticised by those who lean towards more culturally and historically sensitive understandings (Schrock, 2013).

However, in rejecting the essentialist foundations of writing on gender, feminist scholars found themselves at a political disadvantage without a unifying concept which allowed them to unite as a singular group with shared interests. This theoretical impasse is discussed at length by Alison Stone (2004) who builds on the Nietzschean influenced work of Judith Butler. Stone suggests a resolution in the form of understanding women as a group in so far as they share a common history of actively appropriating and reinterpreting the cultural meanings associated with femininity. Put simply, while there exists no universal characteristic that is shared by all women, women can in fact be perceived as a group insofar as they are collectively engaged in a process of redefining femininity. Far from having a shared experience of femininity, women are connected in a variety of complex and overlapping ways by their historical and continuous appropriation of existing standards of femininity, which are always being reinterpreted on the basis of diverse social contexts and personal histories. As Stone explains;

“Within a single generation, each woman’s reinterpretation of femininity will overlap in content, to varying degrees, with other women’s reinterpretations; these overlaps must arise, insofar as all these women are engaged in reworking the same set(s) of pre-existing meanings. An understanding of women as having a genealogy thus entails that, instead of forming a unitary group, they are connected together in complex ways and to varying degrees; and, in particular, that they are linked by their partially and multiply overlapping interpretations of femininity.”

(Stone, 2004: 20)

From a genealogical perspective, there are different branches of relationship, where each woman might be located. Taking this analogy further, these branches are connected to the trunk which represents a shared history of woman actively appropriating and defining femininity.

The closer the branch the more likely that a shared experience of womanhood exists. According to Stone (2004), this genealogical understanding of femininity allows a sense of unity to be retained in spite of the marked differences in the women's experiences of privilege and oppression. It generates a potential for collectivity, despite differences in positionality.

Closely related to this is the concept of strategic alliance discussed by Cranny -Francis et al (2003). From a postmodern perspective gender identity is fluid not fixed. It is multiple, split, and fractured. Such an understanding is politically useful, helping theorists to move beyond the normative and regulatory forces to form temporary bonds that an essentialist identity would struggle to achieve. As Cranny- Francis et al (2003) explain:

'In the post- modern scenario identity is not an essentialist attribute of an individual but a strategy which individual (complex and multiple) subjects can use to create new and varied alliances' (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003:35)

Acknowledging the anxiety felt by some thinkers such as bell hooks at the consequences of strategic alliance if differences are overlooked, women who use drugs from very different backgrounds could potentially act as a collective to challenge stereotypical and pathologising understandings. It is generally supposed that stereotypes are generated by those outside of a particular group and used as part of a wider political strategy to control that group (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003).

Difference centred theories such as intersectionality have developed in response to the perceived failings of 'white feminism'. Intersectionality theory calls for a more nuanced understanding of the role of other important factors in mediating women's experiences. Taking these concerns very seriously, anti -oppressive researchers like Moosa -Mitha (2005) refrain from the privileging of gender as a difference over any other.

Indeed, returning to the perspective of post structuralist feminism, the notion of subjectivity suggests a contradictory and fluid self that is shaped by language, power relations and discourses in the context of everyday practices and relationships (Jackson, 2004). As such, subjectivity is inherently unstable and escapes essentialisation by categories of identity such as race, class or gender. According to Jackson, a woman's subjectivity is one of 'becoming' rather 'being, in so far as her ways of existing in the world are shaped by social relations, material conditions and perhaps most importantly, historical experiences.

Furthermore, the situated meaning of signifiers such as ‘woman’ must also be taken into account: “The meaning of the signifier ‘woman’ varies from ideal to victim to object of sexual desire, according to its context. Consequently, it is always open to challenge and redefinition with shifts in context” (Weedon, 1997: 25). Understanding the construction of subjectivity as an active process shaped by dynamic discursive fields underscores the possibility of reconfiguration. As Jackson (2004) shows in her reflexive analysis of the category of ‘White Southern’, the sociocultural context produces often complicated subject positions for women to use as they construct their subjectivity.

Theories of the subject are implicated within studies which claim to give voice to an under-represented population. In the context of childhood studies Spyrou (2011) points out that the assumption of a unitary subject suggest that it is possible to grasp voice and represent its essence. At its foundations the idea that it is indeed possible to capture the essence of a subject through their words (MacClure, 2009). The notion of a subject which is transparent to themselves and to others is indicative of a rational unitary subject and this metaphysical assumption is implicated in both traditional survey research and more mainstream qualitative research in general (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008). Holloway and Jefferson challenge this idea that research participants are the ‘incontrovertible experts on their own experiences’. Proposing to move beyond the idea of a rational unitary subject these authors put forward a model of subjectivity that is heavily influenced by psychoanalytic theories of the unconscious;

“The notion of the defended subject is interested...threats to the self...either conscious or unconscious. This idea of a dynamic unconscious which defends against anxiety is seen as a significant influence on people’s actions, lives and relations. It means that if memories of events are too anxiety-provoking, they will be either forgotten or recalled in a modified, more acceptable fashion. Defences will affect the meanings that are available in a particular context and how they are conveyed to the listener, who is also a defended subject”

(Holloway and Jefferson, 2008)

The idea of the defended subject therefore questions the assumption of transparency to self and others that underpins traditional qualitative research. Such a model fails to account for the anxiety and unconscious defences that come into play when memories are overly threatening, thus affecting recall and the meaning conveyed to the listener. Psychoanalysis has long been influential in the development of feminist theories of subjectivity as ‘gender is always viewed

as primary in the production of subjects' (Cranny-Francis et al, 2013:50). Multiply marginalised and stigmatised subjects such as women who use drugs could easily be viewed as defended subjects as they routinely face threats to the self in the form of negative judgement. However, what are the consequences of approaching the study of women who use drugs in this way? If their motivations are largely unconscious, what are the consequences of this for the exercising of agency?

The problem of agency

In studies where the aim is to represent the voices and experiences of marginalised populations the overstating of agency is a particular point of contention:

“A reflexive approach to data analysis asks what kind of analytical frameworks and categories the researcher imposes on children’s voices. Does, for example, the overwhelming preoccupation with children’s agency guide researchers to focus on the creative, innovative and productive capacities of children (as evidenced through their own voices) at the expense of investigating social and cultural reproduction” (Spyrou, 2011:8)

Here, Spyrou speaks of the individualizing tendencies of ‘voice’ research which sets out to restore agency to groups which experience asymmetrical power relations in the context of childhood studies. This same problem has manifested in research on female drug use where feminists have sought to address early constructions of women who use drugs as weak, passive and without will power. It is also evident in other disciplines concerned with the construction of the female identity such as domestic abuse (Stuart et al., 2008; Logan et al., 2002), prostitution (Young et al, 2000), and constructions of girlhood in adolescence (Brown, 2011). In restoring agency however, critics think the pendulum has swung too far in the opposite direction. According to Lisa Maher (1997), our understanding of women who use drugs has thus historically been stunted by two dominant and opposing frameworks:

‘one emphasizing women’s victimization and dependence as the driving force for their drug use, the other depicting them as volitional actors virtually unfettered by social constraints’ (as cited in Miller and Carbone-Lopez, 2015:1).

Despite sustained effort to move beyond this limited way of thinking, often engaging performative theories of ‘doing gender’ such as that by Fiona Measham (2002), the field

remains stuck within the dualist constraints exposed by Maher in (1997). In the case of women's initiation into methamphetamine use for example, Carbone – Lopez (2012) points to the pervading paradigm of 'pathology and powerlessness' that frames the experiences of women who use drugs. Using drugs to cope with trauma and being exploited by intimate partners are two of the specific themes that proliferate. While these may be adequate explanations in a number of cases, many commentators agree on the need for a more nuanced perspective.

Subjectivity through the lens of narrative

In the context of women speaking about sexual experiences, Frith and Kitzinger (1998) take to task analysts which take a transparent approach to female talk in interaction, in this case using it as evidence for the existence of 'emotion work', a feminist concept which constructs women as over responsible for the emotional wellbeing of the opposite sex, sometimes to their own detriment. Conversely, by imagining the alternative position that women are resisting in and through this discourse, Frith and Kitzinger argue the theory of emotion work is an artefact of women's careful negotiation of identity as they speak *with other females* about unwanted sexual advances. Emphasising emotional capacity and awareness in taking care of emotionally inferior male counterparts is a preferable explanatory framework which avoids personal deficit that may be implied if one was to openly admit to engaging in an unwanted sex act.

In 'Letting Stories Breathe', Arthur Frank (2010) sets out in his framework for a socio-narratology the idea that stories are 'more than representations that depict life'. A mimetic view which holds that stories act like windows is rejected by scholars of narrative analysis who insist that stories are more like a sketch of a window. This analogy is very useful in understanding what thinkers who reject mimetic understandings are interested in. As Frank points out, one would not attempt to look beyond the sketch of a window to see what lies beyond, the sketch itself is interesting enough. In like manner, stories do not imitate an independent social reality but constitute a social reality in and of themselves (Frank, 2010).

The bulk of research on women and drug use reviewed for this study adopts this transparent approach to analysis. What participants say about any given experience is assumed to be an accurate reflection of that experience, whilst recognising the limitations of retrospective self-report methods. Hidden populations research operating from such a realist perspective such as that by McPhee (2013), by claiming to more or less faithfully represent a truth about drug use which exists independently of the values and positioning of the researcher, are likely to take the alternative narratives as proof of a different kind of population of people who use drugs.

Focus is on finding ways to improve the validity of the findings, and there is little room for speculation about the relationship between methodology and the production of that particular 'truth'.

Challenging approaches which gloss over the constitutive power of language to arrive at forms of meaning are narrative researchers influenced by post structuralism or post modernism (Andrews et al, 2013). The post-structural theory of discourse holds that research participants are only ever capable of locating themselves in relation to existing truths. The individual has a degree of agency but only with the limits determined by discourse. The researcher's position involves a kind of double shift, from observer of reality to observer of observers of reality. This involves paying attention to the dual issues of construction and function. In viewing accounts of drug use in terms of what they accomplish for the teller and not simply as statements of factuality, Martin and Stenner (2004) construct plausible functions of their participants accounts of heroin use. For example, in analysing one particular account of heroin initiation, the speaker is seen to be seeking exoneration for problematised conduct which he achieves through the distribution of agency and therefore responsibility.

In her study of child sexual abuse, Hunter (2009) carefully framed her research so as to allow participants to make sense of their experiences in their own way. She presents four core types of narrative from this data; narratives of silence, of transformation, of ongoing suffering and of transcendence. Narratives of transcendence are characterised by the teller's refusal to be cast as a victim or a survivor. For example, Diana, who was raped by 14 men at aged 14, went as far as to state categorically that she would rather be viewed as a slut than a victim. Although theories of subjectivity are not mentioned by Hunter explicitly, her analysis is an excellent example of how narrators actively construct alternative subjectivities in research encounters in the context of sensitive topics. Such subject positions may not appear rational to the listener, but they are usually very functional for the teller. In the case of Diana, it may well be possible that her peculiar reflexive positioning as a 'slut' served the purpose of avoiding the feelings of disempowerment, vulnerability and stigma that can result from the telling of victim/survivor narratives (Philips and Danaluk, 2004, McDonnell et al, 2017). Indeed for many of the participants in Hunters study, particularly those who told narratives of transcendence, the dominant discourses of sexual abuse were problematic insofar as they anchored the sense of self to this negative experience, and although it had impacted upon them in many significant ways, they choose not be defined their wounds, wishing to be viewed as a person within their own right.

Complicity and conscientization

In exploring theories of the subject, the aim is to arrive at a reasonable point of view concerning whether the people we research are capable of 'knowing their own truth'. This has been a matter of importance for feminist theorists, many of whom seek to explain why women often appear to be complicit in their own oppression. Marxist feminists have mobilised the concept of false consciousness to explicate such complicity while Freudian based theories of subjectivity have understood it in terms of the unconscious which drives much of human behaviour. Either way, the answer to interrupting complicity is a process of conscientisation, an increase in awareness of the conditions of reality and one's part in its reproduction (Cranny Francis et al, 2003).

If this fundamental premise is accepted, then knowledge created by institutions such as the university has a role in effecting this increased self-awareness for those we research. In order to effect social change where research subjects are unwittingly recreating the conditions of their own oppression, the 'enlightened' researcher must assume the role of expert and exercise interpretative authority over their 'less conscious' research subjects.

In assuming the role of 'enlightened' researcher seeking to raise the consciousness of subjects perceived to be complicit in their own demise, it becomes necessary to strive towards greater self-awareness. If privilege and oppression shape our own way of viewing the world, there exist the ever-present risk of viewing the 'Other' through the lens of 'Self', of becoming a normalising force. Taking one's own reality for granted as universal and using it as a model with which to interpret the behaviour of those who exist within a very different social context often leaves no choice but to pathologise the individual in some way when that behaviour doesn't appear to be rational. However, when viewed from the lens of the individual's social context their behaviour is more often than not intelligible. For this reason, many anti-oppressive researchers position in relation to research participants as looking from the bottom up, a learner in different social worlds. As such, researchers are active participants in the co-construction of meaning with research participants and should tread carefully with the desire to finalise participant's narratives. It is within this spirit that one remains open to shifting, what Frank (2010) calls horizons, to accommodate new understandings as a result of moving through the research process.

Negotiating complex subject positions: between choosing and being chosen

Discursive analytic approaches have been criticised for being naively deterministic in their views about social reproduction (Breeze, 2011). Taking post- structuralist notions of subject positioning as a starting point has the potential to generate insight into the formation of drug using subjectivities. In relation to subject positioning in narrative analysis it is essential to understand that;

‘while telling stories, individuals do not speak from a single position. As they draw on available storylines, public discourses and others’ stories, storytellers’ positions continuously change in relation to what discursive resources they deploy. Moreover, while the notions of ‘positioning’ and ‘subject position’ might suggest that people are choosing subjects, as indeed we mostly think of ourselves as doing, the constructionist account of narrative asks us to understand ourselves as chosen, as much as choosing.’ (Esin et al, 2014:7)

The constructionist view of narrative makes sense when we consider the nature of ‘choices’ that women make in constructing a subjectivity as they speak about their drug experiences. Adopting a particular subject position that gives a sense of being an acceptable human being often results in a reproduction of the social structure. For example, in adopting a victim position in their stories of illicit drug use, women gain a sense of moral superiority and integrity, but they achieve this at a very dear cost. In effect, victimhood implies lack of responsibility but the flip side of this is lack of power. As women who use drugs are motivated by the social context of stigma and discrimination to abdicate responsibility, they are given a perverse incentive to give away their personal power and autonomy through the identification with a victimised subjectivity. Through a process of identification with victimhood which reduces social sanctioning, women come to internalise this passivity and vulnerability, performing the stereotypical femininities that they had sought out to resist (Williams, 2017).

In similar vein, Martin and Stenner (2004) highlight the compromise one makes in constructing accounts of drug use which function as ‘excuses’. The cost of distributing agency and therefore responsibility is a troubled position in relation to larger liberal discourses of the autonomous self. Applying a post structural lens involves seeing the work of wider cultural discourses of drug use in the women’s narratives. It involves thinking about the ways in which negative constructions may serve as functional not only for institutions, but so too for the women themselves.

The overarching aim is to create a sketch of women's drug experiences that allows for agency, whilst shedding light on the ways in which the social context and structure limit and contain possibilities for how women who use drugs position and present to others. Post-structural renderings of discourse and subjectivity holds promise for furthering this aim as evidenced by the studies discussed above, however the political value of post structural theories that trouble notions of agency in this manner have been called into question (Andrews et al, 2013). Despite concerns regarding the overstating of individual power and responsibility in debates over conscientization, the idea of complicity remains a useful concept with which to explore the experiences of women who use drugs.

From an alternative angle, the idea of complicity is potentially problematic when it comes to the issue of drug use as it appears to support the notion that certain aspects of the population do harm to themselves out of ignorance. This assumption underpins public health approaches to problematic substance use, including campaigns targeted at tobacco smoking and alcohol consumption. It is believed that if individuals are educated about the negative outcomes of their choices, then they will cease to engage in such problematic behaviours. At the foundations of this approach is a humanistic understanding of agency which assumes that with increased self-knowledge people will have the power to transform the conditions of their existence (Andrews, 2013). Indeed, at the core of the individualisation theses of sociologists such Beck and Giddens is this belief in the ability of people to make changes to their lives in response to knowledge about social circumstances. For them, reflexivity, defined as '*the ability to act critically in the world in ways that reduce struggles over power and politics*' (Boazalek and Zembylas, 2017: 3), was a skill that could be learned as a means to emancipation.

However feminist theorists, following in the footsteps of Donna Haraway, have called into question this theory of the reflexive self which can be located in late modernity, and its potential for social transformation. At its most basic sense, reflexivity, suggests stepping back and looking at one's actions and intentions from a distance, which assumes a human agency that works alone and intentionally. Here the individual, capable of interpreting from a distance, is the constitutive force. For Boazalek and Zembylas (2017) this results in a replication of the same, reinforcing the binary between self and other. This way of thinking and reading has consequences for the theorizing of difference, which remains a central objective of critical feminist scholarship (Cranny-Francis et al, 2015).). That said, although reflexivity is viewed by some feminist theorists as limited in its capacity to effect social transformation, it nonetheless provides a mode of situated writing with which to locate the researcher in the text,

increasing transparency and furthering the aims of the present study. In the following chapter, ‘locating the researcher’ I explore further the nuances of positionality and demonstrate first person, reflexive writing through the inclusion of an autographic vignette.

The promise of narrative

According to Bochner (2012), in the 1980’s and 1990’s, social science writers, against the rationalist and mechanistic mainstream discourses, advocated for the narrative turn, in recognition that narrative is the primary vehicle by which human beings communicate experience. This meant turning attention towards processes of meaning making;

‘focusing on the functions of stories and storytelling in creating and managing identity; the expressive forms for making sense of lived experience and communicating it to others; the entanglements that permeate how interpersonal life is lived and how it is told to others; the reflexive dimensions of the relationship between storytellers and story listeners; and the canonical narratives that circulate /through society, offering scripted ways of acting.’ (Bochner, 2012: 155)

Generally speaking narrative research takes a critical position against naturalism, highlighting the different and often contradictory layers of meaning present in accounts of the social world (Andrews et al, 2013) (Esin et al, 2014). While narrative methodologies can be underpinned by various epistemological positions which can be drawn together in challenging the dominance of the positivist and post-positivist paradigms (Clandinin, 2006), narrative analysis underpinned by social constructionism is interested in how narratives operate dialogically between the personal and social world (Smith, 2016).

The popularity of the narrative turn in social science research is related to the success of its proponents in claiming that such genres as the life story and the narrative of personal experience are pivotal to a rich and nuanced understanding of social phenomena’ (De Fina, 2009). A focus on narrative differs from purely content based qualitative methods in that attention is paid to what is communicated by the research subject as well as how the information is communicated, which gives added insight into the phenomenon under study.

It has been suggested that narrative is the primary vehicle through which human beings communicate experience in the recognition that human beings live naturally ‘storied lives’ (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000). Narrative research is therefore a methodology that is primarily concerned with the understanding of an individual’s lived experience. As Smith (2007) points out, narrative is a key process in the construction of self and identity. It is thus hoped that

adopting a constructionist narrative approach in this difference centred feminist analysis, can help to shed light on the issues of agency, subjectivity and complicity which are implicated in women's studies in general and in the study of women's drug use in particular. A narrative lens foregrounds women's process of becoming and the gendering capacity of storytelling, with the promise of revealing how in the course of female talk in interaction, women who use drugs are engaged in the active redefining of cultural standards of femininity.

Conclusion

The main aim of this chapter is to explore the interrelations of knowledge, truth and power and how this comes to bear on the research process. This has been particularly important in the present study because the knowledge that is produced about women who use drugs has been used to legitimise forms of social control and symbolic violence which manifests in oppressive state policies and creates a pattern of social relations and discourses which constitute women who use drugs as pathological subjects (Campbell, 2002).

Consequently, I locate the present study within a critical anti -oppressive framework, where knowledge is viewed as partial and socially constructed and always political (Brown and Strega, 2005). From the notion of multiple truth and situated meanings comes the question of how to evaluate the research project. What criteria do we use to judge the quality of research which does not make positivist or post-positivist claims to represent reality as it really is? (Potts and Brown, 2005). For Kirby and McKenna (1989), there are many means to achieve this and one important way is to articulate as clearly as possible our intellectual baggage, that is, the conceptual frameworks through which we interpret our data. In this chapter I have tried to problematise the relationship between research methods and certain knowledges of drugs and the people who use them through a particular critique that is both ontological and epistemological in nature.

In particular, recent developments in feminist theory have raised many questions surrounding the nature of the subject and agency. Applying these insights to the present task of accessing and understanding hidden populations of women who use drugs I follow the suggestion of Miller and Carbone-Lopez (2015) who suggests a more progressive understanding of women and illicit drug use can only come from relating theoretical insight from the fields of gender studies and drug use respectively. Like many other feminist theorists I consciously employ a position of strategic essentialism, taking forward a theory of reflexivity which has at its roots a rational, unitary understanding of the subject for the purposes of generating critical self-reflexive knowledge with regards how best to research hidden populations, whilst exploring

theories of fragmented and multiple subjectivities in an attempt to construct a more nuanced understanding of agency. This chimes with Beverley Skeggs experience (1994) when she describes the tensions one must grapple with in feminist theorising, trying to reconcile empirical observations (with naturalist assumptions) from ethnographic fieldwork to critical theories which hold that such naturalism is undesirable or indeed, impossible.

Reflecting upon lessons learned from conducting a post-structural ethnography, Britzman's (2002) advice is to proceed with caution, cognizant of the ever present danger of slipping into traditional modes of representation and essentialising the humanistic subject, ignoring the competing storylines, the contradictory meanings and subjectivities which 'refuse to stand still' in favour of producing a cohesive, unitary account. Indeed, for Alicia Youngblood Jackson (2004), it is in emphasising complexity and plurality, in avoiding essentialised notions of what it means to be a specific category of woman, in this case women who use drugs, that keeps signs unstable and open to redefinition (Youngblood Jackson, 2004:3). It is important to state, that in using critical feminist theories to highlight the compromised state of autonomy, the aim is not to construct women who use drugs as predetermined and incapable of exercising choice. On the contrary, through analysis of the structures which contain and limit autonomy, the hope is that ways to challenge dominant forces in society will become apparent (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003).

Narrative research informed by a constructionist impulse thus invites us to think about the framing of research topics and the consequences of viewing a topic in a particular way. With this in mind, the present study will explore the possibilities of the narrative interview for constructing alternative subjectivities for women who use drugs *when care is taken not to import existing (problematic) analytic frameworks onto their experiences*. Like Carbone-Lopez et al (2012) I am compelled to know if, in doing so, women articulate their drug related experiences in a manner consistent with dominant depictions, or, do they bring to our awareness altogether different reasons and explanations?

Chapter Three: ‘Locating the researcher ‘

On a very practical level, gaining access to this hidden population of women who use drugs required a great deal of personal investment, drawing upon the resources of me as a person in addition to those of me as a novice researcher. Particularly in the recruitment of participants where the building of trust and rapport was essential (this is explored in depth in the next chapter ‘Accessing and engaging’). At this stage in the research process, a degree of immersion within the participants social world was necessary for them to overcome any doubts about letting me in to the ‘inner circle of trust’, where I would later learn about their private experiences with illegal drug use. Being present as a thinking, feeling human being behind the narrative was therefore very important. Consequently, I grappled with the idea of writing entirely in first person to firmly locate myself within the research text and underline my active role as a research tool. While this felt like the right thing to do, it ran counter to my socialisation as an academic who had not up until this point over ten years into higher education, questioned the common practice of obscuring the ‘self’ in scientific writing. As Bochner (2012) points out, we are groomed to engage in particular modes of research and to create very specific types of research texts in the interests of conformity.

Discovering that it was increasingly common for narrative researchers to include their own reflective written or oral comments on the interviews (Squire, 2013), I resolved this crisis of positioning through the inclusion of an auto-ethnographic element to the study. Ellis and Bochner (2000) define auto-ethnography as:

“an autobiographical genre of writing or research that displays multiple layers of consciousness, connecting the personal to the cultural” (as cited in Humphreys, 2005: 841).

The term may be used synonymously with autobiographical ethnography (Reed-Danahay, 1997), first person accounts (Ellis, 1998) or self- stories (Denzin, 1989). Auto-ethnographies can be complete or partial, such as in the use of autobiographical vignettes demonstrated by Humphreys (2005). As Marechal explains;

“Partial autobiographical accounts have also long been used in analytic ethnographic fieldwork to supplement ethnographic narration and provide the readers with details which unveil how fieldwork was concretely performed, often presented separately from the main ethnographic narrative” (Marechal, 2009: 3)

From the beginning of this research process I have kept a reflective research diary (Ortlipp, 2008). This diary documents my own experiences of accessing and interviewing the women from an explicitly situated, partial perspective. The reader will find the most pertinent excerpts of the diary, very rich in context, interwoven throughout the body of this research text. According to Judith Okely, the enduring legacy of Cartesian dualism has created a privileging of the cerebral in fieldwork, while the embodied nature has lacked the level of scrutiny it deserves (2007). For Okely, ethnography is a '*physical labour, a bodily interaction and sensory learning*' (Okely, 2007: 65) Through focusing on this aspect of fieldwork in her discussions with ethnographers from many different cultures, Okely locates the bodily experience of researchers as a legitimate source of knowledge. In my reflective writing I tap into this source of knowledge and suggest its particular significance for the study of women's drug use.

First person narrative is used purposefully within this thesis to assist the reader in approaching the text from a more critical standpoint, restoring dimensions of context so often missing in contemporary qualitative works. In doing so, I welcome charges of solipsism, and their potential to stimulate debate on the important yet neglected issue of voice within research texts (Clandinin and Connelly, 2010).

Elsewhere I write from an apparently more objective standpoint in keeping with the expectations of those who will ultimately judge the quality of this thesis. Like Hyland (2005), I recognise that controlling the level of personality in academic writing is crucial for building a convincing argument. However, in the spaces in which my voice has been neutralised and my self-hood obscured, I continue to be the woman who lives and loves and feels guilt and pleasure and fear and shame, just as the women being researched here so often do. Here I may be speaking in a passive voice but in doing so I am making an active decision to construct my subjectivity in such a way as to be accepted by the wider academic community, in much the same way as the women you are about to encounter choose to present their experiences with drugs in a socially acceptable manner. That researchers shape academic texts in relation to the expectations of an audience is increasingly acknowledged (Hyndland, 2005: Clandinin and Connelly, 2010).

Positionality

Emerging from the reflexive critique of Positivism is the concept of researcher 'positionality'. Elsewhere positionality is described as stance, such as by Savin-Baden and Howell Major (2010). Generally speaking, positionality refers to the researcher's world view as it relates to the subject, which is underpinned by their views on the nature of reality (ontology), knowledge (epistemology) and human nature and agency (Holmes, 2014; Sikes, 2004). However as with reflexivity, the question of what constitutes a researcher's positionality is a matter of ongoing debate. Alternative understandings of positionality marked by differences in what is deemed important to share are influenced by the researcher's epistemological stance and related ways of knowing. Therefore, this section builds upon the previous discussion, and attempts to apply theory to practice.

On a basic level, for Holmes (2014), positionality consists of fixed aspects which are culturally ascribed such as nationality, gender and race. In addition to the more fixed components of a researcher's identity, there are more subjective aspects of positionality which are rooted within personal experience. These elements, which 'colour' the researcher's philosophical commitments, tend to change over time, and as such reflect the chosen position of the researcher within the context of any given research project. According to Holmes (2014) there are three main points to cover on positionality statement: the researcher's stance in relation to the subject, the participants and the research context and process. However, at present there exists no real consensus about positionality and how it can best be defined.

While fixed aspects of a researcher's positionality may predispose him or her to certain views about a subject, it is wise not to assume any particular perspective on the basis of a researcher's political or religious affiliation (Milner, 2007). The key concern for critical researchers is to contemplate and make apparent where they stand with respect to power in society (Takacs, 2002).

The dilemma of disclosure for drug researchers

Being a reflexive scholar involves acknowledging the self in research and considering how it impacts upon the research process, but, as Arnold (1997) states, the understanding that all knowledge is partial and situated does not translate into one form of reflexivity. Many researchers defend the concept of reflexivity but find it very difficult to put into practice; demonstrating the situated nature of knowledge is thus a challenge in and of itself, full of

inherent ambivalences and anxieties. Indeed *'for many auto-ethnographers, there is the question of how far along the self- disclosure/exposure and vulnerability route we wish or feel compelled to situate ourselves, and how "honest" we decide to be in creating and representing the "auto/biographical I" (Allen-Collinson, 2013:5).* Researchers that self- expose within particularly sensitive topics undoubtedly occupy an 'anxiety ridden space' (Vickers, 2002). This matter is particularly pertinent to the present topic. Traditionally ethnographers have chosen to frame their positionality statement within the boundaries of insider/ outside debate, but drug use researchers face potential negative consequences in disclosing the self, when that involves being honest about one's own illegal activity. While research has shown positive outcomes in ethnography where participants feel they can identify with the researcher (see Adler and Adler, 1987) the illegal nature of the social practice under investigation poses an ethical dilemma of disclosure.

In actuality, the subject of my own drug use only rarely came up during the course of interaction with research participants. On one single occasion whilst conducting the interviews I was asked outright whether I had ever 'dropped acid'. I replied simply with a nod. Presenting myself as an 'in group member', to use the language of ethnography, has not been an easy decision to make. In doing so I render myself vulnerable to the stigma and discrimination that women who use drugs routinely face, regardless of differences in regularity or functionality of use.

That said, I firmly believe that my openness and willingness to share aspects of my own experiences where it has been appropriate to do so, has been essential for the building of trust which lies at the foundations of the series of relationships which constitute this research. I fully agree with Leigh Berger (2001) when she claims that *'the inclusion of an autoethnographic method allows her to be more empathic toward those engaged in her study but also how sharing her stories with her field participants fosters their openness as well'*(Berger, 2001:507).

As Clandinin and Connelly (2000) advocate, the most useful starting point of any qualitative inquiry is the consideration of one's own experiences with the research subject. Indeed, many narrative inquirers, novice and experienced alike, use their own experiential knowledge as a signpost for potential exploratory avenues with their research participants. There is both risks and benefits in taking this approach. This work is unlike most narrative inquiries, in that my own stories about taking illegal drugs do not take a prominent place within the text. Although researcher's experiences are an important feature of narrative inquiry, this voice should never overshadow the voices and experiences of participants. As I have deemed it necessary to tell

the stories of accessing and interviewing the women, this has been a very delicate balance. On the basis that all *“interpretive research begins and ends with the biography and self of the researcher (Denzin, 1986: 12),* at the conclusion of this thesis, I include an epilogue, in which I consider the way in which my own narrative of drug use has transformed through the research process.

A salient aspect of positionality in the context of researching illicit drug use is the researcher’s position in relation to the larger political debate about drug policy. At present it is not general practice to state your position within this debate under the guise of scientific objectivity. Having said that, it is important to recognise that *‘stating their political affiliations does not somehow mean that they are absolved from the need for objectivity in their research’* (Breeze, 2011:501). Whether the views of the researcher are implied or explicitly stated, political persuasion can usually be assumed on the basis of whether the researcher appears to condone or condemn illegal drug use and is further evident through the recommendations made for policy, which may be for reform in the shape of legalisation, regulation or indeed a stricter form of control than is currently the case. Traditionally those aligning strictly with harm reductionist approaches purport to be neutral and value free on the topic of reform, neither advocating for or against policy reform per se, except insofar as one or the other may be shown to reduce drug related harm (Keane, 2003).

A matter of social justice

Viewing the issue of drug policy as primarily a matter of social justice does not mean that I dismiss the dangers of using illegal substances. On the contrary, my perspective arises out of concern for the reduction of associated harms and elimination of those unnecessary harms which stem from the policies of prohibition. Evidence that the Misuse of Drugs Act (1971) contributes to many of the harms associated with drug use is mounting and questionable child protection interventions represent but one example of the many additional problems caused by punitive prohibition. As Flacks (2018) has shown, children occupy a privileged position as the biggest victims of illicit drug use and as such are often used as a rhetorical device to resist drug policy reform.

Recent statistics have shown that Scotland is currently experiencing a public health emergency with the world’s highest rate of drug related death (McPhee, Sheridan and O’Rawe, 2019) and as highlighted in the introduction, a recent report has shown that an increasing numbers of

decedents are women (Tweed, Miller and Matheson, 2018). Seeking an alternative regulatory response to drugs within Scotland has thus become the focus of much debate surrounding illicit drug use (Christie, 2019), and an official enquiry was launched by The Scottish affairs Committee earlier this year. While consensus on the subject has been historically elusive, an overwhelming majority of the academics, health professionals and individuals with lived experience that gave evidence to the Committee sung in chorus for policy reform. Consequently, it appears some form of change is on the horizon. At the time of writing the opening of Scotland's first treatment facility offering heroin assisted therapy has been announced and it is hoped that this will go some way towards addressing the national overdose crisis and wider attitudes towards people who use drugs. While no perfect solution to this problem exists, the growing recognition that people who use drugs are not morally defective is one that is much needed within the current climate where stigma and discrimination add unnecessary fear and division to an already fractured society.

As is so often the case any shift within the policy landscape will likely result in unintended consequences. I am particularly wary of the recent shift towards conceptualising those with drug problems as sick as opposed to criminals. This may yield short term gain insofar as less people will be punished with criminal records for claiming sovereignty over their own blood/brain barrier. However much like Heather Brooke and Rebecca Stringer (2005), I worry that in the long run, viewing problematic drug use as an illness will do little to improve the lot of individuals who more than anything require support to take responsibility and control over their situation. In that respect, the debate between public health and criminal justice feels much like the good cop bad cop routine on a grand scale. The exercise of disciplinary power through discourses of public health may be subtler but therein lies its efficiency (In the words of Kath Woodward¹, you can't unread Foucault.)

Therefore, in concert with commentators such as Hathaway (2001) and Ezard (2001) I believe the way forward is to frame the drugs debate as a fundamental issue of human rights. In 2003 Helen Keane voiced concerns over whether mobilising the discourses of human rights for drug users would be politically efficacious, warning of the dangers of a political romanticism which could potentially overshadow the successes of concrete interventions. Since then, arguably must has changed. Much in line with Ezard's predictions, the failure of prohibition to protect the human rights of people who use drugs has hugely contributed to the rise in drug related

¹ Verbal communication within specialist seminar on insider/ outsider debate hosted by British Sociological Society, Sheffield Hallam University, March 2016.

harm that has been documented in recent years. The campaigning for the protection of the human rights of people who use drugs has thus become much less of an ideal and more of a necessity.

Reflections upon researcher identity

According to anti – oppressive researchers such as Absolon and Willett (edited by Brown and Strega, 2005), positionality involves much more than stating one’s politics, ethnic origin or geographical location. A key part of being accountable in the knowledge creation process, putting yourself forward at the outset of a research text requires an exploration of relationships to ‘*land, language, spiritual, cosmological, political, economic, environmental, and social elements in one’s life*’ (Brown and Strega, 2005:98). For Absolon and Willet, the only thing researchers of any kind can truly write about with any authority is the self, and such thorough location creates research texts which are the most ethical and likely to inspire trust in their readers. In like manner, Trussell (2014) challenges researchers to critically reflect upon their changing identity, and the impact of their own personal history on their epistemological lens. It strikes me that the enormity of such a task is overwhelming to most researchers, many of whom would likely question the necessity. Despite this, in the spirit of reflexivity I now offer a brief auto-ethnographic vignette (Humphreys, 2005) in order to locate my voice for the reader, and ultimately to connect the personal and social contexts from which this study takes place (Mizzi, 2010).

Auto-ethnographic vignette – ‘The Outsider Within’

I am a white Scottish, heterosexual female. I was born in 1985 and raised in a working-class family in a North Glasgow housing scheme. My mother worked in a college kitchen, my father sorted mail for the post office. Though their jobs were physically demanding my parents took a lot of pride in their work, and what I remember most is the sense of them both being very tired. In hindsight, I understand that the tiredness was more than physical. It was spiritual and psychological. Both parents had multiple adverse childhood experiences and yet, they struggled on, the impact of abuse and abandonment barely acknowledged. I was an incredibly lively and enquiring child, and not infrequently defiant. This must have added to their burden.

My passion for life stories began at an early age with the routine visiting of our elderly neighbours who over cups of tea would recount tales of evacuation and rationing in war time Scotland. I absorbed every detail with fascination and a genuine interest in their experiences. Depending on my motivation, which at that age may well have been to simply get more cake or avoiding going home, I learned to stretch stories, to ask questions to make a story go deeper and longer. My father, a devout Catholic, took us to chapel regularly, and it was here I developed my confidence for public speaking.

I learned very early on that our everyday use of the English language was looked down upon by others and there were times when a more formal speaking voice was appropriate. One of these times was during my father's somewhat wealthier English cousin's annual visit. To my amazement, my mother and father always appeared to transform in their presence. They would scold me for not 'talking right' and fuss unusually about my appearance. Of course, no sooner had they returned south of the border and the 'water' reverted back to 'watter', yes to 'aye' and so forth. This embedded a sense of shame in my identity, that who we were as people was somehow unacceptable, and had to be hidden. That social acceptability required a transformation in the presentation of the self.

My mother's family were Protestant and very working class, residing in the visibly deprived East end of Glasgow. Her cross-cultural marriage was not accepted by some of her elder family members and consequently she experienced an isolation. We spent a lot of time with the family members that remained in contact, but there existed a bitterness that was often poorly disguised with humour. As a bewildered child, I was alternately exposed to the sectarianism from both sides of the divide, but I learned how to survive in both worlds without drawing too much attention. Identifying with both, and to an extent neither, the duality of my experience meant that the entrenched 'us and them' mentality never took hold.

Amidst a bleak post-industrial landscape, the cottage flat we lived in was in a 'good' street. I found this out from my peer group at school, many of whom lived in appalling conditions, amongst rats and dampness in dilapidated tenement slums. We had a garden, and that made us 'toffs'.

The parents with drug and alcohol issues were well known in the scheme and I was expressly forbidden to enter the homes of those children who had the misfortune of having a 'junkie' for a mother. But being curious and thinking that everyone deserves a friend, I did so anyway, and every time I failed to discover the thing that had been the cause of my parent's fear.

Despite working full time my parents struggled financially, my father was often troubled about money, and yet I remember feeling ashamed that we were somehow 'better off'. To help out I delivered newspapers after school, but after being physically attacked on a number of occasions I never felt safe walking beyond the boundaries of our small community. Territorialism was an ever-present feature of my childhood, and the violently enforced boundaries between our community and neighbouring schemes determined much of my movement.

My attempts to adapt and survive in this frequently hostile environment led me to experience a somewhat troubled adolescence. During this period, I got involved in a female gang and engaged in daily drug and alcohol use and acquisitive crime. The members of this gang came from a range of different backgrounds, and on the surface this must have seemed strange. What we did have in common was a feeling that through our questionable behaviour we were resisting and challenging what it meant to be a girl. What first felt like a family with which I could perform this identity work and be safe, later became a toxic entanglement from which I struggled to free myself from. I regularly used many drugs at this point including alcohol, cannabis, amphetamines, benzodiazepines, MDMA, heroin and LSD. Over time my mental health seriously declined, and I began hearing voices and suffering paranoid delusions, which prompted me to drastically reduce my intake of mind-altering substances. Much of my energy went into keeping my mental ill health a secret out of fear of what people would think of me if they knew. I attended psychiatric treatment and told no one. The fear of being labelled negatively was immense.

Leaving school with minimal qualifications I entered the workplace and attempted to carve myself a more socially acceptable identity in the travel industry, with the underlying aim of escape. However, the most significant change in my identity came soon after in the form of motherhood. I found the love and respect that came with being a mother more intoxicating than any illicit substance. Becoming a teenage mother brought with it many challenges, but vitally it forced me to take care of myself and overcome the sense of fatalism which had plagued me and think about the possibilities for a different future.

Later, at aged 21 with two very young boys, through an access course that has now been withdrawn, I started university at UWS, becoming the first person in my family to enter higher education. In the context of widening access to higher education, like many non-traditional students, I felt like a fish out of water attending seminars, and I find Pierre Bourdieu's concept

of Habitus very useful in understanding this phenomenon. The feeling of being different, of having to teach myself some of the basic things about society that were just not spoken about in my family of origin. The embarrassment of incorrect pronunciation of words from only ever having read them. I remember clearly at the end of my first year my bemusement when someone asked me if I was doing the degree. I didn't know what a degree was. I had never heard of one. Half way through my studies, I gave birth to a third child, but I continued on with my education, balancing coursework with domestic labour, childcare and part time employment. I didn't have the traditional student experience and so never really identified as such. Despite this I valued my education within the social sciences dearly, most of all for my developing sense of class consciousness and the sense of empowerment that came with it. Having grown up in an environment where poverty and inequality shaped much of my experience, my newly acquired sociological imagination allowed me to view the circumstances of my earlier life from a more critical perspective. This was heart-breaking and liberating in equal measure.

In undertaking my teacher training at a post graduate level, deeply embedded feelings of otherness resurfaced with the emphasis on reflective practice and professional identity. But ultimately, it was here that I gained an understanding of the relativity of 'privilege'. Not unlike the children from my neighbourhood, on the basis of outside appearances I had assumed many others to be having an easier time. In reality they were having a very similar experience to me in feeling just as much 'like an imposter'.

In more recent years, during my personal experience of receiving the assistance of a residential service for gender-based violence, it soon became obvious that I was not the typical service user, my support worker admitting not knowing 'what to do with me'. Doctoral level education made me different from the other women in the service and at the same time being in the service made me feel different from other women in the university.

Existing in the space between two worlds is a thread which thus runs throughout my life. The pervasive feeling that no matter where I go, I don't quite belong. Although this marginality has been difficult at times, I can now see it has afforded me a different, perhaps even privileged perspective. The difficult periods in my life have taught me much about being judged negatively by others. My own experience of stigma has given me a truly non-judgemental attitude and I believe my acceptance of difference comes across as genuine in my relations with others.

The utility of a fringe location

In the conclusion of my auto-ethnographical vignette I tentatively suggest that my multiple marginality has afforded me a greater perspective. This notion requires a return to the debate surrounding privileged positions within social research.

In the previous discussion the concept of epistemic privilege was explored in relation to feminist standpoint theory. Marechal (2009) describes the multiplicity that arises from simultaneous participation in diverse social worlds, or ‘marginality’ as the ‘paradoxical position of the native ethnographer’. For Patricia Hill Collins, the status of the ‘outsider within’ brings many benefits. Drawing parallels between the concept of the ‘outsider within’ and George Simmel’s (1921) concept of the ‘stranger’, Collins suggest that the act of being both close and yet somewhat distant at the same time allows researchers to see patterns that may be obscured from those more immersed within the culture while being near enough to have members confide in them about difficult experiences. Marginal intellectuals who tap their ‘outsider within status’ can thus offer an alternative perspective than that more commonly generated. Collins argues that sociologists who share in this marginal standpoint should make creative use of this particular way of viewing reality (Collins, 1986).

For Tang, adopting the position of the outsider within allows her to view the interview data with both familiarity and curiosity (2007). This dual, and seemingly ambiguous positioning allows us to think through the benefits and drawbacks of outside within status. Speculating on this very issue, Gorelick (1996) comments: *‘That might be because I am myself very much like them and subject to some of the same social forces, some of the same distortions and limitations. There are hidden determinants in my life also, and I am both the worst and the best person to uncover them.’* (Gorelick, 1996: 39).

It is important to state that in exploring the benefits of being a marginalised researcher, unlike some authors, I do not contend that I am best positioned to research women who use drugs on account of my gender alone. Moreover, it is the multiple experiences of stigma that exist at the intersection of many facets of my identity that operate as a gateway to better understanding the participants in this study. In terms of being the worst person at the same time, as Gorelick suggests, I am aware that I am blind to certain aspects which perhaps other researchers on account of their positioning would not be. For example, as a heterosexual woman, I am not overtly conscious of the ways in which my sexuality shape my perceptions of relationships and this is something that I must keep in mind, particularly as at least one of my participants identifies as queer.

Embracing vulnerability

It must be stated that engaging in a reflexive awareness about one's own social location and personal history is a difficult process. As Trussell (2014) points out, it is much easier to expose the vulnerabilities of others than it is to lay bare our own. For Ettore, the purpose of auto-ethnography is to extract meaning from experience, rather than 'depict life as it is lived' (Ettore, 2005: 536). Performing auto-ethnography has required me to look inwards, to think about the subject positions I occupy as the researcher and author of this work (Allen- Collinson, 2013). This has not been an easy task and I have become conscious of my own pain as a result of engaging with the pain of others. This constitutes a rarely spoken of yet extremely important aspect of qualitative research, particularly in the study of sensitive topics. As Chatham-Carpenter (2010) illustrates with her evocative account of anorexia, engaging in the analytic self -reflection at the heart of auto-ethnography made her vulnerable to anorexic thought processes and behaviour which she had determinedly sought to leave behind. Yet for Mizzi (2010) while this re-experiencing of challenging events and emotions is painful, it is ultimately healing. In the next chapter, under 'healing vs harmful narratives', I explore some of the ethical considerations raised by this challenge and suggest ways that future researchers of vulnerable or marginalised populations can protect their own wellbeing in addition to that of research participants.

Challenges aside, reflexive auto-ethnography finds a place for the connected life experience of the researcher, which according to Mizzi (2010) is often downplayed or overlooked in traditional ethnographic methods. Crucially, it allows us to become aware of hidden privileges and makes us mindful of how we present ourselves to research participants. For this reason, Minowa et al (2010) posit researcher introspection as essential to the overall trustworthiness of qualitative data, particularly in the context of multi -site ethnography, emphasising the importance of understanding the cultural context in which meaning is conveyed. When viewed from this perspective, it becomes essential for the building of healthy research relationships.

Connecting the dots

For fellow researchers still unsure of the relevance of their reflexive positioning to their research projects, Caelli et al (2003) emphasises that when researchers choose to engage in a study topic it is 'never a naïve choice'. It is often the personal history of the researcher which

leads them to explore a particular avenue of thought and researcher values underpin a variety of important decisions including choice of research methods. Consequently, for authors such as Greenbank (2003), adopting a reflexive approach requires being honest and open about how and in what way these values have influenced the research process. According to Greenbank (2003):

“Reflexivity requires an explicit self-consciousness and self-assessment by the researcher about their own views and positions and how these might have influenced the design, execution and interpretation of the research data findings”

(Greenbank, 2003:9)

In giving this some serious consideration I have come to notice a relationship between the themes that appear to characterise my auto-ethnographic vignette (group boundaries, stigma, language, privilege) and the areas of knowledge I have focussed in on in my thesis. Somewhat unconsciously my life experiences may well have shaped the analytical process within this research project. For example, my experience of being raised with a stigmatised Glaswegian vernacular which made me sensitive to the context of dialect prejudice in the West of Scotland and its links to classed subjectivities (Snell, 2018), inspired an interest in understanding the use of language and narrative methods within the context of hidden population research.

According to Snell (2018), speech is an important marker of positionality. Its purposeful use is an act of identity, potentially signalling alignment with a groups values or a rejection of them. In observing the context and interpersonal dynamics among different social groups Snell (2018) suggests that vernacular forms that lack status within the dominant ‘sociolinguistic economy’ can be used to the opposite effect in a localised context. She found that males are more likely to use non- standard vernacular more consciously in this way to achieve covert prestige by resisting institutional norms, while in females the use of localised vernacular often signals the speaker experiences the situation as non -formal.

Snell (2018) conflict -based model of vernacular use helps to explain the overt pressure I often experience first -hand by friends and family members when I choose to speak in a more standardised form of English. That dialect can either bring individuals together or set them apart as different has caused me to contemplate the importance of the use of vernacular in a research context and its potential to alter relations of power.

In the auto-ethnographic vignette, I describe my early life experiences with language in the context of a working-class background. Through this research process I have come to view my 'native tongue' as an asset which I have used to meet the goals of accessing and understanding this hidden population of women who use drugs. The purposeful use of localised vernacular, in this case Glaswegian, has served as a useful tool to demonstrate solidarity to make the participant relax, signalling a non-formal occasion, thus breaking down the barriers erected within the climate of distrust. I return to this topic in greater detail in the analysis section under 'accessing and engaging', where I discuss the importance of empathy in interviewing women who use drugs.

It is important to note that any auto-ethnographic vignette represents an expression of perhaps only a few of the many voices that exist within a researcher's multifaceted and fluid identity. Mobilising the concept of multi-vocality within auto-ethnography underscores the notion that there is no single and temporally fixed voice that a researcher possesses, rather, a researcher has many voices that represent different aspects of identity (Mizzi, 2010,). These are at times complementary and at times in conflict and not all of them will be expressed within any given story. The question of what voices I may have kept silent in my vignette must therefore be a matter for further scrutiny.

Conclusion

Through the inclusion of an auto-ethnographic vignette, I have demonstrated how first-person writing may be utilised by marginalised researchers to firmly locate the researcher within the text and increase the trustworthiness of the data (Minowa et al, 2010). This goes some way towards addressing the issue of positionality within the highly politicised arena of drugs policy and the process of scrutinising the research evidence which currently informs it (Monaghan, 2008:2010). In making the case for a reflexive approach to the study of women who use drugs, I have examined the social and political context which readily invites a situated perspective. In doing so I have attempted to render explicit the values which have influenced my approach to this work and my understanding of the research population. Further, in exploring my positionality and how this may bear on this research process, I have highlighted the dilemma of disclosure with which drug researchers are faced and the ethical challenges inherent in undertaking a project of this nature.

In the spirit of self- reflexivity I have tentatively explored the links between my own life history and the research focus, explicitly utilising my own multiple marginality as a research tool in accessing and engaging with women who use drugs. Having become conscious of the ways in which my own life experiences have come to shape this research project, I believe I am now in a stronger position to analyse the women's accounts.

Chapter Four: ‘Accessing and Engaging Hidden Populations’

Introduction

This chapter gives an overview of the processes of accessing and engaging with this hidden population of women who use drugs. It outlines the particular research methods used beginning with the sampling method and moves on to explore the particular challenges encountered in the phase of recruitment. In charting the evolution of the research design through the pilot study and early stages of the project, I demonstrate how I came to recognise the need for a particular approach to interviewing the women, placing particular emphasis on the importance of building and maintaining trust throughout, which I illustrate through excerpts of the reflective diary.

Inclusion criteria

Eligibility to take part in the study was dependent on the ability to meet all five of the following criteria for inclusion:

1. Over the age of 18 years old.
2. Female
3. Have current or past experience of using illicit and illegal drugs in the past 24 months.
4. Have used illicit or illegal substances more than once
5. Not currently engaging with treatment services for problematic substance use

The need for an exclusively female focus was highlighted in a hidden population study by McPhee (2013). Due to the fact that non-treatment seeking women who use drugs are largely missing from the research literature, there exists limited data on patterns and prevalence of use to inform the inclusion criteria. Prevalence data which does exist can give an indication of trends, however it is generally skewed by the aggregation of individuals who have used once with those who have used 20 times (Coomber et al, 2013). Therefore within lifetime prevalence data there are a number of people considered part of the drug using population who have in fact tried it once and chosen not to continue. The addition of criteria number 4 is designed to address this weakness.

Although the 24 month time period for use of illicit and illegal drugs may appear somewhat arbitrary, it was in fact a carefully imposed limit designed to allow participation from women who potentially manage stigma and risk of punishment by attributing drug use to a previous ‘self’. A balance was struck between affording this opportunity and increasing likelihood of

participants likely to engage in future use. Interestingly this approach yielded good results as several of this study's recruits initially presented as a type which 'has done but don't anymore', that is, until a level of trust was built up with the researcher to uncover a continued relationship with illicit substances. The 24 month window also allows for individuals who may be experienced but currently having a temporary break in use. For example, in McPhee's 2013 study, several participants presented with an intermittent pattern of use, a mechanism employed purposefully to manage tolerance.

The decision not to focus on any particular substance is deliberate in order to achieve the overarching aim of this study, which is as much about the processes of researching women who use drugs as it is their lived experience of negotiating a stigmatised identity. This appears common to users of all illegal substances, albeit in varying degrees and formations. Furthermore, the framing of the study in such broad terms increased likelihood of capturing the experiences of women with some of the most stigmatised substances, such as heroin. The fear of exposure surrounding this substance is so great that targeting users directly is highly unlikely to prove successful. Shewan, Dalgarno and Reith (2000) for example, sought out ecstasy users and after trust was built, participant's frequent and relatively non-problematic use of heroin became apparent. Consequently, I defined the inclusion/exclusion criteria with these defence mechanisms in mind.

Sampling

Non-randomised snowball sampling, or the chain referral strategy, is the preferred method of sampling in the existing hidden and hard to reach population literature. First introduced by Coleman (1958), snowball sampling is where initial connections are made with members of the target population and further participants are recruited to the study as part of an expanding process. The initial stages of this method involve the identification of several potential 'gatekeepers' who meet the inclusion criteria. Based on informed consent and on a firm foundation of trust, the gatekeeper then facilitates access to a number of individuals within their social network who meet the inclusion criteria for the study.

Snowball sampling is deemed particularly useful for researching private matters where insider knowledge is crucial (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981) and in cases where distinguishing features are not readily apparent (Cohen and Arieli, 2011), thus making it ideal for penetrating the social worlds of people who use drugs. Further, it is especially useful in feminist research as it sheds

light on the social relationships in which women are embedded. Concerned with the experiences of black women in higher education, Woodley and Lockard (2016) suggest that:

'snowball sampling provides one such way for researchers to study marginalized populations by harnessing the power of social networking and personal connections, which allows for the more thorough analysis of individuals and groups that may otherwise remain inaccessible.' (Woodley and Lockard, 2016:322)

Although snowball sampling is not without its problems, for Woodley and Lockard, it is most valuable for its potential to gain access to marginalised populations without further marginalising them, and this resonates with anti-oppressive stance taken in the present study.

Thoughts on limitations of sampling method

According to Salganik and Heckathorn (2003) while the network perspective embedded within respondent driven sampling is ideal for the study of hidden populations, there are limitations and it can be difficult to reproduce systematically (Muhib et al, 2001). In particular, there are concerns over the problem of similarity within social groupings. In the specific context of drug ethnography, Moore (2004) highlights the importance of accessing a wide variety of people comprising a particular 'scene' in order to overcome the potentially problematic practice of accepting key informants as being representative of a particular group.

Looking deeper into this similarity bias in the context of a study of cocaine use in Barcelona, Hendricks et al (1992) suggest that research participants within the artist/actor/music and white collar occupational milieus are more likely to refer participants in the same profession than those situated within other occupational backgrounds. Interestingly, other variables such as gender did not predict a similarity effect. Here these authors are preoccupied with the potential for bias in snowball sampling techniques, seeking to determine the optimal conditions to reduce bias and in turn improve the representativeness of the sample. While such methodological concerns can be attributed to a particular moment in time for hidden population research², it is interesting to note that the findings of Hendricks et al (ibid) helps to explain the apparently high number of participants in the creative industries and white collar occupations in the present study, insofar as this reflects the respective occupations of the key informants.

² see Hidden populations: a brief background, pt.1 chpt.1

Indeed, it is suggested that the issue of generalisability of findings is a matter with which all qualitative researchers have to contend (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008). In order to claim that findings may be projected to a set of circumstances out with the initial research context then it is generally assumed the larger the sample size the better. Consequently, hidden populations studies are often perceived to be limited by a small sample size which reflects the difficulties in gaining access (Cohen and Arieli, 2011)

However as Elliot et al (2002) report in relation to their attempts to identify and interview drug using parents, it is not generally the aim of hidden population research to obtain a statistically representative sample. Often described as exploratory in nature, the unknown nature of the terrain is greatly emphasised. That said, in such studies it is still deemed desirable to have as many participants as feasible in order to capture a wide range of experiences and ensure that data saturation is reached in the analysis stage (Fusch and Ness, 2015). For Guest, Bunce and Johnson (2006) the point at which data saturation is reached is a matter of debate with evidence to suggest that in a large sample of 64 participants this point was reached after only twelve interviews.

Conversely, narrative researchers of sensitive topics frequently have small samples (Andrews et al, 2013) and according to Chase (2005) this should not prevent reflection on the relationship between the sample and a larger whole. Yet as McMullen and Braithwaite (2013) point out, thinking this through with the concept of generalisability ‘diminishes the value of the local and the particular’, which is a key aim of narrative research. It is with this in mind that the relatively modest sample size in the present study, although a reflection of the challenges in gaining access, is not regarded as a limitation.

Snowball sampling has also been criticised for issues with reliability, which concerns consistency and repetition of findings (Woodley and Lockard, 2016). As one of the strengths of narrative research is the way in which it highlights the relationship between context and knowledge production, reliability, like validity or generalisability, does not provide an adequate measure of quality (McMullen and Braithwaite, 2013).

In similar vein, self- report limitations are commonly reported in the qualitative research literature. For example in Polkinghorne (2008), it is suggested that evidence about the participant’s experiences dependent on their ability to reflectively discern the important aspects of their experience and to communicate them effectively through the medium of spoken

language. Such criticism is underpinned by a realist epistemology, contradicting the anti-mimetic view outlined in the previous chapter.

Thus it is apparent that many of the usual characteristics described as limitations in studies utilising snowball sampling are in fact qualities which are perceived as strengths in narrative studies. In light of this differing epistemological framework, the measures used to determine quality in narrative research are different from the usual concepts of validity, reliability and generalisability.

Evolution in research design

In the beginning this study was designed as a critical ethnography that utilises snowball sampling methods to recruit participants. Snowball sampling is widely employed in qualitative research in a broad sense (Noy, 2008) and is employed frequently in narrative research where more theoretical sampling strategies are not possible (Andrews et al, 2013). The narrative focus of the study emerged at a later point in time during the pilot stages as I navigated the early processes of accessing and engaging with participants. Storytelling as a dominant mode of self-representation in the context of women's drug using identities thus made itself known through my unstructured approach to interviewing (for more information on the interviewing technique see page 22). Narrative research always extends beyond the personal and attends to the cultural and social context in which stories are told (McMullan and Braithewaite, 2013) and this satisfied the need for an approach which does not decontextualize the women's experiences of drug use.

When adopting a reflexive stance in research such methodological changes are not unusual. According to Attia and Edge (2017);

'reflexive researchers open themselves up as one element of the phenomena that are to be investigated...in such investigation, while prescribed and learned methodological procedures may well be useful, a developmental approach to research methodology (and a becoming approach to being a researcher) will be equally open to the possibility of shifting insights, emergent goals, and evolving methods in the pursuit of findings more significant than those that initial research questions might have foreseen'

(Attia and Edge, 2017:36)

In essence the aims and objectives of the study remained the same, to investigate the experiences of a hidden population of women who use drugs, and the methods of researching them, however in light of these developments and the researchers own process of becoming, the research questions were rewritten to reflect an emerging narrative framework.

Recruitment

Ethical approval for this study was granted in November 2014 and recruitment of participants began shortly after in January 2015. Guided by supervisors and a vision of data analysis that was at this point, purely thematic and not yet narrative in nature, I set myself an initial target sample of 24 participants. Had I been fully aware of what was considered an acceptable number of participants in narrative inquiry I might have been able to justify terminating the recruitment phase much sooner. In retrospect I am pleased that this was not the case as it allowed me to experience in depth the many challenges and lessons that snowball sampling bestows upon the novice researcher.

Due to the clandestine nature of illicit drug use in a climate of prohibition it is notoriously difficult to gain access to drug using populations which remain out with the gaze of authorities (Taylor and Kearney, 2005) and so it was expected from the outset of the study that exploring the hidden world of illicit drug use would require a degree of creativity and resourcefulness. However, the reality of the recruitment process was more challenging than I could have anticipated. In part, this stems from the lack of transparency surrounding the process of recruitment in existing hidden population studies. The mystification of snowball sampling methods is highlighted by Faugier and Sargeant (1997):

“In the 1960’s, both Lindesmith (1968) in his study of opiate addicts and Becker (1996) in his investigation on marijuana users did use these sampling methods successfully, although both authors gave only a brief reference to the enormous amount of work involved. This created the impression that all that was required to sample difficult to reach populations was to start the ball rolling with one contact, then sit back and watch the sample pile up” (Faugier and Sargient, 1997:792)

In more recent studies and in standard methods textbooks, the lack of attention to the enormous difficulties in sampling ‘deviant’ populations continues (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981). This

might be explained by the wider culture of aversion to softer concepts in sociology, which by their very nature can be difficult to define and operationalise. For example, trust is especially vital to the success of hidden population research, as it is with any study which involves the narration of sensitive topics (Stranden, 2009). However, while the development of a trusting relationship between the researcher the researched constitutes the very essence of this kind of inquiry, guidance on this issue is lacking.

In light of the above, the absence of a traceable pathway in snowball sampling studies should be placed within the context of a culture in which pressure is exerted upon researchers to conform to what is considered appropriate within mainstream academic discourse. With strong emphasis on minimising researcher bias, the objectivist modes of inquiry which characterise this body of knowledge tend to obscure the interpersonal dynamics of the research relationship. The resulting criteria for quality, very often but not always, creates pressure to construct a narrative that excludes the personal in order that the researcher's actions be translated into a rigorous method which can then replicated. This creates a poverty in research texts which could be greatly enhanced by the inclusion of micro -interactional processes, small details that are often pivotal to the securing of trust. Auto-ethnographic writing is one way of addressing this shortcoming. As Stranden illustrates:

“The interview was conducted in the winter, and as she lived in an old house, I brought my woollen socks with me in order to not get cold feet. I told her that I had done so, and smilingly showed her how well darned they were. To my surprise, this was when the tension disappeared and she told me that she hardly needed to be nervous because I had brought with me my socks, which were full of holes and which I had darned. I took it to be the darned socks that had increased the interviewees trust in me” (Stranden, 2009:5)

Following Stranden, I employ reflexive writing to make explicit the series of challenges encountered in the recruitment process and the ways in which they were overcome. This auto-ethnographic element adds a dimension of context which is hitherto missing in the limited literature, assisting future researchers of hidden and hard to reach populations of any nature. In service of this aim there are a total of 8 reflective diary accounts of encounters with the following participants which are presented under a pseudonym of their own choosing: *Shirley, Claire, Mary, Allie, Julie, Aimee, Megan and Summer*. These accounts depict particular moments in research process which felt significant, and were recorded as soon as possible after the encounter (Phillipi and Lauderdale, 2018). In the following section excerpts of some of

this writing is used to highlight and discuss the challenges in accessing and engaging this population of women who use drugs.

Identifying Potential Gatekeepers

In the beginning of the project it was expected that my 'privileged access' to the target group through a range of social contacts would increase opportunities for recruitment (Griffiths et al, 1993). As recommended by Faugier and Sargeant (1997) the early stages of the snowball sampling method involved the drawing up of a map of potential gatekeepers. After searching through all existing contacts, a list of individuals who met the inclusion criteria was compiled. At this point in time, much thought was given as to the issues raised by researching family and friends. There is ongoing debate with regards the benefits and drawbacks of overlapping personal and research relationships. What does it mean for the research validity? How ethical is it?

Yuan (2014) recruited exclusively from his personal friendship network for his narrative inquiry into the museum experience. For this researcher, the existing degree of trust saved time and effort with regards the building of rapport, however that level of trust meant that participants did not take the time to fully understand what was required of them in the study, raising questions about the nature of informed consent. The inclusion of friends in research is often frowned upon by those who view a degree of distance and objectivity as necessary requirements in qualitative research to minimise bias. This may not concern researchers who seek to utilise researcher subjectivity explicitly. As this is one such study, the possibility of recruiting friends as gatekeepers was not completely ruled out. However, given that the motivations of friends to take part would likely differ from those where there is little personal and emotional investment (Yuan, 2014), the decision was made to target acquaintances to be the gatekeepers for the present study.

Pitching the study

Having shortened the list of potential gatekeepers to include acquaintances that fit the criteria for inclusion, the next stage in recruitment involved thinking carefully about the best way to approach them. How much information should be given upon initial contact? Would the request of facilitating connections with others best be made upon conclusion of their own participation? Moreover, what should be said in terms of the aims and objectives of the

research? Would saying too much. For example about my particular interest in parenting, influence participants' perception of what was expected from them, and in some way come to shape or even shut down their narrative? These concerns motivated my decision to say as little about the existing research literature, as possible. The rationale for the study was thus made and communicated in the simplest of terms: very little is known about the experiences of women who use drugs and their voices are absent from the debate.

On the whole this was an effective strategy and a good few of the women recognised the interview as a rare invitation and opportunity to be heard. However, whilst attempting to recruit one individual whom I suspected met the necessary criteria, it became apparent that invitation to take part in the study could be perceived as threatening. As the field notes reveal:

'Megan is aware of my current involvement in academia, as I informed her in a previous conversation that I was currently doing a study about women who use drugs. So when she opens her front door to see me standing with my clip board and my Dictaphone, she laughs and quickly blurted out – "I don't take drugs!" with a surprised but somewhat defensive tone. In this moment, I realised that my interest in her as a potential participant in my study has offended her.

I have to think on my feet. I realise these next few seconds are crucial in gaining her trust. So, I respond "that's okay, I really didn't know if you fit the criteria or not, you know it is really so broad, and even if you had used drugs, you know in the past couple of years at any point, I would still be interested to hear what you had to say...."

She looks at me for a few seconds without speaking and then to my surprise she steps back, widening the doorway. "Would you like to come in?"

We sit down in the living room of her home and as I fumble in my file for the consent forms, I become aware that she is nervous and visibly trembling. (Reflective journal, 12/06/2015)

Upon what transpired to be an interesting and worthwhile interview, I communicated how hard I was finding it to recruit women onto the study, asking the participant how it made her feel when she had been invited. Her response was somewhat enlightening. What was it about her that made me think she would be suitable? Was it her physical appearance? The fact she was a single mother? She explains, as the result of having children very young (15 years old), she feels very aware and sensitive to how others perceive her. The assumption that she was also a user of illicit drugs, implying lack of responsibility, was therefore something she felt the need

to strongly guard against, having to prove her suitability as a parent to the outside world perhaps more than an older woman would feel the need to.

This experience provided a valuable lesson that had an impact upon the manner in which future participants were approached. Asking the question in such a way that suggests a degree of uncertainty as to whether inclusion criteria is indeed met makes the invitation less threatening. In particular, women like Megan, who have multiple stigmatised identities with which I could intimately relate, may require some form of assurance that assumptions about her character have been not made out of ignorance or through reference to negative stereotypes. In cases, such as this, a degree of sensitivity in handling is essential.

Pilot stage

A pilot stage was carried out which involved the recruitment and interviewing of a further four participants. Pilot stages are often used by some researchers to test and develop appropriate questions for semi-structured interview schedules (Turner, 2010). As unstructured approaches to interviewing have been recommended in hidden populations studies (Elliot, 2002) the pilot stage was used in this case to develop my confidence with this hitherto unfamiliar method and also to confirm that it was indeed a suitable approach. This was largely successful. Some individuals required more prompting than others, but one participant, Mary, was visibly relieved by the lack of set questions and the increased control over content.

A common way of communicating was discovered in the course of the first few interviews. The women frequently framed their experiences in terms of good and bad and this appeared to be a natural way of talking about drug taking, perhaps reflecting the binary structure of drugs discourse at large (Brook et al., 2005). This mode of expression was taken into consideration for future interviews. In instances where participants required encouragement to communicate their experience, I asked questions about any good and bad experiences that came to mind. This generated a response that was clearly narrative in nature and so in future interviews I simply asked the women to tell me stories about their experiences with illegal drugs.

A Series of Setbacks

After the pilot stage recruitment progressed very slowly. This early stage in the process was characterised by a series of setbacks such as last -minute cancellations, re-arrangements, and several changes to agreed meeting times. On two occasions one participant failed to show up

at the agreed meeting place without prior notification. This was an extremely frustrating experience and much patience was required. After six consecutive interviews failed to take place as expected, I was forced to re-evaluate my approach. What was going wrong?

Many of these women who proved difficult to pin down had seemed more than willing to take part in the initial face to face conversation. Going over the process in an attempt to detect a fault within this approach, it became apparent that the information and consent forms left with the women prior to the interview seemed very formal. Included was a clause about the limits of confidentiality in relation to disclosure of child abuse. This information, whilst necessary to allow participants to make informed consent, was perhaps causing undue distress in its premature introduction. In the event that this was indeed the case, I constructed an informal invitation letter (appendix A), having the more formal documents signed after a degree of trust and rapport was achieved in the relationship.

Given that the strategies employed in recruitment up to this point were showing limited results, I returned to the literature on snowball sampling methods in a bid to find a solution. A similar study on a hidden population of drug using mothers by Goode (2000) detailed similar challenges in recruitment, but in this case they were largely a product of using formal agencies as gatekeepers. In a review of the various strategies employed to recruit research participants from hidden populations, Duncan et al., (2003) recommend the use of the internet as a tool with considerable yielding power to tap into diverse social groupings with the benefit of increased anonymity. To this end, an advert was posted on the social media page for the Psychedelic Society in Scotland, as the moderator of this website, a colleague in the Scottish drug policy reform circle, had previously offered assistance with the project. This would have added the benefit of including a network where there was no existing degree of connection with the researcher, increasing the diversity of the sample. However, in this case there were no responses to the online call for recruits. (In retrospect this was not surprising, as the literature which had demonstrated success with such methods was based on largely male, less marginalised subjects.) Energy was then focused on chasing up existing participants who had signalled a clear and definite interest in acting as gatekeepers to their social network, particularly those who had communicated that the interview had been a very positive experience.

Upon finally meeting two of the recruits who had been especially difficult to secure, it became apparent that the challenges and set-backs were manifestations of heightened sensitivity

concerning the topic of using drugs. At this point in time, these women were actively experiencing difficulties and problems related to their substance use. As a result, being interviewed was a significant part of the process in coming to terms with their situation, thus requiring a significant investment of emotional energy, which simply had not been available to them on the days originally agreed to meet.

Similar challenges in recruitment from non-clinical populations have been documented by Harvey (2017) in a study exploring experiences of eating disorders. Adopting a similarly non-pathologising approach, this researcher sought to broaden understanding of this issue through engaging with a broader population of individuals than those with a clinical diagnosis, including individuals with an unhealthy preoccupation with eating habits in her sample. According to Harvey, the unfamiliarity of the interview process was itself a barrier to recruitment, as previously engaging in some form of psychological therapy makes it likely that the individual has overcome feelings of shame and embarrassment experienced when discussing sensitive topics that are frequently invite negative judgement by others.

Analysis of the recruitment process constitutes a key strand of this investigation for the purposes of determining the most effective means by which to access hidden populations of women who use drugs. Examining the challenges which characterise recruitment with a critical lens that moves beyond the methodological, is itself a way to generate knowledge about the phenomenon of interest. According to Noy (2008), traditional qualitative methodologies tend to view the sampling process in very narrow technical terms, reflecting the dominance of the positivist approach. As a consequence the interrelationship between data accessing and data collection and analysis is generally overlooked. However when viewed critically, the snowball sampling method generates a unique type of social knowledge that is rich in information about social organisation and power relations. Knowledge gained about the women during the process of recruitment in this study might shed light on significant themes to be analysed in the narrative data.

Why were these women so hard to pin down? What does it mean about this particular social grouping? Readers well acquainted with the literature on treatment populations might well be familiar with the notion that women who use drugs routinely miss appointments, commonly interpreted as a consequence of chaotic lifestyles. However, the picture emerging from the growing sample suggests exactly the opposite. A strikingly similar phenomenon was observed in a study by Krumer-Nevo (2002) on the experience of women living in poverty:

“I had thought that once I had the names of the potential interviewees, who had given their preliminary agreement to take part in the research to the social worker or nurse in the mother and child clinic, all I had to do was set a time and place for the interview, and to proceed with the meetings as arranged. This was not, however, what in fact happened. The list of names I had in my possession was merely the beginning of a series of lengthy, exhausting, meandering and confusing negotiations between the women and myself over every little detail.”

(Krumer-Nevo,2002: 7)

This researcher places her repeated struggle to conduct interviews within the context of unequal power relations between the researcher and the researched. Establishing control over when the interview would take place, often making the researcher wait for long periods of time, was a way for the women to assert their agency and alter the dynamic of the relationship. Therefore, it is possible that a similar process was at play in the current study. As Benoit et al (2005) point out, identification as a member of a highly stigmatised group is inherently threatening, which breeds a degree of mistrust towards outsiders of that group. According to Eisenstadt and Roniger (1884), the act of building continuing social relations is impossible without some element of trust and common meaning. The building of trust thus became my focus in order to move the study forward.

Getting in

Contrary to my expectations, the word of the gatekeeper on the trustworthiness of the researcher was not always sufficient in securing the trust of further participants. Two weeks after interviewing Shirley, who turned out to be the primary gatekeeper, I received an invitation to attend a social gathering where several of her contacts would be in attendance. Field notes document the ways in which my character was put to the test, how my motivation for wanting to learn about their drug experiences was covertly scrutinised and ultimately my trustworthiness determined. I did not predict the significance of attending this music and arts event for building trust, viewing it narrowly as an opportunity for participant observation. In hindsight it represented a breakthrough moment in the recruitment process, the opening of the locked door, the key to gaining access to this wide and diverse social network. For the gatekeeper, it served a very important function; the weight of responsibility for protecting the

interests of the group were shared among those who were present, reflecting the magnitude of risk of exposure for this particular group of women.

While there are many studies in which the primary method of data collection is interviews which claim to be ethnographic in nature, for some scholars true ethnography involves an extended period of participant observation (Atkinson, 2014). As the current study involved only a relatively short time in the field in order to build trust in the recruitment phase, it is perhaps not accurate to say that I was *doing ethnography* in the fullest sense (Green and Bloome, 2004). It is therefore better conceptualised as a narrative ethnography (Gubrium and Holstein, 2008) which can be defined as ‘an approach that renders explicit the relationships formed between ethnographer and informant who engage in ‘ethnographic dialogue’ to create a world of shared meaning’ (Hampshire et al, 2014). Accordingly so, the anthropological literature has played an important part in understanding this ethnographic dialogue, improving knowledge about the process of gaining access to hidden populations of women who use drugs, which was one of the key objectives of this study. The insights drawn from this body of knowledge have been invaluable for making sense of the challenges encountered, particularly in understanding the role of serendipity.

Serendipity

Analysis of the field notes suggests that criteria for being perceived as trustworthy are in fact highly subjective and sometimes unpredictable. While there is evidence to suggest that homo-gendered research contexts are beneficial to interaction (Meurling, 2002), for Claire, it was not enough that I was a woman. Most importantly, it was not enough that Shirley, as the gatekeeper, had vouched for me. Unexpectedly, Claire’s perception of me being on the ‘inside’ and therefore worthy of trust, was based on the way in which I responded to a particular male at the social gathering who was showing unwelcome interest and trying to give me an ecstasy pill. Prior to the interview and upon asking directly how she felt about talking to me about her drug experiences she revealed:

“I wasn’t sure at first, but when I saw how you dealt with that fella I was like, aye, she is one of us” (Claire, 39)

The event to which Claire is referring is documented in the field notes:

‘I did my best to be natural, and to just be myself, though the environment was at times overwhelming with the loud music shaking through the ground and our bodies. I took time to absorb my surroundings, noticing that most people were high on stimulant drugs,

apparent from the pale dehydrated look and wide eyed friendliness. After about two hours, a young man came over and starting chatting incessantly about all sorts of unrelated things, oblivious to the lack of reciprocity from Claire and myself. We responded in a sympathetic manner and gave each other a knowing smile. Another man, perhaps his friend, had been staring over at this exchange, then came over. Standing way too close for comfort, he offered me an ecstasy tablet. In a firm but polite tone I refused and told him that I was driving. He looked somewhat incredulous but accepted it and said nothing else to me, shifting his attention to Claire.' (Reflective diary, 04/08/2016)

It may be useful to note that Claire identifies as homosexual, and through getting to know her at the event it became evident that her views about the opposite sex were fairly negative, and strongly held. Therefore, my polite but swift shutting down of the male's advances demonstrated to Claire that I did not tolerate or wish to encourage what she viewed as a form of sexual harassment. It was in that unsuspecting moment that I gained her trust. Having reflected one of Claire's core values, I became significantly less threatening and more likely to understand her world view as it would be revealed in talking about her experiences with drugs. The unique foundation of her trust in me only came to light through the process of enquiring how she felt about talking to me, and I was able to verify this with recourse to the reflective data. Claire's unique case demonstrated the somewhat serendipitous nature of our budding relationship. Indeed, for many authors such as Rivoal and Salazar (2013), serendipity plays an important part in qualitative research with some going as far as to say it is a key characteristic of ethnography.

In light of the role of serendipity played in the building of trust within this study, I would have to say that replication is not an achievable aim. In any case, there are multiple influencing factors which would have to be taken into account, and even if they could be in theory, in practice it would just not be feasible. This does not mean however that we should be satisfied with the current state of affairs and continue to let new researchers to this area grasp and fumble in the dark to find possible solutions to the challenge of building trust. Based on a self-reflective awareness of the development of research relationships, hidden population researchers should strive to become aware of and make others aware of, the particular interpersonal skills and qualities deployed in real situations where trust was successfully secured. Reflective diaries and field notes, rich in context and description are ideal for this purpose (Pope, Ziebland and Mays, 2000). Indeed, ethnographers have long kept field notes

which detail accounts and impressions of field work, at times ‘haunting and highly personal’ (Berger, 2001). Reflective diaries have been encouraged as an effective tool for developing a practice of ‘bracketing’ (Wall et al, 2004; Chan et al, 2013). Less rarely have they been published as part of the ‘official’ document.

Authenticity

What more can be said about Strandon’s account of the darned socks and the experience of my own in building and maintaining trust with Claire at the music festival? What do they have in common? In addition to serendipity, both accounts have an air of novelty, a natural way of being that seems to ease any tension felt by the interviewee. The researcher is showing herself as a person first and foremost, and a researcher second. Thus, the issue of *authenticity* comes to mind. I behaved in that situation the way I would have had I not been immersed in the research process. In other words, I was my authentic self and I believe this is particularly important when researching defended and demonised subjects such as women who use drugs.

Indeed, according to Sofie Stranden (2009) there are three main aspects which contribute to the building of trust between interviewer and interviewee in the study of sensitive topics: interviewer as a person, the professionalism of the interviewer and social context of the interviewer. Reflecting back on encounters which had felt more successful in relation to others I found that the notion of presenting first and foremost as a person was particularly evident. Consider the following exchange with Mary:

Mary: So what is your version of success?

Karen: For me it is just... surviving.

Mary: Yes! You get to a stage where you don't feel bad about not managing to get changed out of your pyjamas, because you have managed to feed the kids and keep the house clean!

The question whether to share personal information with research participants in the context of a research interview constitutes an area of much debate. I feel strongly that my willingness to share personal feelings and insights about my own life experiences were instrumental in the building of trust between Mary and I, who had started off the interview rather hesitant. As this example demonstrates, the information shared, or in this case requested, may not pertain directly to the subject in question – in this case illicit drug taking. Rather unexpectedly, the research participant probed into the nature of my character, or perhaps my social background,

by asking me to elaborate on my vision of success. In answering honestly, I exposed a level of vulnerability by defining success in terms of survival, paving the way for her to embrace her own vulnerability. This showed her that I was being an authentic person as well as a researcher and I am certain it challenged her initial perception of me, altering the power relations between us thereafter. Hence, I concur with Leigh Berger (2001) when she claims that the inclusion of an auto-ethnographic method allows her to be more empathic toward those engaged in her study but also how sharing her stories with her field participants fosters their openness as well (Berger, 2001).

According to Guba and Lincoln as cited in Shenton (2004), the degree of transferability and dependability is an important marker of quality in qualitative research. Transferability reflects the sufficient provision of context in relation to any fieldwork to allow judgement to be made about the relevance of that phenomena to other research contexts (Shenton, 2004) Thus, in including the trivial details of the interaction which inhabit the research relationship, it can be argued that the overall trustworthiness of the research is greatly enhanced. In addition, the attempt to find commonalities in events which are felt to be crucial in the securing of trust, no matter how novel or insignificant they may be, can be viewed as an attempt to foster dependability, in so far as suggestions are being made which are likely to enable future researchers.

Far from suggesting the interviewer presents with a pair of well darned socks, or waits interminably to politely refuse an unwanted offer of illicit drugs, this means analysing these ‘trust building moments’ to determine the underlying phenomena which allows trust to come to fruition and to remain. As R.D. Laing suggests in the politics of experience:

“Personal action can either open out possibilities of enriched experience or it can shut off possibilities. Personal action is either predominantly validating, confirming, encouraging, supportive, enhancing, or it is invalidating, disconfirming, discouraging, undermining and constricting. It can be creative or destructive.” (Laing, 1967:15)

It might not be possible to offer clear direction in terms of how to build trust in snowball sampling, but in reflecting upon crucial events within the field, critical ethnographers may begin to build a clearer picture of the attitudes and behaviours which make trust more likely to blossom. In addition, the reflective, naturalistic style of transmission of these events through reflective diary data brings to light the degree of context required to assist future researchers in

determining whether such criteria will be applicable to the particular context of their own endeavour.

Learning the language

It is vital that anti-oppressive and critical researchers pay attention to the use of language, which has the power to construct and marginalise research subjects as ‘the other’ (Krumer-Nevo and Sidi, 2012). During the early stages of engaging with research participants in the present study it became apparent the word ‘drug user’ was being absorbed negatively, creating further obstacles in the formation of rapport. Consider the following exchange:

Karen: How do people react to you being a drug user in general?

Claire: ehmm. (Long pause)

Karen: How do you feel about the term drug user? I use it for want of a better word.

Claire: It's horrible. And I get so annoyed, especially in Scotland. Alcohol is the fucking issue here. All the shitty things I have done in my life, the bad things, has been alcohol fuelled. Mayhem, right? When I am smoking weed I just sit in my house and I don't bother anyone! And yet they criminalise you. It's ridiculous. Violence, all manner of murders, drink driving, and also general emotional turmoil in families, all of that. And generally speaking stoners are not causing any of that.

For this participant, being referred to as a drug user was enough to visibly upset her and interrupt the flow of her narrative. The period of silence and change in her overall demeanour prompted me to seek more information about the use of the term. This propelled her into a passionate attack on the perceived injustice in the regulatory response to alcohol and its relative harms. Immediately we can see how ‘drug user’ relates to social problems in Claire’s mind. In a final bid of rejection, or in an attempt to resist the process of othering, she goes on to affix her own label of ‘stoner’. Although this term appears to relate more specifically to cannabis use, Claire was a poly-drug user. Interestingly, Claire was not the only participant to replace the term drug user with stoner:

Karen: Do many people know that you are a drug user?

Mary: A stoner?

Offering a more palatable alternative suggests that ‘drug user’ is not a label that Mary would attach to herself or any other member of the group in everyday communication. Indeed, for

many of the women, the term 'drug user' is loaded with negative connotations and synonymous with 'junkie' conjuring images of deprivation and degradation.

In a reflexive manner, I refrained from using the term 'drug user' in future encounters and removed it from all written text. INPUD (International Network of People who Use Drugs), strongly assert that the use of 'first person language' is a positive step towards distinguishing the person from their diagnosis or perceived membership in a stigmatised group. For INPUD, language is one of the key vehicles through which the stigmatisation and demonization of people who use drugs is perpetuated. Some of these words, such as 'pillhead' or 'drug abuser' are obviously dehumanising, however others are subtler, despite being more generally accepted.

In a recent publication, the Global Commission on Drug Policy stated that terms such as 'junkie' and 'addict' are offensive and should therefore be avoided (O'Dowd, 2018). The WHO have for this reason called for an end to the use of these terms, which are far from neutral, since the 1960's. Despite this, many academics and health professionals continue to label individuals as 'addicts' (Ashford, Brown and Curtis, 2018), a heavily loaded term which connotes a lack of self-control and loss of agency. Identification with this potentially stigmatising label comes likely through contact with services, and so perhaps it is more appropriate for use in the study of captive as opposed to hidden populations.

The wide ranging and at times confusing array of terms in the field of alcohol and drug studies has caused commentators such as John Kelly (2004) to call for an 'addictionary', that is, a set of consistently used and precisely defined terms to describe and thus compare phenomena related to alcohol and drug use. Quite rightly so, Kelly (2004) points out the need to think more critically about our chosen terms given their potential to create real world impact, particularly in the domains of treatment access and policy, and not least in the effects of stigma.

Indeed, it has been suggested that the formulation of a discourse devoid of domination might begin with the use of such affirmative language (Jandt and Tanno (2001). When researching social actors whom are vulnerable to misrepresentation, qualitative researchers can sometimes unwittingly engage in the process of their subjugation. In analysing the underlying assumptions of hegemonic discourse, Krumer-Nevo and Sidi (2012) remark that often we engage in complicitous behaviour, in that our critical discourse mirrors the discourses we critique most particularly in the use of negative language. This is particularly the case for language used to

describe people who use drugs as it is shaped by the surrounding culture and underpinned by the embedded assumptions on illegal drug use which are largely indicative of an underlying morality.

In accordance with concerns highlighted in the literature review, the term ‘recreational’ while preferable to the alternative label of ‘problematic’, also proved to be problematic for the present sample of women who use drugs. To class the use of a particular substance or combination of substances as recreational suggests a hobby of sorts, a pleasurable pastime. For a great many of the women, particularly those passionate about the spiritual aspect of psychoactive substance use, the term simply fails to grasp the reverence with which they approach their practice.

For Brooke and Stringer (2005), this prohibitionist discourse is entirely built around binary oppositions, which serve to oversimplify drug use and marginalise drug users, whilst conferring power and privilege on the non-using population in general, and abstainers in particular. To adopt uncritically the terminology from the dominant discourses is to effectively colonise the participants’ experiences to fit with existing models of drug use that justify and legitimise the current system. In order to avoid further stigmatisation, it is imperative that marginalised research subjects make sense of their life experiences using their own language and frames of reference (Krumer-Nevo and Sidi, 2012). I suggest the considered use of terminology and the avoidance of dehumanising language is an important way of reducing these barriers to engagement, contributing to the ongoing debate surrounding problematic terminology within the field of alcohol and drug studies.

Learning from Failures

There were times in this study when it was not possible to establish the favourable conditions that fostered a fruitful exchange of information between myself and participants. One day stands out in particular. In retrospect I was extremely tired, and as the reflective diary data shows, I had concerns about meeting and speaking with several women in such a short space of time.

Today I have arranged to meet three different women in the East Coast, accompanied by the primary gatekeeper Shirley. I have no idea who these interviewees are. All I know is that they have agreed to speak to me and we will travel to them one after the other. On a personal level I am worried about overstressing myself. I now know how exhausting these interviews can be, particularly if the content is challenging. Will I have enough time to reflect on my practice between appointments? These are valid concerns to have, but when it comes to it do I just have to take these opportunities when they are presented to me? Will

I feel pressured to cut them shorter than usual? Perhaps. I feel nervous about how this day is going to pan out. I am mindful of staying present and conscious. This feels like a challenge. If I manage to make it a success I will be much closer to fulfilling my target sample.
(Reflective diary, 5/3/16)

Despite having had clear concerns about my ability to ‘perform’ under these conditions, the pressure to have interviewed so many participants in time for an approaching deadline caused me to override my instincts to rearrange for a later date. I also worried that the opportunity would be lost and in doing so prioritised the opportunity over my state of mind. The unique nature of snowball sampling methods which makes recruitment somewhat unpredictable together with the challenging work of overcoming participant defences created this situation where I was faced with the choice of quantity over quality. I suggest future researchers should learn from my mistake and refrain from engaging with participants when capacity for understanding and empathy is temporarily inhibited by exhaustion or illness. After all, a missed opportunity is preferable to a bad interview experience which could have knock on ill effects if shared with other potential participants in the growing network.

The negative effects of prioritising the need to take opportunities when they arise over the need to engage with participants in a meaningful way, made me think about the nature and quality of being present with someone. At the end of that day in the North East I met and interviewed Wendy. In retrospect I was present physically, but my exhaustion impacted upon my emotional awareness preventing me from picking up on verbal and non-verbal cues which guide everyday interaction on a subconscious level. Too drained to spot the opportunities within the conversation for overcoming her defences, on this occasion I was unable to achieve the level of closeness that with the others greatly enhanced the flow of information.

Even when I felt fully present there were times when the interview felt less than successful. I now illustrate such a time through the case of Julie.

The case of Julie

I meet Julie in a car park outside a tired looking restaurant at the edge of a busy road in the East coast. This is the place she has requested to meet me. As we enter the building she stops and abruptly says no, I don't want to go in here, and turns and walks back out the door. She is visibly flushed and distressed. I am taken aback but immediately, I reassure her that this is okay, we can go anywhere she feels more comfortable. She looks at me for a second and then ask if I mind if she makes a quick phone call.

For the next ten minutes, I sit waiting patiently in my car unsure what to do next. I feel the opportunity to hear Julie's story slipping through my fingers. I decide to get out and smoke a cigarette. For one, it helps to think, and two, it might make me appear less.... formal. There are a few tables and chairs outside the restaurant and I sit down with my back purposefully facing Julie, as I don't want to appear to be watching her.

My phone rings and I am surprised to hear the voice of gatekeeper Shirley "Can we do the interview in the car? And can I be there?" Not wanting to miss the opportunity to speak to Julie I quickly agree. In my mind I am not sure how this is going to change things. I had never interviewed any of Shirley's contacts with her present before.

As soon as I get in the front seat of the car next to Julie, I notice she is clutching very tightly at a drinking water bottle that has lemon wedges infusing inside. Every now and then she stops to take a drink, scanning the car park nervously. She is not at all at ease.

(Reflective diary, 21/3/16)

The interview with Julie stands out for me as the most difficult in terms of building rapport. What is remarkable about our ensuing exchange is that out of all of the encounters, it most resembles a traditional qualitative interview insofar as the interaction felt more formal, with an air of artificiality. It lacked natural flow and this is very evident in the formation of the transcript text in that the first few pages are full of one words and concise answers. This differs drastically from some of the other transcripts which have full pages of monologue. Performing a narrative analysis which relies on certain narrative properties would thus be challenging in this case.

Defended/ defensive subjects

At the beginning of our conversation when I asked her what drug she took the last time she seemed very nervous and said 'I'm not telling ye!'. She was very defensive. I took from this, that I had perhaps been too direct too soon, as due to her fears and concerns about the implications of sharing her experiences with me, there required to me more building of rapport before she offered up this information. However her reticence to expand on difficult topic areas, such as the 'bad trip' with LSD where she declared forcefully 'that's enough about that!' continued throughout the exchange even as she became more visibly comfortable in her communication.

There were clear limits in terms of what Julie was willing to me share with me and I believe this was in part an effect of the unusual circumstances in which the encounter took place. She was clearly not comfortable in that particular location and so to overcome Julie's defences would have required time and a safer space. I had judged the location as suitable for conducting

the interview, as I had achieved success in similar locations with other women. For Julie however, it was perhaps too exposed for her to feel safe enough to open up. Perhaps more importantly I did not have the opportunity to build up rapport prior to the interview as I did with Claire at the social event. Thus, her reticence about speaking about heroin use was likely a reflection of her lack of trust.

When asked how the experience of talking to me had been for her in the last few words of our exchange she explained that it had brought back long forgotten memories that were making her feel sad, quickly drawing the conversation to a close with ‘ And I think I have talked past my time now’. Through the case of Julie we can see that women are active in their self- construction and aware of times when it feels safe to present as something which is deemed less than desirable. Indeed, narrative researchers have long recognised the influence of audience in the formation of participants’ stories (Squire et al, 2013). A theory of identity as constructed in and through narrative provides a suitable lens through which to understand the ways in which women present and locate themselves depending on the social context of the interaction.

Reflexively aware of the power of setting to impact upon the success of the interviews, I decided to detail the circumstances of any future interviews by giving an account of the interaction itself, where possible.

Interview technique: developing DENIM

The elements which facilitate the building of trust in recruitment for hidden population research will closely overlap with the elements which facilitate the telling of narratives about sensitive experiences. Thus, many of the above recommendations will be useful in achieving success in the interview itself. Based on the lessons learned from accessing and engaging I suggest the following is also essential:

1. An approach which has trust and non -judgementality at the centre due to problem of stigma and resultant defence mechanisms
2. A dialogical approach which recognises the role of the interviewer, in recognition of the role of the interviewer subjectivity in shaping the narrative

In order to meet these objectives I designed an innovative interview method which I have called the Demonstrative Empathy Narrative Interview Method (DENIM). The DENIM draws upon

the empathic method of qualitative interviewing discussed by Sophie Strandon which is particularly suitable for the study of sensitive topics (Strandon, 2010). With the knowledge that drug use is considered a deviant and stigmatised activity, this method was deemed indispensable due to its potential to enhance an exchange of sensitive information by fostering a degree of trust and understanding.

The DENIM builds upon traditional empathic interviewing methods in qualitative research through the inclusion of a narrative focus. According to Mangan (2018), narrative interviewing generally framed as requiring minimal involvement in the interview on the part of the researcher, who sets out to elicit stories/narratives from interviewee about life experiences of particular interest. However I echo Mangan who states '*this was not the approach I took, as instead I acknowledge the interview as a conversation which I as researcher co-created, rather than stood on the sidelines and observed*' (Mangan, 2018: 52).

While it is common to see differences in level of researcher involvement in the interviews as distinguishing feature between semi-structured and unstructured interviewing, it is accurate to say there is much disagreement on the extent of researcher participation in narrative interviews. For example in his work on the maturing out thesis of Winick, Engel Prins conducted narrative interviews with 65 individuals, 21 females, on the life time trajectory of their addiction to heroin and other drugs. Interestingly he also began with a semi structured approach but found he was receiving a well - polished form of responses that had been practiced in formal treatment settings where these questions had all been asked before. The similarities in the present study which led to the developing of the DENIM are such that he is worth quoting at length:

'The original design of this study consisted of an interview method with a half open and half closed structure of questions. This structure was chosen in order to make the research different from but comparable to similar projects in other places (e.g., Winick, 1962, Biernacki, 1986)8). However, the pilot interviews clearly revealed that the chosen structure was not helpful in gaining a deep understanding of the course of the process of hard drug addiction. What we got instead was a "polished" repetition of the normal intake stories that the interviewees had told, sometimes repeatedly, to the different staff members of the treatment centers. The format of the interview gradually changed into an increasingly open type of communication—and finally into a narrative interview in which the researcher interferes as little as possible with the unfolding of the interviewee's

autobiographical narrative which is shaped by certain constraints of off-the-cuff story telling' (Prins, 2008: 6)

There are many parallels between the work of Prins (2008) and the present study in terms of the evolution of research design through a pilot stage of more traditional interview methods and the issue of well –polished stories (this will be taken up again in Chapter two part two of analysis where I look at the apparent differences between well-rehearsed and novel stories of drug use). Prins describes his process as involving as little interference as possible. I do not necessarily agree with the term interference which places an implicitly negative valuation on the contributions of the researcher, which I go on to suggest are a vital component of the narrative interview, however I think what Prins is alluding to is the level of control given over to the narrator, which is a defining feature of the DENIM.

Elliot et al (2002) advocate the use of an unstructured approach to gain insight in hidden population studies where the research is exploratory in nature. Not only did it promise to uncover previously unknown issues, but it altered the power dynamic in a very significant way which was essential for the more controversial aspects of their stories to be aired. Indeed, the giving over of control over content to the women was an observable relief. In stressing that I was curious to learn what was important to them, I demonstrated empathy and understanding of the ways in which they are routinely misjudged by not operating on the basis of presumptions about their experiences with and through drugs.

The DENIM is unstructured in the sense that an interview schedule was not constructed on the basis of gaps in the literature. Rather focusing researcher attention on guiding towards certain topics of interest, the energy is channelled into maintaining a non-threatening presence and responding appropriately and sensitively to emerging verbal and non-verbal cues. This open and indirect approach to talking about sensitive issues is also especially important in maintaining trust and communication in the budding research relationship. In the context of heightened child protection concerns over parental drug use for example, where women are particularly guarded and defensive, asking direct questions is perceived as intrusive and inherently threatening. The narrative interview method which takes seriously the social context and the role of the researcher in co-constructing meaning, in particular the desire for social acceptability, is well suited to the study of hidden populations of women who use drugs (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008), (Esin et al, 2013).

Crucially, the narrative approach which encourages free flowing conversation avoids the imposition of meaning which results from more structured approaches to qualitative interviewing. According to Holloway and Jefferson (2008) the researcher adopts the position of listener and the respondent the storyteller and in doing so the way in which a researcher imposes meaning can be drastically reduced. The emphasis on active listening in the DENIM to be able to maximise the narrative material in the interview cannot be understated. But with this emphasis on listening come the most crucial feature; the existence of empathy.

Empathy has traditionally been defined as the process of stepping into the world of another, to experience their thoughts and emotions as if they were our own and using this very personal experience to gain a sense of what it is like to be that person (Gair, 2012). However according to Ettore (2017) in feminist studies of drug use, having empathy does not involve taking on the feelings of another as your own. Rather;

'by cultivating resonance with the other, the storyteller becomes aware deeply that empathy is not something one person has for another; rather empathy is what a person is with another: a relationship in which each understands herself as requiring completion' (Ettore, 2017: 8)

Like Ettore (2017), I foregrounding the active quality of empathy as something that someone does instead of something they have, and I do this through the emphasis on demonstration.

Consequently, In DENIM, empathy is demonstrative in that this internal experience is actively shown and communicated to the person speaking. This is expressed in various ways appropriate to the context of the utterance and it might be verbal or non-verbal. For example where there is relaying of a distressing event I respond with statements that convey appropriate sentiments in a culturally sensitive way. For example sometimes that might be 'that is awful' or 'that must be so hard'. With women that share my indigenous 'Glaswegian' mode of expression I might even offer a sympathetic 'for fuck's sake', which far from being rude implies 'goodness me, this is far from desirable' in a manner in which they can resonate on a personal level. Where there is desire for confirmation of understanding I respond with an encouraging nod of the head. Sometimes demonstrative empathy takes the form of laughter, a smile, or raised eyebrows. The choice of response is partly reflexive and involves a degree of mirroring of the emotional state of the person being interviewed. Highlighting the importance of the body in ethnographic research, Judith Okely (2007) explores this process of 'bodily mimesis' showing how researchers mirroring of 'subtle rhythms and movements' reveals an unconscious empathy

with those we research. She suggests that through this practice, researchers at risk of being viewed as cultural outsiders can modify perceptions of positioning.

It is my observation, that in hidden populations where the group boundaries are subject to such relentless policing, it is not enough that the researcher feels unconscious empathy, rather, she must actively *demonstrate* it. As Susan Gair explains, the aim is to be able to ‘hear, feel, understand, and value the stories of others and to convey that felt empathy and understanding back to the storyteller (Gair, 2012:134). DENIM thus brings to attention the concept of emotional labour, a feature of interviewing women who use drugs that is usually downplayed or altogether ignored (Ettorre, 2017). An example of my interaction is offered on page 16 in my exchange with Mary where I discuss the successes and failures in interviewing and the need for feminist researchers to embrace their own vulnerability. DENIM addresses the power dynamic inherent in interviews with marginalised populations. Guided by a feminist sensibility, it seeks to stress the commonalities among women and minimise any perceptions of superiority between researcher and researched, without erasing the obvious differences in the process.

The lack of comment on effective qualities for interviewing is particularly evident with narrative research methodologies, according to Bleakley (2005). Through the practice of the DENIM I wish to highlight three key components that combine to create an interview format that is particularly geared towards the study of women who use drugs. They are; control, empathy and relaxation. The interviewee has control over content, the interviewer responds with demonstrated empathy and this interaction takes place in a setting which is relaxed and informal as possible.

Indeed, it appears that denim, the very fabric of informality, is a fortunate and fitting acronym due to the relaxed nature of these interviews. Indeed, in order to secure an agreement to take part the informality of the encounter, which was pitched as a conversation over coffee, was often stressed. Having said that, given the intricacies involved in the building and maintaining of trust it cannot be stressed enough that the process of interviewing hidden populations of women who use drugs is a time consuming, and as we shall now see, sometimes emotionally exhausting enterprise.

Ethical challenges

According to Corbin and Morse (2003) sensitive topics and the ethical challenges they bring are especially likely with the use of unstructured interviews in which there is a different 'risk profile' due to the participant having more control over the content. However, for these authors, such risks are no greater than those encountered in everyday life and can be managed carefully with a level of skill from the researcher.

In the current study, my interview with Allie was perhaps the most challenging ethically and emotionally. During the course of the interview which took place within the privacy and comfort of the participant's home, a disturbing disclosure of sexual violence was made. What follows is my reflective writing entry post interview.

The case of Allie

It has taken almost three days for me to write this entry after meeting with Allie. Her story has raised sensitive issues that require me to pause and reflect on matters of ethical concern. The circumstances of our meeting still feel very fresh in my mind, and as quite a remarkable character, I feel confident that the time passed has not impeded my recollection of the event.

Allie contacted me via email three weeks ago, two weeks prior to the date that we met in person. She gave a brief biography and explained that she had heard about me from a friend who met me at a festival and would like speak to me. I responded swiftly to her proposal and with enthusiasm, and after a few communications back and forth we arranged a date.

Initially Allie indicated her preference to meet in a café in Glasgow. I explained that this would be okay, however it would have to be one that was relatively quiet, for purposes of privacy and also through previous bad experience with my recording device in public spaces. In response she invited me to her flat. I was pleased about this, as it indicated an existing level of trust. I also knew that the most successful interviews so far had taken place within the woman's home. On their own territory, so to speak.

The day before our meeting, I emailed Allie to check that all was still okay for the interview to go ahead. Her response was positive, encouraging.

On the day itself, I had a number of errands to run before I was due at her home in the East end of Glasgow. I knew this part of the city very well, it was my end of the city, and so the anxiety I had felt at finding her was little in comparison to the women who lived on the 'other' side. I parked the car in the area, and about ten minutes later Allie came out

onto the main road to meet me. She first struck me as strong and athletic, dressed in training gear. We shook hands and I followed her to the apartment block in which she lived. We made small talk about house prices and the local area on the way up the stairs. She then revealed that she had been made aware of the study by a trusted colleague, whom I also had professional connections with.

Knowing this, her move to invite me into her home suddenly made more sense.

As we entered her flat, which was very clean and fresh, she directed me to sit in the living area and offered coffee from the kitchen. Minutes later she was sat on the sofa to my left. As I began to explain the reasons for the recording device, she interrupted to tell me that she herself had done research before on drug policy, of which she had always had an interest. She then went on to talk about Foucault and his theory of technologies of the self, and how she had found this particularly useful in understanding the governance of drug use. I realised that telling me this was an attempt to position her own self as an equal to me, and in that moment I became aware of the power relations between researcher and the researched, and how they were being negotiated between us as we sipped at our freshly brewed coffee.

Afterwards she asked me how I 'wanted to do this'. Shall I just start from the beginning? Chronologically? I gave her permission to tell her story in the way that felt best for her and listened intently as she described her first experiences with illegal drugs as a young adolescent.

As Allie spoke, I took a mental note of her body language. She sat on the edge of the seat with her arms folded across her chest. Aware of her need to feel safe, I checked my own body language and consciously made an effort to be as open and natural as possible. The consequence of this was that I laughed heartily when she made a joke about her rebelliousness as a teenager, in a way that conveyed that I had understood and appreciated her light-hearted perspective. Allie responded very positively to my outburst and chimed in with her own lively giggle. I noticed a change in her expression then, a light in her eyes, and she sat back in her chair, more visibly relaxed. Through this laughing I felt we connected in some way.

Most of the early experiences Allie recounted were positive in nature. She described the extreme pleasure she had experienced taking MDMA, and the way in which it had also been very spiritual. Lost in the recollection of one particular event, eyes closed, she took me by surprise by suddenly looking straight at me with a serious expression exclaiming 'Am I boring you?'. I was taken aback by this and wondered if I had done something to give her the impression that I was unimpressed. 'Not at all' I responded, 'please, go on.'

As she moved on to discuss her more recent experience of taking drugs, I noticed a change in her demeanour. She was perched on the edge of the seat and rarely did she make eye contact, focusing instead on the wall straight ahead of her. In what felt like a very long pause, I sensed the mood had shifted. My gut instinct guided me to remain calm despite the surge of adrenaline which was now coursing through my veins, sharpening my focus.

The next twenty minutes proved difficult for both of us, as I listened to Allie talk about deeply traumatic events that had transpired whilst seriously intoxicated with Class A drugs. I was rather shocked, but I don't think I showed it. I concentrated all my effort into conveying empathy and compassion through my facial expression and body language.

As the conversation drew naturally to a close, she acknowledged the vulnerable positions that she had found herself in through taking drugs. I felt compelled to tell her that I too, had been in similar positions through drinking too much alcohol. We spent a few moments reflecting on the potential dangers of losing control like this, and how lucky we were to live to tell the tale. I mentioned how terrified it made me to imagine my daughter in that situation. Allie agreed and told me that her friends had voiced concern about her safety after a particular incident where she had lost all whereabouts after taking too much ketamine and was thankfully taken care of by a kind stranger.

She ended the interview by saying 'That's the thing with taking drugs, you never know whether you are going to have the best or the worst night in your life'.

There is potentially much to explore within this reflective summary of my interview with Allie. For the present discussion I wish to focus in on the disturbing material, my response to it, and how this corresponds to the ethical guidelines for the researching of sensitive topics.

In retrospect, I reacted to Allie's disclosure much on the basis of gut instinct which guided me to remain calm. Demonstrating that I was listening carefully and empathically through the use of gesture and facial expression, I allowed her to speak until her story about this harrowing event came to a natural close. All the while as she spoke I watched her carefully for signs of emotional distress. The events she recounted clearly had a significant impact upon her psychologically and emotionally, but as she shared them with me she appeared largely unperturbed. Nonetheless, I sought confirmation that she felt well enough to continue the interview, reminding her that we could stop at any time, mindful of the guidelines for ethical research. Allie confirmed that she was happy to go on, telling me that she was in a good enough place now to talk about 'all this shit', whereas before it would have been more of a struggle. After the recording device was turned off, I thanked her participant for sharing her experience

with me, acknowledging how difficult such things can be to communicate. Allie responded very well to my offerings of praise and despite the darkness of the terrain we had covered, I had the sense that the interview terminated on a positive note. Yet in the days after I continued to feel unsettled. Replaying the dialogue between us over in my head I sought reassurance I had done all I could to look after her as my research participant. Such difficulties in disengaging with participants in similar circumstances have been highlighted by Dempsey et al, 2016).

Here the distress protocols outlined in the sensitive topic literature (see for example Draucker et al, 2009; Dickson – Swift et al, 2008; Haigh and Witham, 2013) were extremely helpful and I held this information in mind as I progressed through the following interviews, acutely aware of the possibility that further disclosures of a similar nature could arise. It should be noted that I was somewhat dubious about going into the interviewing phase with the expectation that such sensitive information would come up. This came from my critical perspective on the dominant discourses of women who use drugs in which the assumption of victimhood is firmly embedded. Despite my hesitance to assume that topics such as sexual violence and domestic abuse would decidedly form part of the women's narratives, I was nonetheless equipped for the possibility. Overall, such disclosures that have the potential to cause psychological distress were in the minority in this study, but as I learned through my experience with Allie, when they do occur they become an added weight that the researcher has to carry. It is for this reason that researching sensitive topics has been described as a form of emotion work (Dickson-Swift et al, 2009). Moving forward I was much more aware of the importance of looking after myself as well as my participants and I strongly recommend that future researchers who find themselves in a similar position seek advice and support where appropriate.

Healing vs harmful narratives

While it is paramount to ensure the psychological safety of research participants in the study of sensitive topics, it is worthwhile noting that not all participants experience such interviews in the same way. Heather McCosker, in her 1995 study on the experiences of women who have survived domestic violence, highlights that some of her participants benefitted from discussing sensitive material with the researcher, reporting that they found it more useful than counselling. A similar statement was made by one of the participants in the current study;

Karen: Thank you for this today Katie.

Katie: That's okay, I have actually found it very useful to talk about it with you.

Katie went on to inform me that she was moving towards seeking professional help for her unhealthy patterns of drug use that were clearly having a significant impact on her mental health and performance at work. Entering a therapeutic relationship was a big step for Katie, who had gone to a great deal of effort to keep her problem hidden from family, and she felt that talking about these highly sensitive and potentially stigmatising issues with me was a helpful ‘warm up’.

Similarly Joanna indicated that the sharing of her story was beneficial, in that it generated a lot of positive memories, despite the fact her experiences with illicit drug use were often quite dark and depressing;

Karen: And how do you feel now after talking about this?

Joanna: It's making me think about a lot of things. It's making me remember a lot of good times. And it's making me think twice about why we choose to do what we do. How much I would actually, defend it.

Evidently, the interview seems to have prompted Joanna to engage in a process of critical self - reflection. At the closing of the conversation, she appears to be questioning her feelings about her drug use.

On the contrary Mary seemed to gain from the experience a sense of empowerment:

Mary: you know this has been really great. I feel excited now that I am on the right path.

A primary school teacher, Mary was very conscious of how others perceived her after having been actively persecuted from senior members of the community when they had found out about her regular use of cannabis. Consequently, she was used to keeping her drug use hidden from fear of negative judgement from others. The experience of the demonstratively empathic narrative interview, where she spoke freely about the drug use and was met with unconditional positive regard and encouragement, thus stood in stark contrast. That a researcher, whom she clearly viewed as knowledgeable in the field of drug use, actively validated the injustice of her predicament demonstrating empathy through body language as she recounted the story of her persecution, must have been experienced as empowering. The ‘right path’ that Mary describes refers to her decision to continue on with a vocal defence about the benefits of cannabis use, perhaps emboldened by my reminder that not everyone views this behaviour as immoral and inherently problematic.

Narrative interviews clearly have transformative potential for some participants and this should be taken into account by ethics advisory committees when assessing the possibility of harm in the study of sensitive topics. For this reason, some researchers go as far as to say that narrative research is emancipatory (Wolgemuth and Donohoe (2006). However, making the distinction between healing and harmful narratives is not always a straightforward process (Hyden, 2013). To further complicate the matter, the negative bias which characterises drugs discourse at large thus seems to be reflected in the ethical discussions about the risks of researching female drug use. In order that such benefits be realised, it is helpful for research ethics committees to be aware of the negative bias that permeates the ‘drug talk’ on women’s drug use and consider how and in what way this may influence the decision making processes in which they engage. It is argued that taking action to prevent harm to participants can sometimes violate the principle of autonomy, for example by terminating the conversation at the first signs of distress (Newman and Kaloupek, 2004).

In a discussion on reflexivity and responsibility by Clarke (2006), it is argued that consideration must be given to the potential distress caused in the extended research team, including supervisors and transcribers. Clearly the definition of distress here is important, and this requires careful thought if we are not to dilute the significance of the experience for those most affected. I also worry that such precautions will lead to a form of censorship. Having said that, the particularly sensitive nature of the some of the women’s accounts incorporating various highly personal and traumatic themes such as suicide, mental illness and rape, inspired a hesitance to employ the services of a transcriber. Even though professional standards would have been maintained and anonymity protected, doing so felt like a violation of the participants trust in me. On the other hand, a significant level of trust is cultivated between research proteges and their mentors particularly so when sharing of control and fair behaviour are clearly present (Erdem and Aytemur, 2008). This allowed me to share my transcripts with the director of study with confidence. In addition, the reflective writing helped me to process some of own feelings about the disclosure, a process I feel was vital in order for me to transcribe the audio recording of the interview without becoming unduly distressed.

The many challenges encountered by qualitative researchers from maintaining boundaries to forming friendships are further complicated in the study of sensitive topics. According to Milling-Kinnard (1996):

“Efforts to address these issues would be enhanced by more published accounts of investigators’ experiences in dealing with the effects on researchers of conducting studies on sensitive and emotionally laden topics: Too little attention is given to documenting the process of carrying out research”. (as cited in Dickson-Swift et al, 2007: 328)

The last line of this quote is particularly relevant for the present argument as it adds further weight to the argument for hidden population research to be fully or partially auto-ethnographic. The reflective writing method that I have chosen to adopt in the current study, thus addresses the shortcomings of snowball sampling methods, where the processes of trust building are not transparent, and it also further highlights the gap in knowledge about the study of sensitive topics, and the ways in which some of the inherent challenges can be met and overcome. This work can therefore be added to the growing body of literature in which researchers have written reflectively about their own experiences of studying sensitive topics (Burr, 1995; Cannon, 1992; Darlington and Scott, 2002; Ferguson, 2003; Gair, 2002; Harris and Huntington, 2001; Hubbard et al., 2001; Kitson et al., 1996; McCosker et al., 2001; Melrose, 2002; Rosenblatt, 2001; Warr, 2004).

Table (1): Participant profiles

Network	Participant	Pseudonym	Age	Occupation	Current drug/s of choice	Parental status	Ethnic Origin
2	1	Shirley	39	Artist	LSD, Cannabis	No	White
2	2	Claire	38	Painter decorator	MDMA, Psilocybin	No	White
2	3	Mary	52	Primary school teacher	Cannabis, DMT	Yes	White
3	4	Freda	36	Academic	Psilocybin, Cannabis	Yes	White
1	5	Megan	33	Carer	Cannabis	Yes	White
0	6	Summer	50	Support worker	Cannabis, LSD.	No	White
2	7	Maya	44	Housewife	MDMA	No	White
3	8	Allie	28	Lawyer	Ecstasy, Ketamine	No	White

1	9	Aimee	32	Healthcare Support Worker	Cocaine	Yes	White
1	10	Louisa	30	Student	Cocaine	Yes	White
0	11	Katie	32	Academic	MDMA, cocaine	No	White
2	12	Daisy	32	Artist	MDMA, mescaline,	No	White European
3	13	Rachel	39	Volunteer manager	Psilocybin, MDMA	Yes	White
3	14	Marie	41	Third sector	MDMA	Yes	White and Black Caribbean
2	15	Julie	52	Social Services	MDMA	Yes	White
2	16	Joanna	44	Alternative Therapist	Psilocybin, cannabis	Yes	White
2	17	Wendy	37	Local Council	Cocaine, MDMA	Yes	Asian Scottish
2	18	Lana	37	Photographer	Cocaine	Yes	White
3	19	Charmaine	29	Third Sector	Cannabis	No	White
2	20	Jane	40	Nurse	MDMA, cocaine	No	White

Table (1) displays some of the most basic characteristics of the sample. Anonymity and confidentiality are protected by pseudonym, which the participant chose for themselves so that they may readily identify themselves in the published data.

The column which displays the participants' drug of choice highlights the substance most favourably viewed at the time of interview. It is by no means an exhaustive list of substances used historically. For example, participants may have used heroin historically but it is not described in the same functional terms as the substances listed above.

Social Networks

Table (2) labels each social network within the sample and shows how many further recruits were enlisted by each key informant.

Network	Key informant	No. referrals	Total links
0*	Summer, Katie	0	2
1	Aimee	2	3
2	Shirley	9	10
3	Charmaine	4	5

Network 0*: key informants: Summer/Katie. Number of further recruits: 0 (t=2)

Network 1: key informant: Aimee. Number of further women recruited: 2 (t=3)

Network 2: key informant: Shirley. Number of further women recruited: 9 (t =10)

Network 3: key informant: Charmaine. Number of further women recruited: 4 (t=5)

*Summer and Katie were not part of any of the main social networks and had no existing relationships with any other participants. Although viewed as potential gatekeepers, they failed to provide any viable contacts. Katie had set up a meeting for me with her friend, but she failed to turn up without explanation. Contact with Summer was lost after a few months into study.

Conclusion

One of the primary aims of this study was to generate insight into the processes of gaining access to hidden populations of women who use drugs. The key lessons learned from my experiences of the snowball sampling method and of building and maintaining trust have thus been outlined within this section of the thesis. Although already aware of the major barrier that stigma and discrimination presents in relation to researching illicit and illegal drug use, I now have more intimate knowledge of common defence mechanisms encountered and grappled with strategies with which they can be overcome. A degree of sensitivity is required throughout the process of engagement, and this is particularly important where multiple marginality is present.

The period of time where I experienced a series of setbacks and frustrations in making contact taught me how difficult it was for some of the women to talk about their drug use. For some such as Katie, it represented a huge step forward in her journey towards a more positive relationship with illegal substances. With this in mind it is important to be patient and

understanding. Persistence is key too, so long as the individual has communicated a clear desire to take part.

Snowball sampling techniques can be demanding at times in terms of the amount of groundwork required to build relationships and the energy consumed by responding to opportunities as and when they arise. Adding to this is the weight of potentially traumatic/disturbing material being produced in the context of sensitive topics therefore it is important to take seriously the wellbeing of the researcher. The level of trust required for women reveal this hidden aspect of their identity requires constant self- monitoring and mistakes made from lack of preparation or time to decompress can greatly hinder the progress of the study.

Indeed, it should now be apparent that trust is absolutely essential to the success of hidden population research is vital at every stage in the process from agreement to first meet to later opening up to share, what are frequently, intensely personal experiences. It is therefore important that I honour this trust where it has been gained by representing their stories and experiences to the best of my ability.

Chapter Five: ‘Introducing Dialogical Narrative Analysis’

Navigating the field

On first approaching the literature on narrative analysis the novice researcher is flooded with a dizzying array of methods and concepts rooted in various understandings of narrative research and its varying analytical scope. Performing an effective narrative analysis on my data involved clarifying what kind of narrative analysis was consistent with my philosophical position of ontological relativism and epistemological constructionism (Smith, 2016) and what promise this method of analysis had in aiding understanding of hidden populations of women who use drugs. Owing to the considerable development of narrative analysis within the last ten years (Squire, 2010) I learned that more than one analytical framework is justifiably suitable. The three main methods, according to Riessman (2008) are thematic, structural and performative/dialogical and within each of these approaches is a great deal of diversity in terms of how narrative is defined and approached (Duque, 2009).

Yet for other narrative researchers the key distinction to be made is between event-centred and experience centred approaches (Squire, 2010). Focusing on events and the retelling of them was initially considered an interesting way forward and I imagined directing analytical focus to stories about those key events which routinely characterise the trajectory of ‘drug using careers’ such as initiation and cessation. However, according to Wendy Patterson (2013), within this framework there is little room for how a narrator’s experience shapes the reconstruction of events, assuming that internal representations remain more or less constant. Experience centred approaches, on the other hand, are more expansive, seeing singular experiences as generating many possible stories across different places and times, thus being more sensitive to matters of social context (Patterson, 2013).

Collecting and analysing stories of people living with HIV in South Africa, Corinne Squire (1999) shows how the large volume of data contained within experienced centred narrative interviews can result in the ‘glossing over of whole lives’. Like many novice researchers, I feared choosing the ‘wrong method’ and consequently missing the opportunity to portray a really important or interesting aspect of the women’s experiences. Getting past this feeling of being stuck came through understanding that there is no method which is capable of representing the totality of the women’s stories; analysis is inescapably partial and reductive. Indeed, it was the emphasis on the ‘irreducible humanity’ of research participants, of seeing

them as more than data sources which attracted me to a narrative approach in the first place (Smythe and Murray, 2010).

In both experience centred and event centred narrative analyses, narratives are taken as expressions of internal states. As it is my prerogative that the women's stories of drug use are shaped largely by the surrounding culture of stigma and prohibition, I thus chose to ground my analysis in a third option, one which views narratives as forms of social code, and stories as socially and dialogically constructed (Bakhtin, 1981; Frank, 2010). Dialogical narrative analysis emphasises that the researcher and the researched exist in an ongoing state of development and consequently those who practice this method refrain from finalising the narrator (Frank, 2010). In recognition that life experiences shape understanding, it is expected that the meanings the women attach to their drug use are likely to change and with it, their story. So too is it the case with my life experiences which shape and inform my understanding of them.

Molly Andrews (2013) highlights the temporal dimension of interpretation through a discussion of revisiting old data. When researchers look back on their analyses from early on in their career they often resort to self- denigration as they experience a level of disconnect from that earlier perspective. This suggests that as one matures as an academic they are better placed to perform analysis on old data. However, while time and experience, both personal and professional might gift a level of understanding that was previously missing, it is also just as likely that important aspects of the view will be forgotten and left behind. Thus, I agree with a growing number of narrative researchers such as Andrews (2013), Brockmeier (2006), Mishler (2004) when they resist temporal and historical privileging in interpretation; that there is no position or point in time that is more valuable than another for they each afford different and valuable insights. Meaning is multi-layered and complex and consequently, analytic frameworks are always provisional.

[Method as guidelines](#)

Brett Smith (2016) speaks of the sense of bewilderment and anxiety in making sense of storied data which he stresses is a common experience from new and experienced narrative researchers alike, which in part can be explained by the lack of prescribed procedure in producing analysis. Here and in the context of much of the narrative literature 'method' refers to a heuristic guide to interpretation instead of the codified and relatively easy to follow steps that one may find for other more mainstream types of qualitative research such as thematic analysis or grounded

theory (Smith, 2016). In the absence of prescribed techniques many narrative researchers performing dialogical narrative analysis seek out exemplars (Frank, 2010:2012).

Based on this understanding of method, analysis can be viewed as a method of questioning grounded in theoretical assumptions. Rather than following precise steps to arrive at the singular truth of a phenomenon, narrative researchers agree there are multiple valid interpretations and as such the task becomes one of building a persuasive case for a particular interpretation (Squire, 2010). Dialogical narrative analysis does not seek to uncover the truth as much as it creates possibilities for truth (Sullivan, 2012). I follow writers such as Sullivan (2012), whom according to Otrell-Cass (2013) practices dialogism by interacting with the ideas he draws on and reviewing them critically. The purpose of this chapter then is to answer the call to 'let the reader in' to the process of analysis and interpretation (Dickie 2003; Riessman 2008).

Thinking through the issue of ontological relativism highlights the importance of selecting a method of narrative analysis that is consistent with the philosophical framework set out as the foundations of the study. While a theoretical positioning of narrative constructivism would see the women's stories as more or less transparent windows onto their identity and experience, the present position taken is one of narrative constructionism which holds that narratives are the means through which identities and experiences are shaped and constituted as oppose to merely reflected. The former may be viewed as a psychological perspective on narrative analysis while the latter can be understood as a socio-cultural approach (Smith, 2016).

Identifying Stories

According to Mishler (1986), one of the main tasks in approaching interview research from the perspective of narrative analysis is the fleshing out of stories from the transcript. For some researchers who view narrative as but only one way of recounting past experience, then narratives have to be identified and separated from the non -narrative material. On the other hand, there are narrative researchers using interview methods for whom the whole interview is the story. Whether the entire interview is taken as the story or whether the interview contains many stories, according to Elliot Mishler, is a key question as the answer influences the specific aims and features of the study. If the interview is conceived as comprising of both narrative and non-narrative material then it follows that one of the first tasks of analysis is to establish suitable criteria for identifying stories.

In spite of the fact they are commonly used interchangeably, narratives and stories are distinct entities and it is important to be clear on the manner in which they differentiate. However, the question of what constitutes a story is a matter of contention. According to Smith (2016), a story is ‘a specific tale people tell’ (Smith, 2016: 204) which contains characters, which may be people or animals. In contrast, narratives are the building blocks with which we construct our specific stories, given to us by the surrounding culture and passed down through the generations. Stories therefore, can be grouped into narrative typologies. Different ways of organising storied data arise from the different conceptions of narrative. Stereotypical tellings which follow a fairly predictable outline are similar to what literary theorists call fundamental plot lines (Gergen, 2005). For some narrative researchers it is questionable whether it is possible and indeed desirable to reduce stories to a limited number of narrative formations. Kenneth Gergen (2005) proposes a model which has both structure and directionality as the organising principles. Narratives either have stability, progression or regression as a feature and these three trends can be seen as the rudimentary bases for other complex variants.

Beyond big and small stories

For some authors such as Bamberg (2010), small stories are implicated in the construction of identity and the *how*, and big stories are more about the *what* and the representative level. Small stories which occur in conversation are often overlooked in narrative analysis of identity work (Bamberg and Georgakopolou, 2008). These snippets of talk, which she describes as ‘prototypical narratives’ are easily missed out on when looking at narrative through the lens of fully formed stories (Georgakopolou, 2006).

According to Smith (2016) the difference between a big and small story is not only the length but the level of reflection contained and the importance of the events described. Small stories often arise spontaneously in conversation about mundane happenings where big stories relate to significant stages in a life and sometimes an entire life. Labelling a story as big or small on account of this definition can prove problematic. For example, close to end of the interview with Allie, she tells a story about a relatively recent period in her life when she was losing control over her drug use. These events were clearly very important to her and are presented as a turning point in her life. In terms of meaning, it leans toward being a big story but the relative brevity somewhat complicates this categorisation. Using the big /small framework as a way of defining stories is not as clear cut and it is a debate in which it is easy to get entangled. In ‘towards a synthesis’ Mark Freeman (2011) presents this as something of a false dichotomy

suggesting that an integration of theories of big and small stories is required in order to gain a fuller sense of how identity is constructed through storytelling. Allie's story is presented in full in analysis chapter two under stories of 'Lost and Found'. For now, I contend with the question of how to approach analysis of such significant stories within interview data that are relatively short in length, but are nonetheless important sites of identity work.

A dimensional approach to defining narrative

In 'Narrative Lessons' Elinor Ochs (2004) details several key points which have proved indispensable as a workable set of definitions from which to begin the process of fleshing out stories from the transcripts. According to Ochs (2004), there are five dimensions of narrative which can help to distinguish between two different approaches to narrative sense making. The five dimensions of narrative which are *tellership*, *tellability*, *embeddedness*, *linearity* and *moral stance*.

Tellership relates to audience and issues of co-construction. Extent of participation of co-teller exists on continuum, and in most research interview contexts the tellership is one in which the stories are viewed as co-constructed to varying degrees. While the shaping influence of audience is a key part of DNA, my role is also relatively passive and my input minimal (refer to Developing DENIM section for further information).

Tellability relates to the extent to which the events described warrant the act of narration and this aspect exists on a scale. Events which rate high in tellability are often of an unusual character. The non-ordinary nature of drug use thus renders these experiences as high on the tellability scale³.

Embeddedness can be assessed on the basis of whether the narrative is relatively detached from a larger sequence of conversation or embedded within a larger discourse. This dimension helps to contextualise the small stories in relation to the interview as a whole. Detached narratives have an appearance of being unrelated to previous themes, however they are never going to

³ In Frank's (2010) guide to dialogical narrative analysis he asks the researcher to consider what the story makes narratable. It is important to recognise that despite the high tellability of drug use, many of these experiences are not very easy to talk about. Women are routinely judged harshly for using illicit drugs and sometimes their experiences are traumatic in nature).

appear completely out of context. According to Ochs (2004) the key to telling them apart from embedded narratives is the difference in conversational turn taking, and this is easy to see in a written transcript.

Linearity can either be closed and definitive or non-linear and under questioning and it is this dimension which helps to distinguish between narratives of coherence and narratives of inquiry. Without imposing a linearity on the women's narratives through the use of a structured interview guide, the women often jumped back and forward in time. There was no clear sense of events flowing seamlessly into each other, no clear sense of cause and effect, which highlights the influence of context in shaping narrative.

Moral stance is the last dimension of narrative as storytelling is implicated in the cultivation of morality. Narratives allow events to be brought into moral focus in a variety of different ways, for example by seeking affirm an existing moral perspective, which can be seen when speakers adopt the moral high ground in a story. At other times, certain narratives are launched as the narrator is unsure of how to morally evaluate certain aspects of their experience.

Understanding these two approaches and learning to differentiate between them is key to overcoming the overwhelming bias towards coherence, a problem identified elsewhere by Georgakopolou (2006) in her call to focus on small stories. A second kind of narrative which could be called inquiry narratives are often overlooked in narrative studies, and yet they are distinct in many important ways. Broadly speaking, coherent narratives display a consistent form of logic whereas narratives of inquiry involve a probing of different forms of logic. Tellings of the latter involve a process of sorting through different ways of looking at an issue when the meaning of events is less certain and unfixed.

While acknowledging that temporality is an important and indispensable feature of narrative, it has perhaps been emphasised to too great an extent by many narrative scholars. Through his notion of the dialogical imagination, Mikhail Bakhtin (1981) sought to underline the equal importance of the spatial aspects of narrative through a focus on positioning and an emphasis on discontinuity over continuity (Hermans, 2001). Bakhtin's theory of the dialogical self introduced the overlapping concepts of polyphony, multiplicity and multivoicedness; existing simultaneously as multiple and sometimes contradictory perspectives inside one character.

On the basis of Ochs's (2004) dimensional criteria, the narratives in this study are viewed as small stories in which the women co-construct meaning about significant drug experiences which are high in tellability. In the early stages of analysis as I looked through the transcripts

for stories using this criteria in the process of indwelling (Frank, 2010; Beggan, 2017) the differences between detached and embedded narratives became more apparent. My tendency has been to single out narratives that are not composed of repeated turn taking. Firstly, such detached narratives stand out more. The start and finish is often clearly signalled with statements which indicate that one is about to enter the world of a tale, for example ‘it all started a few months ago’ or ‘It was last summer when’ (Gergen, 2005). Secondly, described as compelling in nature, detached narratives are viewed as being more geared towards performance. They employ a range ‘distinctive rhetorical techniques’ (see Pratt, 1977) and consequently these will be analysed for each of the stories presented.

Other, less recognisable kinds of narrative were visible within the transcripts. While such co-constructed conversational narratives are the focus of many interesting studies (see Gubrium and Holstein, 2008), following Frank (2010) I am unsure that they have the same capacity as the stories presented here, insofar as they are unlikely to have been told before and will unlikely be told again.

Due to their distinctly performative nature, I have selected 8 examples of detached narratives of inquiry from the transcripts and will pay specific attention to the moral dimension of these stories as it is particularly relevant in the study of stories told by women who use drugs. These are from Allie, Daisy Clark, Mary, Joanna, Freda, Louisa, Marie, and Rachel.

Questions to guide the analysis of the stories

In addition to the analytical focus described above, the following questions inspired by the work of Brett Smith will be used to direct the dialogical analysis of each of the eight stories on an individual basis.

Resources – What narrative resources are being used and how does this relate to their position in society? Do I see the influence of the dominant discourses of drug use and addiction? Pathology and powerlessness paradigm? What other cultural narratives are threaded in?

Connection – Does the story work to connect her or disconnect her from a particular identity? Do she seek to affiliate with a particular group or collective in the story?

Identity – It is widely accepted that stories help constitute sense of self and identity (Bamberg and Georgakopolou 2008; Freeman, 2003). Through storytelling identities are reworked and sometimes subtly invoked (Georgakopolou, 2006). Identity construction through narrative is

not the same for all people and will be different according to life circumstances. For some the sense of identity is more stable and less likely to be reshaped during the course of interactions with others yet for others whom are 'identity challenged' this process is more evident. Here Smith (2016) gives the example of adolescents whom are typically trying on different identities and jilted lovers whom are undergoing a huge transformation in their sense of self. In the context of this study, the notion of being identity challenged appeals to describe hidden populations of women who use drugs whose identity work, by definition, is particularly challenging in the context of stigma and concealment.

Broadly speaking, does the story give me a sense of who she is and if so how does it do this? Does her identity appear to be unstable? Does her narrative perform a transformation in identity?

Body – How does my body respond to her story and how is her own body used to tell the story? This is very important as embodied responses relate to the concept of narrative habitus (Frank, 2010; Fleetwood, 2016).

Agency/positioning – From the narrative point of view, agency is also exercised through the way that stories are told. Who and what is cast as powerful, as the determining force? Does this change at any point in the story, and if so, under what circumstances? Questions that illuminate the construction of agency, or lack thereof, will be asked of each of the stories of drug use represented here. For example, is there evidence of agentive discourse as according to Brockmeier (2009), Harre (1995) and Bamberg (1997) or attribution of agency and responsibility to self or others through subject positioning? (Bamberg, 1997)

Future – how does the story work to legitimise future drug use? Are they clear about where they are going? Is the function of the narrative to orient themselves along a particular path?

Function – According to Bamberg (1987) each story is likely to be performing a variety of different functions at the same time, for example to entertain, to shock, to build intimacy, as well as making identity statements about the type of person 'I am'. In the genre of studies which looks at narratives of health and illness for example, it can be seen that certain stories have quite predictable effects. What does her story accomplish?

Circulation – Who has the story been told to before? Does it come across as well rehearsed or novel? Are there people that it would not be told to?

Consciousness - Are they aware of the function and effect of the story? Do they give any clues that they know the consequences of telling it? Are they aware they are mobilising potentially problematic discourses or are they more concerned with their immediate effects? What does this mean for the debate over conscientization?

Finding Focus

In Frank's (2010) 'Letting Stories Breathe' there are several key questions which are useful in guiding a dialogical narrative analysis and it is up to researchers to decide which ones are the most relevant to them. The questions which keep thought moving should be influenced by other work in the narrative field while at the same time be adapted to meet the particular needs of that study. The literature reviewed on illicit drug use in hidden populations and the wider theoretical body concerned with feminist methodologies both inform my emphasis in questioning the stories.

Understanding how agency is constructed and exercised is a focus of many women's studies and is particularly pertinent to the study of women's drug use. Some authors looking at women's accounts of drug use from the perspective that they reflect more or less the experiences they describe have situated agency within the very act of using drugs, often as a mode of resistance to dominant and stereotypical constructions of gender. In order to get past the problem of polarisation, where women either have full power and control or none at all, (Charrad, 2010), that in drug research has been highlighted as a particular problem (Miller and Carbone-Lopez, 2015), it is essential to improve our understanding of the interplay of structure and agency.

The focus in this study is on how the women construct agency in the act of telling stories about drug use. From a narrative standpoint, stories are the means through which people act and are acted upon. Here, the women are acted upon insofar as the stories they tell are limited in their construction through the sociocultural narratives which exist about that particular experience. However, they are not condemned to act out passively the narrative resources which are passed on to them through the surrounding culture. Storytellers exercise agency through the choices they make in artfully composing a particular story in relation to the situational context and the cultural narratives they use and reproduce in the construction of their stories is often strongly influenced by social background and positionality (Frank, 2010; Fleetwood, 2016).

In its purest form identity positioning analysis entails a purely discursive approach to narrative analysis which is used by many researchers who seek to understand the different strategies

employed by narrators as they construct their identity in the context of narrative research interviews (see Lucius, Hoene and Depperman (2000) for an in depth exposition of this method). According to Squire (2010), narrative analysts can and often utilise aspects of positioning theory within the broader tradition of their approach to narrative analysis. How can this theory of narrative agency be applied to the dialogical analysis of the stories of women who use drugs?

Inspired by the theory of the dialogical self, I borrow from the positioning literature in my dialogical analysis as it touches nicely upon matters of agency that are especially relevant to the study of women who use drugs. Specifically, in the analysis of the selected stories in this chapter, I explore in particular how the use of certain 'I' statements can bring about a sense of agency in a context of powerlessness. Drawing on the work of Harre (1995), Yates and Hiles (2010) frame the use of pronouns as especially significant:

'The use of pronouns is thus crucial for how people-in-talk are positioned in social space. Pronouns serve not only as referents to people but also have illocutionary and perlocutionary effects in terms of locating agency, moral responsibility, duties, rights, points-of-view, and so on.' (Yates and Hiles, 2010:537)

Shifts in pronouns, for example from I to we, signal a shift in positioning from speaking for oneself to speaking on behalf of a group or organisation. This is important to consider in the present context where negotiating moral responsibility and agency are assumed to be core functions of the women's narratives. Consequently, in analysing each of the selected stories, comments are offered on the positioning of the women in relation to others, and also in relation to themselves (sometimes a past self like in the story from Louisa) and in doing so I draw further insight from the work of Bamberg (1997), who details the three levels of positioning which can be seen in storied data. The 'who am I?' question does not presuppose a unitary subject that is positioned in a rather determined way by master narratives. On the contrary, positioning analysis underscores the subject as self positioning agent in the course of interaction, in which 'discursive repertoires are not given but 'interactively accomplished' (Bamberg, 2005: 224).

The concept of narrative habitus provides a way in to interrogate the process through which discursive repertoires are acquired, bringing together the questions of embodiment, circulation and resources. Stemming from Pierre Bourdieu's concept of habitus, narrative habitus is '*the embedding of stories in bodies*', and it refers to an '*embodied sense of attraction, repulsion or*

indifference, it represents a world of which we are a part or in which we have no stake' (Frank, 2010: 53). Using food as an example, Frank (2010) describes habitus as a person's disposition to like certain things and behave in certain ways due to comfort and familiarity which over time has become like second nature. He recognises that the complexity of narrative habitus cannot be captured easily, however for the purposes of showing how it is essential for understanding how stories live in the body and how function in relationship, he has broken it down into the following four components. Narrative habitus relates to:

1. the repertoire of stories that is shared by a group
2. the competence to use this repertoire as embodied and mostly tacit knowledge, which enables prediction of how others will react to a story that might be told.
3. the disposition of a person to tell certain stories and to which stories they will open to receiving
4. the sense of the right way that a half told story can be resolved, the predictable plot completions which reflects a person's sense of their life's possibilities, which again is tacit knowledge

Narrative habitus has thus been posited as a means of addressing the entrenched structure/agency dualism in narrative criminology, for example in this analysis of the narratives of offenders by Jennifer Fleetwood (2016), In short, storytelling is structured via the habitus, which generates but does not determine social action. In the analysis chapter three, a dialogical perspective on women's drug talk, I delve deeper into this concept of narrative habitus (Frank, 2010), exploring its potential to explain the differences in the stories told by women who use drugs whom are notable for their different social locations.

Many of the questions suggested by Smith (2016) to guide a dialogical narrative analysis deal with interlinking and overlapping phenomena. For example, a way of looking at matters of agency and connection simultaneously is by asking the question 'Who is holding their own in the story, and also who is the story making it more difficult to hold their own after it has been told? For Frank (2010), 'holding one's own' in a story is 'situations which begin with a person who has a degree of self- regard, someone with a sufficient self-consciousness of what is valuable or respectful about herself'. Holding owns own is a function of stories in which tellers seek to avoid threats to value of the self. It hardly surprising then that this aspect of stories would feature strongly in the present context; as previously mentioned women who use drugs

can be understood as ‘defended subjects’ in the context of a culture which readily shames and demonises their behaviour.

Outline of analysis chapters

In the text that follows I apply my growing awareness of how to make sense of storied data in order to achieve a greater understanding of hidden populations of women who use drugs and innovative ways in which they can be researched.

In the first chapter of analysis titled ‘circles of trust’ I look across the collection of narratives and identify key themes along the lines of similarity and difference. Exploring the women’s web of social relations, I attempt to answer the first research question which is concerned with the reasons why women are largely a ‘hidden’ population.

Criteria for defining narrative allowed me to select 7 small stories which form the basis of chapter two. Using an approach to DNA I analyse these stories, hoping to offer a deeper insight into the experiences of women who use drugs (rq 1) whilst demonstrating an alternative way of researching hidden populations (rq 2). In this chapter I enter deeper into the discussion on the women’s self- construction of agency, gender and the performance of various femininities by looking at the various means of accomplishing social acceptance and performing a moral identity through the lens of Bakhtin’s dialogical self (Hermans, 2001 and 2003; Skinner, Valsinen and Holland, 2001).

In chapter three of analysis ‘towards a theory of women’s drug talk’ I attempt to make sense of the ambiguity apparent across the whole collection of stories, drawing inspiration from the way dialogical theory has been applied to the study of exile discourse in order to problematise monological readings of women’s drug use. Finally, I suggest that the concept of narrative habitus and the inner library (Frank, 2010) can be helpful for solving the puzzle of hidden populations and for creating a new and much needed genre of stories about women who use drugs.

How it should be read

In narrative analysis the researcher can either adopt the position of storyteller or story analyst (Bochner and Riggs, 2014). In this thesis I shift between these two positions. For example in the reflective writing in ‘Situating the researcher’ and in the diary excerpts in ‘Accessing and Engaging’, I occupy the position of storyteller. In the next three chapters I purposefully occupy the position of story analyst.

According to Bamberg (1997), narrative analysis can be viewed as encompassing work *on* narratives and work *with* narratives. Work on narratives looks at the narrative means and work with looks at the experiences they are making sense of and both approaches inform each other. The key distinction to be made is between the narrated event, which in this case is the woman's drug use and the narrative event, which in this case is the act of telling me about it in the interview context (Stapleton and Wilson, 2017).

The main reason researchers choose to focus attention on the narrative event is due to the growing body of theory which ties the telling of stories to identity work. In 'Positioning between structure and performance', Michael Bamberg (1997) reflects upon moving to this way of looking at narrative within a framework of positioning analysis which '*grants more centrality to the speakers active engagement in the construction of narrative*' (Bamberg, 1997:341).

In the first part of the analysis, I focus on the narrated event in the 'circles of trust'. In the second part I explore the narrative event, with a focus on how access to different narrative resources permits the telling of particular stories which act to protect the women from stigmatising and simplistic characterisations.

Chapter one: circles of trust follows a more traditional thematic format. The danger in presenting the narratives in this way is that they be read mimetically, as more or less a reflection of the experiences contained within the stories (Frank, 2010). This stands in contradiction to the epistemological stance adopted in this study and like many narrative scholars my desire has to be to disrupt such realist interpretations of women's stories of drug use (Campbell, 2010). The aim of circles of trust is to render visible the web of social connections and relations in which the women are embedded and the narrative means through which group boundaries are maintained.

In this example of DNA the selected stories have been brought together into dialogue with each other to show how they work to simultaneously reject and reinforce the larger cultural narratives of women's drug use. With this approach to re-presenting narratives the guaranteeing of anonymity becomes more difficult as a greater amount of original content from the interview is provided within the text (Squire, 2012). It is suggested that preservation of context should always be balanced with the protection of participant's anonymity. Consequently, in the following chapters necessary steps such as the changing of place names and other circumstantial details which might reveal a participants identity have been taken.

A final word on narrative analysis here concerns its limitations. While it is argued here that interview methods in narrative analysis can generate a wealth of fascinating data, in recognition of the relatively short period of time spent with the participants in comparison to other narrative studies, I proceed in the spirit of interpretive humility advised by Brett Smith (2016). In interpreting the following stories I do not seek to provide a definitive account of these women's lives, but to show them as I perceive them at one particular point in their process of becoming (Raggatt, 2006). It is said that bringing forth new dialogues is largely the goal of dialogical narrative research which fully acknowledges its orientation towards an audience (Mangan, 2018). My aim then, is to open up these accounts to ongoing dialogue which hopefully will inspire a more nuanced understanding that captures the complexity hitherto missing from traditional representations of women who use drugs.

Chapter Six ‘Circles of trust: boundary narratives of drug use and connection’

Introduction

Trust is an essential component in building successful research relationships with this hidden population of women who use drugs. In order to better understand the processes of gaining access, I have written reflectively on my experience of building trust and identifying pivotal moments. Participants were also asked directly, where appropriate, how they felt about talking to me about their drug use in order to gain a sense of just how protective they were of this facet of their identity. In studying closely their responses, and reading through the transcripts of the women’s narratives of drug use, it became clear it would be possible to paint a picture of how trust operates within the context of the women’s wider social network of relationships. In this chapter, I devise the tool of the concentric ‘circles of trust’ to embed the women’s narratives of drug use within the context of key social relationships in order to facilitate a deeper understanding of the social processes through which participants manage this stigmatised aspect of their identity.

In the chapter entitled ‘Locating the researcher’, I explored the concerns and anxieties faced by drug researchers when revealing personal experience of illicit drug use. Here, I return to this ‘dilemma of disclosure’ and how it manifests within participants everyday lives, exploring how the women narrate their decision making processes when it comes to revealing or concealing their identity as a woman who uses illegal drugs. I believe this may shed some light on the nature of hidden populations and help to us to understand not only the reasons *why*, but *how* they constitute an invisible social group.

Circles of trust

Women in this study often refer to their ‘circle’ when talking about their network of important social relationships. According to Hamill and Gilbert (2009) the concept of social circles dates back to Simmel in 1902. Due to its ‘non-linear’ and ‘non-hierarchical’ character, it is argued that the notion of the circle particularly appeals to women (Longman, 2018). The circle is therefore a recurrent format across many social contexts which involve females gathering, such as talking, dancing, drumming and praying. In general terms, a woman’s circle usually describes her friendship group but it can also include kinship relations. This definition of a

woman's circle is not be confused with the more formal 'women's circles', which refers to organised monthly gatherings that provide women-only spaces in which to celebrate sisterhood and the feminine (Longman, 2018).

As well as a way of talking about friendship groups within common parlance, the imagery of the circle has been employed more formally within academic studies as a useful, albeit reductionist way, to address the complex messy work of conceptualising group constructs like social networks, communities and cultures (Moje, 2000). The systematic study of an individual's social embeddedness known as social network analysis is described by Bellotti (2016). While research participants have awareness of and can account for the relationships in which they are embedded, particularly in the context of in-depth qualitative interviews, they usually cannot reach an objective outsider perspective which would allow them to see the 'structural shape of that personal network'. Various models can be constructed to map an individual's web of social ties and these are used for a variety of purposes in research projects where relationships are the focus of study (Bellotti, 2016).

It is for this reason that a systematic approach to social network analysis is often a feature of studies which utilise snowball sampling methods (Woodley and Lockard, 2016) as knowledge of the degree of connectivity of a participant within their larger social network is helpful in identifying suitable gatekeepers. Yet, understanding the characteristics of the social networks of women who use drugs goes beyond the issue of gaining access and recruitment. A report by Arpa (2017) suggests that one of the key challenges faced by women who use drugs is the fact they have less social support than their male counterparts. Such a belief may be underpinned by the social control theory which predicts that individuals engaged in deviant behaviour will have poor social relationships (Kandel and Davies, 1991). On the other hand, from the perspective of cultural deviance theory, individuals engaged in deviant behaviour will demonstrate strong ties with members of their friendship networks. Testing these opposing theories of relationships in relation to illicit drug use, Kandel and Davies (1991) found few differences in the characteristics of the friendship networks of users vs non-users, supporting the cultural deviance theory.

As well as using different models to calculate and map out the total number of relationships or connections for any particular individual, researchers undertaking social network analyses also draw upon a variety of mixed methods with the aim of determining the relative distance and quality within those relationships. An example of this is the tool of concentric circles used in

the study of social support which allows women to map the degree of closeness in their relationships. The process is described here by Bellotti (2016):

“Each of the interviewees balanced out the various nuances of each relationship and consequently placed friends in the circles they considered appropriate, taking also in account other relevant relationships they may have with family, colleagues and other friends.” (Bellotti, 2016:4)

This tool of concentric circles works particularly well with narrative data and according to Bellotti, individuals that occupy the most space within a participant’s narrative are usually those that can be placed closest to the centre, suggesting strong ties and a greater degree of intimacy (Bellotti, 2016). In the remainder of this chapter, I draw inspiration from this method to construct the ‘circles of trust’ upon which each of the women’s relationships have been plotted from analysis of the entire collection of narrative data.

Figure1. Circles of trust (adapted from Bellotti, 2016)

Key: yellow = inner circle, green = the margins, blue = outsiders

The yellow circle represents the inner circle of trust. This is usually based on a *shared status* as a member of a hidden population that uses drugs. The members of a women’s inner circle are those closest trusted individuals she currently uses drugs with.

The green circle represents the margins, the space between. Here are those who do not form part of the inner circle but do not pose threat of enacting stigma or discrimination. Individuals

which can be located on the margins have awareness of drug using activity without active participation.

The blue circle represents the outsiders. This location is thus characterised by complete non-awareness of drug using activity. Positioned here are those from whom illicit drug use is kept strictly secret.

Positioning significant relationships in the circles of trust

In analysing the women's narratives and developing the model of concentric circles it has been both interesting and informative to sketch who the insiders and outsiders are to each of them. What makes one an insider, an individual to be trusted with the knowledge of their illicit drug use? Who are these trusted individuals for each of the women and furthermore, who are they not?

Trust can be gained and it can be lost; the boundaries between the different circles are porous and throughout this chapter I will highlight the women's social and subjective processes that lead to a shift in positioning. The following table displays three different categories in which their relationships with others vis a vis their use of illegal drugs can be placed at the time of interview.

Table 3. Position of significant others in relation to circle of trust

Participant	Inner circle (knowledge, participation)	Marginal (knowledge without participation)	Outer circle (no knowledge, no participation)
Aimee	Friends	Partner, mother, friends, researcher	Grandparents, children (young), colleagues/employer, friends
Claire	Friends	Friends, parents, older relatives, health professionals, researcher	Customers, community members
Shirley	Friends, partner	Friends, family, researcher	Father, friends, community members,
Mary	Friends	Friends, son (older), community members, researcher	Employer, community members
Freda	Associates, friends, partner, mother	Father, friends, researcher	Friends, employer
Megan	Friends	Researcher	Children (older), family, employer
Summer	Friends	Researcher	Colleagues, mother, family members
Maya	Friends, partner	Family, researcher	Employer
Allie	Friends, associates	Partner, researcher	Friends, colleagues
Louisa	Partner	Friends, family, Researcher	Children (younger), friends, colleagues, employer
Katie	Partner, friends	Researcher	Friends, family
Daisy Clark	Mother, friends, associates	Father, friends, colleagues, tutor, researcher	Unspecified others
Rachel	Partner, friends	Parents, colleagues, researcher	Children (younger), friends, health professionals,
Marie	Friends, partner	Parents, colleagues, friends, researcher	Family
Julie	Friends	Friends, (son, older), researcher	Friends

Joanna	Friends	Children (older), friends, researcher	Parents, neighbours, health professionals
Wendy	Friends, partner	Friends, researcher	Children (younger), parents, friends, employer
Lana	Friends	Mother, health professionals, friends, researcher	Friends, children (younger)
Charmaine	Friends	Partner, friends, colleagues, researcher	Friends, family, parents
Jane	Friends	Partner, researcher	Colleagues, family, parents

Table.2 position of partners across sample

Inner circle (knowledge, participation)	Marginal (knowledge without participation)	Outer circle (no knowledge, no participation)
	Aimee	
Shirley		
	Mary	
Freda		
Maya		
	Allie	
Louisa		
Katie		
Rachel		
Marie		
Julie		
Wendy		
Lana		
	Charmaine	
	Jane	

Inner circle: knowledge and participation

There are some differences but there are more similarities in terms of who knows about the participant's use of illicit drugs. In most cases the inner circle is occupied by other women whom are close friends and with whom drugs are shared with. For most of these women the number of relationships within this category is small representing a close circle of trust. Indeed, in their study of the social organisation of friendships, Tamarit et al (2018) argue that only a limited amount of relationships can be intimate, and a large number of connections usually indicates superficial friendships or acquaintances. Drug use does not always take place in the context of these inner circle relationships which are characterised by intense bonding. The differences in experiences of drug use, both inside and outside the circles of trust, are explored.

For a minority of the women, the inner circle is comprised of just them and their male partners. This is compared with the boundary narratives of the majority of women in this study who locate intimate partners on the inner circle alongside intimate female friends.

On the margins: Limited knowledge without participation.

Relationships which can be placed on the margins are indicative of a level trust as these individuals have some knowledge of the participant's drug activity. For many of the women this category includes non-drug using friends or allies who adopt a non-judgemental attitude towards drug use. Sometimes friends on the margins are women who have used drugs with the women historically. A small minority of the women have intimate partners on the margins, who know about their occasional use of illegal drugs with female friends, without actively sharing in the experience with them.

As a result of gaining enough of the participants trust to engage in the interview process, in relation to each of the women, I occupy this marginal position. Stressing my non-judgemental attitude concerning drug use and related experiences and feelings, I demonstrate awareness and understanding without actively participating. In this space between I am no longer outside but neither am I fully in (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009).

In requesting my participation in the use of cannabis on more than one occasion, the primary gatekeeper Shirley demonstrated her willingness to bring me into the inner circle of trust. This may have been in the interests of the wider group who would no doubt have felt greater certainty of my trustworthiness if I had crossed that line and engaged in the drug taking in their presence. That my own location could have shifted throughout the course of the study demonstrates that positioning within the circles is dynamic and not fixed. The boundaries between each circle are therefore porous.

In addition to the fluidity of positioning there is an added degree of complexity in that participants are often simultaneously part of multiple social groups and this is a marked feature of the present sample in which most of the women have friends in each of the positions on the concentric circles of trust. What is clear is that non-drug using friends are trusted by way of their non-judgemental attitude. If a friend or family member is not engaging in the drug use but is not against it, per se, then they are viewed as non-threatening. The knowledge they have of the drug use may be very limited.

Outsiders: no knowledge no participation

The people with whom the women have relationships with that have no knowledge of their drug use, and by extension no participation, can be viewed as outsiders. Drug use is strictly kept secret from the outsiders and many individuals occupying this position are those who identify as 'anti-drug'. Often viewed as ignorant and judgemental, outsiders are not trusted with knowledge of the women's drug use.

As with the other positions on the circles of trust, there is some variation as to who constitutes an outsider from woman to woman. Some of the relationships which comprise the group of outsiders are close relationships while others are more like acquaintances. Close relations that have no knowledge of the women's drug use are usually due to negative attitudes about drug use. These individuals are kept purposefully in the dark to maintain the relationship and this is explored within this chapter in the context of family gatherings.

Other close relationships that are more often than not placed on the outside of the circle of trust are with young children. Children are kept in the dark because it is not deemed age appropriate to share this aspect of their mother's identity. Decisions about future positioning of children as they get older are a feature of women's narratives are explored under the heading 'women as mothers'.

With the exception of young children, outsiders are characterised by their attitude towards drugs and drug users, by negative stereotypes believed about drug users, and marked by ignorance or misinformation. Within this category are generally more formal relationships such as those with employers and colleagues, or with health professionals. They often have the power to enact a range of negative consequences and are therefore perceived as a potential threat.

Having summarised broadly the trends within each of the positions on the concentric circles of trust, I will now go into greater detail about these relationships, beginning with the sub theme

that was most prevalent during the process of coding, which was that of friendship. I then go on to explore the positioning of intimate partners and the different meanings women place on illicit drug use within the context of these important relationships. After that, the complex negotiation of boundaries as they relate to the women's roles as mothers and daughters are fleshed out before finishing with a discussion on identity concealment in the context of relations with employers and colleagues.

Positioning friendships

Unique bonds: social ties in the inner circle

Friendship was the most significant subtheme in the analysis of the overarching theme of relationships. For a great many of the women, their narrative of illicit drug use is inextricably woven with narratives of friendship. These friendships are often described as distinctive in character, both by length of duration and depth of meaning.

“Through drugs I have had some really, really good experiences and made really lasting bonds with people. That I am still close really friends with. I will always be close friends with them” (Allie, 28, Lawyer)

I think there is a unique bond, perhaps because it is an illegal thing. The taboo that surrounds drug taking makes the bond stronger than in other friendships that haven't shared that. Being there for each other no matter what. These are the strongest friendships, I think, anyone could ever have” (Shirley, 39, Artist)

While many of the women have friends in each of the different positions, inner circle friendships involve a greater level of intimacy and trust. It is within this protective circle that the women are free to express this aspect of their identity without fear of harm or negative judgement. The intense bonding experience which characterises the inner circle in the context of a shared experience which is considered taboo within society at large is offered by some of the women as the main motivation for engaging in drug use. According to research within the social psychology literature, rejection by a dominant group can lead to a strengthening of ties in the marginalised group (McNamara, Stevenson and Muldoon, 2013) and this might explain the nature of the friendship ties that are forged in the context of drug use by women in this study.

According to Peter Nardi (1999), friendship is ‘*a social process, embedded in society’s institutions, cultural norms and structural opportunities*’ (Nardi, 1999:2). Like community, friendship is a difficult concept to grasp and define, yet significant to many individuals, and in particular to those of marginalised groups in society. In ‘Invincible Communities’, Nardi explores the role of friendship in gay men’s lives and shows how in the context of social exclusion and disrupted familial relationships as a result of stigmatisation, friendship often takes on a different quality:

“clearly a range of familiarity, along with a diversity of disclosing and sharing, exists along my network of daily interactions. Even so, there is a comfort for me in being amongst my gay and lesbian friends....this comfort comes from more than just a psychological sense of who I am; to participate in spaces also occupied by others who have grown older with a stigmatised identity, and who may have experienced, despite other significant differences – at least some forms of personal and social marginalisation, is a socio-political connection, perhaps one of brotherhood and sisterhood” (Nardi, 1999:3)

While this author describes the characteristics of friendship between gay and lesbian people, his experiences might also generate insight into friendships between women who use drugs as both involve shared marginalised identities in the context of ‘concealable stigmas’ (McNamara, Stevenson and Muldoon, 2013). Indeed, the sense of comfort described by Nardi echoes the feeling of relief within the inner circle of trust that comes from ‘letting the guard down’ in the relative safety of those who do not pose a threat.

While it naturally follows that having a stigmatised identity undermines solidarity and opportunities for social support, it is suggested that having a ‘concealable stigma’ adds further stress in the form of fear of discovery. Although forming alliances within supportive communities is a way of countering the negative effects of stigmatisation, such forms of collective action are thought to be particularly challenging for individuals with concealable stigmas, who often retreat in conditions of adversity (McNamara, Stevenson and Muldoon, 2013). The inner circle therefore has a political dimension, offering spaces of solidarity and resistance to the hegemonic culture which views women who use drugs as deviant and defective.

As trust is conceived to be the very basis of friendship by many thinkers (Pahl, 2002), it makes sense that in hidden populations where trust is a requirement for in group memberships that

friendship would be a prominent feature. Where friendships have been studied in drug using populations it is usually to determine the role of peers in the initiation of drug use and in the informal distribution networks or ‘friendship dealers’. Taking something like friendship which has potentially many positive aspects and framing it in this manner is indicative of a wider trend of dehumanising people who use drugs and their social groups.

“I met all of my best friends during those times. Some people might say...well you all met on drugs, but we...are still like lifelong friends, the kind of friends you could phone at three and the morning and be there for each other you know? We forged really intense bonds”
(Maya, 44, Housewife)

With her ‘some people might say’ comment, Maya reveals a consciousness of the tension between her positive account of ‘drug induced friendship’ and the prevailing cultural narrative of such friendships as unhealthy. The unconditional support which characterises these friendships is demonstrated by Maya through the hypothetical scenario of the 3am phone call. Friendships that operate along the lines of social acceptability might not offer this level of unconditional support, suggesting that personal boundaries are somewhat relaxed in the context of drug induced friendships. The feeling that these friends are ones on which you can really depend is shared by Louisa:

“the friendships I have established through taking drugs, are some of the best friendships I have ever had...the strength of those friendships are such that I could just call on them at any time and they would be there for me”
(Louisa, 30, Student)

When friendships have been the focus of study in the context of illicit drug use of individuals not in treatment services, it is usually from the perspective of peer pressure. However according to Foster and Spencer (2013), rather than viewing initiation into drug use as a product of a unidirectional pressure to fit in with a subculture, drug use should be seen as inextricably intertwined with friendship, intimacy and trust.

This puts into context the centrality of friendship for the women in this sample, who may well have similarly limited opportunities for close bonding in the context of neoliberal capitalist society, as evidenced by the growing popularity of formal women’s circles (Castro, 2019). While formal women’s circles such as the ‘Red Tent’ provide a much needed space for women to have these relational needs met in a socially acceptable way, they have been criticised for reproducing structural power relations in so far as members of these groups are largely

privileged middle class white cisgender women (Longman, 2018). Drug use under prohibition offers opportunities for intimacy between people in a culture where emotional and corporeal connections with other human beings are idealised but limited in the context of alienation and exclusion (Foster and Spencer, 2013).

Intimacy seeking has long been put forward as a primary motivation for women's drug use in the literature. According to Covington and Surrey (2000), that women have been given the primary responsibility for maintaining relationships in a society where *'our important relationships, institutions, and political systems are frequently far from mutually empathic and mutually empowering.'* (Covington and Surrey, 2000*: 2) can account for why many women go down the path of using substances. These authors suggest that substance use can become problematic when a women's relational needs are not being met. During such times the drug of choice might initially appear to 'fill the void' but over time it becomes the organising principle, creating a vicious circle in which the women finds herself increasingly disconnected from others (Covington and Surrey, 1997).

In this rather deterministic view of the progression of addiction, the drug use entails an inevitable loss of control which makes the women's initial state of alienation more profound. This belief fails to account for the centrality of friendship after many years of drug use, through periods of problematic use and through many ups and downs. The alternative narrative presented here by many of the women suggests that 'drug induced friendships' can indeed be lifelong, extending beyond periods of time where drug use is the focus. The circle, a symbol of unending relationships epitomised by the wedding ring, is thus a fitting metaphor to employ in these narratives of drug use and friendship.

Looking at how assumptions about gender influence understanding of this apparent desire for intimacy in women who use drugs, Covington and Surrey (2000) point out that when viewed through the lens of traditional 'self-centred models', this relational drive is often pathologised and, labels such as co-dependency and dependency, marked by female passivity, can be viewed as distortions of women's efforts to build and maintain important social connections.

However, the notion that women have an innate relational drive is in itself problematic, an example of gendered biological essentialism. It is clear that women are given the bulk of responsibility for relationships in society, therefore couching narratives of drug use as intimacy seeking gives it a certain legitimacy and is more acceptable than narratives of pleasure seeking and hedonism. The intimacy seeking, friendship building stories in this study might therefore

be viewed as accomplishing a socially acceptable and gender conforming identity, which lessens the stigma that comes with being a woman who uses drugs. Searching for intimacy should therefore be viewed as a socially acceptable way of framing ones' drug use as opposed to arising from a natural relational bent of women.

The tensions between these competing narratives are negotiated by Charmaine who sees attempts at forging intimacy and friendship alongside passive drug taking behaviour in women:

“The social circles of females.... there is this kind of learned helplessness, you know like I can't roll can you do one for me? I have seen this quite a lot. Can you do one for me? And they could if they practiced but they probably just think it is easier to get someone else to do it for them. And if someone is willing to do it then....I suppose that is a friendship thing. If someone rolls you a joint, they are preparing something for you. They are putting in time and effort to do it. So it could be seen as a gift. Especially if you don't exchange money or actual presents, something like that helps to bond friendships. It's so funny I have never really thought about that before (laughs).” (Charmaine, 29, Third sector)

Charmaine's depiction of female 'learned helplessness' in the context of cannabis culture suggests that women are actively engaging in a form of gendered role play which they experience as functional. Indeed, underpinning the idea that drug relationships are inherently dysfunctional are uncritical assumptions about women who use drugs as passive and vulnerable to manipulation. Charmaine's perspective on the often ambiguous nature of women's drug use, as both passive and at the same time active agents in maintaining social connections complicates the traditional, one dimensional view. Charmaine goes on to reflect on the way she herself has purposefully emphasised a passive style of femininity when confronted with dangerous situations with the police, another form of gendered role play which reported in a recent hidden population of women who use drugs in France (Perrin et al, 2020). I explore the manner in which women employ these protective strategies in the next chapter, under 'respectability narratives'.

Drug use on the fringes: from close friends to associates

In the concentric circles of trust, the inner circle is depicted as the space in which illicit drug use takes place. Although many of the women describe the friendships in this space as important and enriching, there are also reports of experiences of drug use in the context of social relationships that are described in less positive terms. This section will analyse the women's accounts of these individuals, described as 'associates' which serve to highlight the limits of trust in the inner circle. Although every individual that occupies the inner circle is trusted initially, there are situations when it becomes apparent that the circle of trust has to change.

After several years of using MDMA, cannabis, magic mushrooms and LSD on a regular basis with her original inner circle of trusted female friends, Claire moved away to live and work in a different city. She continued to use drugs in the company of her brother and his friends. It was during this time that Claire's drug use took on a 'darker' nature. Excessive alcohol use became much more of a feature and this was often consumed at the same time as cocaine, cannabis and ecstasy. Something which Claire states she would never have done with her group of friends before. In contrast, friendships in the inner circle of trust furnished Claire with a much needed safety net of support, helping her to manage the ups and downs of frequent drug use. The value of these relationships were only fully comprehended with the benefit of hindsight, after experiencing a challenging period of 'addiction' in the context of a qualitatively different peer group.

It is recognised that friendship groups often serve a protective function via the provision of regulatory norms (Foster and Spencer, 2013). Even within the relatively non-judgemental safe space of the inner circle, there are certain behaviours which are not tolerated which if discovered, would result in being cast out of the circle of trust. Use of stigmatised substances such as heroin is one such threat to in-group membership and is therefore usually kept hidden from other women within the inner circle. This marginalised type of drug use is viewed as indicative of an individual out of control and therefore not worthy of the trust that grants one insider status. Already vulnerable to negative judgement from others, individuals that use intensely stigmatised substances are likely to bring shame upon the group as a whole. As Charlton and Bettencourt (2001) point out in their analysis of in-group behaviour in the context of boundary permeability:

'members' evaluations of a positive member of the in-group are extremely favourable because the members actions are generalised to the social group as a

whole; a similarly extreme but opposite evaluation is associated with a negative in-group member' (Charleton and Bettencourt, 2001:82)

There are therefore limits to the level of trust within the inner circle in order to preserve the regulatory function of the group. Long standing friendships can come under threat if the woman has progressed into relationship with illicit drug use that has become more visible. This phenomenon has been reported elsewhere in the study of drug use by Foster and Spencer (2013) using the concept of 'borderwork'. When drug use is taken outside the initial context of strong trusted friendships and into a group where relations are more superficial, women tend to lack the kind of support and connection that keeps drug use within certain boundaries of acceptability. After a period of lost control, it is necessary for some women to cut all ties with people who use drugs to regain a sense of stability. For Claire however, the solution was a return to the original circle from her increasingly fringe location.

Periods of more problematic use are often cited as the catalyst for leaving certain friendship groups behind and doing so creates very little in the way of resistance. In contrast to groups based on things like race and ethnicity which have no permeability, in groups with permeable boundaries such as women who use drugs, there are greater levels of social mobility and this often results in disassociation from an in-group (Charleton and Bettencourt, 2001).

Notably, Claire was not the only woman to couch periods of problematic use within the context of these 'less than intimate friendships'. Allie views the relationships with one particular group she once used drugs with at a particular troubling time in her life as shallow and without meaning.

Allie: the people that I spoke to then, they weren't really pals, just people to get wrecked with"

Karen: what's the difference between people you just get wrecked with and the lasting bonds you have made through drugs?"

Allie: I don't know. I guess...the lasting bonds are people you would meet with outside of taking drugs, you would meet them outside that context and speak to them again and have a really nice time. You just feel like you have known them your whole life. The associates, if you happen to meet one of them in the street you would just be like oh hi how are you? Great party the other night! See ya!"

Karen: So, it's superficial?

Allie: It is very superficial... yes.

Far from the lasting bonds which are spoken of in relation to the group with which she began her drug using career, there is no sense of shared meaning between Allie and these former 'associates', many of whom were male. She describes these relationships in purely functional terms. People to get 'wrecked' with, as opposed to connect with. Rather than purposefully seeking out these people in times of personal need and distress, chance meetings in everyday settings tend to feel awkward and obliged. They have no sense of shared identity, and this is clear as she refers to this group as 'they' while her original group of friends are repeatedly spoken of as 'we'.

Far from the provision of regulatory norms that help to keep drug use within acceptable levels, this particular groups of friends acted as a normalising force to make Allie doubt her own concerns that her drug use was getting out of hand:

"sometimes you feel like you are getting out of control with it. I used to feel like that. And I freak out midweek and ring up my mates and say I am a druggie, I have a drug problem. And they would say, no you haven't, shut the fuck up. We all do it....Now I realise, that actually, it's not normal to be getting wrecked all the time. Normal people don't do that. But they have created this narrative for themselves that it's alright. That it's acceptable behaviour"

In similar vein Katie's narrative of friendship and drug use reinforces the evolving narrative of certain drug friendships as unhealthy. In describing a current group of friends from whom she is actively dissociating from in order to foster a healthier relationship with drugs, she exemplifies someone in the process of changing the configuration of her circle:

"it just isn't funny anymore. I have saw people really lose their shit. And it's not fucking funny. I have been thinking...and I need to be careful about what I am complicit in because I could be helping somebody who is in a bad place to stay in a bad place because I am needing a buddy to be in a bad place with"

Interestingly Katie appears more concerned about the impact she is having on others as opposed to the fact that she herself is not in a good place. In this scenario she locates herself as the problem, and in doing so she remains in control. Negative narratives of previous drug bound friendships are often used to make sense of chaotic periods where women have experienced a loss of control over drug use. Such narratives may accomplish a variety of things, including a

distribution of responsibility for this previous loss of control, and an increased sense of personal power that is implied by the act of ‘cutting off’ these friendships.

Friendship beyond drug use

The sense of agency that women require to overcome challenges, such as losing control may be accomplished in different ways, as evidenced by Shirley’s narrative of quitting her use of cocaine. In this story, Shirley describes how she purposefully remains friends with and spends time with other drug users in periods where she is intentionally abstinent.

‘When I decided I had to stop taking cocaine I made sure I didn’t act like an idiot around it. Basically I don’t think that you can give up a drug unless you are able to be around it, be immersed in it and not have to take it. Otherwise you are still addicted to it. So when I stopped taking it I would make lines for other people. And I would intentionally be around it and not take it. Because if you can’t be around it then you are not over it...I did not think I cannot hang around with you guys anymore, you know that is just stupid. For me that is you still being addicted to it. Of course sometimes you have to let go of people who aren’t good for you, but just because you aren’t taking a certain drug anymore, doesn’t mean you can’t hang around with good people who are’

Shirley’s position which stands in contrast to the others is that it is not necessary to change the people you are with, only your own behaviour. She drives forth this point by telling the story of making a point of being around them, even cutting the cocaine and putting out lines for her friends, stating ‘if you can’t be around it...then you are not over it’. For Shirley, the problem is not that her relationship with her friends is unhealthy, it is the relationship with the drugs that is out of balance. In stating disagreement for the notion that sometimes one has to leave certain drug bound friendships behind in order to have a healthier relationship with certain substances, in this case cocaine, Shirley positions herself as solely responsible for her drug problem and as a result is able to maintain the same attachments whilst working towards having a healthier relationship with illegal substances. Like many of the women who narrate periods of difficulty, achieving a sense of control and autonomy is Shirley’s priority, echoing what Martin and Stenner (2004) suggest is the function of many drug use narratives. However unlike others she achieves this whilst preserving social connections in which she finds a depth of meaning that extends beyond the drug use itself. The period of abstinence that Shirley engages

in to regain control are thus times when her own position in the circles of trust shifts from a centred to a more marginal position.

Many of the women who remain active in their use maintain friendships with other women who formerly used occupied the inner circle. These individuals are deemed a reliable source of support based upon their own personal experience with drug use and the consequent attitude of understanding and non-judgementality that this brings. For Shirley in particular, these friendships have been of particular value in times where it is clear that a break is needed, as they are unlikely to encourage drug use at unsuitable times for their own sake. Having experienced drug users as friends who no longer use drugs, for whatever reason, that one can relate to, particularly if experiencing drug related challenges or problems, is thus a source of capital and should be considered as such in areas where this is of clinical relevance. That there is a perceived kind of knowing that exists between people that have had similar experiences with drugs is important for understanding the insider outsider debate at large. This will be explored in greater detail chapter two of analysis and again in the discussion.

Friendship with outsiders

“I have friends who don’t take drugs, whom are very anti-drugs. They like a good drink. These friends don’t even know that I take drugs...no, no. I wouldn’t cross the streams. There is probably only five people in the world that know that I take drugs”

(Katie, 32, Academic)

Like Katie, a number of the women speak of having friendships with people who do not use drugs. It is interesting that Katie’s ‘anti-drug’ friends like a good drink which suggests that the issue these people have is more to do the illicit and stigmatised nature of it, and less about the act of intoxication itself. Katie describes the manner in which she deliberately keeps these relationships separate as not crossing the streams. She accomplishes this by one important rule that she abides by in order to keep the knowledge of her drug use strictly within the boundaries of a select minority: never sharing any images or status updates on social media which might give away any clues. A similar strategy is reported in a study by Hutton et al (2016), where young women describe the practice of airbrushing photographs on social media which might otherwise express publicly their private performance of ‘drunken femininity’. Katie refers to her online presence that maintains a clean image as intentionally ‘*very vanilla*’. Taking this

projected image as a reflection of reality, these anti-drug friends have little reason to suspect that Katie enjoys a very different experience when socialising with those on the inner circle.

Some of Charmaine's closest friends are outsiders, having no knowledge of her illicit drug use and never taking part in it. Her use of cocaine mainly takes place with friends that live in different cities, to which she travels a few times per year for work related business. She explains:

“to be fair, a lot of my friends up here would be like woaaaah, you need to check yourself out. With them there is less knowledge and more...fear. Maybe some of them wouldn't care but there is certainly going to be more judgement there if they knew about it”

(Charmaine, 29. Third sector)

Through lack of experience, drug naïve friends are especially vulnerable to the misinformation that exists about drug use and are therefore purposefully kept in the dark to preserve the relationship. These friendships, although less intimate, are still deemed valuable to the women for different reasons

Shirley has a particularly large group of friends, and it is this quality which made her ideal as gatekeeper for access in this study. Among this group there are a number of 'non-drug takers', some of whom are privy to her use of drugs and some are not. In the following passage she explains that anticipation of negative judgement is what largely determines their positioning:

Shirley: Not everybody wants to take drugs, I have a lot of folk within my circle and it is just not what they are interested in.

Karen: And the ones that don't, are you happy to do it in front of them? How does that work out?

Shirley: Some friends I just wouldn't take drugs in front of. But I would smoke dope in front of them. Because I have MS I can get away with that. I mean, I have some friends who don't take drugs that I would feel okay doing it in front of. But others, no, I wouldn't even talk about it. I find if they are a non-drug taker, then they don't really understand. Folk who have not been in that culture do not realise. Everybody is just tarred with the same brush.

In feeling that the cannabis does not have to be hidden from non-drug using friends as it is used medicinally, Shirley points to the significance of cultural sanctioning. The use of drugs to

alleviate pain is more socially acceptable and as such does not have to be managed as discreetly as drug use traditionally associated with recreation and pleasure. Shirley also touches upon a phenomenon here that I observed many times across the sample. Very often, the women hold back from talking about certain experiences because they anticipate lack of understanding. This characteristic is very often what sets apart those friends that are placed on the outside of the circle of trust from those placed on the margins.

Positioning new friends: feeling it out

As the boundaries between the circles are porous, at any time the woman occupying a position within the inner circle of trust may choose to bring in another who is currently on the outside, into the space between by sharing information about her identity as a woman who uses drugs. Women are often met with this challenge in the context of forming bonds within new friendship circles in later stages of life, often through getting married and having children. Freda recounts her experiences of grappling with the dilemma of disclosure in the context of her children school friend's parents:

“Interestingly we had a family meeting because my wee one is starting school next week. It’s a really small school with only five other kids in the class, so one of the women organised a get together for all the families.....and we were describing about how we had moved and I had this total dilemma, whether or not to say about the cannabis. I was talking and talking and I thought actually I am just going to do it...and it was felt weird, because I have tried to make a point of not hiding my cannabis use. You know if it comes up in conversation. A lot of it is about paving the way for breaking the boundaries and breaking the stigma, by showing that somebody like myself can be doing a professional job and can at the same time be somebody who smokes cannabis. But when you are in these social situations you get quite nervous, and you need to just make that decision.” (Freda, 36, academic)

The decision Freda is referring to is whether the negative consequences of disclosing the drug use outweigh the potential benefits of doing so. While the dilemma of disclosure presents itself in many different social situations for the women, it almost always induces a state of anxiety. Research on concealable stigmas suggests that psychological distress (as measured by levels of depression and anxiety) due to anticipated stigma increases with the severity of consequences. Quinn and Chaudoir (2009) advise exploring this by asking questions such as

how much prejudice and devaluation is the individual likely to face if the identity becomes known? How salient is the stigmatised identity, as in, how often does the individual think about it? This could range from not very often to several times a day. How central is the identity to the person's self-definition? What is the level of cultural stigma in the community towards that particular identity? (Quinn and Chadoir, 2009). Given that the answers to these questions are dependent on a range of variables such as frequency and type of substance use and employment and parental status, the consequences of disclosure are not likely to be the same for all the women and in any case, it is difficult to predetermine the outcome.

In the end, Freda made the decision 'just to do it' not because she felt confident gauging the level of cultural stigma within that group of parents towards people who use illicit drugs, as this could only be known after the fact. She took the risk because it is something she feels very passionate about and while it is not the key facet of her identity it is still an important aspect of who she is as a person. On this occasion, Freda was both relieved and underwhelmed at their (lack of) reaction.

Lana frames her narrative of frequent poly-drug use as a younger person as an attempt at building intimate relationships in the absence of having close family members. Now that she is older with a family of her own, she no longer requires this substitute family in the forms of friends who are tightly bonded through the intense ups and downs of the drug using experience. Knowing that one can return to this intimate space when required is a source of comfort for Lana and indeed for many of the women, particularly those who have left for reasons that don't involve problematic drug use. Lana continues to use drugs on an occasional basis and enjoys meeting up infrequently with Shirley and the others. During these times they will relive memories of good and bad experiences from the times when life revolved around drug use.

Nowadays Lana's social life largely takes place within the context of a new friendship group where illicit drug use is not a feature. These women are the mothers of her children's friends. In the early stages of being a member of this new group she faced a similar dilemma to that of Freda. Initially, Lana flirted with the notion of sharing her experiences with drug use, which included a period of drug-induced psychosis and a suicide attempt. Aware of the consequences of misjudgement, she cautiously held this information back, forming a story of her past which omitted these significant events. Her decision to do so was further reinforced when she became aware that the new group's notion of female rebellion was limited to occasional tobacco use and overindulgence in alcohol.

Fully aware that her new circle of friends have different values and ways of pushing the boundaries of acceptability, Lana feels very strongly about keeping that aspect of her history secret. She worries that the stigma would transfer to her children and impact their social standing. This of course places a limit on how much about her life she can share and thus how well she can be known by her new friends, but this cost is clearly worth it to Lana who at this stage in her life places greater value on social respectability and social connections which directly benefit her children's lives too. Previous experiences of stigmatisation have honed a certain hypervigilance within Lana that serves a protective function by allowing her to pick up on subtle cues which warn of potential threat to her social standing.

The experiences of Freda and Lana in navigating new friendship circles captures the essence dilemma of disclosure describes the anxiety experienced upon weighing up this decision, one that is often tempered by anticipation of future regret. To bring another into the circle of trust and trust them with knowledge of the drug use, or to err on the side of caution and leave them on the outside, effectively in the dark. Like Freda, they may find that the new group is a safe place in which to share this aspect of their identity, or like Lana, they will learn that this is something better left unsaid. As Fraser et al suggests '*where silence is maintained, the possibility of encountering non-stigmatising, accepting responses from others is lost.*' (Fraser et al, 2017:28).

Positioning Partners

In keeping with my indirect and non-intrusive approach I did not enquire about relationship status in the early stages of building a relationship with the women. Understanding it as a potentially sensitive topic, I waited for this information to be offered up voluntarily in their own time. As I had hoped, in the sharing of stories of both good and bad experiences with drugs information about both current and past relationships came to light.

Looking across the sample, seven of the women were married, six were co-habiting (one of which was divorced), and two were in a committed relationship but living separately from partners. The remaining five were single at time of interview. Of these single women, one of them, Joanna, was also divorced. All but one of the women in this sample self-defined as cisgender and heterosexual. Although friendship was by the far the most referenced relationship in the circles of trust, a number of the women chose to foreground intimate relationships with partners instead.

The majority of women have an inner circle of trust that is populated with friends and intimate partners. Less commonly is a configuration which could be more accurately described as a dyad where the inner circle includes intimate partner only and no friends. This was reported presently by only two of the women, and two others as a feature of the past.

I present some of these stories here, beginning with Louisa who positions her partner firmly on the inner circle of trust before juxtaposing this with the alternative narratives of the women who locate their partners in a more marginal position.

Partners on the inside

Louisa began using drugs with female friends in self-described chaotic manner and is now, at the age of 30, using cocaine in a relatively controlled manner and much less frequently with a long-term male sexual partner that she has lived with for just over two years. Viewing the use of drugs with female friends as a source of embarrassment, Louisa infers that using illegal drugs with female friends is akin to being promiscuous. Her narrative frames the drug use as something more personal, best suited to the confines of an intimate partner relationship. This may be due to the strong association she has made with sex. By keeping it between her and her boyfriend, she is bestowing on him the privilege of her exclusivity. In narratively drawing the boundaries of her circle of trust, Louisa eschews the public in favour of the private. Her friends populate a peripheral position and while they do not share directly in the experience, they are aware of her use of cocaine and other drugs.

Wendy is less disparaging about using with female friends, but she also makes it very clear that the boundary of her circle of trust ends with her husband. Like Louisa, she compares this way of using with a previous history of using chaotically with a group of friends. Having a massive 'blow out' together every couple of months, they gain a sense of excitement in their married life. Looking forward to these weekends enables them to cope with the mundane tasks of everyday life. In addressing their shared drug experiences, Wendy emphasises that she and her husband share the burden of responsibility between them, including taking turns to look after their young children during the 'comedown' period to enable each other to recover from the after-effects of taking ecstasy and cocaine.

Other researchers have attempted to place a decline in frequency of women's drug use within the context of romantic engagement. Herold (2015) calls this romantic identity work and observes this phenomenon in the narratives of 7 women aged 17-20 who are negotiating the role of extensive drug use in their lives during periods of transition and she claims how these

young women position themselves in relation to romantic partners is inextricable from evaluations of the appropriateness of drug use within the relationship. Herold identifies three distinct patterns of subject positioning; heroic boyfriends vis-a-vis decent girlfriends, irresponsible boyfriends vis-a-vis mature girlfriends and equal partners in crime; each of these patterns enable different meanings of drug use within the relationship. Louisa and Wendy's construction of their circle of trust and their partner's privileged position therein in relation to friends, is consonant with the 'equal partners in crime' construct. This was fairly common in Herold's group of women and while at first glance the equal footing in the relationship seems like a positive thing, according to Herold it can have detrimental effects for the cessation of drug use, as making positive changes becomes less likely when a couple perceives themselves as a unified force against mainstream cultural values. Paradoxically the way in which they stand together to face exclusion from mainstream society is also viewed as one of the benefits of constructing the partnership as an oppositional unity. She claims that women who use drugs have usually experience of being marginalised by wider society and the support offered in this kind of relationship can help them to overcome these challenges.

However, the motivation for positioning as equal partners in crime are not the same for hidden populations. Women like Louisa and Wendy are well integrated in society. They are in stable employment; they are parents, and crucially, their drug using status unknown beyond a select few. The degree of marginalisation is different for Herold's women who outwardly reject the mainstream, and this effects the logic behind how they position both themselves and their partners.

Although Louisa and Wendy confine illicit drug use with the boundaries of their intimate relationship, it is not suggestive of an entrenched 'us vs them' mentality. On the contrary, their concern is with blending in with mainstream society and excluding female friends from the inner circle of trust minimises the chances their position will be placed in jeopardy, by severely restricting their opportunities for intoxication. What is clear, is that similar to a recent hidden population study conducted in France, the women in this study are socially included, and it is from this privileged position of social inclusion that they can actively engage in the social exclusion of other drug using females (Perrin et al 2020).

In excluding female friends from their innermost circle, Louisa and Wendy's boundary narratives can also be viewed as a performance of 'emphasised femininity'. A very common form of femininity across mass culture, emphasised femininity is defined as a form of

'compliance with this subordination and is oriented to accommodating the interests and desires of men' (Schipper, 2007:87). Alternative femininities are defined in contrast by strategies of resistance or forms of non-compliance to hegemonic masculinity (Schipper, 2007).

Unequal partnerships: the dark side of the circle of trust

The intimate relationships of women who use drugs is a major theme within the existing literature. In this important area of life, women are constructed as particularly vulnerable to victimisation, suffering greater levels of physical, emotional and sexual abuse in which drug use is perceived to play a significant role (ref) In the context and rational for this hidden population study the limitations of existing literature were pointed out, in that the complex needs of captive populations with multiple marginalities may not accurately reflect the experiences of women who use drugs in a more general sense. During the course of analysing the collection of narratives and plotting the women's intimate partnerships along the concentric circles of trust, 2 out of 20 women depicted unequal relationships as a significant feature of their overall experience. These two women, Claire and Marie, compare historical dyadic configurations of trust, which are constructed as pathological, to present circular configurations of trust, which they position as more position in relation.

Claire has many years of experience with poly-drug use in a range of different social groups and settings. A key aspect of her overall narrative concerns an extremely challenging period of time where she leaves behind the support of her friends and enters into an intimate relationship with another woman that eventually becomes toxic. After spending time healing and learning from the experience she reflects upon the dynamic of that particular relationship:

Claire: She had some major fucking issues. And because I had issues from my childhood, I let myself be her kind of victim. Plaything, whatever. At the time I didn't understand any other way.

Karen: So it was familiar to you?

Claire: Yeah, and I think that is why I got involved with her. I am not saying she was some kind of bad awful person, but she had major trauma issues. She had major issues with addiction. Heroin, crack, cocaine. And I didn't realise at that point that I was getting involved with someone who was starting to relapse. And things became...very dark. I smoked heroin during that time. (pause). Anyway, why

am I going on about this? Ah, relationships. That was a funny one, because I was enabling her addiction and she was facilitating me to.... go to the dark side. Of course, I think I wanted to go there. It lasted ten months. It started off with a glass of wine, and then we would drink hundreds and consume whatever drug we could get our hands on. Ending in heroin. But then, it was over. And it was just a whole different drug taking experience because it was so secretive. It was like...don't. Tell. Anyone. About. This. It just felt so different to any other drug taking experience that I had had."

When the drug use became more stigmatising the circle of trust altered accordingly for Claire and it reduced in size until it became just her and her partner. Bound by the shameful secret of their heroin use, she knew friends would have put distance between them if they knew. It was in the context of this shared 'dirty secret' that the use of illicit drugs became progressively problematic. It started off drinking wine together a few times a week, then it became 'getting high' every night. Claire reached a point where she could see clearly that her partner's intentions were to self-destruct and she found the strength to leave the relationship behind.

Having been scarred by this experience, Claire is now extremely wary of entering another relationship in which drug use is a feature. Claire describes a dominant/submissive dynamic as a pattern that characterises her intimate relationships to date and she fears this makes her more vulnerable to dysfunctional and abusive relationships in which the control she has worked to develop over her drug use is passed over to her partner. In speaking about this she conveys a firm conviction that having a partner who uses drugs is not a healthy decision for her and in looking to the future, Claire is adamant that potential partners and any further drug use of her own will be kept separate. Unlike the women in Herold's (2015) study who were making sense of a decision to stop or drastically reduce drug use in the context of romantic engagement, Claire is justifying her decision to continue using despite the difficulties of the past and she achieves this by placing future partners to the outside of the circle of trust.

The majority of women did not employ such protective strategies in their boundary work, instead narrating inner circles of trust that include both same sex friendships and intimate partners. Within this group there are some instances where this happens at the same time within the same social context, for example at a social gathering such as a wedding. Here, the partners are fully included within the circle of trust. This was the case for Marie, who like Claire, had

also experienced an unhealthy intimate relationship in which drug use was strongly present as a feature.

Marie currently uses MDMA with friends and with her partner and this generally takes place in different spaces and times. She describes these experience as qualitatively different, each one fulfilling a different need. With her friends it is all about fun and feeling young and free again; with her partner it is about achieving greater levels of intimacy, in a physical as well as mental and emotional sense. She also compares using with her current partner to using with her husband.

'I don't get to do all that mad fun stuff anymore. Much. It all started to slow down naturally. I was married before. Oh god. I have a lot to say about using drugs over the years. In my marriage I was still using regularly. Legal and illegal drugs. With my husband. I was going through a bit of a difficult time and it had a bit of a spike at one point, because I wasn't in a very good place. But then I started to get stronger and started to understand what I needed to do. My current partner, we still use drugs. But it's mostly legal. Alcohol. Occasionally cannabis. But actually, weirdly. And this might be an age thing. But we have employed MDMA as a bit of an aid to our relationship. We had a rare holiday, the first since our son was born. Our communication wasn't great. Our sleep, shot to bits. And we planned this weekend. I deliberately went and got the MDMA from a friend. This friend had been using it in a fun time, she also suffers from PTSD, and she was using it with people she trusted and it allowed her to talk about some things without going into a trauma response. So anyway, we used quite specifically to loosen up because we were both wound up so tight. And it was great. It allowed us to chat about ourselves and the relationship. You know when your head has been down and you are one foot in front of the other, just getting on with it, not giving enough time to us as a couple'

Marie locates her present use of MDMA in the context of an intimate partner relationship in which opening up emotionally has been a challenge due to the fact her partner has issues with trauma. Often referred to as the 'love drug', MDMA increases and heightens feelings of empathy, connection and compassion, and is even claimed to stimulate moral development and spiritual insight (McDaniel, 2017). Being able to back up the experiences of her friend with an

awareness of the research from her line of work, Marie was confident of the benefits of MDMA as a therapeutic agent⁴. But she also alludes to the symbolic function of the drug use as marking out time for them to work on their identity as couple in contrast to their life as over worked and sleep deprived parents. This recent ‘holiday’ marks the beginning of a more intentional relationship both with the substance and each other.

The MDMA experience in itself was not new to Marie for she has used drugs with intimate partners in the past. With her husband it became harmful and had to end; with her current partner it is healing and will likely continue. Through this juxtaposition, Marie is subtly stating her present capacity to participate in an intimate relationship in which drug use is a feature and is healthy; she goes out of her way to tell me that taking the MDMA with her present partner was her idea and that she was the one to source the drugs. By bringing her partner into to the sacred space that she has cultivated over time in her friendships with other women, they are able utilise the pharmacological properties of the substance and the heightened intimacy and trust of the inner circle to strengthen the bond in their relationship.

It is important to remember that in positioning partners the woman are also constructing an identity for themselves (Herold, 2015). Cultural narratives of drug use and women in intimate relationships tend to foreground asymmetries of power (ref). In their stories of historical unequal partnerships, both Claire and Marie are performing an identity of an experienced and resourceful woman who uses drugs. Claire is experienced not only in terms of the wide range of substances used, but in the sense that she has been to ‘the dark side’, engaging in a form of drug use that is the most demonised. Rather than make this a story of her victimisation, she retains a sense of agency throughout in stressing that she gave her permission for this loss of power and control. She further inscribes this personal power by extricating herself from this toxic entanglement, returning to the ‘light’ on account of her own will power. In a similar way, Marie uses a previously pathological relationship to emphasise the healthy aspects of her drug use with her present partner.

⁴ See: Sessa, Higbed and Nutt (2019) for an up to date review on this topic.

Locating intimate partners on the margins

A small number of partners can be placed in a more marginal position within the circle of trust, which means they know about the drug use but they don't actively share in the experience, at all, or at the same time as their partners. Jane, an auxiliary nurse in her 40's, has a partner who is currently abstinent. She therefore does not use drugs in his company out of respect for his decision and since entering this relationship the frequency of her own use has markedly reduced. She will use cocaine usually on an overnight in a hotel with a group of friends when it is a special occasion such as a birthday and at present, this happens around four or five times a year. Her partner accepts her decision to do so and it does not have a negative impact on their relationship.

This common decline in drug use with age is fleshed out in the literature on 'maturing out', beginning from the observations of Charles Winick (1962) and further developed in the works of Walter Biernacki (1986) and Engel Prins (1995:2008). Here, the concept of maturing out has been used to explain the decline and eventual cessation of drug use in older 'drug users' without therapeutic intervention or medical regimen. In examining the processes which lead to this maturing out, researchers have tried to understand how involvement in adult roles may be associated with changes in patterns of drug use. It is suggested by Verges et al (2013) that consumption is simply incompatible with the demands of adult roles such as parenting, marriage and employment and these effects are more noticeable for women in particular.

Underpinning this view that marriage acts as a deterrent from engaging in illicit drug use is the assumption that women who use drugs cannot do so and remain functional and accepted within their intimate relationships. Aimee's current pattern of drug use is much the same as Jane's. It is described in similar terms as having slowed down somewhat naturally as other responsibilities in life have taken over. Aimee's partner occupies a marginal position in her circle and her situation is similar to Jane's in that he knows about it but does not participate.

Aimee: If I am in somebody's company who has it (cocaine), I will just take it. I don't plan ahead to make sure it is definitely going to be there at that specific party or function.

Karen: and is it the same with your partner sometimes while the kids are in bed?

Aimee: No. No. Never. I have done it in the house while the kids are in bed, but not with my partner. My man takes it even less than me. It has to be at a party with

pals, it is always a social thing. And none of them take it just with their partner.

Nah. (pause) nah.

Karen: would that be a different experience?

Aimee: Och aye. There's just something about it that feels...weird. To me, that would be a drug habit. I just think...why would you need to do that? You just do it to be...sociable.

In keeping this distance between her drug use and her partner, Aimee feels she is able to keep that identity separate from her everyday life. Like a great many of the women in this study, for Aimee, taking cocaine is an acceptable social activity so long as it does not bleed into and interfere with her family life. For some this means keeping it out of the family home altogether. For Aimee this sense of compartmentalisation is accomplished by keeping it away from her intimate relationship and making sure the children are fed, washed and in bed before using. In juxtaposition with Louisa and Wendy, Aimee views using drugs with a partner as having crossed a boundary of social acceptability and entering problematic territory. She describes this behaviour as constituting a 'drug habit' and while Aimee has not experienced this personally, she has witnessed it in others. The other females within her inner circle share a mutual distain for this particular type of drug use suggesting that within this particular group of women who use drugs the positioning of partners on the periphery is not such an unusual occurrence.

When considering the positioning of partners within the circles of trust, it is interesting to note that there was not one single instance where the partner was completely without knowledge. This may reflect the practical difficulties in doing so but equally it may reflect the importance of intimacy, as keeping this aspect of identity secret in such a close relationship would undoubtedly have deleterious effects for degree of closeness achievable.

Whether drug use is a feature or not, most of the time the intimate partner relationship is a source of respite for the women in this study, a safe space where she can relax her guard and recover from the stresses of managing a stigmatised identity outside the circles of trust. However it is also a space which often requires the careful balancing of dependency and autonomy, and the ways in which this is accomplished through narrative is explored in chapter two of analysis under narratives of respectability.

A report by Arpa (2017) reinforces this significance of intimate relationships for women, suggesting that drug- using men play a role in 'initiation', and that women are more likely than

their male counterparts to have a substance using partner. These are common assertions within the literature and yet often, the experiences of the women in this study, which have come to light indirectly through exploring the circles of trust, run counter to these mainstream ideas about the intimate partner relationships of women who use drugs.

Louisa locates problematic drug use within friendship circles and so she purposefully avoids this by containing the drug use within her intimate partner relationship. On the other side of the coin, Aimee locates the problem drug use within intimate partner relationships and in doing so, by avoiding using drugs with her partner she maintains the identity of a non-problematic user. Thus, both Aimee and Louisa are clear in their mind about what problem drug use looks like, and in many ways their ideas exist in stark opposition. However, from the perspective of narrative functionality these stories work in similar ways to achieve similar ends. That is, by constructing one type of drug relationship as crossing the boundaries of social acceptability and indicative of moral degeneracy, the two women are able to achieve a sense of self which is free from stigma and shame. Keeping distance between drug use and female friendships and keeping distance between drug use and partners are thus two interesting and effective ways of managing stigma and achieving a sense of social acceptability.

Positioning parent/child relationships

Woman as mothers

With the women's potential fear of child protection agencies in mind, I refrained from asking direct questions about children as this could be perceived as threatening and intrusive. Fortunately, the unstructured narrative approach to interviewing provided a safe platform for the women to talk about the things most important to them in the context of their drug use, and for many of the women this was preserving their role as a mother and having positive relationships with their children.

Just over half of the women in the sample (n=11) have children. Of this number, four of the women have children who are 18 years or over: *Mary (52)*, *Megan (33)*, *Joanna (44)* and *Julie (52)*. Three of these four women, Mary, Joanna, and Julie, have adult children that know about their mothers drug use. For these women, their children can thus be located on the margins of their circle of trust. Megan's children are also grown, but they know nothing about this aspect of their mother's identity. Her son and daughter can therefore be viewed as outsiders. The remainder have children under the age of 18: *Freda (36)*, *Aimee (32)*, *Louisa (30)*, *Rachel (39)*,

Marie (41), Wendy (37) and Lana (37). Relationships with children were very important to all of the women who were mothers, particularly for the mothers of younger children who still required a great deal of care and attention. There was no indication that any of these younger children were aware of their mother's drug use.

Several of the women whose children are in earlier stages of development express the desire to communicate openly and honestly about their own drug use in the future. Rachel's children are presently too young, but when they are older, she aspires to foster a trusting space in which dialogue can occur, an important protective feature she felt was missing in her relationship with her own parents. However, she recognises that being honest with her children about her drug use is a double-edged sword. On one hand, the experiential knowledge carries with it a certain authority meaning that her children are less likely to pass off her advice as stemming from fear or ignorance. On the other hand, it carries with it the risk of being viewed as a hypocrite in so far as legitimate concerns or warnings may be seen as conflicting with her own life choices. Rachel works hard to resolve this dilemma in her narrative but does not arrive at a firm conclusion. She recognises that wanting to be a certain way with her kids in theory is one thing, and actually being that way is another.

Mary lives at home with her 18 year old son and his father, her husband. Mary's son knows about her drug use as she uses cannabis every day in the house, and although he also uses the drug, they do not share the experience together. The first conversation about her use of illegal drugs was initiated by her son when he was about 13 years old, when he detected the pungent aroma of cannabis within the family home. While they have had a relatively open and trusting relationship about the subject of drug use since, Mary tells me that her son has knowledge of her drug experiences only to a certain extent, suggesting that some kind of boundary has been set.

Mary describes her relationship with her son as warm and loving, though she believes he looks up to her husband more, as he brings in much more money to the household. She is keen for her son to have some of the same positive experiences with drugs that she has had as she passionately believes they have broadened her perspective on life. Mary feels very strongly about this and yet she is also wary, conscious of how this could be perceived by others. The flow of her narrative here is punctuated by a sense of hesitancy. Actively wanting your adult child to take drugs is not something that most people would understand but nonetheless it is consistent with her positive attitude towards drugs in general. While she is mindful of how

others perceive her as a mother, Mary worries more about her son becoming like his father, who she sees as living an uninspired life of routine and conformity.

Mary is far from ignorant about the potential risks of cannabis; she has concerns that her sons' daily use may be negatively impinging on his levels of energy and motivation. Yet she only expressed this after a bit of encouragement from me to be completely honest about the entirety of her feelings. It was as if admitting to having these concerns was akin to conceding she had been wrong. Although it was clearly uncomfortable for Mary, the interview opened up a safe space in which she could hold these opposites, and gauging my reaction to her positioning was clearly an important part of the process of narratively resolving this tension.

In a similar way, Joanna used our conversation to work through some of the complex feelings that arise during the course of boundary work in relation to motherhood and drug use. She began our conversation by saying:

'You know my friend has brought up her kids around the whole party scene, mostly alcohol. But the drugs weren't hidden, hidden. And, she has been feeling a slight guilt now thinking if I hadn't brought them up like that then would my eldest boy be such a stoner? And I said to her but look at Sarah, she is fine'

In framing the issue first of all around the character of her friend and waiting to observe my response, I felt Joanna was testing my reaction on this controversial matter before proceeding with her own predicament. This was a roundabout way of communicating concerns about her oldest son's problematic relationship with cannabis, for which she feels responsible. After a brief yet significant pause where I felt as though my temperature had just been taken, she continues:

'And I feel exactly the same. My eldest has taken a fair few things, and even though he was given all the warnings, about waiting till you're a bit older and your brain is a bit more formed, he did it, and he has had mental health issue because of it. And I feel guilt, thinking, if I had brought him up completely away from all that then....but I guess that's naïve because kids will go their own route. It is...complicated'

In stating that the drugs were not '*hidden, hidden*', Joanna implies a boundary had been in place but one that did not separate the children and the drug use completely. Reflecting on the potential link between her parenting style and her son's present struggle causes her to feel a

tremendous sense of guilt. She attempts to hold this powerful emotion at bay by first stressing that she gave him all the harm reduction advice, and secondly by affirming his autonomy regardless of parental influence. At the end, in stating that it is ‘complicated’, Joanna acknowledges that she has mixed feelings about where she has chosen to place her children on the inside of the circle of trust.

A common assertion within the substance use prevention literature is that exposure to parental use is a risk factor for adolescent use and adolescents from single parent households in particular are deemed more prone to emotional distress and drug use (Hemovich and Crano, 2009). It is suggested that children who have drug using parents as role models are vulnerable to becoming problematic drug users themselves as such parents set a bad example by normalising the use of harmful substances. As well as modelling unhealthy behaviour parents can also influence their adolescent’s behaviour by speaking favourably about substances and people who use them, increasing the likelihood that positive attitudes towards substance use will be shared (Ebersole et al, 2015).

From the adolescent point of view parental contradiction, that is, saying one thing and doing another, is a huge problem, as it leaves young people confused and unsure where to turn to for advice (Ebersole et al, 2015). A common example of contradictory messaging is the prohibiting of one substance and the allowance of another, for example permitting alcohol use while taking a punitive stance against smoking tobacco. The discourse of prevention which views all illicit substance use as harmful creates the expectation for parents to disapprove of all forms of drug use and to stigmatise the people who use them. These dominant cultural narratives therefore place all the responsibility on the shoulders of the parents, assuming parents have the power to prevent adolescent children from using drugs. Joanna is a single mother, which might explain why for Joanna the burden seemed particularly acute.

The complicated guilt that Joanna and Mary feel arises as they attempt to manage this sense of overwhelming responsibility to monitor, prohibit and control which is in many ways at odds with the values by which they live their lives. From an outside perspective positive and permissive parental attitudes about substance use are unacceptable but for these women the matter is not as monochrome as those on the outside choose to believe. For them, giving ‘contradictory messages’ is an accurate reflection of a lived experience that has taught them that not all substances carry the same level of risk. However in witnessing the struggle as they spoke of their children’s pain, I could not escape the sense that the very same aspect which

desires things to be neat and tidy was inside of them. Seeing the mess that came from adding colour and texture caused a momentary feeling of regret, like an overeager artist that had spoiled something precious in their effort to bring it life, who upon standing back to survey her efforts thinks with great sadness that perhaps she should have left it black and white all along.

The matter of doing one thing and saying another is perhaps more straightforward in such cases where parental substance use is visible. Indeed, it is often the case that studies investigating the effects of parental substance use are recruiting adolescents whose parents engage primarily in licit forms of substance use. For example, in Ebersole et al (2015), in a sample of 72 young people, only 2 of them reported having parents which used an illicit substance, in this case cannabis. Owing to its legality, alcohol and tobacco use are not usually hidden from adolescents.

For some of the other women in this study who did not use cannabis regularly the drug use had been easier to keep separate from family life. Being unaware of their mother's hidden drug use, these children are unlikely to view their mother as a hypocrite and disregard her anti-drug messages. In such cases the feeling of hypocrisy is a matter to contend with privately. Megan is one of the women whose children have no knowledge of her history of illegal drug use.

In recent months there was an incident with Megan's 16 year old son. To her great alarm she received a phone call which informed her that he was in the woods in a 'bit of a state'. It transpired he had been dabbling in recreational stimulant use with a group of friends. After taking a quantity of ketamine which he had been made to believe was cocaine, he had fallen into a 'K-Hole'⁵. Her son quickly recovered after an anxiety filled night of close monitoring and care. When it came to talking to him about what happened Megan remained calm and did not condemn him or his behaviour, understanding the urge to experiment at this age. She could see that this unpleasant experience presented a 'teachable moment'. He had learned for himself the importance of set and setting and Megan saw this as an opportunity to steer him towards a more trustworthy peer group. Her background allowed her to approach him with less fear and more empathy and she achieved this without disclosing her own experiences with drugs. Megan has been bombarded with multiple stigmas over the course of her life as a teenage single parent and is highly sensitive to negative judgement from others and so for her, the risk of losing the

⁵ At high doses > 150mg, ketamine induces severe dissociation, known as a k-hole, and the user experiences intense detachment from the surroundings to the extent that perceptions appear located deep within their consciousness causing reality to appear far off in the distance (see Muetzeltfeldt et al, 2008)

respect of her own son was too great. In the hope that she can protect herself and her children she lives with the silent knowledge of her own drug experiences.

Julie had her first illicit drug experience very young, taking stimulant drugs in school at aged 13. Her drug use reduced drastically on becoming a parent, from every other day to weekends only. Julie kept it firmly hidden from her daughter when she was young, claiming that her drug use was none of her daughters business. She maintained a strict boundary between her party life and her parenting which allowed her to feel that she had a '*separate wee thing, all to herself*'.

Now that her daughter has grown up and left home she knows about this aspect of her mother's life. Julie tells me that it was no big issue talking to her about it, as although she held back knowledge of her own activities, she was always fairly vocal in her view that people who use drugs were not bad people. Her daughter reciprocated with the knowledge that she too had used ecstasy, and Julie was surprised to learn that the secrecy around drugs had existed on both sides of the relationship.

Although Julie maintained a careful boundary between her family and her drug use for many years, she does not frame this in terms of maternal responsibility. According to Julie '*children now are not as wild as we were, they care more about how they look than getting high*'. Indeed, a narrative analysis of drug use, social change and 'drug generations' by Rhodes and Bivol (2012) supports the view that there are generational differences that make drug use less attractive and alluring to younger generations. In order to maintain a sense of separation between her daughters relationship with drugs from her own, Julie foregrounds the influence of culture and in this way her positioning stands out from that of the other women as less troubled.

For the majority of women, the positioning of children, both older and younger, brings a moral dilemma. Thinking about children invites a shift in perspective which serves to complicate feelings about their own drug use, introducing a layer of complexity to the narrative. When this mothering lens is applied to their own drug use the women tend to appraise the risks with greater caution, in comparison to the tone of their story before the introduction of the topic of children. Aimee gives an example of this change in perspective in this exchange which followed a discussion about talking to her teenage children about drug use.

Karen: before we finish, is there anything you would change about your overall experience with drugs?

Aimee: I wish I never took anything. I would rather be the type of person who never tried it.

Karen: and how would you feel about yourself if you never tried it?

Aimee: Better. I can't believe I never for all those years and then done it at that age. It was just stupid. But, I have done it now and there is no point in dwelling on it. But I wish I had never, for the sake of my weans. If I never had them, I don't think I would regret it. But I regret it just now. Because the age they are at just now, the thought of having to be honest with them when they ask me.(pause) I think having weans makes you feel more guilty about everything. No matter what you do. I wished I never have, but I have. But I will never go beyond it. I will never put another tablet in my mouth. I will never be addicted, ever. But, I wish I never done it. Nothing is worth risking your life. Not a couple of hours buzz from a tablet or a ten minute buzz from a line. They say you can't put a price on a life so why you would pay that price for your life, a one pound tablet? I was never scared of anything. I am scared of everything now. It's weird isn't it?

Karen: I guess it is. Thanks for doing this Aimee.

There was a very visible change in Aimee's demeanour when saying this, which made me take notice. For a moment it was as if she had changed her mind entirely about drugs. The voice of Aimee as mother is more aware of the pain in contrast to the voice inside Aimee which speaks of the pleasures. The dialogical tension between these two positions in Aimee's story acts to make her experience a feeling of deep guilt about using drugs. She is aware that if this aspect wasn't present then she would not have this feeling of regret.

This radical shift in perspective in Aimee's story is what Frank (2010) calls 'interpellation'. Interpellation describes the manner in which stories work on those who tell them, calling forth a particular aspect of their identity and compelling them to act in a particular way that is demanded of that identity. Indeed, for Frank, the effects of interpellation are often evident in relation to the parental identity. He gives the example of how the sound of a baby crying can make a person reassume the parental identity after having momentarily slipped out. Aimee's interpellation shows how the story has acted upon her to make her feel guilty, to self-police her behaviour. In order for this to occur she must also have momentarily slipped out of that identity and the calling forth occurred at the moment of locating her children in the circles of trust. Aimee is then filled with dread, mortified at the prospect of bringing the children into

this space. Her story locates her children as firmly on the outside, entirely ignorant of their mother's use of drugs. She talks about taking cocaine sometimes, in another room out of site, and she goes to great lengths to stress that this is always within limit and she is never unable to bathe the children and put them to bed. In this manner the story functions to preserve Aimee's position as a moral subject.

The feelings surrounding the subject of parenting and drug use are messy and complex. Most women are not keen to share the inner circle with children drawing the boundary at the margins, willing to share stories of their drug use but never the act. Some draw the boundary further still, choosing never to share any of this part of themselves. Few go as far as Mary, who communicates her desire for her son to follow in her footsteps. Mary exemplifies a striving for consistency, choosing to remain loyal to her own beliefs regardless of how challenging they may be for others. And still, Mary is very conscious of how others might perceive her; there remains a sense of inner conflict in her story.

In narratively constructing the boundaries with adolescents there is a sense of wanting to give the harm reduction knowledge as it contains the power to protect, but at the same time exists the desire to hold that knowledge back in order to preserve innocence. Competing desires for protection and purity are at play in these narratives making the boundary work with children the most challenging. The extent to which the woman feels that her intimate drug knowledge may benefit her adolescent child in some way reflects the level of internal conflict experienced in positioning them as insiders or outsiders respectively. Bringing in the topic of children was thus an interesting turning point in many of the women's narratives, a visible moment of 'interpellation' (Frank, 2010). Although the moral stance adopted in relation to adult children (drugs are bad) appears to contradict an earlier position in relation to the self (drugs are good), from a dialogical perspective these conflicting perspectives co-exist as different voices inside the woman. According to Bamberg (2005) it is such points of contradiction which represent openings into identity work. The voice of the mother protective and acutely aware of risk, and the voice of the potentially stigmatised woman striving to defend her autonomy and rational for using illegal drugs are brought into dialogue and the result is a more critical perspective than was previously expressed. For the women as defended subjects, the interview created a rare opportunity to perform this identity work. For myself as a non-judgemental audience, experiencing the testing out of these alternative boundary narratives of drug use and motherhood gifted a working example of the manner in which discursive repertoires are not given but interactively accomplished (Bamberg, 2005).

Women as daughters

The majority of women do not share this aspect of their identity with their parents. In general, where parents are drug naïve or anti-drug they are kept in the dark for as long as possible. Where parents are drug-experienced they are located within the circle of trust.

Summer has lived with her mother who requires a degree of care for most of her adult life and yet her mother has no idea that taking drugs is an important aspect of her daughter's life. With the exception of daily cannabis use to treat pain from severe arthritis, her illicit drug use takes place outside the home and with trusted friends. It does not alter her general behaviour or appearance in any way and so she feels quite strongly that there is no need for her mother to know about any of this as she would not understand.

Indeed, some of women whose parents have a degree of knowledge about their drug use, do so not out of choice, but on account of the women having experienced periods of crisis where outside intervention was required. For example, Lana's mother found out in the wake of a mental health crisis. If was not for this happening, then Lana would not have shared this with her mother as she feels it would only have burdened her with more worry. Such parents who are not drug experienced and have therefore only fear based cultural narratives to guide their understanding, are often viewed in need of sheltering from the reality of their daughters drug use. For Rachel, there is a real sense of regret and loss over keeping the drug use hidden from parents for this reason and it is in the context of this longing for a deeper understanding that she resolves to have something different with her own children.

A number of the women in this study have that something different with their parents, a relationship in which illicit drug use is accepted and encouraged, albeit to various degrees. Freda's mother is a key figure within her inner circle as they often smoke cannabis together. While her father is aware that this goes on, this is not something that he chooses to share with his daughter. Drug use in the context of the mother/daughter relationship was only spoken about by a minority of the women, but when it did present as feature of the woman's narrative it felt significant in some way.

Daisy Clark speaks about her parents a great deal, and this is consistent with the idea that degree of space afforded to another in a narrative correlates with degree of closeness in that relationship (Bellotti, 2016). Daisy describes the times she uses drugs with her mother as sacred

and integral to the health of their relationship. She tells the following story about using psychedelics with her mother.

“In recent years I have started to have these really special experiences with my mother. I remember...I think it was September. Yes. It was the end of the summer just before I was going to go into my fourth year at uni. My mum called me up and said this person had started doing these...workshops again. But this time he would be using...medicines. And I was like do you mean drugs mum? And she was like yes. So we went to this amazing place and every day we drank San Pedro. San Pedro is a type of mescaline, a type of peyote. And for me and my mum it was one of the most...it was a moment where we could just be woman to woman. None of this mother daughter. None of that drama. And I held her because she had a headache. And I could see her lightening up. It had been a very long time since she had taken drugs. Back in the eighties she smoked a lot of cannabis and liked hallucinogens. My dad as well. So I am quite lucky that I can speak to her about these things. They tell me their stories and I tell them mine. They have always been a safe place to go. To speak about drugs. I have never felt that I have to hide it, from them. We are very open that way”

Having her parents in the know is a source of capital for Daisy and feels she has benefited from the open and accepting nature of the relationship which has facilitated the exchange of knowledge from both sides. She feels that through this she has come to know them better, and seeing them as individuals in their own right, and not just her parents, has helped to place into context the wider circumstances of her upbringing.

In similar vein, Maya's relationship with her mother takes a prominent place within her narrative of drug use. Her mother, who passed away a few years ago, would often recount tales of her own drug use, both good and bad, from the moment Maya was old enough to understand, in her early teens. She gives several indications throughout the course of the interview that her mother's stories have had a lasting influence on how she thinks about and talks about her own drug use. In describing what she really enjoys about her favourite drug, ecstasy, she relates it directly to what her mother enjoyed about taking LSD in the 60's. Listening to her mother's stories of moderate drug use has thus created for Maya a framework with which to measure her own experiences.

The downside to her being brought into her mother's circle of trust at a young age was that Maya was very frightened for her mother's safety. Having only the horror stories on mainstream media the anti-drug education at school to go on, Maya feared her mother was going to die. But her attitude changed after she had tried it herself;

I knew she was taking ecstasy and I was still believing all the hype on the news about people dying and I was like "please mum don't take ecstasy again" but then when I did eventually take one, it was my uncle who gave me a dove between Christmas and new year and I was just like woooooow! It was amazing, that was my first experience. And then after I was like that to her "it's okay I understand now!" And she just smiled. But she was very...she always did things moderately. When I went through a phase of underage drinking it terrified her, she didn't understand it. She never did that'.

When Maya went through a stage of underage binge drinking her mother was very frightened. She didn't like the emerging culture of excessive alcohol consumption in young people and felt the reduction in awareness and resulting loss of control left Maya and other women particularly vulnerable to predatory behaviour. This was different to the counter-culture of the 1960's in which she spent her own time formative years experimenting with MDMA and LSD and various other consciousness expanding substances. Maya's first ecstasy tablet was given to her by her uncle with her mother's permission when she was in her late teens. Maya describes this first experience as hugely positive and eye opening.

Ecstasy is Maya's favourite drug. Although she complains of a decline in quality over recent years, she still favours it over all other drugs. She describes herself as having a sensitive constitution, and as a result many stimulant drugs tend to have an unpleasant effect on her nervous system. She feels like her heart is about to stop and this is not an enjoyable experience. In a similar way LSD has caused her to freak out more often than not. However, she tells me she persisted with it '*because her mother's stories were so amazing*'. After a time, she accepted that she wasn't going to have the same relationship with it. But leaving it behind was not without an internal struggle; '*I just kept on with it, going along with what everyone else was doing, because I didn't want to let anyone down*'. Maya looked up to her mother a great deal and consequently had very high expectations of LSD, her mother's drug of choice. Ultimately when it did not agree with her, Maya was forced to stop viewing her mother's stories as something to aspire to. The fantastic tales of her mother's hallucinogenic adventures remain

close to her heart, but Maya is weaving her own stories now that speak of quite different experiences. However, the somewhat unusual manner in which her mother has inducted her into the culture is something which she hopes to carry on into the next generation.

Parental figures actively participating in the drug use is an interesting, albeit uncommon aspect of the inner circle. What do the women get from the experience of using drugs with their parents, and their mothers in particular? One of the main benefits for women whose parents are located in the circle of trust is the sharing of stories. Different generations of drug experienced individuals can connect through this sharing of stories, and through this connection the ways in which the meaning of drug use and the surrounding culture has changed over time comes into view.

For women like Freda, Daisy and Maya, drug use is normalised to a degree and not approached as a symptom of pathology. The experience of stigma may not be as pronounced for these women whose primary female role model shares a similar identity. When women have this 'safe space' in their parents as a foundation they have less need to seek support elsewhere. There is a dearth of literature on the matter of adults using drugs alongside parents, but the stories of the women in this study suggest that this is an important avenue to explore in future research on women who use drugs and their significant relationships.

Employers and Colleagues

Consistently placed out with the circle of trust is the women's employer. This reflects the fear of economic prospects being damaged and of one's suitability as an employee being questioned. Consider the following exchange between myself and Summer:

Summer: "If it wasn't illegal I would be shouting it from the rooftops because I had a much better weekend than any of my colleagues!"

Karen: "And if you were asked about it directly?"

Summer: "I would lie. Why would I put myself and my job in jeopardy when I am doing so well at it, getting lots of praise? You wouldn't go into your boss and tell them you had robbed somebody at the weekend would you? And unfortunately it would be treated as an illegal activity. So it's just about being covert, not being open about it in certain circles. Otherwise you will be labelled"

(Summer, 50, Support worker)

Summer relates her definite refusal to talk about her drug use in the workplace says to a desire to protect her performance at work and the positive feedback she receives for this. This is not surprising as women are widely engaged in additional forms of work which are not recognised as legitimate such as domestic labour and caring for dependants. The importance of the workplace as a source of self-esteem in the context of women's reproductive labour being undervalued and ignored (English and Campbell, 2020), should not be underestimated.

Employment is regarded as integral to identity formation in both men and women, playing a significant role in healthy social development (Huang et al, 2011). The women's fear of being negatively labelled was thus particularly heightened in relation to spaces of employment. To illustrate, consider Allie's response when I asked her how open she is in the workplace about that aspect of her identity:

"Oh my god not at all! They will think that I am fucking nuts! Part of me wants to but you need to protect yourself, don't you? Once you have, you can't take it back"

(Allie, 28, lawyer)

What sort of negative behaviours arise from this labelling which women like Allie need to protect themselves from? Hitlan, Clifton and Desoto (2006) discuss the impact of often subtle forms of exclusionary behaviour in the workplace which can take the form of silent treatment, shunning, or being outright ignored. According to Hitlan et al (2006) what often underpins these forms of workplace exclusion is a label that creates a perception that the target is unable to contribute, for example disability. These forms of rejection can be very damaging, leading to poorer performance appraisals and denial of promotion. The stereotypical construction of drug users as untrustworthy, unproductive, and unpredictable makes them likely targets of this kind of behaviour.

To disclose drug use in such a climate is to invite misunderstanding in the form of assumptions commonly made about people who use drugs. For example periods of absence may then be wrongly assumed to be a consequence of drug use and intoxication. And as Summer points out, the association of drug use and crime might mark one out as morally suspect. The need to manage impressions in the workplace is more pronounced as such spaces are generally comprised of individuals from a range of different social and religious backgrounds, making the presence of discriminatory attitudes quite likely. The women have to spend a lot of their

time there and so facing consistent negative judgement would be overwhelming, impacting upon their capacity to perform work related task and duties.

Wendy, who has a permanent position within the local council, was extremely concerned about colleagues finding out in particular. She was very nervous at the beginning of the interview and sought repeated assurance of confidentiality. When I asked her to share her concerns with me, she replied simply '*I work for the council*'. Wendy made it clear that she had worked hard to build an image of respectability within her community;

'if they found out they would think badly of me. I just think that people who haven't taken drugs have this picture in their mind, they think of someone who is a drug addict, someone who can't control, whereas we just use it like it is alcohol'

(Wendy, council worker, 37)

According to Ellemers and Barreto (2006) attempts to be positively evaluated at work by hiding a socially stigmatised identity are fairly common on account of members of socially stigmatised groups having a harder time advancing in employment. Where the source of stigma is invisible and the person has the choice to make their group membership known, they generally choose to hide the stigmatised aspect of their identity to be more valued and accepted by others. However as these authors show, the consequences of hiding can be considerable, and attempts often undermine wellbeing more than they protect it. Hiding in the workplace can cause feelings of shame guilt and apprehension about being exposed and can create a continually self-monitoring mind -set that adds to the cognitive load (Ellemers and Barreto (2006).

That said, being valued and accepted in the workplace requires different strategies of self-presentation depending on the nature of the women's employment. For example, both Rachel and Marie work in harm reduction which has non-judgementality at its core and being drug experienced is viewed as an advantage within the context of this profession. And yet, despite this apparently safe environment, they still hold a lot back from colleagues.

Marie has a senior role within one of these organisations and having the respect of her employees is crucial. Because drug knowledge is highly valued in this context, she tends towards obscurity with regards the extent of her lived experience, not to avoid stigma but to avoid the perception of being drug naïve in relation to some of the more 'hard core' drug users amongst the staff.

Over the years, many of Rachel's long established colleagues have been very vocal and open about their drug experiences, but she has reservations about disclosing too much in the context of the current environment which she feels is getting even more 'repressive'. Recent policies of non-disclosure capture this climate of increasing self-censorship of which Rachel is unhappy:

'I will always challenge our policy that we don't talk about our own experiences, I mean it's not like a strict policy and I will always say to volunteers that it is your choice if you want to disclose, as long as you can say why you chose to do that, so it wasn't just to impress someone or because they were stuck for something else to say. Which I've witnessed. But I've also saw when it can really help to be able to relate to someone who is going through a hard time. So I see the advantage of it. You now when I am working with young people, groups of young people you always get what have you taken? And I can definitely side track but also I am not going to lie. But I am not always going to tell you the whole truth because actually you are sussing me out a bit. But there's always a way you can say indirectly, like going through the list of drugs that I haven't taken. Which is normally enough. Because they are just kind of testing you.'

What stands out in this statement is when Rachel declares that she is 'not always going to tell you the whole truth'. This suggests that there are degrees of disclosure. In situation where the women feel safe enough to share aspects of this stigmatised identity, they make further decisions as to how much to share.

Unlike most of the other women, Marie and Rachel have a workplace that is built around talking about illicit drug use, but even this environment is becoming less safe to be a known user of illicit drugs. The value Rachel speaks of, of being able to intimately relate, is what underpins the perception of lived experience as an asset in the arena of drug treatment. However, as a recent paper by Ross (2020) highlights, within the chorus of the voices of lived experience that are now taking up space in debates about drug policy reform, some are privileged and others devalued. Ross describes experiencing a loss of legitimacy to contribute to drug policy debates after disclosing certain aspects of her own recreational drug use, suggesting the voices of recovered addicts are exalted above all others, and those represent 'living' experience through continued use are generally side-lined or ignored (Ross, 2020).

Thus stigma persists even in those spaces that place explicit value on being drug experienced, on account of a perceived lack of objectivity that is associated with individuals who use drugs.

In some employment sectors this requirement of objectivity is more pronounced, making potential discovery of drug use riskier than for those women whose intellectual capacity is not as central to their occupation. As Allie explains above in relation to being open with employers, the anticipation of future regret is a key feature of the dilemma of disclosure. Her belief of being labelled as ‘nuts’ shows that she is aware of the social construction of women who use drugs as bad, mad or sad. (Klee, 1998). To avoid being categorised in this manner, she chooses to keep this aspect of her identity a secret. What about the part of her that wants to? What can be said about that?

Many of the women want to take this risk for different reasons, to share an important aspect of themselves and have that reality validated by peers. For example, Summer shares her desire to make it known that she is ‘*having a better time*’ than her colleagues. In the end she decides it is better to be perceived as ordinary over deviant. What is clear is that misjudging an individual’s attitude towards drug use can result in stigma and discrimination which as Mary’s experience illustrates, can seriously inhibit social functioning:

“I am a board member of the community council. I haven’t made it to the last two meetings actually. You see, there is another member, a man, and since he found out he has treated me sooo differently. My god he is really looking down on me. Oh god. You see, he was a policeman. But he had made jokes about weed so I thought he was open minded about it. But no. He has totally changed towards me. He talks to me like I am a lesser species. Maybe I should try and talk to him about it. I don’t know.”

(Mary, Primary school teacher, 52)

It is perhaps the nature of Mary’s employment which makes the negative judgement more acute. As a primary school teacher Mary’s professional identity carries normative gendered expectations of being a nurturer and a positive role model for the younger generation. Complicating this responsibility for social reproduction is the fear that the morality of the children will be compromised through exposure to Mary’s alternative beliefs about cannabis. In this manner she faces a dilemma that has long been appreciated by teachers who manage lesbian identities in the education system insofar as their private lifestyles have been similarly viewed through the lens of moral contagion and as a threat to traditional family life and values (Clarke, 1996).

In Scotland in 2019, the debate re-emerged over proposals to bring in a system of random drug testing for teachers, reinforcing the notion that teachers should be moral paragons when it comes to illegal drug use (Hepburn, 2019). The move is viewed as necessary by its proponents on account of the perceived risk to students and is framed in terms of the council's duty of care to ensure its workers are not under the influence of drugs and alcohol. However, some have been vocal with concerns over the unnecessary policing of teachers behaviour and its infringement on their right to privacy, given that cannabis intoxication in particular is likely taking place when teachers are off duty. Despite this, positive tests will lead to disciplinary action and a permanent character blemish.

Erving Goffman's seminal work on stigma focused on the psychological dimensions of wellbeing and distress in those that are stigmatised. Indeed, the experience of stigma is generally assumed to induce feelings of shame, guilt and disgrace (Vas, 2003). More recently, anthropological contribution to the understanding of stigma aims to embed and locate that suffering within a local moral context and value system. Stigma, which '*decays the ability to hold on to what matters most to ordinary people in a local world, such as wealth, relationships, and life chances*' uniquely affects lives and degrades moral standing (Kleinman and Hall-Clifford, 2009:

As this research demonstrates, the penalties faced by professionals who use drugs can be severe such as loss of employment and reputation but more often they are social in nature, subtly dispensed, as in the form of disparaging looks. According to Link and Phelan (2001) for individuals with concealable stigmatised identities such social slights are relatively infrequent. Nevertheless, when they do occur they can be very powerful; the reaction of the former policeman to Mary's self-disclosure has been enough to keep her away from the meetings which she formerly enjoyed and contributed to.

At the end of her story Mary is unsure how to respond to the ostracisation going forward. She fears it is but a matter of time before someone informs her employer and her career is ruined. According to Das (2013), attempts to manage a spoiled identity can involve a range of responses including concealment, defiance or irony (Das, 2013). Mary sways between defiance and reparation, unsure whether to continue defending her use of cannabis despite the negative consequences or to attempt to build bridges with the man who is treating her 'like a lesser species'. Doing so, she dwells within the space between two competing desires; to contest the stereotypes of women who use drugs and the standards of normative femininity within her local

professional world, and to repair the damage caused by her disclosure and recover her previously held moral status within the community.

Mary's experience shines a light on the way in which women who use drugs are often dehumanised when viewed through a traditional male gaze, which in her story is embodied by the figure of the ex-policeman. Mountian (2005) dives into the social imaginary and discovers a change in the position of women who use drugs from passive victims to polluted women when the drug use, or knowledge of it, extends to the public sphere. She argues, as 'keepers of society's morality, in the traditional social roles of mothers and carers', women who reject femininity in this manner are deemed therefore worthy of rejection as by 'using drugs they threaten their own lives, the lives of their families (especially children), and the nation, as they would (re)produce an unruly society' (Mountian, 2005: 85). These patriarchal discourses of women's drug use, which have undertones of sexual promiscuity, construct Mary as doubly deviant. She has visibly transgressed moral boundaries insofar as her use of cannabis is viewed as complicating her traditional role as moral paragon and to extent that she unapologetically violates the norms which seek to contain and restrict female pleasure.

Discussion

As highlighted in the chapter on hidden populations, women who use drugs are predominantly non-treatment seeking, and hidden (National Treatment Agency, 2010). It is the purpose of this research to understand the reasons why women who use drugs are largely a hidden population and there is much speculation as to why this is the case. Indeed, it is widely accepted that women who use drugs face greater levels of stigma and discrimination than their male counterparts (Simpson and McNulty, 2008). Lack of appropriate treatment services which are gender sensitive is thus believed to be a significant factor in the underrepresentation of women within the treatment sector (Ettorre, 2004). Fear of social work involvement and child protection intervention might also serve as a powerful motivation for women to keep their drug using status hidden. For many of the women in the current study who have professional and parental responsibilities there are serious consequences to be faced if the illicit drug use comes to light.

Relationships are a central feature of the women's narratives of drug use which supports the findings of a broad range of studies into women's use of illegal drugs. Like a very recent hidden population study focusing on women in France (Perrin et al, 2020) the women in this study can

be conceptualised as 'socially included'. It is the context of this social inclusion that the women describe the social network in which illicit drug use takes place as a circle based on trust. Previous hidden population studies provide little information in relation to the social networks in which participants are embedded. To address this I have drawn inspiration from the work of Bellotti (2016) to construct a model of three concentric circles which depicts the inner circle of trust where individuals have knowledge and participation, the margins where individuals have knowledge without participation, and the space which outside the circle of trust where individuals have no knowledge of the women's drug use and therefore no participation.

I explore where each participant has chosen to lay the boundaries of knowledge and awareness in relation to the circles of trust, for the purpose of understanding the social processes that assist their wider social inclusion. In doing so it has become apparent that there exists a degree of similarity in terms of which relationships fall within and without the circle of trust. For most the inner circle is small, occupied by other women who use drugs. Outsiders are a larger and fairly diverse group of people; friends, family, employers, colleagues, neighbours and health professionals. What they appear to have in common is a simplistic understanding of drugs and the people who use them. A proportion of these outsiders pose a risk of enacting discrimination.

The relative benefits of being an outsider or insider to the group under study has been given much attention in recent years in the social sciences and it appears there are as many arguments for and against either position (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). As highlighted by Dwyer and Buckle (2009) participants are often sceptical about researchers who adopt an outside position and may question the ability of the researcher to truly appreciate their experience. This reflects the women's attitudes towards outsiders in the social circles. The limitations of outsider positioning for researchers appears to mirror the perceived limitations of friendships in the outsider space for the women. In contemplating the discussion on insider status from Adler and Adler (1987), it strikes that the relative degrees of group membership: complete, active and peripheral, exist in parallel to the positions within the circles of trust. The significantly more developed literature on researcher positionality might then be useful in developing knowledge about the relative benefits of different relationships for women who use drugs.

As I am positioned on the margins of the inner circle, it is expected that I have some kind of knowledge about drugs, and throughout the process of listening to the women's stories I have got the feeling that they are seeking confirmation that I indeed do 'get it'. Being able to demonstrate that I do, to an extent, through the use of the DENIM has thus been vital in keeping

the channels of communication open. A fundamental condition of the sharing of stories is thus the experience of resonance, which exists to greater or lesser degrees within the inner circles and margins respectively. I shall return to this matter in the final discussion.

Descriptions of friendship with outsiders, and what is lacking in these relationships, brings into focus one of the main benefits of friendship with women on the inside. The women in this study who have experienced drug use in the context of less intimate friendships understand, often with the benefit of hindsight, that they are safer in more supportive friendships and are able to change their circles accordingly and continue with more functional patterns of illicit drug use. The relational model (Covington and Surrey, 2000), which downplays women's agency, does not construct them as subjects which are capable of effecting this transformation. From this perspective, women who are experiencing problematic drug use are viewed through the lens of an inevitable spiral into addiction. The drug becomes all-consuming and the woman is utterly powerless. This study therefore contributes to the growing body of evidence which demonstrates the use of informal social controls through the provision of regulatory norms that help to keep drug use within relatively socially acceptable levels.

It is important to state however, in highlighting friendship as the most important category of relationship in the circles of trust, I am not saying that women use drugs *for* this intimacy or for the friendship. In the spirit of narrative analysis I am less preoccupied with discovering the 'why's' and more interested in the how such understandings come into being. Consequently, while the quality of friendship and intimacy appears to be an important influencing factor in understanding the difference in drug use that is functional and that which is not, I wish to stress that foregrounding intimacy is a relatively socially acceptable way of narrating women's drug use as opposed to bodily pleasure. In this way women are adopting a position of strategic essentialism to defend from stigma.

Indeed, much of the literature concerning the intimate partner relationships of women who use drugs exists predominantly in the context of intensely stigmatised drug using practices such as intravenous use of heroin or crack cocaine. The invoking of relationships with male partners can thus be viewed as strategic within the context of social sanctioning in such captive populations. While Herold's (2015) study brings to light the complexity of narrating romantic relationships in the context of female drug use, little is said about the existence of or lack of friendship networks and how this impacts the women's positioning of intimate partners. Analysing the women's boundary narratives through the lens of the circles of trust permits an

exploration of the narrative construction of many different important relationships. This is important as the stories of the women in the present study demonstrate that narratives of friendship and narratives of intimate partnership are relatively interwoven.

The two women who foreground intimate partner relationships in their narrative, Louisa and Wendy, portray these partnerships in largely positive terms. Although they use exclusively with partners, their relationships are multi-dimensional, and the shared identity as a couple does not revolve around their drug use. Sharing the secret of occasional illicit drug use serves to deepen an already existing bond, in contrast to a 'drug relationship' like the one described by Claire, which has drug use as its sole foundation and is often characterised by an asymmetry of power (Martin, 2010).

Keeping drug use within the boundaries of intimate partnerships might also protect from the marginalisation that is experienced by some women as a result of contravening society's gendered norms and behaviours. Whether it is over exaggerated forms of femininity, as in psychiatric diagnoses of histrionic or borderline personality disorder (Ussher, 2013) or underwhelming forms of femininity as implied by constructions of drug using women are uncaring and selfish (Klee, 1998), that which contradicts an idealised form of femininity, is pathologised. Performance of idealised forms of femininity is thus a way of avoiding negative attention and passing under the radar. However, these dominant gendered norms which underpin the notion of the 'ideal mother', are largely shaped around white middle class norms, which excludes lower class women and women of colour from gaining access to these groups (Springer, 2010). The role of positionality and privilege in allowing the women to perform this 'emphasised femininity' will be explored in the next chapter.

In addition, both Louisa and Wendy have access to non-drug using friendship networks on account of their drug of choice, cocaine, being relatively socially acceptable. As the earlier section on friendship shows, when the level of stigma attributed to the drug use is particularly intense, such as with the use of heroin, the women generally have fewer opportunities to access friendship networks, making it more likely that the drug use takes place within an intimate partner relationship. In situations such as this, as Claire's story shows, the inner circle of trust can become a dangerous place.

Key to the narrative approach to interview data is the notion that stories always perform a function (Frank, 2010). Consistent with this view, it is my suggestion that the women are actively constructing the group boundaries as they speak about their drug use, positioning

themselves and others within the concentric circles of trust. Bearing in mind the anti-mimetic epistemological stance adopted in the present study, it therefore follows that the circles of trust are not independent realities which are merely revealed in our discussion, they are constructed and maintained through narratives of drug use. Narrative is the vehicle through which group boundaries are brought into being and the ‘borderwork’ described by Foster and Spencer (2013) is performed.

In essence, circles of trust is about boundaries and bonding. In this chapter I have demonstrated some of the reasons and rationales that women in hidden populations have for sharing their identity and the drug experience with some people and not others. What has become clear is that while all of the women are affected by the stigmatising culture and concerned with the matter of achieving social acceptability, this means different things for different women. Historically, definitions of problematic drug use have been centred on substance/s used, frequency of use and the route of administration. Due to the shifting landscape of the ‘drug situation’, the Professional body which informs drug policy at the European level, the EMCDDA, now defines problem drug use more broadly as:

‘Recurrent drug use that is causing actual harms (negative consequences) to the person (including dependence, but also other health, psychological or social problems), or is placing the person at a high probability/risk of suffering such harms’ (EMCDDA, 2019)

There is then, a disparity in how outsiders see problem drug use and how those on the ‘inside’ view it themselves. For the women in this study, problematic drug use is that which invites the most stigma in their local moral world and as Louisa and Aimee demonstrate, this is largely dependent on social context and in particular, the values placed on certain relationships within the social circle. For some women, using drugs in the context of an intimate partner relationship is a source of shame and stigma while for many others it is a tool for building greater trust and intimacy. The women in this study narratively construct their own definitions of what constitutes problematic drug use and they use this to manage not only their drug use but any potential stigma and discrimination and I suggest that future research on the stigma experienced by women who use drugs take this variation in perception and experience into account.

While some women actively seek to challenge the misunderstandings of others such as Freda who desires to ‘break the stigma’ by showing that professional women can also be a woman who uses illegal drugs, most women feel it is not worth the risks. Mary made a poor judgement

in being faced with the dilemma of disclosure primarily as she had believed that general attitudes to cannabis users have shifted away from the demonising narratives of the past. Her overestimation of this progression ultimately furnished her with a false sense of security. While mainstream society has moved on from the sensationalist caricatures of ‘Reefer Madness’ of the 1930’s, the association with female drug use and moral degradation remains fervently alive (Mountian, 2005).

Morality work is an aspect of boundary narratives in general, and it is much more pronounced when it comes to stories of drug use and motherhood. In the cases of friends, family, partners and colleagues, it was relatively straightforward for the women to draw a boundary and say here is who knows and this is why. These people are in the circle of trust and these people are without. With talk about adult children in particular, the boundary narratives took on a different quality, fraught with tension and heavy emotion. Some women trouble their own stated position on illegal drug use when it comes to thinking about their children. They appear to contradict themselves, for example, by arguing for the benefits for themselves and then adopting an anti-drug position at the thought of their adult children using. The apparent shift in feeling and moral perspective demonstrated above by Aimee shows that subjectivity is indeed multiple and fluid, and this changing of subject positions was especially noticeable with talk of motherhood.

There is comparatively little data on the employment of women who use drugs; the captive populations which are overrepresented tend to be characterised by records of low level and inconsistent employment and training (Neale, 2004). This study is remarkable in that all of the women are currently employed. The degree of social inclusion in this group of women who use drugs, is evidenced not only in the range of different relationships that occupy multiple spaces on the circles of trust but in the extent of their involvement in the workforce. Women are naturally very guarded in the workplace, aware of the potential of being negatively labelled. This exists in domains where it is relatively acceptable to disclose, and there are clear limits in terms of what the women are willing to share. Indeed, acute self-awareness is a marked feature of the boundary narratives used to construct this collective account of the circles of trust and this will be looked at in greater depth in the proceeding chapter.

Erving Goffman has argued for stigma to be articulated, not only through attributes but through the language of relationships (Fraser et al, 2017). While it would benefit from further development as a tool of elicitation in narrative interviewing, the model of the circles of trust is a promising way in to generate storied material which illuminates how a woman’s friendships

and other important relationships influence/shape/control her drug use in both beneficial and harmful ways. The inherent complexity in constructing the circles of trust demonstrates the need to move beyond simplistic notions of drug use as all bad and all drug relationships as unequally balanced and pathological.

Chapter Seven ‘Seven small stories of illicit drug use’

Introduction

‘Circles of trust’ explored the women’s narrative means of making sense of drug use in the context of a network of social relations. To reiterate, narratives are the scaffolds which women use to construct stories about their self and their place in the world in relation to others (Smith, 2016). The following excerpts from the interview transcripts which are presented here can be viewed as small stories contained within the larger context of the overall narrative constructed throughout the interviews. Thinking dialogically about these stories through asking questions, I aim to think critically about the work of the women’s drug storytelling, with the intention of opening up the dialogue further (Smith, 2016).

Brett Smith (2016) suggests building narrative typologies that capture content, structure and function, and ideally, these types should be clearly defined from other narratives, expressing something unique about their experience. Looking through the collection of transcripts for small stories which can be viewed as sites of identity work (Bamberg and Georgakopoulou, 2008) there are three clear areas in which these small stories go to work for the women; relocating risk (risk narratives), constructing a socially acceptable identity (respectability narratives) and retrieval of that which is lost (retrieval narratives). However, stories operate on multiple levels and simultaneously achieve many different effects (Bamberg, 1997). Therefore, the grouping together of stories on the basis of some similarity will equally bring into focus the myriad ways in which they are different:

- ‘Risk narratives’ are the same in terms of the dominant cultural narratives they are acting to trouble and reshape. These stories from Joanna and Freda both work to reformulate and re traditional conceptions of risk yet they achieve this in different ways peculiar to professional background and social class.
- ‘Respectability Narratives’ are the construction and performance of a socially acceptable identity and, following on from the circles of trust, we see that this is achieved in different ways for different women. The exemplars offered from Louisa, Rachel and Marie highlight the way in which dominant patriarchal narratives of femininity and women in relationships are used to make illicit drug use more palatable.

- 'Retrieval Narratives' the stories from Allie and Daisy Clark are again, different in many ways, but unified in their work of recovering something that was previously lost. This is often a sense of control over drug use after it has been lost, but sometimes it relates to the women's sense of self and identity.

The analytic and aesthetic approach I have taken is to bring these stories into dialogue with each other, exploring similarities and differences between the narrative resources used to achieve the goals of women's drug talk in this hidden population. In the spirit of dialogical narrative scholarship (Frank, 2010, Smith, 2016) I expand the context of the women's utterances to include the interactional context of the interview, attempting to situate the identity work therein in relation to the wider cultural narratives of women's drug use.

Risk narratives

The following small stories from Joanna and Freda are exemplars of narratives which act to resist the dominant cultural narratives of risk which underpin the stigmatisation of women who use drugs (Stengel, 2014). Joanna displaces risk from the 'natural' substances which she prefers to the pharmaceutical drugs which have recently caused the death of two acquaintances. She reinforces this position through mobilising alternative discourses of healing and drug use as practiced within other cultures. Freda performs an alternative narrative of drug use and motherhood which acts to challenge the dominant moral framework in which parental drug use is generally situated. I analyse the similarities and differences between these two stories using Smith's (2016) guide to dialogical narrative analysis (DNA), whilst paying special attention to the narrative resources used and relate them to the women's positionality and social context.

As a woman who gardens - Joanna

When I was younger, the first thing I ever heard about drugs was about LSD and somebody thought they were an orange and tried to peel off their own skin. Horrific. And that, was told to me by a nurse, so you know, it is a 'true story'. So I was terrified of the stuff. It took years before I started hearing more positive things. About creativity, spirituality. Healing, actually. Other cultures use hallucinogenic herbs as part of their cultural practice. As part of their celebrations. But here, we don't. At least we pretend we don't. I think as women, we are judged a lot more

harshly on a lot of things. And I don't see this issue as any different. I think what does upset me, is the fact that so many natural plants are banned. And then so many chemicals are given to people to apparently make them feel better. And it is not that clear cut by a long way.

In the last few years I have known two people that have died from taking medication that was given to them. Legal medication that had side effects. And it has been the cause of death! So it really frustrates me when recreational drugs, sorry plants, are misaligned because as research is starting to prove now, when it comes to cannabis and mushrooms especially, that they could be really, really useful. And there has got to be a heap more plants out there that have other benefits. And that, I feel very strongly about. As a woman who gardens, I feel triply annoyed. I have a real connection with plants. I grow things. And I wish I could grow cannabis. It is a plant that I like. I would like to have cannabis oil in my tea one day and then lemon balm the next.

Having problematized common understandings of the dangers of illicit drug use with the example of the story told to her by the nurse, Joanna continues with the complicated task of negotiating a socially acceptable and morally accountable identity. She widens the context of her story in order to locate the stigma within a European cultural context, deflecting it away from herself. Effectively she is stating 'If I lived in a different space or time this would not be a problem'. She thus aligns herself to abstract and far away civilisations and social practices, momentarily disconnecting from the present culture in which she lives, in which prohibition is accepted as the norm.

Joanna appears primarily concerned with challenging common understandings of cannabis use when halfway through, she emphatically corrects herself and substitutes the word 'recreational drugs' for plants. She also does this in the beginning of her story when she sets out the problem that the dialogue seeks to address. Here, she could have said that drugs are illegal, but instead she opts for the phrase 'that natural plants are banned'.

The emphatic manner of expression in which she relays the death of two people on prescription medication functions to problematize culturally sanctioned drug use, while the narrative of the relative purity of nature is brought into sharp contrast. This is consistent with what Widding (2015) calls 'extreme case formulation', a common discursive device people utilise in the construction of stories when they feel defensive about their ideas or actions. The 'extreme case

formulation' emphasises extreme cases to persuade listeners of the particular righteousness of their behaviour. That Joanna is performing her identity work against a backdrop of stigma and discrimination is suggested when she says: '*we as women are judged more harshly*'.

Joanna problematizes pharmaceutical drugs to frame her own drug use as safe in comparison. A somewhat exalted conception of 'mother nature' is juxtaposed with a less desirable culture with the negative casting of 'man-made chemicals'. In contrast to the comedowns and hangovers experienced with synthetically produced substances such as ecstasy or ketamine, the healing effect of natural plants is emphasised along with the relatively fewer negative consequences.

This bias people have for natural vs synthetic substances appears to be very common and is hypothesised by Meier et al (2019) as a product of a long evolutionary process in which ancestors were dependent on nature for survival. Natural products have become associated with purity and synthetic products with human contamination and consequently in the world of marketing the effects of this narrative have come to be well known (Meier et al, 2019). What is interesting here is not that Joanna has this particular preference, it is in the way she imbues her drug use and by extension herself with the purity implied by the concept of nature when she identifies as 'a woman who gardens'. In this way she rejects the patriarchal dominant cultural narrative and tells an alternative story of drug use that conjures images of feminine nurturing and growth, as opposed to the neglect and decay that is usually associated with women who use drugs (Kasmin, 2019). In challenging this stereotype, Joanna relies upon an interpretation of nature that is perceived as pure and unspoiled. The danger of employing this narrative device is that nature is also widely regarded as wild and untamed and in need of domestication. She proceeds nonetheless with a tone of righteous indignation; that the use of 'natural' plants for healing purposes has been disrupted by 'cultural' policies of punitive prohibition is a clear source of injustice for Joanna. Ironically, in seeking to disconnect from a Western perspective on drug use through talk of other cultures, Joanna goes on to reproduce its most enduring binary opposition; that of nature and culture. The nature/culture dichotomy has long been the subject of anthropological critique (Boyd, 2004). The emphasis on female roles and behaviours as 'natural', for example in childbirth and domestic labour and the male roles on the other hand as 'cultural' and located in the public sphere, are far from a universal structure. Rather, these oppositional categories represent but one way of looking at the world, a way that is distinctly Western (Boyd, 2004).

The nature/culture dichotomy which Joanna perpetuates in order to manage stigma is perceived as the common factor that grounds the parallel oppression of women and nature alike (Forbes and Sells, 1997). Women and nature are both positioned by male ideology as fundamentally inferior (Salmen and Dhent, 2020) and ecofeminists focus on disrupting hegemonic masculinity through the reproduction of hierarchical dualism. However, in emphasising the connections between women and nature, ecofeminism has been criticised as essentialist and elitist. Informed by post-structural thinking, Gough and Whitehouse (2018) are critical of the move to align the categories of women and nature as a mode of empowerment, suggesting this merely reproduces the binary thinking which erases complexity.

Nature is often endowed with maternal symbolism and women's role in reproduction explains in part why women are often animalised and portrayed as closer to nature (Salmen and Dhent, 2020). According to Teodorescu (2017), the women/nature connection is what underpins dominant western constructions of 'good' motherhood and the associations of nature as nurturing and benevolent are what erases ambivalent meanings of motherhood. It is also argued that the social construction of women as closer than men to nature and therefore animals is what underpins what Salmen and Dhent (2020) call 'benevolent sexism'. Discourses which connect women and nature, are often instrumental in the dehumanisation of women and should therefore be viewed in relation to a context of male dominance.

It should be noted that the connection of women and nature is itself a stereotype, albeit one which colours them in a subjectively positive way- an assertion supported by research which suggests that women who align themselves with nature were more likeable than women who did not (Salmen and Dhent, 2020). Joanna thus swaps one stereotype for another in a bid to manage her identity and others' perceptions of risk on which stigma is so often based (Stengel et al, 2014).

The notion of strategic essentialism helps us to understand Joanna's positioning as 'a woman who gardens' insofar as she attributes inherent qualities to the highly contested categories of 'woman' and 'nature' respectively in order to achieve a specific aim. Spivak (1990, as cited in Voronka, 2016) points to both the potential benefits and dangers of naturalising one's identity. While it can be advantageous it is also be problematic; in treating identities as given universal facts the processes of domination become obscured. In similar vein, Voronka, (2016) suggests that when we rely on strategic essentialism to authorise lived experience, we risk erasing important differences between those that might be 'boxed' with the same identity.

Joanna's primary concern is thus with challenging perceptions of cannabis as harmful and she does this indirectly by comparing it to another herbal substance. Having cannabis oil in her tea one day, lemon balm the next. While seemingly innocuous, this last statement works rather effectively to challenge stereotypical constructions of the female drug user; it is quite difficult to entertain notions of depravity in the context of partaking in a socially approved ritual as mundane as drinking a cup of tea. She also demonstrates a level of control over her drug use, in implying a relaxed and unhurried mode of consumption.

Living rurally on a croft, Joanna has access to narrative resources about the environment that perhaps women living in densely overpopulated cities do not on account of her having a different, more visceral relationship with the land. Growing and harvesting her own food, herbs and flowers, cannabis and mushrooms are viewed simply an extension of this and their use synonymous with living in harmony with Mother Nature. In a reflexive narrative of the gendering of psychedelic discourse, 'consciousness researcher' Tolbert (2003) refers to 'gardening' euphemistically when talking to other women about the cultivation of prohibited plants, suggesting this is a narrative resource that is used by other privileged women as a form of etiquette.

Indeed, she is not the only woman in the present study to imbue her drug use with an ecological sensibility (Gaard, 1993). Claire also draws upon this narrative resource in telling her story of magic mushrooms, claiming it her 'birth right to ingest the fruits of the Earth'. Shirley too, makes a clear distinction between natural substances and pharmaceutical drugs and this dichotomy is laid as the foundation upon which the rest of her narrative is constructed. In situating drug use in the context of a lifestyle that includes a plant-based diet and an environmental awareness, such narratives act to unsettle taken for granted assumptions about health and personal responsibility. Joanna practices alternative and holistic therapies such as massage and Reiki⁶, an Eastern based energy medicine, which in part explains her view of the world and by extension the lens through which she is able to tell her story. She uses to her advantage the knowledge gained from her professional background concerning the therapeutic use of psychoactive plants, at one-point drawing upon the authority of science when she says '*as research shows*'. Coupled this with is an awareness of different cultural norms and the

⁶ See systematic review of the therapeutic effects of Reiki from Vandervaart et al (2009) for background information

result is that she speaks with a voice of authority, which is convincing in giving the impression of a responsible and educated woman who uses drugs.

Joanna's story can be viewed as an expression of the wise woman archetype (Gladstar, 1993). Prior to the rise of allopathic medicine, wise women were the 'centre and source' of healing within communities, growing plants and making herbal preparations. Wise women were feared by religious patriarchal institutions and consequently persecuted in large numbers during medieval 'witchhunts' (Szasz, 2003). Thus, the art of healing was replaced by the science of medicine, and with this shift, came a disconnection from feminine sources of healing. In forgetting about plant medicine women also lost the urge to heal themselves, instead relying on external, masculine structures. However the old knowledge of herbalism is undergoing a resurgence and as Gladstar suggests '*some women simply remember how to find it buried in the fertile soil of the hearts*' (Gladstar, 1993:21). Joanna's small story is a challenge to power; it challenges the dominance of malestream medicine through the radical assertion that she can and should be allowed to heal herself by whatever means necessary.

This sense of agency she seeks is impressed upon the listener as she brings her story to a close with the repeated use of first-person statements. Where she begins from the position of speaking in a general sense for a group 'we, as women are judged more harshly', she ends with a series of powerful statements about her experience in the present moment; 'I feel strongly', 'I am annoyed'. She retains this agentic position until the end whilst orienting towards an imagined future; '*I wish I could grow cannabis*' and '*I would like...*'. It has been suggested that drug narratives function in anticipation of a future relationship to drugs (Jarvinen and Ravn, 2015). Joanna stays faithful to her proposition that the problem lies with a toxic (masculine) culture and it is from here that her story projects into the future a hopeful vision of a society in which her own feminine 'connection with plants' is both allowed and accepted. Through this, she reframes the risks of her drug use in terms of the illegality and criminality of it and less about the dangers of consuming the substances in and of themselves.

A little pick me up - *Freda*

*The last Class A drugs I had was some coke. At a wedding. In fact, it was a total fuck up. This is a **hilarious** story. So, we got a gram of coke and had a couple of lines each. Fantastic. I actually used to hate coke because I thought it was a total kind of snob drug. You know? But as I have grown older, I actually quite like it for*

social situations like weddings, stuff like that. You have been eating and drinking all day and you just need a little pick me up. MDMA is going to completely string you out. But cocaine is just going to straighten you up, make you chat loads and dance a bit more. So a couple of lines of coke are brilliant. Anyway, we still had a couple of lines left over in a wrap and I was staying at my dad's. I took it out of my zip wallet and into the other bit of the wallet because I didn't want it to be there when I went in for change. But the next day, I was home and on the phone to the working tax credit people, I was trying to sort something out, and I had put it on speakerphone because they left me waiting, so bla bla bla I started looking for this wrap of coke. I have got this little box where I keep things, it has got I don't know maybe three dabs of MDMA, some magic mushrooms, and I was going to put my coke in there for a special occasion. But I couldn't find it anywhere! And I was like oh shit man. Looking and looking. Searching and searching. So I lean over my phone and say..man I have got to find it...I can't leave a gram of coke with kids around! And at that point, the music just stopped and I heard this silence. Either I had just been cut off or the person on the other end had thought that was hilarious, and just hung up. But I never did find the coke.'

There is much to explore within this small story from Freda. To begin, I wish to draw attention to how she places emphasis on *hilarious*. Freda clearly has access to narrative resources that come from being raised by middle-class parents and is consequently able to tell stories in such a manner as to portray middle-class respectability. However, the interesting thing is that she makes references to living a life that is more working-class, for example by placing the context of her story within a phone-call to the working tax credits agency. In doing so she makes a double statement about her social positioning. The first is that she is within the qualifying bracket to receive this benefit, locating herself in a low-income bracket, which at the same time is a denial of middle-class values which she affirms by stating '*I always hated cocaine because I thought it was a snob drug*'. At the same time she locates herself as a working mother, providing a legitimate source of income, suggesting there is a limit to how low she is willing to take the perception of herself in rejecting the values of the middle classes and other perceptions of her as privileged.

This appears to be a recurring theme within Freda's larger narrative and might be explained by her having been privately educated. Just as Megan⁷ is acutely aware of how others judge her as being too 'easy' and shapes her story accordingly, Freda anticipates that others will see her as having had it too easy. Indeed, a similar phenomenon has been reported in relation to middle and upper class students who have a tendency to present socioeconomically downward versions of the self in order to establish what Regas (2016) calls 'struggle cred'. Students actively try to negate aspects of privilege in order to align with a more marginalised ethos and such individuals '*may seek to ascend the class ladder in a structural sense while clinging to cultural or perceptual markers of lower class status*' (Regas, 2016:16). It is suggested that this is a form of boundary work which occurs due to the lack of morality associated with privilege. In her small story, Freda is actively performing class when she troubles potential perceptions of privilege by simultaneously performing and rejecting it. For example, later on in her interview she says '*We are not like other parents, we are chaotic. We don't have loads of money and this could be blamed on our use of cannabis, which would then be used to stigmatise us*'. But then she quickly follows this with an indignant defence that betrays a confidence bestowed by the privileged position that she goes to great lengths to reject: '*Can you imagine? I would just take it to the papers*'.

Laudably, Freda wishes to utilise her professional identity to challenge the stereotypical perception of drug users as forming the 'dregs of society'. She is keenly aware of the risks involved in exposing herself to do so, but she is equally aware of her capacity to defend from any subsequent attack on her ability to parent. So much so that she would be willing to bring it to the public attention. As Charrad (2010) suggests:

'It is the absence as well as presence of channels for communication with power holders at different institutional levels that define the life chances of women and their (in) ability to overcome structural obstacles to make their voices heard in order to assert themselves as full citizens of their societies. (Charrad, 2010: 518).

As a professional academic, not only does Freda have access to the appropriate channels for communicating with power, she also has access to a richer pool of narrative resources which she draws upon here to displace the dominant narrative of risk that usually permeate stories of drug use and parenting. That Freda's parenting capacity is not routinely subject to scrutiny is

⁷ Megan is another participant in the study whose defensive reaction to being approached to take part in the study are explored in the chapter 'Accessing and Engaging'

clear from the unapologetic tone of her small story. Indeed, the story itself is about losing a quantity of cocaine in a space which is shared with young children and then ‘accidentally’ announcing this fact to a government agency. The lack of shame and the framing of this event as highly amusing is significant insofar as Freda is able to tell such stories in exchange for laughter, boldly navigating a terrain which many others would tread more fearfully. We can learn a lot about Freda’s positionality and her access to narrative resources through imagining the different expectations held by other, less privileged women if they told the same story.

Freda’s story thus works to construct her identity as a parent who uses drugs unashamedly. At the same time it manages others potential perceptions of her as being overly privileged, while carefully negotiating this territory in order to avoid the stigma of being perceived as something which is equally undesirable, being poor. Her agency is exercised in this story through resisting traditional definitions of social class, ‘I am neither this nor that’, which suggests in Freda a level of awareness of how social status is performed in interaction and how this can be used to her advantage in managing the multiple stigmas experienced by women who use drugs.

In conducting DNA, Frank (2010) suggests that we think about who cannot use similar narrative resources to the same effect. Research by Chandler et al (2014) analyses the ‘mother’s little helper’ narrative in contrasting accounts of methadone and benzodiazepines, in a cohort of 19 drug dependent post -natal parents in the UK. In contrast to the construction of methadone as stigmatising and wholly consistent with the ‘addict identity’ (Radcliffe and Stevens, 2008), benzo use was not stigmatised the same way and framed in highly functional terms; it helps them to get going and keep going, it helps them to manage anxiety and so parent more effectively, and it is in this way that the ‘mother’s little helper’ narrative works to legitimise continued use.

The fact that men cannot use these narrative resources to achieve the same effects, illustrated by the heading ‘mothers’ little helper: fathers ruin’ is evidenced when male parents tried to stress the functionality of their drug use in similar fashion. Far from being greeted with the same cultural acceptance, men are confronted with rejection which is reflected in the greater difficulty they faced in obtaining prescriptions for benzos. Chandler et al, (2014) point out that it is likely that local or cultural contexts will shape the types of narratives expressed and further qualitative research is needed. Most certainly the particular context of this study will have influenced it in significant ways, as the parents were under the watchful eye of services and

their parenting capacity under intense scrutiny. Thus, it is hardly surprising that parents stress the way in which benzos improved this aspect of their lives.

Describing cocaine as a ‘little pick me up’ is indicative of a classical drug use narrative employed widely by white middle-class women that signals conformity to society’s gendered ideals (Campbell, 2000; Miller and Carbone-Lopez, 2015). This is a variation on the ‘mothers’ little helper’ narrative and it is clear that such narrative resources have a strongly gendered aspect. Stressing functionality and the way it helps with fulfilling of gender-based roles is a common way of managing the stigma of all illicit drug use. That said, there is quite a difference in needing drugs to parent and needing drugs to party; they represent transgression of different aspects of normative femininity and arguably the former invites greater vilification. Consequently, it is likely these narrative resources will be adopted by women in different social locations. The gendered role expectation which is perceived by others to be potentially threatened by the drug use is foregrounded in such narratives. When Freda’s story is viewed from this perspective, we get a hint of how she is expected to perform not within the home but in the public sphere.

It is unclear whether Freda knows that her story could be read as a performance of privilege. Structural advantage is generally deemed invisible, and as Barbara Flagg (2005) suggests ‘*whiteness does not acknowledge either its own privilege or the material and sociocultural mechanisms by which that privilege is protected*’ (Flagg, 2005:6). In similar vein Peggy McIntosh (2007) argues that although many women are very conscious about male privilege, they are often ‘*conditioned into oblivion*’ regarding their own white privilege. McIntosh uses the concept of an invisible backpack to detail the numerous privileges that white people take for granted. Amongst this extensive list of privileges, McIntosh points out that she can ‘*criticise the government and its policies and behaviour without being seen as a cultural outsider*’ (McIntosh, 2007: 4). It was this same confidence in Freda that alerted me to the working of class privilege in her story, and it was only through thinking more deeply about this that the influence of whiteness gained clarity.

For Campbell (2000), becoming aware of the gendered and racialized nature of discourses of women who use drugs is fundamental to understanding the governing mentalities which have ultimately made drug policy a matter of social justice. Freda’s story is shaped by her whiteness but not determined by it. Twenty of the twenty-one women I interviewed in this study are white yet relatively few of them employed the ‘little pick me up’ as a narrative resource. An

intersectional lens is thus vital in understanding the way whiteness and other structural privileges help to structure the narratives of women who use drugs.

Similarities and Differences

In many ways, the stories from Joanna and Freda are quite different. Joanna's is more serious in tone, there is a sense of desiring to be understood and accepted. On the contrary Freda's story is told to elicit humour and demonstrates that she requires neither of these things. Where Joanna is noticeably defensive in her mannerism Freda comes across as self-assured. In a later section on the circulation of women's stories I determine what these differences may mean, for now I seek to highlight the important similarities between them that might otherwise pass by unnoticed.

In telling these particular stories, both Joanna and Freda utilise narrative resources developed in the context of their professions. Joanna draws confidence to reach for the goal of social justice in her story on the basis of her knowledge about other cultures and the history of Western medicine. Freda is emboldened by her knowledge about the field of drug policy and human rights and her resulting ability to defend from attacks on her style of parenting.

Women in captive populations are generally deemed to have little or no control to resist structural stigmatisation (Stengel, 2014) and the risk perception of health and social care professionals is internalised, resulting in self-loathing and guilt. Through repeated telling of such stories within their circles of trust, both women have developed an authoritative voice with which to defend their drug use. Joanna claims a right to use drugs on the basis of her identity as a woman who gardens, while Freda's right to use drugs is more implied by her positionality. Thus in both these stories, risk discourse is being rejected and reformulated. Joanna downplays the risks of using illicit drugs by weaving her story with narrative threads of healing and nature while relocating danger in licit pharmaceutical drugs. Freda draws upon narratives of female drug use that have been associated with responsibility, control and the white middle-classes. Such narratives minimise risk through a clever use of language and by emphasising the positive and functional aspects of the drug use.

Reminded by Frank (2010) that stories can be dangerous and that they can work to connect or disconnect people and groups (Smith, 2016), I reflected upon how I felt in hearing these stories to analyse dialogically their particular effects. With Joanna, I was compelled to think and listen, to take seriously her feeling of injustice. I wondered whether there was something to her claim that women intrinsically have a special relationship with plants and nature. But that curiosity

quickly turned to concern, when I realised that by extension of the same logic, the seemingly benign category of ‘plants’ could just as easily be substituted for ‘children’. With Freda, I was amused and entertained but also quite uncomfortable, perhaps acutely aware, that hers was a story that I, as a mother who had experienced the intrusion of services, would not be able to tell. I briefly thought of the Belfast women I had met at a conference that had lost their children on account of their drug use. Women who had neither the linguistic nor the material means to perform socially acceptable identities, and I felt sad. Through Freda’s story I felt connected with these far away women, and momentarily experienced a gulf between us, an embodied dissonance, as we sat together across a table in a university café.

The stories from Joanna and Freda work on different levels to achieve similar but apparently contradictory ends; to an extent the authority with which these women speak and defend their right to use drugs comes at the expense of reinforcing existing discourses and structures of inequality. From the perspective of dialogical forces, the women can be seen as consciously striving for difference and change, while the manner in which they are conforming, or reproducing sameness, is largely unconscious. As Cranny-Francis et al (2003) illustrate, the business of resisting stereotypes is often fraught with difficulty and the choices women have in rejecting a particular position are usually very limited. Bridging risk research and intersectionality, Nygren et al (2015) suggest that:

‘To do risk is to act in the knowledge that something unwanted might happen and at the moment one acts to pass according to the hegemonic norm to avoid the unwanted, one does risk as well as reproducing the systems of power, that is, gender, sexuality, ethnicity, class, and age.’ (Nygren et al, 2015:4).

These authors draw parallels between the doing of gender and the doing of risk, suggesting the ways that risk is constructed in every day interaction cannot be considered separate from the dominant structures of power. The cost of Joanna and Freda’s rejection of the dominant discourse of risk, which underpins the stigmatisation of women who use drugs (Stengel et al, 2014) is the reproduction of an essentialist discourse of gender, class and white privilege.

DNA underscores the local and contextual nature of stories and identity work and so final consideration is given to the ways in which I may have influenced the ‘artful presentation’ of these stories. I assume that I was not perceived as a speaker of risk discourse as I had made no effort to couch our discussion within that particular framework, even though it is common practice to do so. On the contrary I had made it clear I was interested in the good and bad

aspects of their experience. Thus in rejecting this cultural narrative of risk, Joanna and Freda were addressing an audience beyond the immediate social context of the interview itself.

Respectability Narratives

It has been consistently demonstrated across the literature on gender and substance use that in order to minimise negative judgement, both genders must perform the act of intoxication within the boundaries of social acceptability and that *'young women, in particular, are faced with contradictory demands, such as being expected to be heterosexually attractive, free and empowered, but without becoming 'unrespectable'* (Frank et al, 2020:1). Campbell (2000) uses the concept of 'gender failure' to describe the demonization of women who are unable to perform, both socially and psychologically, to the standards of normative femininity, a practice which is most evident in relation to parents and pregnant women who use drugs (as cited in Stengel, 2014).

In this section, I interrogate three different stories which perform social acceptability and analyse them through the lens of DNA, which suggests approaching analysis with a series of questions (Frank, 2010. Smith, 2016). In thinking about positioning and resource questions in particular, I suggest there are several cultural narratives in play which are used by the women, whom are all partners and mothers, to construct an identity of a women that uses drugs but is still worthy of respect. Adopting a stereotypical femininity helps to combat stigma, particularly that which comes from the male gaze, but this places them in a troubled relationship to discourses of aging and drug use and female passivity which construct women who use drugs as pathological in relationship. In striving for respectability through the performance of normative femininity, the women here are thus presented with the additional narrative task of maintaining respectability in the eyes of other women through the balancing of autonomy and conformity.

Louisa - That, is just not me

I am getting that boring now I don't know whether I will take another line of coke again. I have had lots of opportunities lately, and I just say no. And the people that have offered have been like what do you mean, no?! But you know, I like a drink, I like a wee vodka. Sometimes I am on nights out and I just say look I've had enough and go away home. This has happened more and more lately, I think it just an age thing. I get really tired. So I order a diet coke and I phone a taxi. The thought of

sitting up wired all night just doesn't interest me. I have things to be getting on with. I can't afford to be under the duvet for two days. But you know, I think the way it all happened is the way it had to happen. And I wouldn't change it. I see people who were sticking in at school, bla, bla, bla, and a lot of them are actual junkies now. Everybody is different, but my personality....I had to go wild, get wired and block out two whole years of my life. Two whole years that I will never get back....in order to be the person that I am today. I had to sicken myself like that. It was formative in the long run. At the time I was an absolute train wreck of a lassie, but I was young. And I would rather be like that at that age than at this age. Because back then you have no responsibilities. But at this age you just become a joke to society. No prospects. No future. Useful for nothing. And that is just not me.

For Louisa, the theme of age runs through her interview. Note that Louisa is 30 years old; yet she opens up her story by telling me it has been a while since she last took drugs, almost a year, and that is because these days she is 'old'. Feminist scholars have long shown how the concept of aging is associated with the cultural devaluation of women in western society (Woodward, 2006). Consequently, aging is something which women are generally expected to fight (Winterich, 2007). Thus at first, Louisa's positioning seems counterintuitive; the value she places on herself appears to be demeaning in a culture which privileges the young and beautiful.

The narrative resources which Louisa uses to cast her current drug use in a more agreeable light invoke ideas of the good mother and the good wife. This patriarchal discourse is underpinned by a strong moral aspect of what women should and should not be doing and the nature of these societal expectations tend to change with age. Louisa understands this and uses it to her advantage, mobilising a narrative of age appropriateness as a way of performing social acceptability and as a way of rendering previously socially unacceptable behaviour as a natural phase of life. In striving for respectability, Louisa's negotiation does not threaten or challenge the dominant social values which relate to the place of women and girls in society (Adams and Bettis, 2003) and this allows her to pass, relatively unnoticed.

In order to bolster her position then women of a certain age who are still engaging in heavier patterns of drug use become the targets of disdain. This is evident in the manner in which Louisa ends her small story with a merciless devaluation of other women, behaviour which, according to Gosselink et al (2008) is widespread in the context the western culture of

beautyism and has a divisive effect in relationships between women. Comparing their particular mode of drug use to that of other women, is a common rhetorical device used by many of the women in the study.

Louisa's small story goes further to cast present drug use as acceptable by bringing in a historical pattern of her own that is much more shocking in comparison: *'I was a train wreck of a lassie'*. Here the sense of propriety is further achieved through the comparison of current drug use with that of a previous self. In the stories where other women are 'othered', there is little effort to excuse their behaviour, they are embarrassing, irresponsible, and undesirable. In Louisa's story where a younger-self is the counter point, such moralising judgements do not apply. Instead, the lack of control is framed within a discourse of being young and carefree and thus excusable.

There is a degree of similarity in this self -othering to other stories of redemption which are epitomised in recovery narratives in terms of leaving the shameful behaviour behind in the past. Recovery stories perform an identity which is made anew in the context of total abstinence and in such narratives, there is generally a complete break with this previous self which is associated with shameful behaviours that are put down to an all-encompassing state of disease. For example it is suggested that women defend from stigma using 'that's not me anymore' narratives which assist in the construction of replacement selves that allow them to dissociate from a demonized drug-using identity (Gunn et al, 2018). For Louisa however, the story of getting older and wiser allows her to continue on with the use of drugs whilst achieving a sense of redemption that does not come at the cost of a total break with the past.

Although Louisa actively colours the past to make her present life choices seem less exotic, she does this without resorting to self -condemnation. In fact, she goes a step further in defending her past behaviour by framing the chaotic period of drug use as formative: *'I had to go wild, get wired and lose two years of my life'*. This bestows upon her a certain authority to speak about these things as a person who has taken drug use to extreme levels and come through the other side without conceding that her identity has been spoiled. Through this Louisa accomplishes two important goals in her identity work; she is drug experienced but at the same time responsible and respectable. In drawing upon the dominant discourses of aging and femininity Louisa positions as responsible and mature, while effectively defending from the stigma of transgressing moral boundaries as a mother who uses drugs.

Following Frank's (2010) suggestion that analysts might consider what allows narrators to tell their story, it struck me that in many ways Louisa's appearance is stereotypically feminine. She is slim with large breasts, with long blonde hair and large bright blue eyes; she is strikingly pretty. There are no obvious signs of an aging female body and I suspect it is the lack of blemish in her physical form which allows her to narratively disconnect from the category of youth with relative ease. Embodying the standards of the 'feminine ideal', Louisa can adopt this subject positioning of 'old' to exaggerate the depth of her experience without jeopardising her desirability. Normative femininity is not static, it is constantly being defined and redefined in the course of interaction and one of the ways this is achieved is through compliance, negotiation or resistance to the norms of beauty (Winterich, 2007). Louisa's capacity to comply with the dominant cultural standards of beauty allows her to use this narrative resource of aging in her small story to perform an identity of a women who uses drugs that is experienced but not 'used up'.

By stating clearly at the very beginning of the interview that her reasons for using cocaine are to '*heighten sexual arousal*', Louisa signals clearly and provocatively that she is also open to challenging the normative expectations of gender. It is telling that some women can use the enjoyment of better sex as a justification for using drugs while others cannot. This is seldom heard, for example, from women in prison or in other therapeutic based contexts who tend to downplay the pleasurable aspects of illicit drug use, emphasising instead the relieving of pain (Ettorre, 2004).

It is common for stories and texts to contain both feminist and patriarchal discourses and this is a reflection of the complexity and multiplicity of subjectivity (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003). Louisa's positioning strategies to protect from being seen as an undesirable partner and poor mother require a complex negotiation of other subject positions. Specifically, her framing of drug use and intimate relationships might invite perceptions from other women of a submissive femininity, suggested by the manner in which she goes out of her way to make her drug use more palatable for her partner by prioritising his needs, and foregoing the social pleasure enjoyed on cocaine by women like Aimee⁸. She pre-empts any potential questioning of her autonomy by performing an exaggerated form of agency in the beginning with a running series of first-person statements, '*I have had opportunities, I have just said no, I just order a diet coke, and then I just phone a taxi and go home*' and in doing so stresses that the decision to bow out

⁸ Aimee is another participant in the study whose story was presented and analysed in the circles of trust.

from the party scene in which she was formerly engaged is entirely her own. Through this small story, the manner in which anticipations of negative judgement shape the narratives of women who use drugs becomes apparent.

Keeping it nice - Rachel

The times I have taken mushrooms I have really, really enjoyed. I haven't drank a lot because I haven't wanted to. But it has all been very nice, very social. Fun. You know kind of like slightly cheeky, playing around with other people. A wee bit sparkly round the edges. All in all, just a really nice experience. And I don't want to have alcohol in that space. I want to keep it clean. And fun. Like, if I wasn't under the influence this would just be silly. Before Freya was born our friends were getting hand fasted in Rosslyn at Beltane. A bunch of us were camping. Most people had gone to bed but a few of us were still awake and me and Mike were sitting round the fire. Mike isn't into mushrooms, he doesn't like it, it makes him feel sick. I had had just enough to in that kind of nice place. I was having so much fun. We were throwing flour, cooking flour onto the fire which creates a really nice effect. I was just loving it! Then we went a walk into the woods and there was lots of nettles, and they were totally....alive! Like chatting! I hadn't taken a lot of psychedelics, but it was so lovely. I guess it's that classic pairing of psychedelics in nature. It gave me such a warm loving feeling. A happy space. It felt very playful, but very innocent.

In the beginning of her story Rachel juxtaposes her use of mushrooms with the use of alcohol. She describes the times on mushrooms as times she has really, really enjoyed, full of 'fun'. That alcohol is not allowed in that space suggests that she has placed a boundary of acceptability on her conduct. Emphatically drawing the line at alcohol which is implied as dirty in relation by describing her chosen substance as 'very clean'. She associates the former with a loss of control and the latter with a controlled exploration of consciousness.

The repeated use of the words 'nice' and 'lovely' suggests that Rachel achieves social acceptability through the deployment of narrative resources which allow her to perform

stereotypical femininity. When Rachel finishes the story by stating *'It felt very playful, but very innocent'* she is engaged, like many of the women, in the process of constructing a subjectivity that is fraught with tension. The challenge here is the one which all women face in speaking of illicit pleasure in a context in which it has been thoroughly demonised and associated with destruction. However the pleasure Rachel speaks of is one which is on the contrary, quite creative. She prefixes her description of the joy and the fun with *'If I wasn't under the influence then this would just be silly'* suggesting the mushrooms give her permission to indulge in a playful almost childlike carefree frivolity that is otherwise lacking in the context of her day-to-day life as a wife, mother and service manager.

Research demonstrates that similar claims of a moral gendered self are made by other women who use drugs who must also grapple with the contradictory discourses of women's drug use as immoral and irresponsible (Miller and Carbone-Lopez, 2015: Klee, 1998). Such identity work takes the form of stories which stress how the drug use encourages the fulfilment of feminine ideals, as in the claims that amphetamine use makes for better mothering and housekeeping. This in part, explains why many women's stories of drug use 'coalesce' around themes of motherhood, domestic duty and beauty. Women's accounts serve to position them as gendered actors in culturally acceptable ways in the face of engaging in a highly stigmatised activity:

'Women's gendered narratives of self and drug use were responses to the specific norms they were held accountable to by virtue of their gender, race, class and place positioning'
(Miller and Carbone-Lopez, 2015:7)

Indeed, these authors recognise the context of incarceration in their study may have influenced the women towards such stories, on account of their especially troubled relationship with gendered expectations as women caught within the criminal justice system. Rachel must also narrate her illicit drug use in the context of these cultural discourses which threaten to position her as immoral. However the options she has available to her are different in accordance with her relatively privileged position. As a softly-spoken married working mother, Rachel embodies the feminine ideal and she actively performs this protective femininity in her storytelling through her performative expression. This is evident in her specific word choices, her intonations and subjective appraisal of the experience as nice and clean, and innocent, which stands to counter the construction of women who use drugs as having polluted bodies and soiled identities (Manning, 2013).

The lesser influence of gendered norms in shaping the stories across the present sample are thus perhaps explained by the differences in place and positionality: in the prison study redressing a problematic relationship with gender was more pronounced, and perhaps in the context of these interviews where stigma was less a feature of the environment, such defences were not deemed as important. This is one example of how hidden and captive populations might do gender differently in their narratives of drug use, despite coming from similar backgrounds in all other respects.

Marie - myself, this wee girlie

This was before my husband, this was with another guy, and actually, I was engaged to him. This was the person I started going out clubbing with. Taking MDMA. He was the first person. I had used other drugs beforehand. I was using cannabis and speed before I went to college. In my heady days where I grew up. We had nothing to do, it was a rural town. Apart from drink and use substances. I was drinking quite early from about fourteen. Smoking from thirteen. And I though, quite late getting to cannabis..eighteen. Speed was before that. And by the time I was down in Newcastle where I met my partner at the time, we went out to a club to see Sasha, to one of his nights. And we went out with a pal of his who was this local character/dealer. Everybody's friend type of thing. And he said he would get me some speed. But, by the time he remembered he was supposed to get me some, he was completely off his nut. And everybody was going to be in a different space to me. My partner had got a pill off this guy. So unbeknownst to him I went and scored. Off a bouncer! (laughter) You know, I'm not daft, I'm a quick study and I had got the impression that bouncers were often connected to how the drugs got in. And I though, if I just go and ask myself, this wee girlie, I might get away with it. And I did. I went up and asked this big black burly bouncer who stood on the stairs, where nobody else was there, have you got any ecstasy? And honestly his face, he couldn't believe it! Like, what! Are you for real? But after a moment he just said, wait there, and he went down stairs. And for a moment I was like oh no what have you done!? But then he reappeared and he brought a dealer with him. I put on my strongest Scottish accent, like a wee girlie Scottish accent. Inside I was shitting myself, sorry for swearing, but I was, I was bricking it. But I just gave him

the money and went thank you, thank you! And ran off. My boyfriend was worried because he couldn't find me for a bit, and when I showed him what I had got, he almost freaked!

In the beginning of this small story Marie lays the groundwork to give me the impression that she is 'in-the-know' about a lot of different drugs. This identity work makes sense from the point of view of her professional background which is built in part on a particular lived experience and authority to speak about drug use.

Like Louisa, Marie's illicit drug use primarily takes place within the context of romantic relationships. While this could be perceived as a passive form of femininity, in this story Marie is actively challenging the normative expectations of gender by taking the initiative to source her own drugs. In doing so she is aware of the dangers and she mitigates these potential dangers by performing a sweet and innocent femininity. The effect of this story is that one is left with the impression that in her experience, obtaining drugs is usually the province of males, and she signals this through emphasising both the shock and surprise of the dealer and boyfriend and indeed herself when she exclaims '*oh no what have you done?!*'. Almost instinctively Marie launches a kind of charm offensive with the dealer as a way to protect herself, suggesting she understands the unwritten rules and is highly perceptive of others and how best to position to achieve her goals, which in this case was the procurement of drugs. This small story is about Marie pushing the boundaries of femininity whilst exploring the boundaries of 'pushing'.

Her performative skills were evident in the atmosphere of suspense which she created in narrating the moment she was waiting on the bouncer to return. She also talks about '*putting on her strongest Scottish accent*', which in that context would have marked her as an outsider and as such in the event that her behaviour was met with disapproval, she would be well positioned to occupy a place of ignorance in defence.

This strategic performance of stereotypical femininity and innocence in 'myself, this wee girlie' announces that Marie was aware that her behaviour was pushing the boundaries of acceptability, and yet, being a self-confessed 'quick study' she must also have intuited that the environment was a safe-space in which to challenge these gendered norms that govern drug use and related behaviour. Indeed, an ethnography of how women viewed their own participation in club scenes conducted by Fiona Hutton (2004) suggests that certain clubs are particularly fertile spaces for the negotiation of a femininity that is more empowered:

'The negotiation of femininity and sexuality in club spaces is highlighted as problematic for the women concerned. In constructing identities within club spaces however, a positive femininity can be produced in opposition to traditional, passive images of femininity and sexuality.' (Hutton, 2004: 223)

The problematic negotiation she refers to is the attempt of many of her female clubbers to subvert the norms of femininity against the prevailing sexist attitudes of male clubbers, DJ's and promoters (Moore, 2006). Hutton suggest that in the context of 'underground' club spaces as opposed to those constructed as more mainstream, women are at greater freedom to express their individuality and sexuality without the intrusion of negative attitudes from male clubbers.

The main event of Marie's story takes place within the context of this underground club scene, and Marie goes out of her way to communicate this through naming the particular DJ. As this scene is associated with dance music connoisseurs, I took this namedropping as a deliberate performance of an authoritative and experienced drug user identity and her seeking of my recognition as an attempt to decipher my relative positioning in relation to this mainstream/underground binary, which would in turn have affected my ability to appreciate the nuance of her story. Through this exchange I became aware of how Marie's story was actively constructing group boundaries (Smith, 2016).

Similarities and differences

In the small stories presented above, all three women engage in a form of othering, an active demonization of other drugs, other women or drug-using behaviours. This is a deliberate strategy to deflect stigma and to create a narrative that not all women who use drugs are morally bankrupt individuals (Carbone – Lopez and Miller, 2015). As well as casting present drug use as acceptable in relation to other women's drug-use, in Louisa's story, there is another object being 'othered' and that is a previous version of herself.

Male partners are in the background of each of these stories. In assessing the function of these stories within this context, they each perform an 'ideal' intimate relationship, where freedom and autonomy are balanced with dependence and constraint. For example, in negotiating the freedom to use drugs within the context of her intimate relationship, Marie asserts her authority by going off on her own and sourcing the drugs by herself, much to her boyfriend's surprise. She balances out this powerful statement of autonomy by adopting a more deferential position when she hands over the tablets to be checked over by her partner before consuming them. It

is unclear whether this represents a gesture of appeasement or a seeking of recognition for her triumph. Either way I am left with the impression that she is considerate of her partners concerns but does not give up her own desires in the process. This story can therefore be seen as an attempt to resist the dominant narrative of women who use drugs as completely at the mercy of their male counterparts. She plays an active role in conveying a sense of going against the grain. Yet hers is a resistance constrained by boundaries, in so far as she remains encased within a man's world. According to Adams and Bettis, '*when women enter a masculine discourse and assume masculine signifiers, mainstream society is threatened, and when a woman steps over the boundaries of acceptable feminine behaviour, she is typically viewed as gender deviant*' (Adams and Bettis 2003: 88). Marie's story challenges the stereotype of women who use drugs as helpless passive victims, but she does not over-emphasise agency in the process. It is this delicate balance which allows her to perform an identity of idealised femininity and resist notions of double deviance (Manning, 2013). '*Myself, this wee girlie*', would not have been possible or believable had the pendulum swung too far in either direction. Marie describes playfully, yet strategically, assuming a position of innocence and vulnerability in order to manage the risks of buying illegal drugs, yet unlike Rachel she refrains from using this in her present 'talk-in-interaction', suggesting she did not want me to perceive her as such. In fact, her vocal intonation of 'this wee girlie' had a slightly mocking, irreverent tone and I interpreted this as an attempt to 'hold her own' in the context of an interview with a feminist drugs researcher (Frank, 2010).

Rachel stays true to her motto of 'keeping it nice', subtly commanding respect in her story by gently stating that she continues to use the mushrooms even though her husband doesn't like it. Yet at the same time she has got to emphasise never losing control. Measham (2002) describes the differing ways that men and women describe their drug use to give examples of the gendering of drug cultures. While men tend to brag and make light about excessive intoxication in order to perform masculinity, such talk jeopardises the performance of femininity for women, who are more likely to speak about in terms of staying in control and minimising negative consequences. Indeed, the talk of Rachel and a number of women in the present study can be viewed as consistent with this view.

Purposeful hyper-femininity is described elsewhere in this study by Charmaine, as a strategy employed to escape arrest from the police. This form of gendered role play is also in evidence in a recent hidden population study conducted in France by Perrin et al (2020) where a cohort

of socially included women describe accentuating their femininity in their dealings with authorities. This allows them to remain undetected and unpunished in the context where rigid stereotypes and images of stigmatised figures of women who use drugs prevail. According to Nancy Campbell, in ascribing increasing rates of addiction in women to social change in familial roles and in sexual relationships, women centred treatment is thus conceptualised as ‘a training ground for heteronormative behaviour and cultural conservatism’ (Campbell, 2000: 23). In thinking of the absence of women in treatment populations, which essentially is the research puzzle upon which this study is based, it should thus be considered that women are capable of going under the treatment radar to the extent that they already know how and when to conform to societies gendered expectations.

A recurrent finding is that women’s illicit drug use is more subject to social control than that of their male counterparts (Dahl and Sandberg, 2015). Even when engaged in the same behaviours as men, women are judged more harshly and subject to different expectations in terms of staying in control. Indeed, it is widely accepted that cultural expectations about gender shapes expectations and standards of social acceptability. In analysing the three stories above it has become clear that drug use is gendered in the sense that it is shaped by gender norms but also in that it is constitutive of gender.

Achieving a balanced form of agency has been highlighted as problematic in the study of women who use drugs (Miller-Carbone – Lopez, 2015). In each of the above stories, Louisa, Marie and Rachel can be experienced as women who are capable of ‘holding their own’ (Frank, 2010). To reiterate, holding one’s own means *‘seeking to sustain the value of one’s self or identity in response to whatever threatens to diminish that self or identity’* (Frank, 2010:33) Indeed this is a feature of all seven of these small stories. In respectability narratives, it is achieved in the context of narrating the dynamics of an intimate relationship in which the women construct themselves as individual autonomous beings but at the same time as caring considerate partners. An increasing body of research demonstrates that through drug using cultures new forms of masculinity and femininity emerge (Connell, 2005). This study highlights women’s drug talk as sites of identity work in which realistic and functional forms of femininity in the context of illicit drug use, can be brought into being.

Bakhtin’s theory of dialogism suggests that every mode of text *‘derives meaning from the degree of opposition with alternative meanings’* (Nesaria, 2015:644). This line of thinking shows how respectability narratives follow a distinct approach to identity construction in the

context of stigma and discrimination. Similar to the women in a study by Opsal (2011), respectability narratives align with conventionality and it is this relative alignment which makes them stand out from risk narratives which, on the other hand, perform a defiant and outright rejection of the dominant narrative of women who use drugs.

Lost and Found: Retrieval Narratives

Looking dialogically at the function of women's stories, very often this work involves a retrieval of that which has been lost. At times this is a complete sense of identity, as in the following story from Daisy about a particularly distressing experience on LSD. More often, retrieval narratives function to recover a sense of control over drug use after it has been lost. Indeed, this function was an aspect of the narratives of several women. Less frequently, retrieval narratives work to recover a sense of personal mastery and empowerment after becoming victimised during a drug experience. The following short story presented from Allie attempts both of these things.

'Making myself lost': Allie

There is another story I should probably tell you as well. I started making myself very vulnerable about 18 months ago taking drugs. The best times are mixed with some of the incredibly worst times as well. There was one time where I went to a party in Glasgow, went to the Subclub, then went to another party. And I ended up, my friends had left me, and I ended up coming to in this... hallway. And I thought I was in a hotel in Sheffield that I had stayed in a few months previous. I was absolutely fucked. I don't even know what drugs I had taken. I couldn't remember. And I was running around the corridors with no shoes, no bag, no phone. Looking for my hotel room. And I was trying to find the reception of this hotel, so I started knocking on people's doors. It was a block of flats like this. I was asking where is the reception, can you help me? And they were like what are you talking about this is a block of flats! I was like...what...the fuck...is going on? Then, some woman found me and took pity on me and she took me in to use the phone and phone my flat mate. And he had to come and collect me. Which was quite funny, because it was ridiculous. But at the same time I was like, that was scary. My friend was like,

no Allie I don't like to think of you making yourself vulnerable like this. Anything could have happened to you that night. (pause)

That was in May last year. There was another time as well, at the Kelburn Garden Party, the psychedelic disco one. I actually ended up meeting the boyfriend that I am currently with there. But I got lost from him and I ended up getting with this guy. And I can't remember but I think something ended up happening with him in the woods. I don't know if we slept together but something happened. I remember he was quite forceful, you know? I was lost. And those two things happened within two weeks of each other. I kept making myself lost. And really freaking out. Putting myself in really vulnerable situations. It was then I realised that no, this is not acceptable behaviour. I spoke to a friend about it who was like oh yeah that was like the time when I was in a k-hole and blah, blah, you know, normalising it and I was like NO, it's not normal! This, is not normal.'

In this small story, Allie refers to being lost repeatedly, and in two separate moments in time. In the first event, the loss of control over her drug use has resulted in her literally becoming lost. She cannot remember which drugs she has taken and is so severely intoxicated she has lost all bearings of her spatial surroundings. In a helpless state of extreme confusion, Allie has to be rescued by her flatmate, with the help of a stranger that took pity on her. In the second event, which happened two weeks later, Allie attends a music event at which she becomes lost in the woods and has a somewhat fuzzy yet frightening sexual encounter that she describes as forceful.

Hall and Moore (2008) suggest that women's excessive intoxication is linked to greater vulnerability to sexual predation, and underline the need for this to be addressed without negative judgement. However in reality victims of drug facilitated sexual assault often experience victim blaming and lack of empathy. The women are viewed by perpetrators as 'fair game' which induces in victims a deep sense of guilt and shame, particularly so when ingestion of psychoactive substances has been voluntary (Hall and Moore, 2008). Exploring the multiple intersecting factors which make women vulnerable to drug facilitated sexual assault, Prego-Meleiro et al (2020) suggest there is generally a lack of recognition of victimhood, which makes re-victimisation more likely. This small story is one which depicts Allie's realisation of victimhood in spite of a surrounding culture of normalisation. Even though it was being

downplayed by her 'friends' Allie recovered the strength to recognise the loss of control and with an emphatic NO she exclaims *'It's not normal. This, is not normal.* By the end of the short story she has found her voice and a sense of clarity that what has transpired, even if it is shared with other women, is not acceptable.

There is a strong sense of ambiguity in this story captured by the statement *'the best times are mixed with the worst times.'* On the one hand Allie finds the situation absurd and rather funny, but on the other she is appalled and frightened for her safety. Indeed, the dialogical approach to making meaning highlights that it is possible to approach monolithic constructs like death with an attitude of seriousness and humour (Nesari, 2015). Unable to reconcile these contradictory feelings, she cleverly uses the narrative device of the friends, which function to embody the opposing position. She brings in the character of a friend twice, the first time it is to counter her sense of humour about the event, being the voice of reason. The second time the friend, which feels like a different one from the first, is a voice which minimises the danger. From a Bakhtinian perspective of multi-vocality (Bakhtin, 1981: Hermans, 2001) the friends could be said to symbolise the opposing and apparently contradictory voices which Allie speaks about her recent drug experiences.

That Allie sees herself as both victim and villain can be deciphered from the manner in which she describes her predicament. *'I kept making myself lost'* is a curious statement indeed, for the act of getting lost is usually unintended. Perhaps anticipating stigma, Allie imposes a negative self-judgement at the end, getting in there first to deem her behaviour unacceptable. At this point she is reproducing the cultural narrative of questionable responsibility, and it is in this way she exists as the force behind the change in her behaviour and retains a sense of autonomy and self-direction.

Allie foregrounds her autonomy in her imaginary dialogue with the friend, who acts as the point from which to mobilise her relative defence. Indeed, stories often function to allow their narrators an opportunity to adopt a moral high ground (Ochs, 2004). By putting the friend down, who perhaps was trying to make her feel better about the situation by occupying the same space, she gains the leverage to lift herself further up, thus restoring a sense of self-respect in the face of a series of events which have the potential to generate a toxic and disempowering form of shame.

As was evident in respectability narratives, women's attempts to construct a non-stigmatised identity frequently involves the stigmatisation of other women who use drugs. Negatively

casting other women, other drugs, and alcohol are narrative devices used to perform a socially acceptable drug using identity. Such narratives mobilise a defence of relativity which serves a protective function at the individual level whilst at the group level reproduce the conditions of oppression. Members of a disadvantaged group often unwittingly perpetuate or exacerbate their disadvantage by putting down others within the group (Ellemers and Barreto, 2008). However, in living within the constraints imposed upon them by the structure, women are often ‘strangled within the politics of survival’, sometimes agency; ‘*can serve to challenge the dominant norms that reproduce their lives and sometimes it can reproduce them*’ (Charrad, 2010: 518).

‘I found myself lost’ - *Daisy Clarke*

Can I tell you a story? I had a very bad trip on acid when I was twenty-one. I had been taking acid a lot. And I was in love with someone at the time, and he took lots of acid. But we were working at the time. At the festival. I was serving lukewarm drinks out of a bucket, it was horrible. Everyone was pissed and drunk. And this friend came along and gave me two drops of liquid acid. It was horrendous. I remember just feeling completely lost and trying to manoeuvre myself around the festival and people were worried about me, coming to offer help and I was just running away from them. I found myself lost and in someone’s tent. My clothes were off, and I was really disoriented. I was just kind of...confused. So my partner came. We were at the point we were breaking up as well. And I had this feeling that I was going inside. Deep inside the earth. I must have been really clenching everything. So he came and put me in the front of the truck, where we had been sleeping. He said, guard this box with your life. So I just sat there, for what felt like hours thinking it was full of cocaine and some sort of secret drug deal was going on. I became super paranoid and at the exact moment that I threw the box out of the window all the fireworks went off and I thought it was me who caused an explosion. I thought everything was on fire. That was a really intense trip. Internally. I woke up the next morning and had one white hair which had grown out of the centre of my forehead. And I felt really fucked up for a long time after that. I would just sit for hours and hours and stare into space. My friends were really worried about me. Eventually, I just packed up and left and travelled round

Spain for a bit. When I came back, I spoke to my mum's friend and I told him that I still felt really lost. Like I didn't know who I was anymore. And he said to me, well that's great. Because now you can rebuild your life, brick by brick. And him just saying that to me, it made me feel much better'

Throughout this small story Daisy Clark's positions shift back and forth from an assertive position to a more passive one. It is interesting to look at this positioning from the point of view of what might be achieved by it. For example, when stating *'this friend came along and gave me two drops of liquid acid'*, the friend is placed in the agentic position and Daisy is constructed in relation as a more submissive, although willing participant. In doing so she lessens any potential negative judgement as she gives some of the responsibility away here, and by extension her power.

This positioning is placed into reverse as she reinstates her sense of agency by *'running away from those trying to help'*. Such a move absolves others of blame and places her back in control in the story, even if the cost of that autonomy is a troubled subject positioning (Widding, 2015). To remind, subject positions can be identified by the manner in which people describe themselves and others in their stories. Building on the ideas of Wetherall (1998), Widding (2015) explains that;

'Untroubled positions are talked about as 'normal and righteous', while troubled positions are constructed as 'inappropriate, destabilized, difficult' in various types of interactions and in relation to specific orderings of power. For example, if you are part of the ruling norm in a specific context, it is possible to talk about yourself in an untroubled manner, as an ordinary and normal person and without feeling the urge to explain your position or actions (Widding, 2015: 50/51)

The manner in which Daisy's positioning appears troubled in this case, is thus evident in the way in which she must explain her actions as difficult and inappropriate, suggesting she is in the wrong for refusing help. She makes a similar move at the end of the story when she positions herself as problematic in relation to others when she says: *'my friends were really worried about me'*, but she finally resolves this by showing that she just *'packed up and left'* and sought about finding the solution to her problem of being lost.

In the statement *'I found myself lost in someone's tent'* the dialogical tension between self-as-passive and self-as-agent come together in an apparently illogical contradiction; she is the 'damsel' in the story who is lost and vulnerable in an unfamiliar space, and at the same time, the rescuer who finds herself there. That Daisy's relationship was coming to an end in this story feels significant. This suggests she was entering a period of identity transition - however she attributes this sense of being lost to the LSD. Her partner finding her naked in another tent, is a difficult event for any woman to narrate. In emphasising that she was lost and disoriented, she desires to impress that she was confused and would not intentionally have behaved in this way. Although she seems to have lost her dignity at this point, she retains a sense of control and awareness of her body when she speaks of *'really clenching everything'*. That she has experienced a symbolic death at this point is suggested her haunting depiction of feeling like she was being lowered down, deep inside the earth. Daisy describes waking up with one long white hair after this experience, a depiction of the extreme stress she has endured which also hints that some kind of wisdom has been gained. Such crises are not unusual in the context of psychedelic use at festivals, and if handled correctly, can give way to a cathartic experience of psychic reintegration (Ruane, 2015). While it appears to be a negative outcome of psychedelic use, loss of sense of self is framed as a relief from the existential suffering that is created by a rigid focus on an enduring self. It is however one which brings the task of integrating this broader perspective (Ltheby, 2017).

It was perhaps the lack of appropriate support that prevented an earlier transformation in identity for Daisy. For it is not until later on when the character of mum's friend is used to define the point at which her story of being lost becomes one of being found - or rediscovered anew. Almost sage like, he gives her permission to finally take full control over the situation and build a new life 'brick by brick'. This metaphor highlights the active role Daisy plays in constructing her post-crisis identity, but the use of the additional character conveys that this integration does not occur in isolation. By the end of the story, her power and sense of self have been retrieved and consequently there is a clear transformation in terms of how she is now seeing the situation as an opportunity filled with potential.

This story works on many levels for Daisy. Although it is a story of a terrifying experience, it constructs her as a phoenix who has risen from the ashes of a symbolic death. At the same time it positions her as somewhat privileged; her experience of crisis takes place against the bosom of a middle-class family in which there are options unavailable to other women, such as packing up and travelling around another country. She also has capital in the form of older, trusted,

more experienced drug users helping to make sense of her adverse and frightening experiences. So clearly there are structural factors and relational factors which make the narrative resources available to Daisy in telling this story of overcoming adversity. In thinking further about the narrative resources employed, Daisy's background in the creative industries perhaps explains the particularly artful presentation in this story; it is colourful and thought provoking. I explore her particularly interesting use of metaphor in greater detail on page 32, in the tools of 'good stories'.

Similarities and Differences

In the identity work that they perform, retrieval narratives are closely related to themes of rebirth and renewal which are common aspects of narrative identity work (Smith, 2016). Whether it is about losing sense of self, personal power, or control over drug use, or indeed mixture of all three, these stories work in a manner to give the woman the feeling that something important has been regained. Asking dialogical questions about the above stories highlights the ways in which this is achieved.

Both are stories of losing control and entering dangerous territory, involving compromising situations that involve a loss of bodily autonomy through intoxication with illicit substances. Allie when she offers a somewhat hazy recollection of being subject to the forceful advances of a stranger in the woods, and Daisy when she was recovered, naked and in the tent of stranger. *'I found myself lost and in someone's tent'* is very similar to Allie's statement *'I kept making myself lost'*, indicate that both of these women engage in similar narrative strategies in an attempt to retain a sense of agency in narrating situations where control over the drug use and body has been lost.

In concentrating for a moment on the narrated event, from the perspective of Norman Zinberg (1984) in drug, set and setting, there appear to be certain environmental factors which are unlikely to be conducive to a positive experience in both of these accounts. Daisy Clark's negative experience with the liquid acid is set within a context of emotional turmoil and abandonment, at a time when her relationship was coming to an end, and this abandonment was compounded by the fact she was left alone in the truck by her partner after displaying obvious distress. Allie's story can be located within a broader context of recovering from sexual violence, and she speculates whether the continuously making herself 'lost' and vulnerable was an attempt to re-enact the original trauma of her rape.

Although the immediate setting of each of these events was undesirable, aspects of the larger social context in which they are embedded appear to be more positive. In both stories the women allude to people who are worried about their behaviour, suggesting some level of social support. As mentioned in the circles of trust, Daisy Clark has a special relationship with her drug experienced parents who she feels she can turn to for advice.

In each of these retrieval narratives, there is a sense of the new and a significant drug experience which wipes away the old. The stories from Allie and Daisy Clark are thus narratives of rebirth in that they convey a sense of transformation in identity which is associated with a significant negative drug experience. While they are similar in this respect, the catalyst of the transformation is quite different. Daisy's transformation is the result of a process of feeling lost spiritually for an extended period of time following a 'bad trip' on LSD which marked the end of an intimate relationship. From this point, with the support of her drug experienced elders and a degree of financial independence, she rebuilds an identity and a sense of self. The catalyst of Allie's transformation is a frightening realisation that she is endangering her life in an attempt to rewrite the story of the past. The sense of personal power she recovers in her story is vital for her future. It will be taken forward as she writes a new chapter, one in which she continues to use drugs but in a conscious and considered way. Vowing never to be lost again.

In overcoming adversity and retrieving the lost aspects, narratives of retrieval perform an identity that is resourceful and authoritative. This will be explored further 'the agony and the ecstasy' in analysis chapter three, where I consider the women's possible motivations for narrating the bad times over the good.

Conclusion

The purpose of this chapter has been to explore what the stories of this socially included and 'hidden' group can tell us about the identity work and positioning of women who use drugs. The 'circles of trust' chapter made it clear that the women value many things in common; maintaining relationships and achieving intimacy, feeling in control of their destiny and feeling empowered, avoiding negative judgement /achieving social acceptance and feeling understood.

In chapter, I have demonstrated that this hidden population of women who use drugs in Scotland have a rich pool of narrative resources which are drawn from to tell stories about different aspects of their drug use. The seven small stories presented in represent three narrative typologies that share similar functions: *risk narratives*, *respectability narratives* and *retrieval*

narratives. Consistent with Bamberg (1997), it is recognised that the women's stories strive for more than one goal at the same time. Thus, although the narratives have been separated into three typologies as a means to pulling out and analysing these different functions, it is important to stress that such separation is to an extent artificial. In reality the different aspects of identity work are inextricably entwined and simultaneously realised. One can see the striving for respectability in risk and retrieval narratives, the reworking of risk in respectability narratives and so on.

In a challenge to the dominant paradigm of pathology and powerlessness, the seven small stories reveal a diversity in experience and also an awareness of the dominant cultural narratives of women who use drugs. Joanna tells a story about knowing people who have died from pharmaceutical drugs which reveals her anger that she is prohibited from growing plants that she feels would bring a healing benefit to her life. Freda unashamedly tells a story about taking cocaine at a wedding and then losing it at home the next day with kids around. Louisa tells a story about slowing down and becoming boring with her drug use as she gets older which shows the manner in which she looks down on other women of the same age that are still engaging in heavy use. Rachel tells a story about a time taking mushrooms with her husband and friends in the woods and how lovely and nice and playful it all was. Marie tells a story about going to a nightclub and procuring her own ecstasy much to the shock of the men around her. Allie tells a story about taking a large quantity of an unknown substance and becoming completely lost and at the mercy of strangers, on two separate and close occasions. And finally, Daisy Clark tells a story about taking acid at a festival at the time of a breakup and experiencing a bad trip which marked the beginning of an identity crisis.

Rather than purely descriptive, these small stories reveal the manner in which gender, social class and risk is actively performed by the women in the course of interaction. Small stories are embedded within talk in interaction (Clifton, 2014) and they reveal the '*discursive resources that enable speakers to talk themselves into being*' (Clifton, 2014: 100). Analysis of these performances through the lens of troubled and untroubled subject positions, can give clues about the narrators relationship to the structures of power (Widding, 2015). To this end, I have shown how narrative resources are related to the circumstances of women's life experiences in general, beyond the drug use, such as the nature of their employment and the extent to which they have experienced other cultures. For example, Joanna as a holistic therapist and gardener, is able to place emphasis on healing in her story of drug use to deflect the dominant discourses of risk. Freda who is a lawyer and academic is able to place emphasis

on social justice and exhibits a particular confidence in her ability to defend her parenting which she relates to her professional status in society. I suggest that Freda's performance can also be located in relation to more salient aspects of privilege such as whiteness and social class.

In several of the small stories there emerges the importance of place. In forming her story, Joanna draws upon her relationship to the land as a resident of a small rural community to defend her consumption of, and desire to produce, the legally prohibited cannabis sativa. In struggling to express the ethereal qualities of the DMT experience, Mary draws upon her time travelling in Egypt to capture the essence of a renewed sense of wonder. As far as knowledge of other cultures is concerned, Daisy Clarke speaks about just packing up and going to Spain in order to find herself and then coming back and feeling reborn. She has travelled extensively and has developed a capacity for self-reflection and allows her to draw from a wider range of meanings in making sense of her drug experiences, including when not to speak of them.

Through exploring the similarities and differences between the three typologies, what has become apparent is that in resisting the dominant cultural narratives of women who use drugs, the stories often serve to reify existing problematic categories about desirable and undesirable and good and bad women. The reproduction of normative femininity is a common strategy to achieve respectability and social acceptance in the face of an identity which is perceived to contradict the prescribed social norms of womanhood. Adopting subject positions that give a sense of being an acceptable human being often results in a reproduction of the social structure (Esin et al 2014). Women's accounts of drug use thus shape and are shaped by the surrounding culture of stigma, shame and prohibition.

In the next chapter, I explore in greater detail the narrative tools which are used to perform socially acceptable identities across the collection of small stories, moving the focus from questions of positioning and resources to questions of circulation and embodiment (Smith, 2016), in order to offer a dialogical perspective of women's drug talk.

Chapter Eight: a dialogical perspective on women's drug talk

Introduction

The chapter 'circles of trust' portrayed a picture of a feminine collective through friendship and kinship networks of which the sharing of drug stories was an important feature. In 'seven small stories' we saw how women are actively engaged in a struggle to negotiate various complicated subject positions. Indeed, as a hidden population, a core facet of the identity work for these women is reconciling aspects of identity which operate in different social groups and different social worlds, which are at times conflicting and without cohesion. This creates narrative complexity and often a very visible struggle to capture the multiplicity of their being. With this complexity in mind, I explore the features that make a good story for hidden populations of women who use drugs. Here, the focus is on the narrative tools which are used to perform socially acceptable identities across the collection of small stories. To illustrate, I offer an exemplar of a good story narrated by Mary, who compares her experiences with DMT to a time travelling in Egypt.

Stories are improved through repeated retellings (Smith, 2016; Crossley, 2000). In part two of this chapter I draw insight from the field of narrative research to explore the difference between well-rehearsed and novel stories and what this tells us about the boundaries of acceptability and the surrounding culture in which women who use drugs are embedded. This leads to a discussion on the embodied nature of the women's storytelling. Here, I explore the agony and the ecstasy as women re-experience the highs and lows of their drug use. The concept of narrative habitus (Frank, 2010) is suggested as an appropriate lens through which to view the circulation and embodiment of stories, and by extension, the limits of expression implied by the stories that struggle to find their way out of the body (Smith, 2016).

Part One: The features of 'good stories'

Remembering that stories motivate actions as they are *enacted* in the world, it is necessary to think about the impact different stories may have on the lives of the women. According to Frank (2010:2012) stories can be healing, and they can be dangerous (this was explored in the previous chapter in accessing and engaging where I touched on the debate over harmful and healing narratives). While it is common practice for narrative researchers utilising a dialogical

framework to determine if a particular story ‘works’ better than another, not all researchers agree it is our job to place such value on the narratives of others. Privileging certain narratives over others, for example as Michelle Crossley (2010) does in her analysis of stories of living with HIV is a contentious matter (Squire, 2012). For Crossley, it was clear which type of story was more adaptive for her participants, and that was stories which made it possible for them to have a sense of living in the future. Such judgements on what constitutes good and bad stories are embedded within a particular system of values and in the case of women’s drug use what is functional and indeed desirable is far removed from any measure of consensus.

The literature on women’s drug use and agency uniformly highlights the need for a form of agency which allows them to take responsibility without giving away all their power and becoming a victim in their own story (Charrad, 2010). From a narrative perspective, agency lies in their artful presentation of the available narrative scaffolds that are passed on to them from the wider culture (Frank, 2010) and with this in mind, it is the purpose of the first half of this chapter to explore what makes a good story for hidden populations of women who use drugs.

Ambiguity

Women who use drugs are all too aware of being caricatured and reduced to a singular stereotype and the ways in which they defend from this have been a theme throughout this study. It is my contention that a ‘good story’ for hidden populations of women who use drugs is one which acts to confuse and unsettle such simplistic characterisations. Through the example of Freda in the previous chapter I suggest one of the ways this is achieved is through playing with ambiguity.

Frank (2010) comments on this ‘slippery’ quality of some narratives which make sense from the point of view of resisting what he calls finalisation. In emphasising that those we study exist in an ongoing state of becoming, the dialogical perspective represents a middle ground between the universalism of modernism and the relativism of postmodernism suggesting ‘*the formerly polarised dominant modes of thought are part of a wider, more heterogeneous process*’ (Owen, 2011: 136)

The striking sense of ambiguity conveyed in the women’s storytelling can thus be viewed as an effect of the women’s earnest attempts at capturing complexity, weaving contrasting strands of experience, the dark and the light, into a coherent whole. This becomes even more challenging when narrating certain drug experiences in which there are many shades of grey.

For example, an interesting theme across the data is the way in which apparently negative experiences are described and understood by the women. Rather than something to be feared and avoided, so called ‘bad times’ are an inevitable and valuable part of the overall experience. This was particularly evident in relation to narratives about the use of psychedelics.

“Some folk do have a bad time but I think the bad times, as in life, are just all part of the whole experience. It doesn’t have to be good all the time, quite often if you have a bad time, you can really learn stuff about yourself.” (Shirley)

“I just find, with tripping, there is something so healing about it. Especially times when it’s all been a bit, well I don’t like to say a bad trip, but times where it’s been a bit scary, a bit perhaps... intense, then its..... och, it’s such a difficult thing to put into words.” (Freda)

The bad times present opportunities for healing, to gain self-knowledge, to gain control over the mind, and to remain humbled by the power of the drug itself. It is for this same reason that many of the women reject the framing of their drug use as recreational. Implying a purely hedonistic function, the term privileges the pleasurable dimensions and negates the aspects of their drug experiences which are inherently challenging and unpleasant, and very important. As this excerpt from Claire illustrates, good and bad experiences are highly subjective and at times very surprising:

“The last mushroom trip that I had I was pretty self-contained, and I had a big vomit, you know how you puke on the mushrooms sometimes, and oh it was like, it was cathartic! It was the best thing ever! It was a big nature vomit.”

Claire’s description of vomiting whilst intoxicated on psilocybin as ‘the best thing ever’ calls into question the taken for granted assumptions blurring the boundaries between what is considered good and bad in relation to drug use. As we saw in Allie’s reflection of her experiences in the last chapter, the best times are often also the worst times. The contrary meaning attached to challenging experiences associated with psychedelics such as ‘freaking out’ or ‘losing it’ thus troubles essentialist readings, highlighting the ambiguous nature of these common drug experiences. According to Gashi, Sandberg and Pederson, (2020), this ‘inside knowledge’ of the inherent value of these apparently negative experiences is implicated in the symbolic boundary work in the circles of psychedelic using groups. Individuals who reject the

idea of a ‘bad trip’ are positioned as insiders and those who attribute common sense understandings are marked as naïve and therefore outsiders.

From a narrative perspective, this level of ambiguity leaves the phenomena open to multiple ways of interpretation and according to some narrative scholars this quality in a story makes it a good one: *‘Many researchers suggest that narratives that are not ‘closed off’, and that contain multiple possibilities within them, are better than more apparently dogmatic stories* (Freeman, 2004; Wengraf, 2004; see also Squire, 2012). Indeed, preserving the ambivalence in women’s accounts often leads to different understandings in which ‘problem’ behaviour becomes intelligible; Susan Batchelor’s analysis of women’s accounts of committing violence problematizes the propensity within academic literature to analyse the experiences of women through the lens of neat essentialist dualisms such as structure/agency, masculine/feminine or victim/perpetrator (Batchelor, 2007).

As suggested in the circles of trust, these contradictions and ambiguities are the openings to delve into identity work (Bamberg, 2004). Informed by Bakhtin’s theory of dialogism, DeSantis (2001), speaking about exiles says:

‘they are located between two worlds, precariously balanced between feeling both loyal and faithful, love and hate, fear and security, because of this disjunctiveness, exile discourse has a schizophrenic quality, unable to commit to any firm conclusions about their lives, their identity, their future’ (DeSantis, 2001:3)

Like exiles who find themselves between ‘two worlds’ hidden populations of women who use drugs are similarly marginally situated. The dialogical interpretation of exile discourse is thus an interesting lens through which to examine the ambiguity of the stories presented here. From a Bakhtinian perspective human experience is inherently full of dialogical tensions, but traditional monological thinking leaves no room for this in its quest for false unity and its either/or thinking. With monological interpretation comes the tendency to see such inconsistencies as a consequence of psychological disturbance or illogical thought processes. Reading the contradictions in the women’s stories dialogically means to see the centripetal and centrifugal forces in action, the simultaneous push pull dynamic. Centrifugal forces strives to keep everything ‘various, separate, apart and in a state of becoming’ while centripetal forces desire ‘together, unified and same’ (De Santis, 2001: 5). It is argued that narrative research methods can become transformative when they allow narrators the space to express the contradictions of experience. According to Wiersma (1992) such stories are *‘filled with dynamic tension,*

encompassing the good and the bad, the acceptable and the unacceptable wishes and roles, motivations, and obstacles..capturing the bittersweet ambiguity of life and of all lives' (Wiersma, 1992:211).

Resolution

Dialogical narrative analysis invites researchers to think about what is not said in any given story. Even in the stories where the theme is about being lost, this feeling is brought to a sense of resolution before the story ends. Not having a sense of where one is headed, of being carried away completely by external forces, is absent in these stories of women's drug use. This absence of narratives of drifting in which women cast their role as entirely passive, on an unchosen journey to an unknown destination suggests that in telling stories of their drug use, autonomy is very important.

That bodily autonomy is threatened in a multitude of ways by the socio-political context in which these women are embedded can be read in each of the seven stories; in healing the body, in reproducing the body, and in experiencing bodily pleasure. In some cases there appeared to be an impaired capacity to erect and maintain physical boundaries. The drug talk examined in this thesis suggests that storytelling is a means to preserving and regaining this sense of autonomy, or self-empowerment, which is often realised through narrating difficult and ambiguous experiences and then bringing it to a close with a clear sense that the difficulty or problem has been resolved in some way.

Resolution narratives are about building resolve and are often darker in nature; there is a strong sense that change is on the horizon. Sensing potential for negative judgement, the making of a resolution is a way of managing perceptions of them as weak willed or victims of present circumstance with little power to effect positive change. Such stories work to affirm a decision to make some kind of change and often leave the women feeling more certain about a future course of action. For example, in 'circles of trust' Claire's story of positioning of future partners on the outside of the circle of trust is an example of a resolution narrative. Katie's story is also mostly about changing her relationship with drugs, and she intentionally focuses on the bad times to create the motivation to do this. She tells me that the interview has been useful in getting her ready to see a professional about her substance use that recently has gotten out of hand and started to have a negative effect on her self-esteem and sense of wellbeing.

Common tools for building good stories: artefacts and metaphors

Like exiles, the self-analysis of hidden populations of women who use drugs is permeated with dialogical tension and narrators respond to these dialogical forces in different ways. Anchoring to artefacts is thus one of the strategies employed by the exiles to reconcile an identity in crisis arising from being ‘caught between two worlds.’ For a participant in DeSantis’ study, this was drinking strong sweet coffee as it was closely associated with the aspect of identity he was striving for, which in this case was being Cuban.

Some of the particularly good stories that work to construct a socially acceptable identity for the women in this study use similar, yet very subtle narrative strategies. There are several examples of the effective use of artefacts in the above stories, aspects of identity work which might otherwise go unnoticed. For example, I suggest Joanna’s repeated references to drinking tea could be viewed as an effort to perform a benign identity by anchoring herself to a culturally approved practice that suggests conformity to instead of a subversion of the feminine ideal. Louisa’s apparently innocent statement about ordering a diet coke and phoning a taxi sends signals about the kind of woman she is, health conscious and independent.

Daisy Clark’s lucid description of serving lukewarm drinks out of a bucket, invokes a feeling of disgust and thus sets the tone of impropriety and lack of societal convention for the events to follow. Allie’s story of being lost with ‘*no shoes, no bag, no phone*’, while a literal description of her dishevelled state also functions to signal the lack of items deemed essential for her to navigate her way through the world safely. For younger privileged women in particular, the absence of these accessories tends to leave a woman feeling ‘naked’ and Allie utilises this symbolic nudity to creatively convey her extreme state of vulnerability.

In order to identify the main points of struggle in the women’s stories, DeSantis (2001) suggests looking for the use of metaphors which can signal sites of dialogical tension as they are often used when the complexity of feeling cannot be conveyed. For example Allie uses the Roulette metaphor to capture the essence of being a ‘willing victim’. All at once she is powerful and powerless. The centripetal forces are those which pull her towards conformity, while at the same time the centrifugal forces push her to resist. The result is a feeling that one embodies two very different states of being; states which appear to be mutually exclusive, yet when viewed dialogically, exist as simultaneous contradictions (DeSantis, 2001).

Smith and Sparkes (2004) discuss the narrative fabric of identity construction in which metaphor plays an important role, ‘*both as a resource in the process of reconstructing selves*

following a disruption to body-self, and as a cultural resource that gives shape and form to life stories' (Smith and Sparkes, 2004:599). Thinking about this understanding of metaphor in relation to the retrieval narratives above, something which stuck with me was the box Daisy talks about that was to be guarded with her life when she was 'freaking out' on acid. She didn't know what was in it, but she surmised it must be something very important. After a while she became frightened and threw it away, believing she had caused a massive explosion, which was actually fireworks. At first, I thought this was merely a description of drug induced warping of the perception of cause and effect. Upon reflection, I wondered if there was a deeper meaning to her account of these two separate events perfectly timed but not causally related, and if the throwing of the box was actually a metaphor for the exaggerated sense of responsibility she had felt for the events that transpired on that occasion.

Good stories: an exemplar

The following story from Mary serves as an excellent example of a 'good story' which utilises many of the above properties which constitute a good story for hidden populations of women who use drugs. In this story we see, ambiguity, resolution, and an interesting use of metaphor.

When I was in Egypt: Mary

Karen: I would love to hear about your experiences with DMT Mary.

Mary: When I was in Egypt, I had basically lost the plot. I had been travelling with my friends all over the place. When I was a kid, I didn't realise that people saw the world through different eyes. Then travelling, you learn that everybody sees the world through different eyes. You also realise that everybody can get on with everybody. Because all sorts of folk can hang out together and get on you know? And it's brilliant. Nobody is left out. It's amazing. When I was in Egypt, I fell in love. The first time I kissed this guy, the whole world was just white. We were all that existed. No drugs! No mention of it, no thought of it. Just real life. Mind blowing! So the whole world went white and I was elated. It was just amazing. But then, it turned bad. I was uprooted and that is when I basically lost the plot. Before that life really did feel like a dream. A beautiful, beautiful dream. We were always just as close as a thought to each other. I've never felt so safe, the sky was just a ceiling and every single person there was my friend. I mean...it was more complicated than that. I guess it is how you feel when you are a kid, everything is

just fresh. Everywhere you look is a whole other world to absorb and explore. And appreciate.

Karen: like a sense of wonder?

Mary: Absolutely. And we tend to lose that as we get older. Anyway, my friend said to me, this stuff will lift you into the next dimension. And it did. Absolutely lifted. For just a short while I was light as a feather. Everything feels like..eh, whats the best words for it? Absolutely part of everything. I felt like a Goddess, like I was shining from the inside out. But not just...eh, maybe, yeah maybe that is it. Shining. A real sense of the divine. And I felt...reassured. That this is how life really feels. Because I had already felt it.

Karen: so you had experiences something similar without being on drugs?

Mary: I did. When I was in Egypt.

Mary clearly struggles to express the quality of the experience with DMT. In comparing DMT to her first experience of falling in love and her time of discovery in Egypt, Mary is able to sidestep this difficulty through accessing narrative resources that she has developed from having had experiences of other cultures. Mary's time in Egypt represents a time when her sense of wonder was at its peak. A life altering experience which changed her view of reality, birthing a completely new sense of self. Her story of taking DMT thus draws upon her experiences of discovering the land of Egypt and she draws parallels between the two, even though they are events unrelated in time.

Like all good stories it is rich in metaphor. Mary begins by stating that she had '*basically lost the plot*'. This is a widely used nautical metaphor that alludes to the rich maritime history of her home culture and this perhaps illumines the sense of bewilderment as she navigates foreign waters, both physically and metaphorically. This sets the tone for the remainder of the story which has a transcendent quality; charting a journey in which she moves beyond a previously known limit.

Her imaginative use of metaphor does not stop there. She describes the rejuvenating effects of romance when describing her experience of a kiss after which '*all the world went white*'. Although a seemingly strange use of words, the colour white is powerful in depicting a blank slate, or a clean sheet. Through this we get the sense that the kiss was a turning point in Mary's story. The start of a new chapter. She reinforces this sense of renewal when she says:

'Everything felt like when I was a kid, fresh', attaching a similar meaning of innocence and purity to her drug experiences as Rachel. Mary expresses the physical sensations of being high and 'floating' on DMT when she says: *'I was light as a feather'*. This 'unburdening' signals a shift in subjectivity which takes place commonly in the psychedelic experience which involves:

'a temporary suspension of—or deliberate flight from—everyday identity as a unitary neoliberal subject, constantly engaged in processes of self-monitoring, self-governing and efficiency maximisation... While one is thus unburdened, a different subjectivity reveals itself. Experiences of selfhood within the space are characterised by fluidity, integration with others and periods of dissolution into ecstatic states'

(Ruane, 2017: 60)

This fluidity in subjectivity is captured in the story through Mary's weaving of complexity and ambiguity. For example, she makes two seemingly contradictory statements about the same time and place *'When I was in Egypt, I lost the plot'* and then *'When I was in Egypt, I fell in love'*. At the same time she feels untethered and yet anchored in a deeper sense of belonging. In Mary's story of Egypt we can see the dialogical tension between feeling lost and found and this captures the essence of her experiences with DMT. The aspect of self which is lost is the ordinary sense of Mary as a physical body rooted in time and space and the aspect of self: she has found is a knowledge of her spirit as *'a Goddess, part of everything and shining from the inside out'*. For Mary, the restoration of a sense of wonder and renewal came from having this mystical experience of the divinity of her own being.

In the end of her story Mary speaks about being reassured by this experience and through the reliving of it in her storytelling she re-experiences this feeling of reassurance once more. Telling this story perhaps serves a deeper function to resolve a sense of inner conflict, at a particularly difficult time in her life when her life choices to use illicit drugs have been subject to external scrutiny, as we saw with her experience of social exclusion in the 'circles of trust'.

In listening to this story, I was entranced by Mary. The embodied quality of her narrative was very much in evidence. She sat cross legged on the floor with her eyes closed and hands placed over her heart. There was a strange mix of emotion that moved me, and it felt like sadness and joy all mixed in, similar to Maya's reliving of ecstasy. I explore these important yet largely unacknowledged aspects of women's drug talk later on in the chapter under the heading 'vicarious intoxication'.

Part two: Circulation and embodiment

As Crossley (2000) points out, good stories are adaptive, but stories can be improved with repeated tellings. This is echoed by Frank who views meaning as a chain of narrative enactments developed through repeated retellings (Frank, 2010). According to Frank (2010) perception and memory are filtered through narrative resources, in turn shifting and expanding these resources. Consequently, issues of circulation are a key facet of DNA (Smith, 2016).

In this, the second half of this chapter I examine the difference between stories which come across as well rehearsed and those which appear to be entirely novel in their telling, exploring what such features of storytelling can tell us about the circulation of stories within hidden populations of women who use drugs. Finally, I consider the processes which govern when stories are told and untold...and I offer some reflection, both my own and that of the women on the embodied nature of the women's stories and what this may mean for

Novel and well- rehearsed stories

I have intimated that DENIM encourages the expression of novel stories which perform an identity that is often challenging to stereotypical constructions of women who use drugs. What are the differences between well-rehearsed vs novel stories? The former is culturally acceptable and thus, being told more often have a particularly polished feel to them. Eric Prins (2008) relates the latter kind of story to a semi-structured interview method and, desiring to hear those stories less frequently told, he changed the design of his study to an unstructured narrative format.

The most highly polished stories, the stories that came across as very well-rehearsed were the respectability narratives, those that signalled a level of conformity and were least challenging to the status quo. As we saw with Louisa's 'That is just not me' these stories often deflect stigma and discrimination whilst reinforcing hegemonic cultural narratives about age, femininity or whiteness and social class. Indeed, one of most obvious differences in the risk narratives from Joanna and Freda was the level of confidence, 'As a woman who gardens' felt intrepid, whereas 'A little pick me up' seemed especially performative.

Novel stories, on the other hand, are the counter narratives. These are stories which are not heard very often, like Mary's story of Egypt or her earlier story of wanting her son to use drugs. Or like Allies story of playing roulette with her life, Louisa's story of using cocaine to have better orgasms or Maya's story of being given her first ecstasy by her uncle and her mother. The novel stories told by the women in this study are consistent with Ochs' (2004) narratives

of inquiry. With such stories the plot is less integrated and they do not follow a coherent linear sequence where there is a clear sense of cause and effect. These narrative events represent ‘an occasion for untangling experiential possibilities’ and it is with this potential that women do the messy work of making sense of drug use within a surrounding cultural context where conflicting meanings abound. Indeed, it is precisely this quality which lends these stories well to a dialogical narrative analysis (Ochs, 2004).

A space in which to contest the mainstream processes of meaning making for women who use drugs, novel stories have a peculiar quality to them, you can see and feel that the women are somehow testing out a position, gauging your reaction, and moving forward cautiously. In telling these stories women are relatively uncertain in terms of what reaction they will inspire in the listener. They are thus characterised by hesitation and require a degree of courage to be told. In this manner novel stories serve as a window into what is less acceptable and can tell us a lot about the dangerous territory within women’s drug talk. Such stories bring into focus the moral boundaries of acceptability, often challenging gender stereotypes and culturally sanctioned femininity.

On the other hand, well-rehearsed stories are told more confidently with the expectation of a particular response. There is a definite performative feel to these stories. Identifying the two types of stories can generate insight into what are socially acceptable narratives of women’s drug use in the context of each of the women’s lives. Having said that the audience can still be misjudged, as we saw with Freda and her story about losing drugs in the house with young children, which acted to disconnect us momentarily. It is interesting that Freda’s well-rehearsed story was one which challenges the dominant discourse of parents who use drugs, and the highly performative tone suggests she has had previous opportunities to tell such controversial stories with impunity, reflecting the relative safety of her circle of trust. This suggests there is a relationship between untroubled subject positioning and the external social context of the speaker (Widding, 2015).

Ochs (2004) suggests that stories may provide a means to adopt the moral high ground and this was apparent in many of the seven small stories, which I have described through the language of othering (Ochs, 2004). According to Fleetwood (2016), such narratives of othering are ‘highly agential’ and availability of these narratives is dependent on social structure. Indeed, I have emphasised that the context in which stories are told are important and it has been stressed many times now that the narrative resources used to achieve the goals of storytelling are

dependent on positionality and privilege (Fleetwood, 2016). From the chapter ‘Circles of Trust’ we have learned that many of these women perform quite different identities as they go about their everyday lives and conduct a variety of relationships. Fleetwood suggests that ‘*thinking of capitals helps us to understand why individuals in the same field might construct different narratives*’ (Fleetwood, 2016: 178).

Stories told and untold

Analysing the differences between novel and well-rehearsed stories requires an understanding of the processes through which stories come to be circulated. Indeed, thinking about the circulation of stories is an important aspect of DNA (Smith, 2016). The concept of narrative habitus (Frank, 2010:2012) elucidates the role of storytelling in connecting and disconnecting groups of people. It also speaks to this embodiment of stories, suggesting that over time, stories become embedded within the body, creating a certain disposition towards certain stories. Having a shared narrative habitus describes the repertoire of stories shared by a group and the competence to use this repertoire. Group membership depends on narrative habitus, the stories people tell and the knowledge of how to react to hearing particular stories are what determines one’s positioning on the inside or outside. When stories are shared between two people whose habitus are incompatible then it results in what Frank and Bayard call ‘*the dialogue of the deaf*’ (Frank, 2010: 58).

The concept of narrative habitus implies that stories seem to find their way to the right people, implying an almost magnetic quality that guides one to those who share a similar ‘inner library’ (Frank, 2010). A similar phenomenon has been described elsewhere, for example Shotter (2014) who, building on the constructionism and relational ontology of Kenneth Gergen, argues in the course of our interactions there is an ‘acute discriminative awareness’ available to us which we use to shape the forms of our expressions. This implies that an implicit understanding of what is appropriate and what effect one wishes to have on those being addressed acts as a guide to what is actually expressed.

Yet the literature on narrative habitus suggests it is more a sense of being guided by feeling than cognitive awareness. Some stories appear to feel right, while others don’t. According to Frank (2010) narrative habitus is goal oriented but not necessarily consciously strategic. It is:

‘the embodied sense of attraction, repulsion, indifference, people feel in response to stories, the intuitive, usually tacit sense that some story is for us or not for us,

that it expresses possibilities of which we are or can be part, or that it represents a world in which we have no stake' (Frank, 2010: 53)

The stories analysed in the circles of trust and in seven small stories highlight the multifunctional nature of narrative, including the manner in which narrative is a means to construct and maintain group boundaries. 'Narrative habitus' alone may not capture the complexity of women's drug stories, told and untold, but it represents the beginning of framework that may help us to understand why some women are disposed to tell certain stories about their drug use. However, this notion of predisposition does not equate to predetermination. Like Bourdieu's habitus, narrative habitus can be changed, often slowly over time.

This process of expanding narrative resources and narrative habitus is described by Frank (2010) using the concept of the inner library, taken from the work of Pierre Bayard. The inner library is a way of expressing the organisation of narrative habitus, and it reminds us that stories have meaning only in relation to all other stories, heard and unheard. The inner library invites us to understand that the process of meaning is possible only through shared cultural resources. Narrative habitus forms a grid that filters our perceptions of the world meaning that the same story may well be understood differently by someone with a different habitus. Importantly, there is usually a sense of resistance in creating a new section of this inner library, as we tend to ignore stories that do not fit preferring those which can be shelved neatly in existing locations. That said, people can still be responsive to new stories. Frank calls it 'narrative ambush' when stories affect people with a different narrative habitus (Frank, 2010).

In thinking through the issue of gaining new narrative resources for the women in this study, it strikes me that in many ways, the inner library is analogous to a woman's home. Not only is it where they generally feel most comfortable, under ideal conditions of course, but the quality of it affects how they feel about themselves and how others see them, and crucially, their ability to improve it is dependent to a degree on external forces and the social structure. We have seen many times already in this study where I felt my non-judgemental stance was instrumental in the telling of the novel story, suggesting audience reaction is an important part of the process of enriching the inner library.

Analysis of the transcripts and of the reflective journal highlights difficulties in expression when it comes to communicating certain aspects of experience, mostly in relation to the use of

psychedelic substances. Persistently, I was met with the feeling that there are certain things which are difficult to put into words and that certain experiences can only be understood by other people who have shared them. However this is not always limited to the phantasmagorical experience of hallucinogenic drugs which can often seem to take place in otherworldly dimensions. The following exchange between myself and Daisy Clark is worth quoting at length:

DC: there are some people I just don't feel the need to talk about it with. Because...I feel that they are very personal things and if you talk about them too much then you take away the magic of it. It should be an experience that you share with certain people. And I feel that sometimes when I share the stories, I just don't do it justice at all. I don't think we have the language. A lot of my art is stories of my drug taking. Art is another way to share your story. Even with the ones that aren't so trippy, there are feelings or something else that is connected to it.

K: well when you were talking about taking mescaline earlier you said it might be better to write me a poem about it and that made me wonder if it was hard to explain.

DC: it is. It's almost as if the more I try to repeat them, they more they lose something. The really deep experiences that is. I think there are just some things that you can't vocalise. It's like trying to explain a colour to someone. Just difficult.

Not only is the drug use kept quiet from friends on the outside due to anticipated judgement and recognition that they have greater levels of fear, it is expected that they lack the capacity to appreciate the profundity of some of the experiences. Daisy uses the metaphor of trying to explain a colour to someone to describe the limits of narrative to convey what she labels 'the really deep experiences.' Daisy expresses this depth of emotion through alternative means such as art and poetry; so too does Freda, suggesting creative research methods might prove successful in exploring some those aspects of women's drug experiences for which the poverty of our common language appears increasingly apparent.

According to Squire (2013), narrative researchers may look at hard-to-transcribe fragments, contradictions and gaps within narratives, as well as the words themselves; or at the paralanguage of for instance tone, pauses and laughter that accompanies words (Squire, 2013). Finding it difficult to explain, self-interruptions, long pauses, trouble finding the correct words and repeated attempts to satisfactorily describe the extraordinary, were especially common in

accounts of ‘tripping’. Despite being very articulate, the women frequently sought verification of my understanding by using phrases such as ‘you know?’ and ‘do you understand what I mean?’ The struggle to express the profundity of the experience often visibly frustrated the narrator, conveyed through hand gesture and body language. I responded in these situations by paraphrasing for the participant, which often appeared to help.

The women often talk about how this isn’t possible to share drug stories with others who haven’t experienced the same things. There is a feeling of discomfort and unease when sharing stories with someone who has had experiences that are quite different. The anticipation of resonance or dissonance is thus a factor which determines circulation, as we saw in ‘the dilemma of disclosure’. Like the way Lana heard the story from one of her new female friends about her own relatively tame experiences with alcohol and tobacco and decided to keep quiet. This was her discovering a dissonance in narrative habitus and her ability to register this different vibration in the body, through the ‘gut feelings’ which determine whether a story should be told (Smith, 2016), served a protective function for Lana and her children. Sharing what appear to be highly significant experiences with someone who is unable to ‘get it’ through lack of shared experience, through the medium of a language which also feels inadequate, is thus a strong motivation to stay silent in order that the meaning is not reduced or distorted. On the contrary, the pleasure of someone ‘getting it’ is a way of describing the shared sense of comfort and familiarity in telling stories with women who share a similar narrative habitus.

That the narrative habitus of women who use drugs is likely to change over time is suggested in this passage taken from the transcript of my interview with Katie:

I have a few good stories. Of good times. But do you know what is interesting, right? Somebody rocked up into my life from about ten years ago, we had went to Fabric and all that, totally crazy, popping pills I had never taken before, but, do you know what? He rocked up into my life recently and it totally changed how I felt about those experiences, and I would have told this story differently to you today had I not saw him again. Now I just feel that this is all in the past and all those pill stories, I am over reliving that. Now I know what it does. When I heard him talking about it, it just felt really cringey. Like, how many more amazing things have we done since then that outweigh that? For me this has been the tipping point. Seeing him and hearing him tell the story. It’s cringey. These things are shared amongst friends but if I went up to my mate and were like remember the time you were

like...and they were trying to stop for whatever reason and were like yes but I'm trying not to...you just don't know what is going on in other people's heads.

(Katie, 32, academic)

Katie describes hearing stories that she would once have enjoyed sharing with this old friend as making her feel really 'cringey'. This acute discomfort suggests that her narrative habitus is in the process of changing as a result of recent experiences. Through this Katie is becoming more conscious of the effects of telling stories on other people and how it can impact the way people see you. In particular she is aware of the dangers of reminiscing on the good times for people who are renegotiating their relationship with substances. '*I would have told this story different had I not seen him*' is a very powerful statement indeed, and it demonstrates that stories are constantly changing in response to not only the audience but as a consequence of interactions and experiences the teller has with other people. This is the 'acute discriminative awareness' that Shotter (2014) speaks about which guides our creative expressions. The same level of awareness is demonstrated by Marie when, after relaying a story about taking more ecstasy than she would normally in a nightclub, ends it by stating:

'And this is why I don't usually share things you see, because I don't want to give people the wrong impression. Not everybody can handle it'.

Marie is concerned that others will think negatively of her and indicates clearly that her desire to manage their impressions is what stops her from sharing her stories. In stating that 'not everyone can handle it' she is aware that some people lack the capacity to consume the story without reacting badly, not unlike the drug itself. While she does not explicitly state it, through this it is evident that Marie has a tacit knowledge of narrative habitus.

Vicarious intoxication

As mentioned above, Daisy Clarke also shares in a concern for how her stories will be received and is reticent to tell her stories as she has learned through past experience that in the wrong context, the act of narration can have a diminishing effect, reducing the value of the experience as she re-experiences it subjectively. Preserving the special meanings attributed to these experiences, cherishing them, is thus very important for Daisy, as it is for many of the women. Indeed for Rachel, 'reliving those really nice feelings' is one of the key functions of telling drug stories:

'I am thinking now about how I felt coming to talk to you today and I think there is something about vicariously living through these experiences again by having this

dialogue. Like, Mike smoked a lot of weed. I was never a heavy weed smoker, he stopped just after the kids were born. My drug of choice was acid. But now we barely even drink and he has given up cigarettes in the last six months. So there is definitely that sort of vicariously living through it again when we share stories. I also got totally hooked on 'Breaking Bad'. I think that was me living through it again through a tv series. Because I am not doing it, I am reliving those really nice feelings that I associate with the drug taking years. It's like hearing certain pieces of music again...'

In vicariously re-experiencing the highs through sharing their stories in the inner circles of trust, Rachel re-experiences the thrills of illicit drug use without physically doing it, thus avoiding the threat of stigma. Out with the circles of trust where the sharing of stories may not be as wise, this reliving of the intense highs can be achieved through alternative means such as music and television. The less a woman's outer circumstances become conducive to experiencing the drug use first-hand, the more important these vicarious forms of intoxication become.

Where there is strong sense of resonance, or a shared narrative habitus, the women often feel safe enough to relive the agony and ecstasy of their chosen drug experiences. This represents the more intimate function of drug storytelling and as Daisy Clark shows this 'magic' is protected through the exercising of discrimination. Narratives in which women relive the highs and lows of their drug use have a very strong element of embodiment and the reflective diary captured these embodied and extra linguistic features of women's drug narratives. In accounts of MDMA in particular, the woman appeared to be intoxicated through the memories brought back by the story, visible in her body language and gesticulation, eyes closed and smiling. This re-experiencing of sensual bliss reveals what Hyden (2014) refers to when she speaks of the hands, eyes and voice of storytelling.

In the context of stigma and discrimination, embodied ecstasy and bliss is a rare feature of women's stories of drug illicit drug use. As an observer I felt privileged to witness these private moments of illicit joy. According to Elizabeth Ettorre, this 'sensual hedonism' is commonly a feature of men's narratives of drug use, suggestive of an embodied and gendered sense of agency. It is generally lacking in women's accounts which tend to foreground the avoidance of pain as opposed to the pursuit of pleasure (Ettorre, 2004).

In these re-living narratives, the lines between the agony and ecstasy were not always clear cut. As Maya remembered the good times gone by when the ecstasy culture was at its peak, a time which she describes as the best years of her life, she was suddenly overcome with emotion and as the smile she wore faded the tears began to flow down her cheeks. The contrast of that heightened state of love and connection with her present state of anxiety and alienation was enough to make her weep.

In her feminist auto-ethnography, Elizabeth Ettorre (2017) recalls her experiences of empathy in her research relationships, of feeling ‘the pain, the terror, the sadness, but also the joy, celebration and hope’ (Ettorre, 2017: 8) with the women, in the moment of listening to the story and again in the process of remembering through writing. According to Ettorre, empathy is ultimately the experience of resonance and it is the aim of auto-ethnography. In similar vein, with the use of DENIM in this study, the bodies and emotions of both researcher and researched are brought into focus, which when viewed through the lens of ‘embodied deviance’ become sites of feminist knowledge production in the study of women’s drug use.

In the chapter on accessing and engaging I described at length through the case of Allie how my observations of her body language, for example a shift in gaze to the floor, suggestive of shame, guided my ‘instinctual’ responses to hearing her story of sexual trauma. Again, the reflective diary was indispensable for arriving at insight with regards to how embodied agony presents itself to the audience. In stark contrast to the narratives of ecstasy where the women embrace and melt into the bodily sensations, having seemingly gone deep inside themselves, in narratives of agony there is a frozen rigidity and a strange sense of them having momentarily left the body. In the former I felt a dimming in awareness of audience, almost as if for a moment they had forgotten I was even there and, in the latter, an acute consciousness of what I myself was doing with my own body. As such both represent a different kind of vulnerability that requires to be managed sensitively.

As I suggest in analysis of retrieval narratives, women tell stories about pain and loss in which they re-experience the lows of their drug use in such a way that it creates a sense of mastery and empowerment.

Stressing the healing value of revisiting painful experiences, T-Aho (2014) asserts that reliving painful and traumatic experiences through storytelling is the beginning of the healing process. This kind of storytelling is an exercise in self-determination and serves to re-empower through the achieving of a level of consciousness in which the relationship between past events and

current reality becomes apparent. This perspective emphasises the transformative capacity of narrative (Wolgemuth and Donohue, 2006) where stories which describe desperation and despair can become narratives of resilience and survival (T-Aho, 2014).

A preference for telling stories of the bad times may not always be about gaining a sense of mastery over victimisation. As Katie shows it may also be a form of identity work that is useful in periods of transition:

“As I am moving on with my life I find it much easier to remember the worst times. I think that is quite telling that. I know that my mind-set is shifting but I don't want my identity to be associated with good times...on that” (Katie, 32, academic)

Katie prefers to tell stories of the lows because re-living the highs is dangerous for her at this point in time, where she is negotiating a new relationship with drug use after a recent period of out-of-control cocaine use. This suggests that indulging in stories where the bodily pleasures are re-experienced may potentially cause a temporary forgetting of the negative aspects putting women like Katie at risk of ‘relapse’. Good stories are thus dependent on the women’s individual needs, at this point in her life, a good story for Katie is one which helps her to stay healthy and not get back into using drugs frequently. For a number of the other women in this hidden population, such as Maya, Daisy and Rachel, a good story is one which allows them to re-experience the heightened bliss and intense sense connection of days gone by. Thus, good stories mean different things to different women and they may be about positive or negative experiences with using illicit drugs.

Improving the work of stories

Different discourses are learnt through social interaction (Fleetwood, 2016) and it is precisely this ongoing practice of reconstruction in different times and places which improves the work of stories (Crossley, 2000). In order for narrative resources to develop which allow an alternative performance of risk, social class and gender such as those evident in the previous chapter, opportunities for sharing stories are required. Thus, women who are denied access to these social networks through stigma and discrimination are likely to be quite limited in the identity work they can and do perform. The greater the bank of narrative resources, the better a woman can conduct her life and perform a socially acceptable identity that allows her to remain part of the hidden population. However, in the present climate the opportunities for women to share their stories are few and far between. The surrounding culture of stigma and discrimination which fosters silence stunts the growth of these counter narratives. Indeed, it

was evident that this interview was highly unusual in that it gave the opportunity for the women to speak about this aspect of their identity in a non-judgemental environment and for many of whom this was a highly novel experience. That many of stories analysed here have not been rehearsed and reshaped in relation to other audiences is a particular feature of hidden population narratives in general and the importance of this should not be understated.

Conclusion

In his hidden population study McPhee (2013) calls for a method which analyses the ‘drug talk’ of addiction discourse in recognition that ‘the representations it produces are often at odds with drug realities’ (McPhee, 2013:238). In this study, the women’s efforts at narrating the grey areas of experience act to trouble traditional, one-dimensional representations of women who use drugs. Mikhail Bakhtin’s dialogical theory of the self provides an interesting lens through which to contend with the ambiguity that is apparent throughout the entire collection of stories. Frank (2012) makes an important point when he says that adopting a dialogical approach to analysis of narrative material does not mean monological analyses are not useful and do not have their place. However in the study of sensitive topics in particular, it is important to be wary of ‘concealing’ those we research in their suffering, by becoming too caught up with the dark side of their lives (Hyden, 2013). The primary manner in which monological analyses of women’s drug talk manifest is the tendency to foreground either the good or the bad, though the latter is much more common. To favour pro-centripetal or pro-centrifugal interpretations is to discount half of the narrator’s dialogic voice (DeSantis, 2001). What I have begun with the demonstrative empathy narrative interview method (DENIM) is the development of a research method that, in highlighting the multiplicity of subjectivity, assists in the countering of stereotypes which act to caricature them as amoral and passive victims.

Through dialogical narrative analysis I have demonstrated the inherent complexity of women’s identity work and the resulting textured quality of women’s accounts of illicit drug use, contributing to a growing understanding of the importance of storytelling in the lives of hidden populations of women who use drugs. Good stories, that is, stories which achieve the goals of women’s drug talk, employ effective narrative strategies such as the use of artefacts and they are rich in metaphor; they are ambiguous, and they provide a sense of resolution. They reveal the complex negotiations women must make in order to manage their identity as a women who uses drugs in a climate of moral condemnation.

In the second half of this chapter, drawing on the work of narrative scholar Arthur Frank, (2010) I suggest the notion of narrative habitus can help us to understand the process which governs the circulation and retelling of stories of drug use. The notion of a shared narrative habitus draws together the essence of each of the analysis chapters; it explains why in ‘accessing and engaging the women were reticent to share stories and therefore identity, with some people and not others, which later became more evident as they constructed boundary narratives of connection in the ‘circles of trust’. It also helps to explain why some interviews were successful and others were not; how after spending a while talking some of the women came to see me as one of them and opened up with the expectation of being understood. The concept of a shared narrative habitus brings together questions of embodiment and circulation, through it we come to appreciate how stories live in the body and how they are circulated (Smith, 2016).

Delving deeper into matters of circulation has highlighted differences between well -rehearsed and novel stories and what this reveals about the local contexts and social networks in which narrative resources are developed. Well -polished stories are those which from previous experience have been shown to achieve particular effects. Distinctly performative in nature, they normally work very well to achieve the goals of women’s drug talk, which are complex and context dependent.

Conversely, the novel stories I have described are similar in nature to the previously untold stories that Hyden (2013) talks about in her study of domestic violence. According to Hyden, these kinds of stories are not compatible with a traditional question and answer format and if sought through these means they are likely to remain untold. Prins (2008) is similarly guided towards an unstructured narrative interview format in order to avoid the oft told tales of addiction. I therefore relate the phenomenon of novel stories in this study directly to the use of DENIM. Often controversial in nature, these stories are precarious and proceed with a manner of caution. Empathy and a sense of resonance with the listener are essential for bringing these stories out into the light.

Making a dialogical commitment to analysis of narrative demands that researchers consider what the stories ‘do’ for those who tell them (Frank, 2010, Caddick, Phoenix and Smith, 2015). I suggest the women relive drug experiences through storytelling for a variety of reasons. Stories of the ‘bad times’ help them to gain a sense of mastery and self- empowerment in the context of losses of control or victimisation through drug use. The focus on negative experiences can also assist them on a chosen pathway of reduction or cessation of certain types

of drug use. The 'good times' are narrated and indeed re-experienced at times when it feels safe and appropriate to do so. In reliving the ecstasy the embodied sensations of heightened sensual bliss and intense intimate bonding are remembered very fondly. This is described as a form of vicarious intoxication and for some of the women this acts as a substitute for the real thing in the context of family and work commitments where opportunities to participate are fewer and further between.

The stories of this hidden population of women who use drugs, although at times very sensitive and distressing, are often therapeutic (Hyden 2013). Using the same dialogical narrative analytic framework, Caddick, Phoenix and Smith (2015) highlight the therapeutic effects of the collective storytelling of war veterans, adding a new level of understanding of the benefits of peer relationships for this population. The collective story told by these veterans fosters camaraderie and a deeper sense of connection which counters the effects of PTSD. Social support has been similarly highlighted as crucial for maintaining well-being for women who use drugs, whose experiences of trauma and alienation mark them as different from 'normal people'.

In much the same way, it is my contention that the storytelling of hidden populations acts as a form of medicine. This story medicine has multiple properties that reflect the multiple functions of the narratives; it can retrieve, relieve and re-empower. Yet the women can give and receive this story medicine so long as they remain connected within these networks. As previously mentioned, the surrounding culture is one in which emotional and corporeal connections with other human beings are idealised but limited in the context of alienation and exclusion (Foster and Spencer, 2013). Sometimes through engaging in especially stigmatised social activity, the women are excluded from the circles of trust and are therefore denied this access to method of healing. In such cases women can become vulnerable to predation from problematic individuals or the state, eventually becoming part of the captive population. Due to the power and important function of these stories, this underground narrative network must be preserved, hence why boundary maintenance is such a strong aspect of the women's drug talk.

Elizabeth Ettorre (2018) suggests that gender sensitive harm reduction might be achieved through paying attention to the neglected arena of embodiment in feminist analyses of illicit drug use. I suggest a starting point is the unifying concept of narrative habitus, which links women's narrative identity work with the body and the construction of group boundaries, making a unique contribution to knowledge in the study of women's drug use. It also links the

idea of the circles of trust with narrative resources, allowing us to appreciate how women experience safety in numbers, through the sharing and building upon narrative resources that allow them to perform socially acceptable identities in the context of a potentially hostile culture.

Indeed, part of expanding the inner library' of narrative resources with which to narrate illicit drug use is the exercising of an 'acute discriminative awareness' which signals to the women when it is safe to speak. While the relational context accounts for many of the instances in which stories remain untold, in the narration of psychedelic substance use in particular, there are real limitations to the language available to express the ineffable, non-ordinary and liminal nature of the experience. Recognising this, some of the women who are more artistically inclined suggest extra-narrative modes of expression such as poetry and art. The implications of this for future research in this area will be explored in the discussion.

Chapter Nine: Discussion and conclusion

Introduction

Broadly speaking, it is the purpose of this study to redress the imbalance in the study of illicit drug use caused by an overwhelming focus on largely male, captive populations recruited from formal agencies (Watters and Biernacki, 1989). Although atypical in nature, such populations have been mistakenly taken as representative of all individuals who consume prohibited mind and mood altering substances (Duncan et al, 2003). This fallacy has largely taken hold due to the climate of stigma and discrimination which discourages most drug users from disclosing this aspect of their identity. Within this social context, women who use drugs are perceived and treated as particularly deviant and dangerous (Simpson and McNulty, 2008). Consequently, they experience particularly powerful incentives to keep their drug use discreet and out of sight (Malloch, 2004). As a result of their resounding success in doing so, women remain a largely hidden and therefore unknown population and arguably, within the wider hidden population of illicit drug users, the hardest to reach. The key objective of this study was to identify and gain access to a reasonable number of such women in order to shed light on this contemporary social phenomenon.

The purpose of the following discussion is to make clear how the present knowledge contributes in a much needed way to the broader landscape of women's illicit drug research. It is divided into four sections in which I describe in detail the nature of these contributions which are analytic and methodological in nature. First of all, for convenience they are presented here in brief.

The first contribution concerns the application of existing knowledge to present the Bourdieusian concept of narrative habitus as a highly effective theoretical framework which can account for both structure and agency in the stories that women tell about drug use.

The main analytical contribution concerns the primary objective of this study - to further knowledge of the phenomenon of hidden populations. This is achieved through reconceptualising the women's stories as capital. I suggest this allows them to manage potential stigma and discrimination through the deployment of narrative resources that have been developed in the context of economic privilege and social inclusion.

A second contribution to the field, also made possible through the application of a narrative perspective, demonstrates the manner in which the group boundaries of this hidden population

are constructed and maintained through storytelling. Unlike any other study concerned with the relationships of women who use drugs, I have analysed the meanings and values constructed in relation to intimate partners and friendships concurrently using the model of the circles of trust, which shows that women construct risk in a variety of subjective ways.

This study also contributes to the field by demonstrating the capacity of dialogical narrative analysis of small stories as sites of identity work which preserves the ambiguity and complexity of women's experiences and accounts. This thesis show how women's everyday drug talk serves multiple functions; to manage risk, to achieve respectability and to retrieve lost aspects of personal power and autonomy. I suggest that such functions, which are critical to sustaining membership in the hidden population, are dependent on access to narrative resources which are developed in various social and professional contexts.

The main methodological contribution is the development of the demonstrative empathy narrative interview method (DENIM) and an additional conceptual contribution is the 'resonance effect' which offers an alternative perspective on the role of the researcher in drug research to stimulate further debate.

[The parameters of present knowledge claims](#)

The general trend in studies of women's illicit drug has been to frame its utility in terms of knowledge that will benefit or improve the existing treatment or policy landscapes. Given that the ontological premise of the present study is to reject the representational logic of most drug research (Martin and Stenner, 2004), arguing that data is not a transparent window onto the lives of the research subjects (Frank, 2010:2012), there is an added complexity to the discussion on the implications of the knowledge for the wider field. It has been suggested that if qualitative methods have greater transparency surrounding their methods then they are more likely to be used within policy arenas (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). However, according to Martin and Stenner (2004), in order for qualitative drug use research to be counted as evidence that will influence policy making decisions, it must produce knowledge that exists independently of the conditions in which it is 'discovered'. The underlying assumption of claims to report the cold hard facts of what is really going is that it is possible to capture reality transparently through language. Thus, when qualitative research is used as evidence in drug use research it is generally rooted within a realist ontology.

Realist accounts are thus traditionally read with a view to informing interventions for people who use drugs such education and prevention. These interventions often situate the problem within the individual minds and bodies of drug users as opposed to a broader problem that exists within the culture. This, for Martin and Stenner (2004), explains why despite increase of qualitative drug research in recent decades, nothing fundamental has changed. Alternatively, drug use research that does not focus on discovering independent facts, that is relativist and constructionist in nature- such as the present study, has the capacity to explore the ways in which drugs and the people who use them are constituted as social problems. Focusing on and analysing ‘talk’ highlights the constraints that are placed upon what is thinkable and doable for people who use drugs in the context of prohibition.

Researchers such as Hammersley (1992) and Andrews (2016) have questioned the usefulness of the findings generated from studies with a basis in ontological relativism, on the basis that multiplicity of accounts produced can each claim legitimacy. According to Andrews (2016) if research is not contributing to knowledge in any meaningful way, then its usefulness may be questioned, especially when it relates to matters to health.

More recently, Stevens (2021) comments on this issue in relation to drug research specifically. In the ‘ontology of drug politics’ he claims that while constructionist critique in drug research has generated interesting insight, he claims it is ‘analytically paralysing’ and self-defeating. However, unlike the stance taken in the present study, Stevens critique is concerned with a radical constructionism which holds that reality is ‘*internal rather than external to our methods of studying it; that there is no reality anterior to observation*’ (Stevens, 2021: 4) .

It is thus important to note the error in assuming that all research rooted in a constructionist epistemology is incapable of acknowledging the existence of a material reality. Indeed, for Willig (2016), the lines between realism and relativism are becoming increasingly blurred and as such it is not always possible to exclude one or the other in any particular project. He explains the following process: people construct meaning which influences their actions, and these actions then have the potential to transform the material context and any further constructions of meaning. This same process is accounted for in the narrative literature. An advocate of the constructionist approach, Brett Smith suggests narratives ‘*shape what becomes experience through teaching us what to pay attention to and how to respond to those kinds of things*’ (Smith, 2016:205). This is evident in this thesis in the manner that stories of drug use interpellate the women to act on the parental aspect of their identity.

Far from neglecting those ‘tangible, oppressive structures’ (Presser and Sandberg, 2015) the present narrative study can be aligned with those concerned with the ‘*limitations on creative storytelling due to social context, class, race, gender and so on.*’ (Presser and Sandberg, 2015: 14, as cited in Fleetwood, 2016). This is important as according to Campbell and Herzberg (2017) ‘*The bodies, identities, practices, and ideas associated with gender do not occur naturally but are actively produced and reproduced socially in dynamic tension with historical circumstances and relational inequalities.*’ (Campbell and Herzberg, 2017: 253). A constructionist approach provides a means to theorise power relations and the construction of the drug using woman as subject along the lines of classed and racial divisions. Indeed, it is difficult to see how any other approach than constructionism could begin to account for the manner in which gender is constituted both in the stories that women tell about drug use and the larger stories we, as researchers, tell about their stories.

In sum, this thesis rejects the notion that privileging the speaking over doing in research inevitably reduces analyses to post-structural language games, unable to address issues of relevance in the real world. Stories act to shape concrete reality; it is in exploring the effects of women’s drug talk that I make the claim to have reconciled a relativist and constructionist stance with a concern for social justice. While this study may have limited appeal to drug policy actors, it will appeal to those invested in understanding the relationship between gender and illicit drug use and also to narrative scholars who see the potential in small stories as sites of identity work. Having set out the parameters, the remainder of the discussion will address the main contributions to knowledge before considering how these can be taken further in various directions of future research.

Analytical contributions

In the context of existing research which suggests that women withdraw from social interaction and alienation through internalisation of negative stereotypes (Ahern, Stuber and Galea, 2007), the research question in the present study was designed to explore the relationship between the women’s narratives and the dominant narratives of drug use. The present analysis contributes to knowledge by demonstrating the manner in which the existing narrative scaffolds provide these women with limited choices in constructing subjectivity. In this section, I highlight the limited choices these women have in assembling the available cultural narratives and the manner in which their stories shape, and are shaped by, the surrounding culture of stigma and discrimination. I highlight the thesis further contribution to understanding the gendered nature

of women's drug storytelling, paying specific attention to women's significant relationships and the potential of the circles of trust for analysing the social networks of women who use drugs. My focus then shifts to how viewing stories as capital contributes in a unique way to the understanding of hidden populations and how understanding the power in silence can provide an alternative viewpoint in understanding why women who use drugs are so challenging to engage with.

Limited choices

In 'dope girls', Lisa Maher (1996) highlighted the inadequacy of the victim /volition oriented readings of women's participation in illicit drug markets, pointing to the need for theories which cover the 'middle ground' of structure and agency in women's lives and the extent to which young women are free to shape their own identity and consciousness in relation to the broader social context in which they are embedded, is a recurring question in the context of women's studies in general (Bachelor, 2007).

Applying the concept of narrative habitus to the women's small stories, it is the central tenet of this thesis that women's drug storytelling is at once creative and agentic and constrained by the surrounding social structure. While it is often the case that '*agency takes centre stage in the work done by individuals constructing narratives that work for them, potentially reducing structures, such as gender, to a narrative performance*' (Fleetwood, 2016: 179), I have purposefully avoided the tendency to overstate agency as existing solely within narrative creativity by reflecting not only on what the woman is trying to accomplish in her story, but also on what options are available to her. In doing so, it is clear that in making these artful compositions, which very often end in otherwise troubled and subject positions as they attempt to narrate socially and morally acceptable identities, the women have limited choices.

For example, attempts to redefine femininity in the context of potential devaluation by inscribing drug use with meanings of nurturing and growth result in the reproduction of essentialised notions of womanhood. Indeed, Gough and Whitehouse (2018) are critical of such moves to align the categories of women and nature as a mode of empowerment, suggesting this merely reproduces the binary thinking which erases complexity and difference. This confirms the observation that adopting subject positions that give a sense of being an acceptable human being often results in a reproduction of the social structure (Esin et al 2014).

Normative femininity is not static, it is constantly being defined and redefined in the course of interaction (Winterich, 2007). Within this hidden population at least, the reproduction of normative femininity is a common strategy to achieve respectability and social acceptance in the face of an identity which is perceived to contradict the prescribed social norms of womanhood. Indeed, stories and texts often contain both feminist and patriarchal discourses which reflects the complexity and multiplicity of subjectivity (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003). As the present analysis suggests, through storytelling women recreate the social fabric. In resisting the dominant cultural narratives of women who use drugs, the stories often reify existing problematic categories about desirable and undesirable and good and bad women. It is in this way that these women's accounts of drug use both shape and are shaped by the surrounding culture of stigma, shame and prohibition. This somewhat complicates the view that stereotypes are generated by those outside of a particular group and used as part of a wider political strategy to control that group (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003).

Constructing risk and relationship

While historically, there has been scant attention paid to the friendships and network relations of women who use drugs (Room, 1998), there is a recent buck in this trend with an increasing number of studies have women's social network as their focus. For example, a recent study from Francis, Taylor and Tracy (2020) titled '*Choose who's in your circle*' explores women's relationship actions during and following residential rehabilitation treatment and how they help create recovery oriented networks. There are some similarities in this study to the present research; both are concerned with women's social networks and what they mean to women with histories of drug use and both attempt to place particular value on certain types of relationships. That said, they are distinct in a number of important ways.

Where Francis et al (2020) took a direct approach to questioning women about their relationships, the present study involved a purposefully indirect approach, instead positioning significant relationships along the circles of trust after the use of the DENIM. Avoiding asking about relationships directly was intentional to avoid eliciting socially acceptable responses and well-rehearsed narratives (Prins, 2008). The analytic focus is also very different given that I subject their narratives to a dialogical analysis which interprets what the woman is trying to accomplish and what narrative resources allow her to tell that particular story.

In the Francis et al (2020) study in each of the categories of action, labelled as: limiting contact and deliberate disconnection, isolating, and maintaining and strengthening existing contacts, the women frame all of their changes with the logic of the still using/abstinent binary. The

women make a clear point of staying away from other women who still use drugs, and there is a lack of nuance and any recognition of the positive aspects of continued relationship with other women whom are still actively using. While it seems apparent to me there is a strong incentive to tell these kinds of stories for those particular women, the authors fail to consider how the recovery discourse learned in residential rehabilitation and the immediate interactional context of the interview might have shaped and influenced the women's narratives of group boundary maintenance. This is particularly evident in relation to risk which is determined externally for the women in the Francis et al (2020) study by recovery discourse. Conversely the women in the present study construct risk in a variety of interesting and often contradictory ways that coincide with a performance of stereotypical femininity.

Bridging risk research and intersectionality, Nygren et al (2015) draw parallels between the doing of gender and the doing of risk, suggesting the ways that risk is constructed in every day interaction cannot be considered separate from the dominant structures of power. Thus where women are doing risk they are also doing gender and in the context of hidden populations this does not automatically involve the exclusion of other drug using women. Francis et al also talk about social inclusion but it is framed as involvement in social activities. As is common in women's drug research (Maher, 1997) this over-emphasises women's agency in making healthy prosocial choices without explaining the processes which facilitated access to these activities.

The 20 women in the present study are not in recovery but instead comprise a hidden population, which means their identities as drug experienced are not common knowledge. Across a range of social contexts, women's accounts serve to position them as gendered actors in culturally acceptable ways and can be viewed as specific responses to the norms they are held accountable to on the basis of race, place and class positioning (Miller and Carbone-Lopez, 2015:7). This explains why the women in the present study do gender differently from other women in different social and interactional contexts. In prisons or treatment agencies for example, women tend to downplay the pleasurable aspects of illicit drug use, emphasising instead the relieving of pain (Ettorre, 2004). One of the contributions of this thesis is in highlighting that only are the pleasures spoken of in this hidden population, they are actively re-experienced in a manner I describe as vicarious intoxication. This particular function is especially evident in the narratives of those women whose stories are consistent with a 'maturing out' view of women's drug use (Prins, 2008; Verges et al, 2003). Future research might explore the potential of stories which facilitate vicarious intoxication as sites of multiple

and interlocking forms of identity work covering pleasure, risk, gender, age and group boundaries.

This thesis also underscores the local and contingent nature of knowledge of women's drug use. For the women in Francis et al (2020) study will power and autonomy is achieved by excluding other women which also serves to function as a statement of commitment to living a drug free life. In the circles of trust chapter I suggest stories of cutting ties with other significant others are told as a means to demonstrating willpower and autonomy, two attributes which illicit drug use is commonly thought to compromise.

Indeed, it is suggested by Francis et al (2020) that social network analysis should form a critical aspect of the assessment process of women seeking treatment, in order to identify social networks which pose risk of relapse, and tailor interventions according to the woman's relational context. However, the values of different friendships are context dependent and influenced by larger cultural narratives of addiction and recovery; the alternative narratives from this hidden population construct friendships with other women who use as integral to well-being and those relations which encourage unhealthy patterns of drug use are described as associates. The concept of 'recovery endangering individuals', if classified on the simple basis of 'still using' does not do justice to the advantages of these relationships. The underlying assumption is that all women who use drugs are unhealthy and will encourage you to begin using again. The propensity to pathologise the relational bent of women to fit dominant models of female drug use is not new, and has been previously highlighted by commentators Covington and Surrey (2000). I suggest future attempts to gauge risk on the basis of social networks should acknowledge the important distinction between close friends and associates in order to avoid this.

The experiences of the women in this study confirm the findings of Staton- Tindall et al, (2008) who, in studying the social networks of women in drug courts underline the difference between close friends who appear to have a reducing effect on level of risk as opposed to casual friendships which are conversely associated with increased participation in high risk behaviours. The present data thus complicates the view that women in recovery have closer relationships (Collinson and Hall, 2021). Practitioners working with vulnerable women who use drugs should take into consideration the positive role of same sex friendship and the potential for other drug using women to help moderate levels of drug use.

Developed from the tools of social network analysis from Bellotti (2016), the model of the concentric circles of trust has been utilised in the present study to generate valuable insight into the women's network of important relationships and by extension, the extent to which substance use is integrated in the context of everyday life for the 20 women in this hidden population. It offers a unique contribution to knowledge in that it analyses women's narratives of intimate partnerships alongside their narratives of friendship, positioning both in the circles of trust. The data generated suggests, while method is useful for highlighting the various relational patterns in which illicit drug use configures it may not serve as a reliable indication of potential harm to women, as 'toxic relationships' both with people and substances, at least as they are subjectively defined in retrospect by the women themselves, occur in various and often contradictory contexts. While the circles of trust is a very effective research tool and holds particular promise for narrative elicitation, its utility in treatment contexts requires further exploration.

Alternatively, as stories of drug use have been highlighted as an important aspect of 'borderwork' (Foster and Spencer (2013), the circles of trust may be very useful for investigating further the manner in which group boundaries in hidden populations are narratively constituted. To reiterate, discursive repertoires are shared by groups and as such, stories are analytically fertile as they shed light on the worlds in which we are part and those in which we have no stake (Frank, 2010). My interpretation of the values narratively constructed in relation to total outsiders is that such characters provide the opportunity for the women to perform a more normalised identity which in turn, helps to keep the drug use within socially acceptable levels. Inability to tell stories of outsiders suggests a powerless position of social exclusion, from which there is no 'other' to exclude.

The literature on the maternal relationships of women who use drugs is limited to treatment seeking populations, and these individuals tend to be very vulnerable, having complex needs (Neale, 2004). Where women have mothers who use drugs it is thus described in pathological terms as an 'intergenerational relationship problem' (Neale, 2004). The narrative data in this study offers a different picture of mother daughter relationships. Far from being a problematic relationship, the perception of the women was that having drug use as a feature of the parental relationship was a means to increased bonding and intimacy.

Sharing this aspect of identity with mothers, and fathers although to a lesser extent, was described as a positive experience, offering a source of support and understanding which

allowed the women to navigate potential problems with greater ease. In support of this notion many other women perceive not having the opportunity to be honest with parents about their drug use as a disadvantage, suggesting that privilege sometimes manifests in unexpected forms. The relationship between having this unique source of support and being a non-treatment seeking user of illicit drugs requires further exploration. Studies taking forward a narrative focus might explore in greater depth the role of this significant relationship in the development of narrative resources which function to mitigate the stigma associated with illicit drug use.

Stories as capital

The concept of recovery capital has been used to describe the personal, social, and collective components that support the process of recovery from problematic substance use (Best and Laudet, 2010; Best et al, 2015; Best, Musgrove and Hall, 2018). It seeks to account for structural and agentic factors by encompassing not only internal qualities but the ‘capacity to access the range of resources in the lived community’ (Best et al 2021: 4). The literature suggests recovery capital is an evolving concept, and recently it has been used to study desistance to crime.

The present study, while it refrains from using the language of addiction and recovery, adds to this knowledge of the range of factors which are support of growth and well-being amongst communities of people who use drugs. It invites the wider research community to acknowledge that these various forms of capital, including supportive relationships and social networks, are inextricably bound to the storytelling practices which bring them into being.

Viewing stories as capital may thus be the key to unlocking the mystery of hidden populations without unwittingly engaging in the reproduction of inequality. While it may be the intention to challenge prohibitionist logic, hidden population research runs the risk of reinforcing the dichotomy of hidden populations as responsible drug users, capable of managing the use of dangerous substances vs. captive populations whose lives are deeply troubled and chaotic, and the drug use problematic. The danger rests in its pairing of discourses of responsibility and agency with discourses of middle-classness and whiteness, forces largely silent which, according to Kasmin (2019) are so implicit they do not require to be named.

Previous research has rendered visible the stark differences in terms of how women’s drug use is popularly depicted along class and racial divisions in public domains such as the media (Campbell, 2000). Stories depicting white middle class women’s drug use in the media offer a

clear sense of hope and redemption, and this is rooted in fears over the reproduction of the ruling class. This narrative analysis has brought to attention how such stories are reproduced in the private sphere, by the women themselves. While a degree of variation exists, it is important to explicitly state that the population accessed and engaged with in the present study are representative of a relatively privileged population. This is reflected in their access to narrative resources which allows them to tell hopeful stories and perform socially acceptable identities in the face of potential stigma and discrimination.

Indeed, it is the key contribution to knowledge of this thesis to highlight access to narrative resources which perform socially acceptable identities as the key difference between groups of drug using women. The 20 women in the present study use draw upon narrative resources to construct stories which operate in the world to keep them socially included are available, at least in part, on account of their participation in multiple social groups.

The degree of complexity in the women's social networks calls into question the utility of the hidden/captive population framework. In future research, I propose a move away from a binary opposition between hidden, who are ascribed total agency and captive populations, who are ascribed none, in preference of a continuum of social and economic integration. At one end of this continuum are the most socially included women who use drugs and at the other are those women who experience the greatest degree of social exclusion.

Indeed, the potential reasons put forward in the introduction for why women are largely a hidden population in the introduction; motherhood, lack of appropriate services and stigma are also worth revisiting from a more critical perspective. These explanations which are deeply embedded within the paradigm of pathology, appear inconsistent with the meanings attached to drug use by the women in this study. One of the most common assertions in the literature surrounding women's drug use is that they actively avoid or resist formal intervention from treatment agencies due to fear of having children removed (Gilchrist and Taylor, 2009, Collinson and Hall 2021). From previous engagement with women who had their children removed I understood this fear was legitimate hence why it was put forward as a potential explanation for why women who use drugs in Scotland constitute a hidden population at the beginning of this thesis. However, such a fear was not present in the current sample of women, and as such it cannot be deemed a fair explanation for why these particular women remain part of the hidden population.

Alternatively, I suggest it is due to their differing levels of social and economic capital that provides access to a broader range of narrative resources with which to narrate stories of drug use in a socially acceptable way. The narrative habitus of these particularly privileged women, many of whom occupy a position of professional status, appear particularly confident in defending from attacks on parenting. Their stories are interwoven with cultural narratives made available through participation in a variety of social networks across various spaces and times; such stories work to actively construct risk and gender in manner which constitutes a socially acceptable identity. Management of stigma and discrimination and ability to remain part of the hidden population, is inextricably linked with access to narrative resources.

To assert that women remain hidden due to fear of consequences for themselves and children, is to reproduce the binary logic of treatment discourse of addiction and recovery. Such discourses subtly construct women who continue to use drugs as pathological and those in recovery as desirable, for example by suggesting women in recovery evidence ‘moral values, self-awareness and responsibility’ (Collinson and Hall, 2021: 1). Yet it is abundantly clear that all three of these pro-social attributes are features of the narratives of the present sample of women, all of whom have long standing and *continuing* involvement with illicit drug use. Indeed, it is arguably the presence of such attributes which gives these narratives their distinctly textured quality. The manner their storytelling inscribes a sense of moral agency is particularly evident in the circles of trust narratives where the women deliberate and agonise over the positioning of their children.

The narrative focus of this study was something that evolved over time, after engaging with the women for a number of months. I understand the degree of attention paid to storytelling may seem whimsical to some, in the context of a culture which has record numbers of drug related death - an increasing number of which are women (Tweed, Miller and Mathieson, 2019) However, ‘*stories have the capacity to deal with human troubles and they also have the capacity to make trouble for humans.*’ (Frank, 2010:28). Indeed, the literature on women’s drug use highlights the need for a form of agency which allows them to take responsibility without giving away all their power and becoming a victim in their own story (Charrad, 2010). I suggest it is therefore not only justifiable, but essential that we reflect on the relationship between certain storytelling practices and poor outcomes for women who use drugs.

Indeed, it is widely regarded that informal social controls such as group norms and rituals have significant influence on how drugs are used and the consequences of their use (Harding, ed by Coomber, 1998). Through examination of the women's small stories of drug use through the lens of narrative habitus and emphasis on stories as capital, I hope to stimulate much needed discussion on the role of privilege in allowing women to defend from stigma and perform socially acceptable identities. According to Cranny–Francis et al, 2003, the key to interrupting women's complicity in their own oppression is a process of conscientisation, an increase in awareness of the conditions of reality and one's part in its reproduction. As narrative has the potential to be transformational and emancipatory through achieving consciousness of how past shapes the present, I suggest that opportunity to tell different stories is what is required. On the basis of this study I agree with Fleetwood (2016) who suggests, the greater amount of storylines available the more the narrator can refuse to let stories act on them in a way that is undesirable.

The power in silence

Stereotypical assumptions about women who use drugs underpin the reasoning about the longstanding challenges in engagement, such as irresponsible parenting and the trope of chaotic lifestyles (Klee, 1998). Desiring treatment and experiencing barriers to treatment was not a theme in the collective experience of this cohort of women. The one exception to this was Katie who and was, at the time of interview, in the process of seeking help. She was particularly hard to engage and cancelled the interview several times. She was exhausted and was aware of the degree of emotional investment it required to talk about her problematic relationship with cocaine. So another potential barrier to accessing treatment is lack of emotional energy and not being able to prioritise self-care, and it is interesting that a significant portion of Katie's energy was invested in maintaining employment and managing her intimate relationship.

Reports from the current sample of women suggest a feeling of dread, anticipation of negative judgement and anxiety prior were common prior to the interview. Managing these negative emotional states requires a level of energy which is often unavailable in the context of the multiple demands of everyday life, particularly as a working mother. In such instances, the woman will engage in protective avoidance of encounters with professional figures who appear inherently threatening. Reflections on gaining access to this hidden population are consistent with the notion of a defended subjectivity in hidden populations of women who use drugs, most visible in those women with multiple marginality. However, the present study did not adopt the same psychosocial approach as Holloway and Jefferson, whose analysis of the narratives

of defended subjects takes the form of ‘reflexivity with a psychoanalytic accent’ (Holloway and Jefferson, 2013).

Indeed, such selective withdrawal from outsiders including services designed to help has been cited as a common mechanism for coping with ‘concealable stigma’ (McNamara, Stevenson and Muldoon, 2013). Through a dialogical narrative lens, women exhibit an awareness about the dangers of sharing their story insofar as it has the power to shape and shift the meaning of the experiences for the women themselves. They are reticent to share their most intimate feelings about drug use with people that they fear ‘do not understand’. Sharing stories with audiences who have preconceived notions about drugs and the people who use them, and who do not accept that there are benefits to illicit drug use, can have a diminishing effect on the subjective value of the experience. Through anticipation of these often fragile, tentative meanings being transformed by these powerful audiences, the women have learned of the power in silence.

Methodological contributions

To reiterate, it is part of the dual purpose of the present study to explore the most effective ways of researching hidden populations of women who use drugs. Consequently a significant proportion of this discussion concerns contributions to the methodological literature.

In this section I will outline the present claims to knowledge, firstly by re-examining two points of positivist critique through the lens of narrative habitus to provide an alternative angle for the debate surrounding positionality in drug use research and the related debate on the politics of lived experience. The focus then turns to the development of the DENIM and how this unique approach can be used in future hidden population studies and across a variety of areas of social research on sensitive topics.

Resonance effect: an alternative view on the role of the researcher

Similarity bias describes the process whereby investigators recruit a sample of participants which exhibit a high degree of similarity in social characteristics and it is regularly cited as one of the weaknesses of the snowball sampling method (Moore, 2004). However if narrative habitus is ‘*the embedding of stories in bodies*’ an ‘*embodied sense of attraction, repulsion or indifference, and it represents a world of which we are a part or in which we have no stake*’ (Frank, 2010: 53), to what extent does similarity bias reflect the manner in which stories find their way to those who share a resonant narrative habitus?

Hendricks et al (1992) have previously found that studies with key informants from the artist/actor/music professions are likely to evidence a similarity bias whilst gender does not appear to be predictive of such an effect. The resonance effect would thus offer a causal explanation for this finding insofar as men and women do not automatically share a similar narrative habitus on the basis of gender alone whereas those who practice in the same creative occupations are more likely to have had similar experiences with drugs and in turn share a similar narrative habitus.

If similarity bias is simply a way of observing narrative habitus in action through a positivist lens, then this would explain its persistence despite efforts at mitigation. As we have seen consistently in this study, the feeling of resonance or dissonance is an aspect of sharing stories which is guided by ‘gut feeling’, which, being embodied and mostly subconscious makes it difficult to manipulate. Since drug stories are generally told to those who are expected to understand and appreciate them, a phenomenon for which I have coined the term ‘the resonance effect’, it is likely that in previous hidden population research participants narrative habitus has been resonant, to a degree, with that of the researcher or the primary gatekeeper. Building on the example of this study, inclusion of a reflexive element to such research would reveal the extent to which into the surrounding culture is shared between researcher and researched, transforming hidden population research into a more critical branch of drug ethnography, more attuned to the politics of representation and the need for social justice.

This form of reflexivity requires disclosing as a drug experienced drug researcher and while this has been historically rare for drug researchers there is evidence to suggest it is somewhat of a budding trend in the present context where the voices of lived and living experience increasingly take centre stage (Ross et al, 2020). It is widely recognised that a shared biography benefits the research process in facilitating a much needed sense of trust in drug ethnography however certain drawbacks have also been suggested. According to Ross et al (2020):

‘while drug-taking researchers may gain a deeper understanding of the data and reach interpretations and conclusions that may be harder for the non-drug taker to reach, there is also a distinct risk of confirmation bias’ (Ross et al, 2020: 275).

In similar vein it is worthwhile considering how an appreciation of narrative habitus might transform the discussion around confirmation bias. If we dispense with the positivist delusion that researcher subjectivity is a force that can and should be contained, then what we are left with is the predisposition of researchers, as human beings, to hear and tell certain types of

stories. The question then becomes how can we make narrative habitus work for us and not against us in our research relationships?

The strong sense of resonance that is experienced between people with a shared narrative habitus was a noticeable feature in my relationships with a number of the 20 women. In engaging in an analytical process that is unavoidably selective, I had to be mindful that despite this magnetism, I did not focus on these women to the exclusion of those whose experiences were quite different. With an awareness achieved primarily through auto-ethnographic writing, my capacity to sense when our stories were bleeding into one another became greater.

However the key to avoiding the privileging of stories that were highly similar to my own was focusing on the circles of trust and the predefined criteria for selecting narratives; both of which provided structure and focus for the analysis. Although DNA is not a prescribed set of techniques, by focusing on small stories as sites of identity work, I was able to identify a selection of detached narratives of inquiry that appeared ripe for further analysis. Had I proceeded analysing the women's accounts without engaging in the reflexive process and without the questions to guide analysis suggested by Smith (2016), I fear I would have become less balanced in my approach to presenting the range of women's voices and experiences.

Stigmatised populations such as women who use drugs are deemed to be particularly at risk of indirect harm from researcher's implicit normative judgements (Snoek and Horstkotter, 2018). In the context of accessing drug using parents in particular, Elliot et al (2002) suggest the use of peer interviewers to overcome the potential issues faced by more orthodox researchers. However there are potential drawbacks to utilising peer researchers. As well as the increased time and resources to train them, analysts often report feeling removed from the data. It is generally accepted that researchers with lived experience of illicit drug use circumvent such problems. While I agree the extent to which those marginal intellectuals (Collins, 1986) are capable of demonstrating empathy and non-judgementality is likely to be far greater, on the basis of the present study I have concluded that such assertions are somewhat problematic.

For one, the assumption that drug experienced academics are the best people to access and engage with drug using populations ignores the important fact that drug users frequently scapegoat and demonise other drug users. This study shows that the othering of other women who use drugs is one of the ways in which the women in the present study achieve a socially acceptable identity. Indeed, a very similar study conducted in France by Perrin et al (2021)

suggests that socially included women who use drugs remain largely invisible to health and control enforcement agencies as a result of such scapegoating practices. Like Perrin et al I suggest the strong desire to avoid stigmatisation results in the stigmatisation of others.

Further, it is argued that people who use drugs are more likely to trust self-disclosed, drug – using drug researchers on the basis that they both run the risk of criminal sanctioning, however on the basis of the present data I would argue such a risk is unequal due to the protective function that a professional background confers through the development of narrative resources that bestow a particular confidence in defending from potential discrimination. It is therefore as erroneous to assume that simply ‘coming out’ to participants will neutralise power differentials as it is to assume that people who use drugs from very different backgrounds will automatically have a common understanding.

The concept of the resonance effect invites a reconsideration of the notion of insider- ship from the vague and over-simplistic notion of similarity on the basis of past shared experience, which erases the influence of culture and social inequality. Drug users are not a monolithic and cohesive entity; there are many different subcultures within the larger hidden population of illicit drug users. Indeed, Voronka (2016) points out how ‘*essentialized notions of lived experience risk effacing the material, ontological and epistemological differences among us that matter*’ (2016: 189). It is thus essential to understand shared worlds of meaning are not a guarantee on the basis of drug use alone.

I suggest that one of these most important yet overlooked differences between those that are drug experienced is narrative habitus - as a result of unequal access to narrative resources with which to tell stories about taking illicit drugs in ways that minimise negative consequences. Whilst there are criticisms of the Bourdieusian theory of social reproduction, it is generally agreed his concept of narrative habitus, in highlighting alternative forms of social and cultural wealth (Davey, 2009), has resulted in a move away from deterministic and stable conceptions of social class (Huppertz, 2012). While it cannot explain the entirety of how stories bring people together and keep others apart (Frank, 2010), narrative habitus provides a theoretical starting place from where we can begin to account for the ways in which drug researchers and their participants can be simultaneously similar and yet quite different, creating a sense of dissonance or resonance that can be located, as some researchers have argued, firmly in the body (Harris, 2015).

The development and potential of DENIM

Ultimately, the challenges in accessing and engaging hidden populations of women who use drugs and how I felt my way through and past them resulted in the development of the Demonstrative Empathy Narrative Interview Method (DENIM). DENIM avoids a direct and potentially confrontational approach to qualitative interviewing. This feature, combined with the provision of a relaxed and informal environment, makes it conducive to the elicitation of alternative narratives of women's drug use. The narratives of inquiry that provide a means to analysing the complex feelings surrounding drug use, parenting and children in this study are a good example of the capacity of DENIM to generate alternative discourse that broadens thinking about the subjectivities of women who use drugs.

Perrin et al (2021) argue that gender sensitive harm reduction aimed at more privileged and socially included populations of women who use drugs should be carried out by '*health professionals who are trained to receive women and listen without judging*' (Perrin et al, 2021:7) as they are especially protective about this aspect of their identity. In addition to constituting an effective method to facilitate the construction of meaningful narratives, the distinctly human element in DENIM, with its emphasis on empathy as social action and not just an internal experience, makes the research participant feel held and supported as they narrate challenging life experiences and attempt to navigate highly moralised territory. Consistent with the findings of Corbin and Morse (2003) who discuss the benefits and risks of conducting unstructured interviews on sensitive topics, I argue the case that, particularly in the event of disclosure of sexual trauma, this demonstrates a greater sense of ethical responsibility towards research participants than maintaining professional distance and signposting to counselling services. DENIM is thus well suited to the study of sensitive topics beyond illicit drug use and especially useful for researchers which are interested in the elicitation of small stories as sites of identity work that take place in the context of multiple areas of social life where there is concerns over social justice and stereotypical representation.

Part of the process of this DNA has been to analyse the particular work of the women's stories. Having done so, I suggest that good stories are ridden with ambiguity and a complexity which hints at the multiplicity of subjectivity, similar to those described as slippery by Frank (2010). Such stories can convey the same experience as both good and bad, or the self as powerless but at the same time powerful. For Bakhtin, there are at least two voices in every person, and to ignore this fact is to create guilt or cognitive dissonance. If this is indeed the case, then the

monological bent of drug treatment discourse has the potential to add to the psychological burden of women who use drugs. A dialogical approach might be useful for practitioners who seek to empower their clients, in stressing that such struggles are products of linguistic structures and not necessarily a fault within the mind of the individual (DeSantis, 2001)

Many of the women often reported feeling better after the interview experience, suggesting the DENIM may be useful out-with research contexts, in more purposefully therapeutic settings. The power of an authentic empathic conversation, the opportunity for women to weave a narrative that helps them to navigate their social world in the context of a wider culture of secrecy where such identity work is discouraged outside of the circles of trust. Indeed, the stories of this hidden population of women who use drugs, although at times very sensitive and distressing, are often therapeutic (Hyden 2013). This study therefore contributes to the growing body of knowledge using dialogical narrative analysis to highlight the therapeutic effects of the collective storytelling (Caddick, Phoenix and Smith (2015). I suggest dialogically oriented methods of therapy might allow the women to work through complex feelings and emotions without fear of negative judgement or sanctioning.

Recommendations for future research

In making recommendations for future research it is important to recognise that the field has changed in the context of a worldwide Covid-19 pandemic. The research community is working hard to adapt to this ever shifting landscape, which at time of writing remains uncertain. While the fieldwork phases of ethnographic projects (such as the current ‘relations study’ exploring parental opioid use in the UK led by Whittaker et al) have been delayed significantly, many interview based studies have transferred successfully to online methods using platforms such as Microsoft Teams and Zoom. Indeed, the technology for conducting online interviews has no doubt improved markedly since the original literature on accessing hidden population was published almost two decades ago, suggesting at least some of the earlier difficulties in online access may no longer be as relevant (Duncan et al., (2003).

However, in the early stages of this project when I faced challenges in access there were no responses to the online call for recruits. It was then I discovered that the literature which had demonstrated success with such methods was based on largely male, less marginalised subjects. In addition to this, reflections on ‘getting in’ and the effective use of the DENIM suggest the importance of spending time in the same physical space in conditions that are as natural as

possible, so that the women can get a 'feel' for the authenticity of the researcher and experience a resonance or dissonance in narrative habitus. Thus, I must remain sceptical about the success of hidden population research with women in particular which excludes traditional ethnographic methods of observation and building trust which have been integral to the present study.

This study highlights the culture of stigma and demonization, not just as a factor to be considered in relation to accessing the hidden population but also as a constitutive force which shapes the data itself. A narrative lens borrows well for such a task in emphasising that the stories which are told cannot be divorced from the interactional context. In terms of methodological advancement then, the use of DENIM will assist in enhancing engagement with particularly stigmatised segments of the population, such as opioid using parents, including fathers. Narrative analysis of the stories told by more socially excluded men and women who use drugs using the model of the circles of trust would explore further the relationship between narrative resources and the management of stigma. Such knowledge could be mobilised to empower those individuals most affected by the war on drugs, underscoring the utility of narrative evidence to inspire change and inform social change efforts (Frost, 2018).

Critics of narrative methods often point to aspects of the human experience which escape narrative, such as unconscious material (Frosh et al, 2003). That there are core aspects of women's lives that are difficult to narrate does not always come down to matters of trauma. According to Erdman (2009) ordinary women who have lived routine lives in the private sphere usually do not have compelling storylines. In an oral history five different women found it difficult to tell stories about being a mother when asked, articulating experiences from the public sphere instead. Such stories would not rate highly in terms of Ochs' (2004) dimension of tellability.

On the contrary, the women's experiences with drug use are highly compelling, yet they are often difficult to narrate. In the case of psychedelic storytelling, far from being unconscious, the aspects which escape narrative are very lucid and the struggle emanates from a deficit in cultural narrative resources. A realist approach underpinned by representational logic would struggle to account for these highly novel experiences which, by their very nature are highly abstract: often involving dramatically altered perceptions of time and space which challenge taken for granted assumptions of temporal linearity and the traditional logic of cause and effect.

Analysing narratives of psychedelic drug use thus has much to offer the ontological debate surrounding the relationship between language and reality. For researchers choosing to focus on the novel stories told by users of these substances, both as sites of identity work and as forms of symbolic boundary work (Gashi, Sandberg and Pederson, 2020), I recommend that they build upon the conceptual narrative framework constructed in this study and frame these stories as detached narratives of inquiry (Ochs, 2004).

George et al (2020) make an important point concerning the dominance of white male discourses of western psychedelic science which are overwhelmingly implicated in cultural appropriation and the perpetuation of systemic inequality. Future narrative research focusing on psychedelics would therefore benefit from a dialogical perspective to expand upon the findings of the present study; namely the significance of the use of metaphor and the use of artefacts and how these interesting features of drug use stories are related to various forms of economic, cultural and gendered forms of capital. In the context of the recent psychedelic renaissance, drug researchers interested in gender might build upon the methodological and analytical contributions of the present study and focus their efforts on accessing and engaging with a proposed subsection of the female hidden population that is an underground network of unlicensed psychedelic therapists (George et al, 2020).

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to make a unique contribution to the Scottish tradition of hidden population research through accessing and engaging a cohort of women who use illicit drugs in Scotland, currently unknown to treatment or criminal justice agencies (McPhee, 2013). The outcome is a combination of critical ethnography and narrative research which emerged as a result of a pragmatic and reflexive process. Consequently, the style of this thesis somewhat challenges accepted norms through the inclusion of auto-ethnographic writing and reflective diary data which underscores the social constructionist theory of knowledge as partial, situated and contingent. On a practical level, the reflective data highlights the difficulties in gaining access to this hidden population and how these challenges were overcome and I suggest this knowledge will be useful to future researchers of hidden and hard to reach populations.

For Ettore, the purpose of feminist auto-ethnography is to extract meaning from experience, rather than ‘depict life as it is lived’ (Ettore, 2005: 536). From the perspective of dialogical narrative analysis, which is a broad and varied interpretive approach (Sparkes and Stewart,

2019), I have been interested in both the content of the stories and their effects. Unlike much research in the drugs field, it is not an attempt to construct knowledge about drug use per se, but of the identity work of the less visible social groupings that use them.

Perrin et al (2021) suggest future research on hidden populations of women who use drugs should focus on understanding of the factors which contribute to the invisibility of socially included women who use drugs, whom they describe as the antithesis of stereotypical representations. However, stressing the intentionality of their invisibility either through ‘managing’ stigma or managing their levels of drug use does little to explain the social processes and structures which enable them to do this. These works must be commended for paving the way in breaking free from the dominant paradigm of pathology in which drug use has been firmly situated. However, in overemphasising the agency of hidden populations as their primary mode of resistance, not only do they fall into the perennial trap of partial accounts which downplay the role of structure, they unwittingly engage in the reproduction of equally problematic discourses of whiteness and middle-classness which operate to exclude and further marginalise that which is other.

This hidden population study has sought to account for the interplay of structure and agency using the theory of narrative habitus. Approaching the women’s narrative identity work from this perspective has provided a solution to the theoretical impasse created by the dominance of two opposing frameworks: one emphasizing women’s victimization and dependence as the driving force for their drug use, the other depicting them as volitional actors virtually unfettered by social constraints (Maher, 1997).

I looked across the women’s narratives and used them to construct the concentric circles of trust in which significant relationships can be positioned. I also looked at them closely and in depth, presenting seven small stories of illicit drug as sites of identity work. In both cases, the ontological premise is that stories do not imitate an independent social reality but constitute a social reality in and of themselves (Frank, 2010). While limited claims are made in relation to the material practices surrounding women’s use of illicit substances, the knowledge constructed in this thesis is valuable as it shows how identities and group boundaries in hidden populations are constructed through storytelling. This renewed focus on storytelling shows how stigma is managed, defended from and at times deflected by privileged groups of women who use drugs through deployment of narrative resources that have been developed in the context of relative social inclusion.

Everyday stories of drug use give women who use drugs a much needed sense of agency and empowerment that is integral to a dynamic and ambiguous sense of self that is not entirely identified with or reduced by previous instances of victimisation. Consequently, they provide a rich and fertile ground to analyse areas of key relevance to the study of hidden populations specifically and gender and drug use in general: relationships, stigma, identity, agency and privilege. Yet rarely, if ever, have they been subject to the level of analytical scrutiny demonstrated in this thesis.

In line with difference centred theorists the present study has avoided the privileging of gender as a difference over any other (Moosa-Mitha, 2005). As such, it not an example of what Campbell and Herzberg call ‘deep engagement’ in theories of gender. These authors recognise however, that in the study of women’s drug use “paying meaningful attention to gender does not require reorienting or redefining oneself as a gender scholar” (Campbell and Herzberg, 2017: 253). Conversely, a critical drug studies should incorporate a diverse array of analytical tools capable of analysing the complex relationship between gender and drug use. I argue that a dialogical narrative analysis should form a key part of this, as it sheds light on the gendered, racialized, classed and indeed local nature of women’s drug storytelling.

That drug storytelling must not be analysed in separation from the immediate social and interactional context in which it takes place is evident in relation to the success of the Demonstrative empathy narrative interview method (DENIM). In contributing this innovative research tool to the methodological literature, I have emphasised the importance of and indeed the requirement for non-judgemental approaches to carrying out qualitative interviews and conducting research relationships with women who use drugs. But more than that, with the emphasis on empathy as an embodied action, I have shown how non-judgementality is more than the absence of negative attitudes, it is communicated in subtle yet powerful ways through the body.

Analysis of small stories of drug use which are shared within the circles of trust, shows how doing risk and doing gender are inextricably intertwined. The dialogical approach to analysis reveals the complex and limited nature of subject positioning for women negotiating and defining femininity against a backdrop of devaluation. A key thread which runs throughout the core of this thesis is that in exercising their limited narrative agency women who use drugs who have limited choices. Even so, they have the means to communicate their drug experiences

in way which troubles their positioning in relation to normative femininity within socially acceptable boundaries.

Where traditional monological drug discourse privileges one aspect, usually the negative, as though it defines the totality of a woman's drug experiences, through the emphasis on complexity and ambiguity, the women in this study are constructed as wrestling with conflicting emotions and challenging dilemmas that they encounter as a result of their drug use. Their stories capture and hold in tandem both the pleasurable and painful aspects of illicit drug use, which are often difficult to disentangle. Thinking about the work of women's stories from a dialogical perspective thus assists in the development of a more critical understanding of gender and drug use.

Ultimately it was in resisting both the taken for granted logic that drug research should be focused on reducing harm (Martin and Stenner, 2004) and the convincing arguments for adopting a critical realist ontology (Stevens, 2021), that such an analysis was possible. The present study, while underpinned by a relativist ontology and constructionist epistemology, retains the capacity to comment on the relationship between social inequalities and women's drug use, without privileging structure or the agential creative aspects of their storytelling.

Much like so called 'poverty porn', there are individuals who consume stories of women and illicit drug use for reasons other than education and social justice. To point this out is nothing new- Tammy Anderson called out this voyeuristic character and sought to disrupt it through the rejection of the paradigm of pathology and powerlessness as far back as 2005. Yet problematic and uncritical constructions of women who use drugs remain a contemporary phenomenon (Campbell and Herzberg, 2017). It is my firm contention that the original contribution to knowledge of this thesis was only possible as a result of suspending the enduring fixation with the deviant behaviour that drives most mainstream research on women who use drugs. Perhaps as a result of my own cultural positioning, illicit drug use is less exotic for me than it is for others.

In bringing to life a narrative ethnography of hidden populations of women who use drugs it has been my intention to provide some nuance and restore the humanity that is desperately needed within this field. Each step in this process was guided by a feminist sensibility within the context of a crisis of representation in qualitative research that asks '*who and what is this research for?*' (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). Acutely aware that women were being asked to make themselves vulnerable, it was hoped research would benefit them in some way, if not

directly then indirectly through helping to transform the monstrous figure of the female drug user in the collective consciousness into something more simply human. It is in adopting a dialogical, narrative approach to the data, through presenting a range experiences of the women's small but very intimate stories of drug use, that I hope to some extent this has been achieved.

Dialogical narrative analysis always resists finalisation (Frank, 2010). This thesis makes no claim to have provided a definitive account or captured the essence of these women, indeed the aim has been to highlight how any such claims are inevitably reductionist and oversimplistic. Neither does it represent a snapshot of these women as they are, but a sketch of these women as they exist in a larger process of becoming, crafted from an inescapably partial and situated perspective. Claims to give marginalised subject's voice do nothing to change the fragmented and incomplete nature of the subject from which there is no central point to tell the truth. Thus I agree with Frosh who states 'however much, for therapeutic and strategic reasons, one might want to make a coherent narrative out of a subject's chaotic account, don't believe a word they say' (Frosh, 2007: 638). In eschewing the desire for cohesion and neat storylines, I have tried to make space for the contradictory meanings and subjectivities which 'refuse to stand still', aware of the ever present danger of slipping into traditional modes of representation (Britzman, 2002).

This dialogical view of the self represents a middle ground between the universalism of modernism and the relativism of postmodernism suggesting 'these formerly polarised dominant modes of thought are part of a wider, more heterogeneous process (Owen, 2011: 136). As Gergen and Gergen (2000) suggests, in qualitative research the task is as much solving problems as it is generating new ways of thinking about them. In reflecting upon this I am reminded of Mary, and have come to the conclusion that doing narrative research is a lot like taking DMT. It is thoroughly mind-blowing; you go into it with a sense of wonder and curiosity and come out the other end considerably expanded. Having started off with a few questions you end with many, many more.

One of these questions that I argue must be debated further, is how can knowledge of the role of narrative habitus in sustaining hidden populations be used to inspire meaningful social change? Indeed, the hope in highlighting the structures that contain and limit women's autonomy, was that ways to challenge dominant forces in society would become apparent (Cranny-Francis et al, 2003). Stories can resolve human troubles and they also have the

capacity to cause trouble in people's lives (Frank, 2010). I suggest the more stories a woman has available to her, the more power she has to resist the manner in which stories may cause her problems, for example by causing her to act on a particularly troubled or troubling aspect of identity. It is said that bringing forth new dialogues is largely the goal of dialogical narrative research. Future work must continue this alternative discourse on hidden populations by focusing on the features of good stories which assist in the management of stigma, and the manner in which these narrative resources are shared and developed in and across social networks. Finally, in the interests of social justice, such research might explore if and how this knowledge can be used to empower those groups of women who use drugs that are considerably more disadvantaged and socially excluded.

Epilogue

Brett Smith (2016) suggests, as narrative researchers, getting to grips with one's own stories enables us to better understand those of another. I wish to add that through deeper understanding of another's stories, we can make much more sense of our own. For now, at the end of this research process, as I turn over *'the outsider within'* with the same dialogical sensibility in mind, I can see it acts in many similar ways as the respectability narratives of the women. Like Louisa, I strive to be at once experienced yet respectable. There is an apologetic tone to it that had formerly escaped my notice, common in many stories of women who are known to use drugs, who after crossing the other side of the dilemma of disclosure, requires to negotiate acceptance and re- entry into the everyday world of womanhood. The opposing forces that I seek to reconcile in my vignette are also much clearer to me now.

Outing myself as former problematic drug user and criminal was a claim to knowledge and insider status. In seeking to achieve this I also had to manage cultural expectations to be trustworthy and have integrity; I can see that I reach for forgiveness for transgressing moral boundaries by rehashing the trope of motherhood as redemption. I told this story because it felt right, it reflected at that point in time my narrative habitus. But the effects of this story on my life are such that I now have to navigate my professional and social world as that woman who has embodied a range of mad, bad and sad dark feminine figures. As the narrative scholars suggest, stories do indeed have the capacity to cause trouble for lives. As this process comes to an end, I could tell a new story and perhaps enjoy being cast as the central character in a heroic struggle, however I know the story will sooner or later interpellate me to act out the trauma that is carried by these identities that still live within me.

Indeed, looking back at the auto-ethnographic vignette I can see clearly how I have evolved in my narrative capacity through hearing and retelling the stories of these women. One might say that through the experience of being thoroughly immersed in the story world of 20 interesting women, that my own inner library is far richer as a result. But more than that, I have learned of the power in silence. The people with whom I wish to share my stories are becoming less and less. More and more, like Daisy, I find myself holding on to my stories like little nuggets of gold, preferring to share and shape them in dialogue with one who 'knows'.

Through the practice of DENIM I have become more emotionally mature. In learning to hold non-judgemental space for women in which to experience contradictory feelings, I am getting better at allowing this complexity to flow within myself. I can penetrate the silent shame of my

drug induced psychosis without it defining the totality of my being. Yet the words to express this life changing experience continue to evade me. The story may be stuck in the body, yet the empathy I have as a result, the resonance as a similarly marginalised and deviant female body, flows forth and allows me trace the contours of our often similar but sometimes very different experiences (Ettorre, 2017).

According to the theory of narrative habitus stories have a curious way of finding their way to the right person (Frank (2010)). Like Marie, I found myself reliving my own experiences through hearing the women's stories, at times the agony and at times the ecstasy. Far from acting as a call to re-engage with negative behaviours and thought processes, in both cases their stories have been as medicine for my soul. In the beginning of this thesis I argued that one of the benefits of being a researcher and a member of the same culture in ethnography can mean that similar life experiences are shared. What is less discussed is that these inside experiences can come later, years after the research encounter. During the course of writing up this study my eldest son developed a potentially worrying relationship with cannabis, in which he sought relief from the endless boredom and social isolation of lockdown. Alone in how to deal with this dilemma, I found myself returning to the transcripts of the women who felt similarly torn over this issue. Knowing that other women were tangled up in much the same way was incredibly comforting. This showed for me, in the most intimate way, just how strong women can become simply by hearing the stories of other women and how important it is to keep these channels of communication open.

During the same period, I have spent an unusual amount of time with some of the women in my community. The weekly clap for the NHS in the street presented an opportunity for sharing resources like food and medicine, and with this quite naturally came the sharing of stories. Under these unprecedented conditions, intoxication became somehow more acceptable. Some nights we shared bottles of wine and beer and cannabis joints in the streets until the late hours, when all the children were fast asleep. They were not the women I would normally have done this with, but under the circumstances it provided a much needed sense of connection and community.

One of the women, whom I will call Judy, was missing more and more from the circle as the weeks went on. I started to worry about Judy, hearing whispers and sniggers that she was 'back on the crack' and 'on the game'. There was a definite visible difference in her physical appearance and behaviour. In the context of this unfolding I saw for myself how women like

Judy are subtly dismissed and excluded when their conduct crosses the boundaries of acceptability.

When I had the opportunity to speak with her alone, she told me she was back ‘on it’ again and that truth be told she had stopped caring about herself, feeling it was pointless. I told her that I had been feeling like that recently too, and that I managed my cravings for alcohol and other drugs by working in the garden. I did not preach to her; I accepted her just as she was, and showed her empathy. Consequently I have been available as a life line of support during times of need. However I do not sit in judgement of the other women for rejecting Judy, for the wisdom gained through conducting this study has enabled me to recognise that I am privileged in a way that they are not. Although similarly marginalised in many respects, my level of education means that my social standing is less dependent on who I choose to associate with. Attacks on my character are not as devastating as they would be for the others. I am aware this sets me apart from the group, but not to the extent that I am entirely on the outside. In fully absorbing this realisation it occurred to me that I had more in common with Freda than I was previously able to appreciate. Indeed, this entire reflexive process has taught me that for all the ways in which women are different, there are just as many in which we are same. Like all of the women in this study, my circle of trust is constantly shifting, sometimes taking unexpected forms, and somehow I remain, as I always have, in the space between.

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Appendices

Appendix One: Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Accessing hidden populations of women who use drugs: narrative inquiry

Ethics Approval Number:

Investigators names: Karen Hammond

Researcher Email:

Personal details withheld.

By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and photovoice instruction sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and I need not answer any questions, and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after taking part without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of personal information I may provide (<i>age, sex, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to take part participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Participant number..... Audio Recording number:

1 Study title: Accessing hidden populations of women who use drugs: a narrative inquiry

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

3. Who Am I?

The researcher is a postgraduate student from UWS conducting research for a PhD in Alcohol and Drug studies.

4. What is the purpose of the study?

This study is interested in hearing the experiences of women who use illicit or illegal drugs and have not been in contact with treatment services or the criminal justice system as a result of their drug use.

5. Why have I been chosen?

You will have been identified from information provided by a friend or acquaintance as someone who fulfils the requirements of this research, which is confidential. Your real name is not required, neither is your place of work. This is an academic research study.

6. Do I have to take part?

No. Participation in this study is voluntary, I would be grateful for your help, but the choice is yours.

If you choose to take part in the study you can withdraw at any time you wish and your questionnaire and will be destroyed.

If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, is your right and we will not be offended.

7. What do I have to do?

All we would like you to do is:

- fill out a consent form
- Answer some questions – these include general questions about yourself and your drug use.

- Agree to have the interview recorded

The interview takes about 45 minutes to complete and will take place in a quiet private area of your choosing. You have the right not to answer any questions and can stop the interview at any time without having to give a reason. At the end of the interview you will be given the opportunity to ask anything you wish, and will have an information sheet with contact details of the researcher and their supervisor.

Your name is not being recorded in this study. This means that neither you, nor anyone else, can find out your answers.

For accuracy, the interview will be digitally recorded and typed into a word document which will be stored on a password protected computer. You will not be identified at any point in this process.

8. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

If you disclose information relating to terrorism or child abuse then confidentiality will not be upheld.

9. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

As you are to be considered the expert in your own life it is hoped that the interview will for you be an opportunity for reflection and being heard and for society it may influence academic thinking in this area.

10. What happens when the research study stops?

The researcher may contact you before the research is completed to ask you additional question, you may choose not to take part.

11. What if something goes wrong?

Should you be unhappy with how you are treated you may complain directly to the supervisor of the researcher at any time, without informing anyone that you are doing so. This is your right.

12. Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All information which is collected about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. Your name will not be recorded on the transcript of the interview. Your individual answers will not be given to anyone else.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered under the Data protection Act and has an Information Security Policy to safeguard the collection, processing and storage of confidential information.

13. What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this research may form part of a publication in a research journal; you will not be identified in any report/publication.

14. Who is organising and funding the research?

This is a student research study and is not funded by any external organisation, although support to the researcher is provided by the University of the West of Scotland as part of their responsibility as academic supervisors of this PhD research.

15. Who has reviewed the study?

The University of the West of Scotland Research Ethics Committee has granted permission for this study to commence.

15. Contact for Further Information

If you want to find out more about this research or have a complaint about this research, please contact:

PhD Student

Karen Hammond
Drug and Alcohol Studies
Faculty of Social Sciences
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
High Street
Paisley
PA1 2BE.

Telephone: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Academic Supervisor

Dr. Iain McPhee
University of the West of Scotland
Faculty of Social Sciences, Paisley Campus, PA1 2BE

Telephone: [REDACTED]

Please keep this sheet for your information. **THANK YOU FOR YOUR HELP** Your privacy and your rights within UK law will be protected and upheld. This study is confidential.

If you have a drugs problem and wish to seek confidential help call the National Drugs Helpline:
0800 77 66 00